

**AN EXPLORATORY STUDY OF HOW PRICING IMPACTS ON CONSUMER
BEHAVIOUR: A CASE STUDY OF EURO GARAGE**

Md Ismail Mizi

Doctor of Business Administration

April 2021

**AN EXPLORATORY STUDY OF HOW PRICING IMPACTS ON CONSUMER
BUYING BEHAVIOUR: A CASE STUDY OF EURO GARAGE**

Md Ismail Mizi

**This Research Thesis Submitted to the University of the West of Scotland In Partial
Fulfilment of the Requirement for the Degree of Doctor of Business Administration
(DBA)**

University of the West of Scotland

2021

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

Firstly, I would like to express my respect to my director of studies, Dr. Pravin Balaraman, for his inspiration, encouragement, unlimited support and guidance including his valuable feedbacks and comments throughout the course.

Secondly, I would like to extend my respect to my second supervisor, Dr. Xin Guo for his knowledge, constant support and guidance in forming this thesis

Thirdly, I would like to thanks to the UWS Business School and Graduate School's members of staff for their support during my study.

Finally, I would like to thank to all Managers and consumers who participated in this research.

DECLARATION BY STUDENT

I, the undersigned, declare that this is an original work of mine not submitted to any other institution, college or university other than University of the West of Scotland for academic credit.

Signed: Md Ismail Mizi

Date: 13/04/2021

Student ID: B00299469

ABSTRACT

Purpose

This study investigated the pricing impacts of consumer buying behaviour in the case of Euro garage fuel stations and convenience stores, United Kingdom. This exploratory study focuses on price as the only element of the marketing mix that affects business revenue and profit. This research explores how various pricing strategies significantly explains choice of store and product, as well as the purchase amount and timing of fuel service stations. Extant literature shows that pricing strategies and decisions of business managers impact customers' buying behavior.

Design/methodology/approach

Adopting a mixed methods approach, this study interviewed 16 Euro Garage store managers across Scotland and administered 400 5-point Likert questionnaires. Pearson's Correlation Analysis was performed to determine the relationship between the dependent and independent variables.

Findings

The analysis showed a negative relationship between low pricing and consumer's age and a positive relationship between low pricing and the household of the consumer. There was a negative relationship between bundle pricing and the age of consumers. On consumer attitude, consumers with an increasing member of households compared prices of different products in the store before they decided to buy. There was a positive relationship between the influencing factor of family in the buying process and age and consumers' households. Nonetheless, as the age of customers increased, the likelihood that branded products in the store influenced their buying behaviour decreased.

Practical implications

It is suggested that store managers adopt data-driven approach to implement pricing strategies instead of intuition. Consumers are price-conscious, but that does not mean they will always buy only low-priced products. They were also willing to pay a little extra for convenience. Another essential aspect discovered is the effect of the family on the purchase of goods and the price of goods. It influenced how most of them bought products in the store, and the bundle pricing worked well for younger, adult shoppers compared to older shoppers.

Originality/value

This study contributes to enhance knowledge and understanding on pricing strategies as influenced by consumer buying behaviour in service stations.

Keywords: Pricing, Pricing Strategies, Consumer, Consumer Behaviour, Fuel Station, Convenience Store.

TABLE OF CONTENTS

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT	i
DECLARATION BY STUDENT	ii
ABSTRACT.....	iii
TABLE OF CONTENTS.....	v
LIST OF FIGURES	x
LIST OF TABLES	xi
CHAPTER ONE	1
INTRODUCTION	1
1.1 Study Background.....	1
1.2 Statement of Problem.....	4
1.3 Research Aim and Objectives	9
1.4 Research Questions	9
1.5 Significance of Study	10
1.6 Methodology	10
1.7 Structure of the Study.....	11
1.8 Academic Benefits from the Study	12
1.9 Practical Benefits from the Study.....	13
1.10 Study Scope.....	13
1.11 Chapter Summary.....	14
CHAPTER TWO	15
LITERATURE REVIEW	15
2.1 Introduction	15
2.2 UK Forecourt Retailing Overview	15
2.3 Pricing Strategies at Forecourt Retail Stations.....	18
2.3.1 Promotional Pricing	22
2.3.2 Discount Pricing.....	24
2.3.3 High-Low Pricing	24
2.3.4 Bundle Pricing	25
2.3.5 Everyday Low Pricing	26
2.3.6 Regular Pricing	28

2.3.7 Meal Deals	28
2.4 Euro Garages Business Model and Pricing Strategies	29
2.4.1 Pricing Model.....	30
2.4.2 Customer Value-based Pricing Strategy	30
2.4.3 Competition-based Pricing Strategy	32
2.4.4 Cost-based Pricing Strategy	32
2.5 Consumer Buying Behaviour Overview	33
2.5.1 Factors Affecting Consumer Behaviour	37
2.5.2 Buyer Behaviour Model In Relation To Euro Garages:	42
2.5.3 Consumer Decision Making Process	46
2.6 Effect of Pricing on Consumer Behaviour	49
2.7 Chapter Summary.....	52
CHAPTER THREE	53
THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK OF THE RESEARCH	53
3.1 Introduction	53
3.2 Theoretical Foundation	53
3.2.1. Theory of Planned Behaviour (TPB).....	53
3.2.2 Motivation-Need Theory	60
3.2.3 Engel, Kollet, Blackwell (EKB) Model of Buyer Behaviour.....	64
3.2.4. The Hawkins Stern Impulse Buying Theory	66
3.2.5 Pavlovian Theory	71
3.3 Research Framework.....	73
3.4 Theoretical Framework of the Research:	79
3.5 Chapter Summary.....	80
CHAPTER FOUR.....	82
RESEARCH METHODOLOGY.....	82
4.1 Introduction	82
4.2 Research Design /Nature.....	84
4.3 Research Philosophy	86
4.3.1 Types of Research Philosophies	92
4.3.2 Justification of Chosen Research Philosophy.....	97
4.4 Research Approach and Rationale for Choice	100
4.4.1 Deductive Research Approach.....	101

4.4.2 Inductive Research Approach	103
4.4.3 Abductive Research Approach	104
4.4.4 Justification of Chosen Research Approach	105
4.5 Research Strategies	106
4.5.1 Survey Research Strategy	107
4.5.2 Case Study Research Strategy	108
4.6 Research Design	118
4.6.1 Qualitative Research	120
4.6.2 Quantitative Research	123
4.6.3 Mixed Methods Research Design	126
4.6.4 Justification of Chosen Research Design.....	130
4.7 Type of Mixed Method Research.....	133
4.7.1 Convergent Parallel Mixed-Method Research.....	134
4.7.2 Data Collection	135
4.7.3 Data Analysis	136
4.7.4 Interpretation.....	137
4.7.5 Validity	137
4.7.6 Explanatory Sequential Mixed Method:	138
4.8 Time Horizon	138
4.8.1 Cross-sectional.....	139
4.8.2 Justification of Chosen Time Horizon:	139
4.9 Population and Sampling Techniques	140
4.9.1 Sampling Technique	141
4.9.1.1 Probability sampling	144
4.10 Sample Size	149
4.11 Data Collection Procedure	150
4.11.1 Primary Data	151
4.11.2 Secondary Data	152
4.11.3 Justification of Using Data.....	153
4.12 Collecting Primary Data Using a Semi-Structured Interview:.....	154
4.12.1 Semi-Structured Interview	157
4.13 Collecting Primary Data Using Survey Questionnaire	161

4.13.1 Survey Questionnaire.....	161
4.14 Research Procedures	163
4.14.1 Ethical Consideration.....	164
4.15 Data Analysis Method.....	164
4.16 Chapter Summary.....	165
CHAPTER FIVE	166
RESULTS AND FINDINGS	166
5.1 Introduction	166
5.2 Results from Semi-Structured Interviews	167
5.2.1 Effect of Pricing on Consumer Buying Behaviour As Observed by Employees Of The Euro Garage	168
5.2.2 Theme 1- Consumer Buying Behaviour	173
5.2.3 Theme 2 - Pricing Affecting Consumer Buying Behaviour	192
5.2.4 Proposed Hypotheses	250
5.3 Results From Survey Questionnaire.....	252
5.3.1 Testing for Reliability.	252
5.3.2 Descriptive Analysis of Questionnaire Responses	254
5.3.3 Demographic Information.....	260
5.4 Inferential Analysis of Questionnaire Responses.....	263
5.5 Promotional Pricing Strategy	265
5.6. Bundle Pricing Strategy	267
5.7 Triangulation of Analysis and Discussion of Research Findings	274
5.8 Chapter Summary.....	283
CHAPTER SIX.....	284
DISCUSSION, CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS.....	284
6.1 Introduction	284
6.2 Summary of the Study.....	284
6.3 Results Against the Research Objectives	290
6.3.1 Does Pricing have an Effect on Consumer Behaviour?	290
6.3.2 What is the Effect of Pricing on Consumer Behaviour from the Perspectives of Store Managers and Customers?	293
6.4 Testing the Research Hypotheses.....	296
6.5 Similarities and Differences between Organisations and Customers	297

6.6 Conclusion.....	298
6.7 The Main Lessons Emerging from the Research (Contribution of the Study to the Area of Research).....	302
6.8 Limitation of the Research and Recommendation for Further Research.....	303
6.9 Managerial Implication (Contribution to Management and the Manager)	304
6.10 Recommendations	305
6.10.1 Recommendations for Possible Improvement	305
REFERENCES AND BIBLIOGRAPHY	308
APPENDIXES	352
Appendix I: Semi Structured Interview Questionnaire	352
Appendix II Survey Questionnaire.....	353

LIST OF FIGURES

Figure 3. 1: The Theory of Planned Behaviour. (Ajzen, 2005)	55
Figure 3. 2: Maslow's Hierarchy of Needs (McLeod, 2007)	62
Figure 3. 3: The Hawkins Stern Impulse Buying Theory (Rook, 1987).....	67
Figure 3. 4: Pavlovian Theory (Lashley and Wade 1946).....	72
Figure 3. 5: Consumer Decision Model.....	76
Figure 3. 6: Kotler Pricing Strategy Matrix.....	78
Figure 3. 7: The Theory of pricing and consumer buying behaviour. (Adopted by the researcher).....	79
Figure 4. 1: Research onion (Saunders et al., 2014)	85
Figure 4. 2: Research Choices (Saunders et al., 2012)	119
Figure 4. 3: Sampling technique (Saunders et al., 2012).....	143
Figure 4. 4: Interviews Structure	155
Figure 5. 1: Key factors from social groups.	191
Figure 5. 2: Key factors from social groups (II)	249

LIST OF TABLES

Table 4. 1: Research Philosophy.....	99
Table 5. 1: Participants Profile for Qualitative Research	167
Table 5. 2: Codes from Qualitative Data	169
Table 5. 3: Response Rate.....	254
Table 5. 4: Low Pricing Strategy	255
Table 5. 5: Promotional Pricing Strategy.....	257
Table 5. 6: Bundle Pricing Strategy	257
Table 5. 7: Customer Attitude and Behavioural Response to Buying	258
Table 5. 8: Social Influence on the Customer's Buying Behaviour	259
Table 5. 9: Brand Awareness and Influence on Customer Buying.....	260
Table 5. 10: Gender of Respondents.....	260
Table 5. 11: Age Distribution of Respondents.....	261
Table 5. 12: Employment Status	261
Table 5. 13: Household of Respondents	262
Table 5. 14: Effect of Low Pricing on Age Groups, Income Groups and Household Types using Pearson Correlation.....	263
Table 5. 15: Effect of Low Pricing on Household Types	264
Table 5. 16: Effect of Low Pricing on Income Level	264
Table 5. 17: Effect of Promotional Pricing on Age Groups using Pearson Correlation	265
Table 5. 18: Effect of Promotional Pricing on household types	266
Table 5. 19: Effect of Promotional Pricing on income level	266
Table 5. 20: Effect of Bundle Pricing on Age Groups using Pearson Correlations.....	267

Table 5. 21: Effect of Bundle Pricing on household types267

Table 5. 22: Effect of Bundle Pricing on income level.....268

Table 5. 23: Social influence on consumer buying Behaviour (emphasis on consumer age)269

Table 5. 24: Social influence on consumer buying Behaviour (emphasis on consumer household).....269

Table 5. 25: Social influence on consumer buying Behaviour (focus on consumer income level)269

Table 5. 26: Effect of Brand Awareness and buying behaviour of the consumer (focus on consumer age)270

Table 5. 27: Effect of Brand Awareness and buying behaviour of the consumer (focus on the household).....271

Table 5. 28:Effect of Brand Awareness and buying behaviour of the consumer (focus on income level).....271

Table 5. 29: Customer Attitude and Behavioural Response to buying (with focus on consumer age).....272

Table 5. 30: Customer Attitude and Behavioural Response to buying (focus on consumer household).....272

Table 5. 31: Customer Attitude and Behavioural Response to buying (focus on consumer income level).....273

CHAPTER ONE

INTRODUCTION

1.1 Study Background

The consumer is the most important element for marketers in the marketplace (Kotler and Armstrong, 2016). Understanding consumer behaviour is a significant factor that leads the organisation to success (Dapkevicius and Melnikas, 2009). Understanding consumer behaviour is essential for a company to find success for its current products and new product launches (Cloutrack, n.d). The term Consumer behaviour describes how an individual (consumer) or group makes a purchase decision and how they use and dispose of goods, services, experiences or ideas to satisfy their needs and demand (Kotler et al., 2016). In order to understand consumer buying behaviour and satisfy target markets, marketers must consider and carefully design the marketing mix (4Ps, which are product, price, promotion and place) and its relevant components (McDaniel, Lamb and Hair, 2006).

Pricing is the process where a business sets a specific price for selling its products and service, and it is an essential aspect of marketing (Tay, 2019). It is arrived at after considering a few things, such as how much it costs to manufacture the products or services, the marketplace and conditions, the business brand, the competition, the quality and how much they can get the products or services for (Tay, 2019). Price is one of the four main aspects of the financial model (product, promotion, place and pricing), which is considered the most flexible marketing mix (Otiende, 2018).

Price, which is the amount of money charged, or the cost of solving an existing problem among consumers because they are paying to mitigate the existing issue (Kotler et al., 2008), has two

reciprocal roles in the mind of the consumer - the positive, where it is a cue of high quality and the negative, which is the monetary sacrifice made in exchange for a good or service (Saricayir, 2018). As a two-sided notion that creates both positive and negative feelings in consumers' minds, the marketer's ultimate duty is to emphasise the positive role of prices, which impacts the perceived value of a product or service, increasing the likelihood of purchase (Saricayir, 2018). One of the most intriguing subjects for marketers is how consumers perceive prices. Research suggests that consumers' perception of the highest and the lowest price for a product impacts their purchasing decision (Saricayir, 2018).

Studying consumer buying Behaviour has a vital role in understanding the factors that influence consumers' buying decisions (Al-Suleiman and Al-Hassan, 2016). Customers are the primary focus of the marketing process and the benchmark to measure the success or failure of goods and services; therefore, most of the companies study consumer Behaviour to increase the possibility of their success (Al-Suleiman and Al-Hassan, 2016).

Consumer behaviour is influenced by various factors. According to the author, these include marketing factors (product design, price, promotion, packaging, positioning and distribution), personal factors such as age, gender, education and income level, psychological factors of buying motive, product perception and attitudes towards the product, situational factors, social factors such as social status, reference groups and family and cultural factors of religion and social class. Although consumer behaviour is not static, undergoing changes over a period of time caused by increases in income level, education level, marketing factors and more (Chand, n.d), understanding

the buying behaviour of customers helps pro-active companies increase their market share by anticipating the shifts in consumer wants (Khadwal, 2019).

Price is the value that is put to a product or service and is the result of a complex set of calculations, research and understanding and risk-taking ability. A pricing strategy takes into account segments, ability to pay, market conditions, competitor actions, trade margins and input costs, amongst others. It is targeted at the defined customers and against competitors (Economic Times, 2021). The marketer's duty is clearly not an easy job because the nature of the customer is very dynamic and volatile (Guerguis, 2018). Marketers should, however, leverage research findings and apply them to their products in a timely fashion (Guerguis, 2018). According to Gajjar (2013), marketers are highly committed to understanding consumer needs and offering better products so that customers become loyal.

In organisations, marketing strategy depends on how consumers react to it. A better understanding of consumer behaviour enables marketers to satisfy their consumers better because the marketer can be able to develop more appropriate marketing strategies (Dibb et al., 2012). For Bianchi and Andrews (2012), covering consumer perceptions and analysing their needs to develop effective marketing strategies and offer products or services is considered the prime objective of marketing functions. Consumer buying behaviour is dependent on effective marketing approaches used by marketers to attract customers.

This study shall explore how pricing decisions impact consumer buying behaviour at fuel service stations with attached convenience stores. Pricing is important to the consumer. It defines the value

that a product is worth for the business to make and for its customers to use. It is the tangible price point to let customers know whether it is worth their time and investment (Campbell, 2020). Everything comes second to pricing, and price optimisation has a significant impact on increasing profits (Campbell, 2020). This study will therefore evaluate the different strategies in pricing adopted by these service stations and how they influence the way their customers buy. Findings will add to the existing literature on the subject and shed more light on it.

1.2 Statement of Problem

Pricing strategy has transformed the retailing landscape (Constantinides, 2006), and marketers are constantly researching the changing consumer behaviour for building and engaging a profitable relationship with a particular target market, which might directly influence organisational sales (Kotler and Armstrong, 2016).

The activities of an organisation like Euro Garage are a reflection of the 4ps of marketing. This includes the product, price, place and promotion. However, in this marketing mix, pricing is of paramount importance. The scheme of pricing is an important determinant of a firm's success or failure and attempts to make or break the firms' objectives. A product's price influences the other factors of production, such as land, labour, capital and entrepreneurship. Price is a major determinant of the market demand for an item; thus, it affects market share and an organisation's competitive edge.

The modern consumer is more empowered than before, due to its immediate and widespread access to information, through the use of digital media and smartphones (Kaplan & Haenlein, 2010).

Companies need to be aware of this when analysing their consumers' behaviour and targeting the consumers, as they have to align their marketing and advertising tactics to the needs and desires of the consumer.

Consumers tend to rely heavily on price as an indicator of their decisions without complete information. From the point of perception, consumers assume that product quality varies directly with the price. Thus, it is believed that the higher the price, the better the quality. Marketing strategies are based on consumer perception in the retail business industry because it includes frequently used products in daily life (Laroche, Bergeron and Barbaro-Forleo, 2001). Managing relations with the customer is complex due to low switching costs and availability of similar products as well as different cultures, situations and individual characteristics in the market (Kotler et al., 2016). Consequently, too low a product price might be perceived as having low quality (Hawkins, Mothersbaugh and Best, 2007).

Marketers are paying significant attention to pricing to design attractive marketing strategies and position the store compatible with the consumer expectation (McDaniel, Lamb and Hair, 2006).

According to Steinhart, Ayalon and Puterman (2013), successful companies have strong customer-related strategies to increase consumer/customer satisfaction, manage their human resource and develop the brand image to increase market share among competitors. Hence, marketing management is a highly active department in the organisation to recognise the consumer needs and develop a solution in the form of products and services to fulfil the customers' needs (Jang, Prasad and Ratchford, 2012).

With huge competition in fuel prices, marketers introduced convenience stores as alternative profit opportunities. Nowadays, it has become an essential concept for consumers, where at one point, a consumer can fuel their vehicles and buy their newspaper, bread and milk, food as well as other conveniences products.

Since it began, the concept and business model of roadside retail convenience service stores have grown rapidly, becoming dominant food retail outlets as they provide better access and convenience for the consumers. There are many difficulties that are associated with pricing and its concept. Price is a very flexible element; though it can be changed quickly, its competition is one of the most crucial problems a company can face when not handled appropriately.

The Euro Garage offers such an innovative approach to roadside convenience as it doubles as a convenience store and service station. However, the Euro Garage is also faced with the challenge of attracting large customers as the retail industry is highly dynamic, whereby customers have various options at very low switching costs (Hu and Jasper, 2006).

This study will examine how pricing decisions and strategies impact consumer buying behaviour in UK petroleum service stations in the context of convenience stores, with special reference to Euro Garage. With the concept of convenience stores attached to service stations growing in acceptance, this is a business model seen as a successful one for players in the field.

The Televisory report, 2017, states that convenience stores usually have an area of 2,000 to 4,000 square feet. A fuel station normally has ample space and can accommodate a convenience store,

ATM, fast food takeaway or a small restaurant to generate additional revenue. There are different types of fuel stations with an attached convenience store combination; a few are independent mom and pop type retail outlets with a single facility (Televisory, 2017). The second type is company-operated retail chains for fuel stations with an attached convenience store. These companies may have as low as 10 facilities or as many as 10,000 or more facilities. The third type is oil companies that have forward integrated to open fuel stations and operate an attached convenience store.

According to a 2015 NACS Consumer Fuels Survey of 5 fuel stations with attached convenience stores in the US, around 35% of the fuel customers visit the stores. The performance of these companies largely depended on their fuel purchasing behaviour, fuel inventory management practices and pricing strategies (Televisory, 2017). Gasoline prices are highly volatile. Therefore, purchasing the right quantity of fuel at the right time can positively impact the performance of the fuel segment. The cost at which the fuel purchase is made depends on whether a firm sells branded or unbranded fuel, the contract with a supplier and the wholesale price on a given day (Televisory, 2017). There is usually high competition among fuel retailers. Therefore, there is a limit to the mark-up at which they can sell their purchased fuel. Occasionally, there is a price war among fuel retailers (Televisory, 2017).

The companies analysed in the study above earned a low margin from fuel stations compared to the convenience stores. As customers visit supermarkets to buy in bulk to meet their household needs, they visit convenience stores to quickly buy a product or two without wasting their time shopping in a supermarket. Therefore, supermarkets mostly sell their products at a discount, whereas convenience stores sell these products at a premium. Hence, convenience stores operate

at high gross profit margins (Televisory, 2017). The survey concluded by stating that the competition among the retail chain operating in this industry was oligopolistic; thus, having an attached convenience store was a wise use of space for a fuel station and helped in the generation of additional revenue, which in turn could be beneficial in improving the margins of a company.

Euro Garages operates a wide chain of retail fuel service stations around the UK with over 300 outlets. Attached to its fuel stations are stores that retail the most well-known brands, including KFC and Starbucks. However, there is a limited empirical study on how its pricing decisions impact its consumers and how they buy from them. There is limited empirical research on pricing and consumer buying behaviour in fuel retail service stations. This study aims to bridge that gap in research and contribute to existing knowledge with its findings. With competition rifting to keep and retain customers, many companies and marketers understand the importance of studying consumer behaviour when it comes to purchasing and are now designing pricing strategies that will best address the needs of their customers. Price, the value placed on a good or service, is the only element of the 4 P's in the marketing mix that directly determines the revenues and profits, hence its importance to marketers. Consumers have also been found to have their buying decisions influenced by price, according to several studies.

This study will examine how pricing strategies impact consumer buying behaviour in fuel service stations with attached convenience stores. The purpose is to understand how various pricing strategies are significant in explaining product choice, store choice, purchase amount, and purchase timing. By focusing on fuel service stations with particular reference to the Euro Garage in the UK, the study will be filling a gap in the literature on this subject. Findings will be useful to

marketing managers who will understand the relationship between their pricing decisions and how their customers buy, thereby helping them come up with prices that attract customers more. Findings in this study will also contribute to existing academic knowledge on the subject while shedding more light on the concept, theory and discussion.

1.3 Research Aim and Objectives

This study examines how various pricing strategies are significant in explaining product choice, store choice, purchase amount, and purchase timing. This is done by exploring how product pricing, decision impact and consumer buying behaviour in service stations.

The objectives of this study are as follows:

- To determine the consumer buying behaviour and the pricing strategy within the service station.
- To investigate the pricing strategy that influences the consumer's buying behaviour from the organisation's perspective.
- To evaluate the pricing strategy from the customer perspective that influences their buying behaviour.

1.4 Research Questions

The following research questions have been developed to guide this study. These include:

- What impact does pricing have on consumer behaviour?
- How does pricing decision affect the buying behaviour of fuel service station consumers, as observed by the store managers?

- How does pricing influence the way customers buy at the service station, as reported by the consumers?

1.5 Significance of Study

Findings from this study would be significant in the following ways:

- Assist marketing managers by highlighting strategies that could be considered to make their prices attractive to the customer.
- Provide marketing managers with a clear distinction between their pricing and consumer purchase decision in UK service stations in order to gain a competitive advantage.
- Address the lacuna on pricing and its impact on consumer behaviour in fuel retail service stations.
- Add to the existing body of knowledge and academic literature on the subject.

1.6 Methodology

This study explores pricing strategy and its impact on consumer buying behaviour at fuel service stations. In order to do this, mixed methods research was adopted as the results of both qualitative and quantitative methods were required to answer the research questions in this single study (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill 2012). A mixed-method research design provides the opportunity for collecting and analysing both forms of data, qualitative and quantitative and integrating in a way that can describe, explain or evaluate a phenomenon in a single project (Leavy, 2017).

In this study, the pragmatism research philosophy is used. This entails the description of the real facts and information from the literature to draw the conclusion. The inductive and deductive research approaches have been taken into consideration. Sampling techniques were also employed

to select respondents and for data collection. Respondents were selected for qualitative data collection through subjective sampling technique, while snowballing sampling technique was used for data (Quantitative) collection, and non-probability sampling technique, particularly convenience sampling technique will be used to collect information from the customer's questionnaires.

Primary data were collected using semi-structured interviews with 16 store managers of the Euro Garages and the distribution of Likert-type questionnaires to 400 Euro Garage Customers. Collection of data was carried out at different times of the day, throughout weekdays and weekends, to ensure better representation. This lasted up to two weeks for questionnaire administration.

1.7 Structure of the Study

This study employs the findings from qualitative research to develop hypotheses about the consumer's buying behaviour at the Euro Garage convenience stores. These findings will be used to validate or invalidate the hypotheses formulated. Conclusions and recommendations will be made based on findings and results from the survey questionnaire distributed to 400 Euro Garage customers.

This study is structured into six main chapters as follows:

Figure 1. 1: Structure of Thesis

1.8 Academic Benefits from the Study

By reviewing existing literature on the subject of pricing and consumer buying behaviour, the study was able to identify some important research gaps. By addressing the gap in research on pricing and its impact on consumer behaviour in the context of fuel retail service stations in the UK, the current study will hope to contribute valuably to existing academic knowledge. The

findings in this study will also add to existing literature and also shed more light on the subject of consumer buying behaviour and how this is impacted by pricing.

1.9 Practical Benefits from the Study

Retail marketing managers will better understand how customers behave in response to the pricing strategies in their stores. Researchers and academicians can build on the findings of this study to conduct further studies or better understand the subject. Euro Garage marketing managers will have a clear understanding of the relationship between their pricing and how their customers buy. Marketing managers of fuel service stations in the UK may be able to refer to the findings in this study to understand their customer behaviour and how their pricing impacts on it.

1.10 Study Scope

The study is limited to Euro Garages in the UK. Euro Garages is one of the UK's biggest private-owned businesses that was started in 2001 by the Issa Brothers. It operates a wide variety of petrol and catering facilities across the country with more than 300 outlets. Headquartered in Blackburn, Euro Garages, also the EG Group retails branded fuel from BP, Texaco, Esso and Shell. With a presence in 10 countries in Europe and Asia and more than 8,000 outlets globally, Euro Garages operates third party retail brands, including KFC, Spar, Carrefour, Louis Delhaize, Starbucks, Greggs, Burger King and Subway. Since starting its operations in 2001 with one petrol station, Euro Garages has expanded its portfolio in forecourt operations.

1.11 Chapter Summary

With competition rifting to keep and retain customers, many companies and marketers understand the importance of studying consumer behaviour when it comes to purchasing and are now designing pricing strategies that will best address the needs of their customers. Price, the value placed on a good or service, is the only element of the 4 P's in the marketing mix that directly determines the revenues and profits made by a business, hence its importance to marketers. Consumers have also been found to have their buying decisions influenced by price, according to several studies.

This study will examine how pricing strategies impact consumer buying behaviour in fuel service stations with attached convenience stores. The purpose is to understand how various pricing strategies are significant in explaining product choice, store choice, purchase amount, and purchase timing. By focusing on fuel service stations with particular reference to the Euro Garage in the UK, the study will be filling a gap in the literature on this subject. Findings will be useful to marketing managers who will understand the relationship between their pricing decisions and how their customers buy, thereby helping them come up with prices that attract customers more.

CHAPTER TWO

LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Introduction

The literature review chapter provides existing academic contributions on the current research topic in order to present a theoretical base to justify the study. Existing literature on the subject is highlighted, their contributions revisited, and gaps noted that justify the undertaking of the current work. The literature review is an important part of the research, primarily concerning itself identifying theories and models that are relevant to the terms incorporated within the said study. This section focuses on the theoretical foundation, concepts, reports and previously published academic research on pricing strategy and consumer buying Behaviour, particularly at fuel service stations with convenience stores using Euro Garages as a case study.

In this section, attention is given to the elements that affect consumer buying behaviour as a response to the pricing and marketing strategies of the organisation. The impact of pricing on consumer buying behaviour and how it leads to their decision will be examined.

The Euro Garage is a fuel service station that also provides the facilities of convenience stores at their back forecourt to cater to the basic and convenient needs of customers while travelling on their journey.

2.2 UK Forecourt Retailing Overview

Although forecourts have been on the decline for the past decade, they are still considered the fastest-growing part of the convenience retailing sector, demonstrating the power of the shopping experience within petrol forecourts (Rapid Retail, 2020). For some shoppers, stopping off at a

forecourt store is favourable to visiting the local high-street supermarket as a result of accessibility and the range of goods now available (Rapid Retail, 2020).

Forecourt retailing entails two important domains that provide various services to the customer (Waweru, 2018). Fuel retailing for automobiles involves petrol and diesel sales and serves the personal transport customer in a direct manner, while the much smaller non-fuel sector concerns the retailing of commodities that are not essential within the accompanying forecourt outlet and mostly has no relationship with the transportation sector (Globe,2003 as cited in Waweru,2018).

The positive economic impact of filling stations across the UK is widely felt despite the supermarkets' growth in market share coinciding with a rapid expansion in the large out-of-town stores while smaller and more remote filling stations have closed (UKPIA, 2019). People are making fewer purchases but more frequently, in a hurry, and though these convenience stores charge more than supermarkets, people are willing to accept the higher prices in exchange for convenience (Underhill, 2000) as cited in Molefe (2006).

Petrol retailing is a highly competitive business, a trend that has accelerated from the 1990s to now, with a number of significant players in the UK retail fuels market (UKPIA, 2019) and the growing presence of supermarkets has led to a significant change for the sector (UKPIA, 2019). In light of increased competition, fuel retailers have led the way in developing their sites to boost volume throughput with a particular emphasis on larger shops or convenient stores, which are a vital element in overall site profitability (UKPIA, 2019).

Convenience is the name of the business model (Prisloo, 2004:13, as cited in Bailey, 2011). Euromonitor, a London based market research firm, supports the fact that as consumers lead increasingly busy lives, the growing demand for convenience and value for money has steadily increased (Bailey, 2011).

Filling stations cater for daily convenience purchases mainly because they offer convenient and ample parking and a safe environment. The most popular additional source of income for filling stations is the convenience store (Bailey, 2011), wherein many situations, it appeared to fully supplement losses made by forecourt activities resulting in an overall net profit for the fuel station (Bailey, 2011).

The role of the forecourt shop has changed markedly over the course of the last two decades, moving from being a small kiosk that stocked oil and consumables for the motorist to today's convenience-type stores (UKPIA, 2019). Convenience, location and customer experience help fuel the rise of forecourts as convenient retail destinations (Retail Voice, 2019). And a change in consumer behaviour has forced forecourt retailers to invest in their stores in order to make their sites a destination for shoppers and not just petrol stations (Talking Retail, 2020).

Consumers often buy more than just fuel when visiting a fuel retail station (Netz and Taylor, 2002 as cited in Bailey, 2011), and it is expected that operators will adapt to competitive market pressures with the expansion of convenience store offerings (IBIS world,2020). However, the changing shopper missions of visiting forecourts have resulted in major changes to the forecourt structure (KPMG, 2020).

The customer preference for an outlet right now is based on their convenience function, fuel price, and discount offers on their debit/credit cards as they begin to embrace technology and safety in the light of the Covid 19 pandemic (KPMG, 2020). For this reason, it was important for retailers and suppliers to understand that forecourts were now not seen only as petrol stations but rather as convenient stores selling petrol (KPMG, 2020).

This study examines consumer behaviour inside the service station's convenience store and how the retailer successfully attracts purchases through their pricing to help supplement the revenue of the station.

2.3 Pricing Strategies at Forecourt Retail Stations

Price is a major parameter that affects company revenue significantly, and adjusting these prices is called pricing strategy (Dolgui and Proth (2010), Marketing strategies are therefore based on consumer perception in the retail business industry because it includes frequently used products in daily life (Laroche, et.al, 2001).

The oil industry finds itself in the ripe phase of its life cycle (Petra, et.al, 2017). Besides the basic offer, fuel quality and location, which are crucial for the survival of petrol stations, there have been great changes in the way they conduct business, with companies focusing more on the consumer (Petra, et.al, 2017). Now, petrol stations look more and more like supermarkets, offering consumer goods at shops besides oil, its derivatives and car equipment (Petra et al.,2017).

According to Engel et al. (1993), as cited in Bailey (2011), the price level of a store is a determinant of store image. The perceived or psychological price may differ from the actual price. Consumers often form their image of a store's price more on the basis of advertisement, displays and the physical layout than the actual price level of the store (Engel et al., 1993).

Retail store owners adopt a varying range of pricing models to appeal to the needs of their customers, increase patronage and sales, and thrive in a competitive space. The pricing strategies employed by fuel service convenience store owners follow a similar path. According to Monroe (2003), as cited in Toni et al. (2015), price decisions are one of the most important decisions of management because it affects profitability and the companies' returns along with their market competitiveness.

The task of developing and defining prices is thus complex and challenging because the managers involved in the process must understand how their customers perceive prices, how to develop the perceived value, what are the intrinsic and relevant costs to comply with this necessity as well as consider the pricing objectives of the company and their competitive position in the market (De Toni et al., 2015).

Pricing strategy has transformed the retailing landscape (Constantinides, 2006), and marketers are constantly researching about the changing consumer behaviour for building and engaging a profitable relationship with a particular target market, which might directly influence the organisation's sales (Kotler and Armstrong, 2016).

A pricing strategy has notable advantages, such as attracting customers. Nafuna et al. (2019) state that, pricing is a powerful force in attracting attention and increasing sales and that it can also have a major influence on customer loyalty which determines the ability of the firm to consistently generate revenues to boost profitability and liquidity in the long run. A pricing strategy thus has a goal to establish an optimum price with current profit maximisation of the number of units sold, etc. (Dolgui and Proth, 2010).

According to Yan & Ke (2018), pricing helps to identify the survival of the company. As an adjustment parameter for profit, price is also the easiest and fastest way to increase competitiveness (Dolgui and Proth, 2010). Despite all of this, however, it is important to note that pricing is a difficult aspect of making decisions (Chen et al., 2016). Sousa et al. (2008) state that, understanding pricing strategy is highly important because it has an immediate as well as a powerful effect on the performance of an organisation. For Raymond et al. (2001), using strategy is never sufficient. The use of adequate pricing strategies is critical for making managerial decisions and achieving success in the competitive market. Studies show that the effect of pricing has a far-reaching effect more than the cost of the product (Hameed et al., 2012).

Before developing a pricing strategy, an understanding of the current, as well as potential customers is crucial. In addition, various other factors must be considered, including the cost of product production and distribution, prices offered by the competition, identification of the potential buyers and demographics and the image of the product in the consumer's mind (Yan & Ke, 2018).

Pricing decisions are also made based on internal and external considerations. Internal factors include the objectives of the enterprise, cost factors, characteristics of the product and price elasticity of demand. External factors which influence the pricing strategy of an organisation are the demand of consumers, competition in the market, suppliers, the economic condition of consumers and governmental policies (Jang et al., 2017).

Pricing strategy, therefore, tries to take advantage of the time by playing with the seasonality of demand, for example, customers' preferences and purchasing behaviour, and the spectrum of available products (Dolgui and Proth, 2010). A business organisation needs to focus on pricing strategy if it wants to grab the highest market share and obtain a higher level of profit in addition to long-term growth. However, they have to keep the price in such a way that consumers are willing to pay without any hesitation (Liu et al., 2018).

Setting the right prices can help forecourt operators achieve their goals. Indeed, fuel and convenience retailers, now more than ever, try to achieve a delicate balance between fuel volumes and margins and the customer's broader objective of meeting brand image along with various other factors.

According to Pieterse (2005), a forecourts convenience store strategy should focus on driving and growing impulse and convenience products, growing fast goods and the ready-made meals business, and limiting the range of groceries stocked. However, based on research on convenience marketing at Engen Petroleum South Africa, Pieterse (2005) found that forecourt convenience stores were hopelessly overstocked, with up to 85% of their product classes accounting for less

than 5% of their revenue. Product purchases in order of popularity were snacks (including cool drinks, chocolates, sweets and ice cream), baking goods, milk, cigarettes, newspapers and takeaway/ready-to-eat meals (Pieterse, 2005). Customers to these stores were, however, particularly endeared to the promotion and price offers strategies employed in the store (Pieterse, 2005).

Forecourts and convenience stores adopt an array of pricing strategies to deliver specific outcomes. From target-margin pricing to specified pricing, promotional pricing, time-of-day, seasonal and event-based pricing (PDI, 2019), today's convenience stores are doing it all to drive customer interaction and revenue target. However, these pricing strategies must be well-thought-out and informed so that marketing managers do not utilise significant human and material resources to implement a campaign that is ineffective or yields zero results from the onset.

The following are pricing strategies usually employed at fuel retail convenience stores:

2.3.1 Promotional Pricing

Livesey (1976) defines promotional pricing as the setting of a price on a temporary basis below the price normally charged for that good or service.

Price promotions are an essential element of a company's marketing policy because they affect sales, profits, and key intangible assets, such as brand equity (Kuntner and Teichert, 2016).

To be successful in a competitive environment, many companies take into consideration different sales techniques like promotion (Urun, 2011). They spend immense amounts of money on promotions, be they as a direct result of coupons, rebates, contests or payments to retailers to

display or promote a product at a reduced price (Urun, 2011). Kotler (2003) states that promotions can be described as stimulations and rewards which lead customers to buy now rather than later. They are short-term tools that trigger buyer actions, and their effect on sales revenue can be measured quickly and easily (Kotler, 2003, as cited in Urun, 2011).

Jarvenpaa and Todd (1996), as cited in Jean and Yazdanifard, (2015), indicate that the types of sales promotion have played an important role in influencing the purchasing behaviour of potential customers. Monetary sales or price promotions are mostly favoured by consumers, especially immediate price reductions (Huff and Alden, 1988, as cited in Jean and Yazdanifard, 2015). For the consumer, price and quality of products are the two main characteristics that determine purchasing behaviour (Jean and Yazdanifard, 2015), and due to the competitive marketplace, most retailers have selected price reduction promotion to promote their products and compete with rivalry brands, rather than spend money on advertisement or designing coupons (Jean and Yazdanifard, 2015).

Groceries and/or supermarkets use price promotions because these types of sales promotions have traditionally focused on convenience goods (Zerres and Hunerberg, 2009 as cited in Urun, 2011), however, according to Aydinli et al. (2014), although the most distinguishing feature of price promotion is its emphasis on getting consumers to take action and managers tend to defend its use as the fastest and most reliable means to increase sales, it is not only an incentive to purchase, but it can also be a disincentive to think.

2.3.2 Discount Pricing

A price discount is a very prevalent marketing strategy to attract consumers by providing an extra value or incentive, which encourages consumers to purchase the promoted products immediately (Yin and Huang, 2014, as cited in Lee and Chen-Yu, 2018). Discount is one of the major marketing tools (Zhong et al., 2018).

Price is a very important factor to influence and attract consumers to purchase a product (Bhatti, 2018). Discounted price means not only the reduced price, but it also means getting the same services by differentiating the price for the same product; it is a deduction of specific money from the total price for a short time period to enhance sales and profits of the consumers (Bhatti, 2018). Price discount has a great influence on the high price of products and affects the consumers, and increases the value of the products (Chenetal, 2012 as cited in Bhatti, 2018).

According to Gedenk (2002), as cited in Al-Salamin and Al-Hassan (2016), the short term and long term effects of promotional pricing on a firm are that, in the short run, consumers switch to the particular store that offers promotional prices and switches to brands that engage in promotional pricing frequently. New customers are generated, and in the long run, brand loyalty is created through this strategy.

2.3.3 High-Low Pricing

High low and Everyday low pricing are two dominant retailing formats. Everyday low pricing refers to shops offering low prices at all times, and high-low pricing refers to retailers selling their products at a higher average price with frequent price discounts (Fassnacht and El Hussein, 2013, Hoch et al. (1994), as cited in Fassnacht and Husein, 2013).

According to the CFI (n.d), high-low pricing is a pricing strategy in which a firm relies on sales promotions to encourage consumer purchases. It is a pricing strategy where a firm initially charges a high price for a product and then subsequently decreases the price through promotions, markdowns or clearance sales, with product prices alternating between 'high' and 'low' over a given time period.

This pricing strategy aims to drive store traffic and hopefully encourage consumers to purchase additional items once they are at the store (CFI, n.d). High-low pricing is intended to give the consumer perception of a bargain, thereby generating high sales during a promotional period, and by applying a discount to a product priced "high", consumers will be more likely to purchase the product because of their presumption that it is a bargain (CFI, n.d).

2.3.4 Bundle Pricing

According to Musa (2017), global competition has forced organisations to deploy their marketing strategies in order to attract customers' attention which eventually leads to market share extension. A great product is not enough. Organisations must be able to formulate their marketing strategies in order to win the competition.

Bundling is an efficient method to achieve business objectives in many industries (Fang et al., 2017). Bundling pricing strategy as one of the advanced marketing strategies is best known for its effectiveness (Stremersch & Tellis, 2002; Prasad, Venkatesh, & Mahajan, 2015; Shaddy & Fishbach, 2017, as cited in Musa, 2017).

Product bundle pricing is a pricing strategy in which several products, services, or any combinations of them are presented to the customer as a single package with a single price (Al-Salamin and Al-Hassan, 2016). According to Tellis and Stremersch (2006), price bundling is the sale of two or more separate products as a package at a discount without any integration of the products. According to the authors, because the products are not integrated, the reservation price for the price bundle is by definition equal to the sum of the conditional reservation prices of the separate products.

In other words, bundling itself does not create added value to the consumer and thus, a discount must be offered to motivate at least some consumers to buy the bundle (Tellis and Stremersch (2006).

2.3.5 Everyday Low Pricing

An Everyday Low Price (EDLP) strategy is a product-portfolio level pricing strategy by which a firm attempts to convey to consumers that prices across its product portfolio are consistently low (Sin et al., 2009).

Every Day Low Pricing (EDLP) strategy has proved to be a successful innovation resulting in higher profits for supermarkets adopting it in competition with Promotional Pricing (PROMO). Conventional wisdom attributes this success either to lower costs or to EDLP better serving time-constrained consumers while discouraging cherry pickers who seek promotions (Lal and Rao, 1997). EDLP is a pricing strategy in which a company charges a consistently low price over a long-time horizon (CFI, n.d).

The research examines how consumers choose retailers when they are uncertain about store prices prior to shopping. Simulating everyday choices, participants made successive retailer choices where, on each occasion, they chose a retailer and only then learned product prices. The results of a series of studies demonstrated that participants were more likely to choose a retailer that offered an everyday low pricing strategy (EDLP) or that offered frequent small discounts over a retailer that offered infrequent large discounts (Danziger et al., 2014).

However, in a paper and study, Stanford GSB looks at the strategic pricing decisions made by grocery firms during that period in response to the shock to their local market positions by the entry of Wal-Mart. The paper answers the age-old question in the supermarket industry: Is "everyday low pricing" (EDLP) better than promotional (PROMO) pricing that attempts to attract consumers through periodic sales on specific items? Investigators found that while EDLP has lower fixed costs, PROMO results in higher revenues — which is why it is the preferred marketing strategy of many stores.

The research is also the first to provide econometric evidence that repositioning firms' marketing approaches can be quite costly. Switching from PROMO to EDLP is six times more expensive than migrating the other way around, which explains why supermarkets did not shift en masse to an "everyday low pricing" format as predicted when Wal-Mart entered the game.

EDLP seems to have its advantages. It enables retailers to reduce inventory costs, better coordinate supply chains, and reduce the risk of stock shortages by smoothing the demand variability induced by frequent sales.

2.3.6 Regular Pricing

According to Hosken et al. (2000) supermarket pricing Behaviour defers across goods and over time for many individual goods. Theoretical work on retail pricing dynamics suggests that retailers periodically hold sales-periodic, temporary reductions in price-even when they are cost are unchanged. Retailers seem to have a "regular price, and most deviations from that price are downward.

In many Retail industries, a pricing strategy can be characterised as a choice but offering relatively stable pricing across a wide range of products, often called "everyday low Pricing" or emphasising deep and frequent discounts on a smaller set of goods, referred to as Promotional or PROMO pricing. However, by the late 1990s, the penetrations of everyday Low Pricing had slowed, leaving a healthy mix of firms following both strategies and several others who used a mixture of the two (Ellickson and Misra, 2006.)

2.3.7 Meal Deals

Meal deals, usually involving a main (such as a sandwich or pasta salad), drink and snack for a set price, are considered by many to be an affordable lunch option (Independent, 2017). They are packaged food items sold together at a discounted price in a store and are usually bought by those in a hurry as a time-saving option for a ready-cooked meal.

In his study to address the relationship between meal bundling called "Meal Deal" and driving customer traffic in food service and food retail stores, Zwanka (2017) found that; " if we aim to grow customer acquisition and sales, and entrepreneurial innovation process with a current trend (meal solutions) can be used as a traffic builder for the foodservice department".

The right meal deal drives traffic, brings repeat business, generates loyalty, increases the perceived value of the restaurant, increases profit, enhances your customers' experience and brings in traffic on slow days (Restaurant Engine, n.d).

However, according to Reeves (2020), increased consumption of food outside the home means that the nutritional content of meals served in restaurants now makes a significant contribution to the overall diet. Studies have found a logical sequence of effects linking food promotions to individual-level weight outcomes, especially in children (Kelly et al., 2015). Since eating out is a simple pleasure that many people enjoy, the key is not only to create the right meal deal by considering the business' brand and promoting with a purpose (Restaurant Engine, n.d), including healthier snack options in the bundles is a successful consideration for the firm.

2.4 Euro Garages Business Model and Pricing Strategies

The Euro Garage Group is one of the global leaders in forecourt convenience retailing, operating in the UK since 2016 and expanding by acquisitions and mergers. By opening convenience stores at the back forecourt of its fuel stations, Euro Garages adopted a retailing model to help with market positioning, market share, consumer loyalty, and revenue targets.

The convenience stores are designed to meet their customers' other basic needs besides filling auto tanks while on the road by leading non-fuel offerings to include brands like Starbucks, Subway, KFC, Burger King and more. Customers can go into the stores to grab food and snack items, toiletries and a varying array of other immediate item needs. The company prides itself on

successfully investing in consumer-facing multi-site businesses, a unique owner-managed business model and proprietary branded retail offers.

The stores adopt a number of strategic pricing methods to appeal even more to their customers. Low Pricing, Bundle Pricing and Promotional Pricing were especially employed by the stores' managers to appeal to customer preference and interaction, loyalty, patronage and influence their buying behaviour while in the store (Field data).

2.4.1 Pricing Model

According to Hinterhuber (2008), as cited in De Toni et al. (2015), prices have a high impact on the companies' profitability, and pricing strategies vary considerably between sectors and markets. Researchers, however, agree that pricing strategies can be categorised into three big groups of Cost-based pricing, Competition-based pricing and Customer Value-based pricing (De Toni et al., 2015). It can therefore be stated that the pricing strategies employed at Euro Garage fall under the three broad groups listed above.

Nagle and Holden (2003), as cited in De Toni et al. (2015), argue that there must be a balanced consideration of information, perception and intrinsic behaviour of the 3C's of this process (Cost, Competition and Customers) as a way to reach the optimal price.

2.4.2 Customer Value-based Pricing Strategy

Value establishment can be defined as the offer of benefits of equal or superior value to the sacrifices incurred by the purchaser for a product and/or service (De Toni et al., 2015). The value

establishment process includes the transformation of the results from the organisational strategy into programs aimed to extract and deliver value to the customer. Additionally, it identifies the benefits and costs of products and experiences resulting from the relationship between the customers and the organisation (De Toni et al., 2015). Payne and Frow (2014), as cited by De Toni et al. (2015), conclude that the superior value proposal represents an offer for the customers which increases the value or solves w problem in a better way than those offered by similar competitors.

Customer value-based pricing is favoured by academics and a number of practitioners. Ingenbleek et al. (2003), as cited in Hinterhuber (2008), posit that customer value-based pricing is increasingly recognised in the literature as superior to all other pricing strategies, with several companies in the IT and pharmaceutical industries successfully adopting it. Academics and practitioners endorse customer value-based pricing owing to its essential features of understanding the sources of value for customers, designing products, services, and solutions that meet customers' needs, setting prices as a function of value, and implementing consistent pricing policies (Hinterhuber, 2008). It is the pricing strategy with a direct link to customer needs (Hinterhuber, 2008).

However, the customer value-based pricing, as found in perceived value pricing and m-performance pricing, is least favoured by several companies as data is difficult to obtain and interpret here, and a customer value-driven pricing approach may lead to overall relatively high prices of the product or service (Hinterhuber, 2008).

2.4.3 Competition-based Pricing Strategy

The main advantage of competitor-based pricing is that it considers the actual pricing situation of the competitors, and its main disadvantage is the non-consideration of the demand related aspects of it (De Toni et al., 2015). The competition-based pricing uses as key information the competitors' price levels, as well as behaviour expectations, as observed in real competitors and /or potential primary sources to determine adequate pricing levels to be practised by the company (Liozu and Hinterhuber, 2012, as cited in De Toni et al., 2015).

2.4.4 Cost-based Pricing Strategy

Cost-based pricing is the most simple and popular method for setting prices (De Toni et al., 2015). It involves adding a profit margin on costs. The revenue is first determined, and then the unit and total costs are calculated, followed by checking the company's profit objectives and finally establishing the prices (De Toni et al., 2015). This means that for professionals involved in this process, it is necessary to show customers enough value on products and commercialised services in order to justify the prices charged by the company Urdan (2005) and De Toni et al. (2015).

Cost-based pricing derives from data from cost accounting, with its key strength being the availability of ready data. (Hinterhuber, 2008). Examples include cost-plus pricing, mark-up pricing, and target-return pricing (Hinterhuber, 2008).

The success of the implementation of the pricing strategies of Low Pricing, Bundle Pricing and Promotional Pricing by Euro Garage marketing managers in their store can be deduced by the buying behaviour of the customer inside the shop. Although distinct methods, all three pricing strategies have a similar goal, which is to increase customer interaction and boost revenue.

This study will investigate these pricing strategies and how they have influenced the buying behaviour of Euro Garage customers. By doing this, it will become clear if they are successful strategies for the Euro Garage or not so. The findings will be useful to the marketing managers as they develop programs and policies for the organisation's profitability.

2.5 Consumer Buying Behaviour Overview

Studies have shown that pricing and how a consumer reacts to it share a relationship. Sometimes, this is a positive relationship, other times; it is not. An overview of what consumer behaviour means and theorises becomes imperative in this section. The consumer is the most important element for the marketer in the marketplace (Kotler and Armstrong, 2016), and understanding consumer behaviour is a significant factor that leads the organisation to success (Dapkevicius and Melnikas, 2009). Stallworth (2008) defines consumer buying behaviour as a set of activities that involves the purchase and use of goods and services which result from the customers' emotional and mental needs and behavioural responses. It is a psychological part of an individual which makes the difference in purchasing any goods or services (Barmola and Srivastava, 2010).

According to London (1993, p.5), "consumer buying behaviour is the decision process, and physical activity individuals engage in when evaluating, using, or disposing of goods and services". This view is broader than the traditional method, which focuses more on the buyer and the immediate antecedents and consequences of the purchasing process (Hawkins et al., 2007). However, Churchill and Peter (1998) argue that consumer purchasing behaviour is the thoughts, feelings, and actions of the customer and the influences on those exchanges.

Thoughts, feelings and actions are taken by individuals in buying any product, service or idea to satisfy needs and desires (Solomon, 2016). To Kuang and Ng (2018), though, whole consumer buying behaviour depends upon what should be purchased, which brand is highly suitable, from which place the product needs to be purchased, at what time the product needs to be purchased, how much money needs to spend, how many times the products needs to be bought and in what interval it needs to be bought.

Various authors have given their very own definitions with the aim of simplifying the complex phenomenon of consumer behaviour as a subject and concept:

1. Consumer behaviour as stimulant: In a marketing sense, it generally means consumer behaviour is a motivation to achieve specific purposes (Kilbourne, Beckmann and Thelen, 2002). Behaviour is simply meant to achieve some set goal (Loudon and Bitta 1993).
2. Consumer behaviour as encompassing many activities: Consumer behaviour is the reflection of individual activities, which are fixed to reflect how individuals behave or respond to the external environment (Morris et al., 2012).
3. Consumer behaviour as a process: Consumer behaviour is also defined as a process to recognise the need, researching the problem, develop alternatives, and selecting an alternative to mitigate the problem (Mowen and Minor, 1997). The consumer process involves five steps starting with problem recognition, information search, evaluation of alternatives, and purchase and post-purchase evaluation (Dibb et al., 2012).
4. Consumer behaviour is different in terms of time and complexity: Consumer behaviour is a complex phenomenon because it supports the emotional, psychological and physical environment.

The individual uses number of activities to take a decision (Hawkins, Mothersbaugh and Best, 2007).

5. Consumer behaviour as including various roles: Particular situations change individual behaviour, and sometimes introverted personalities behave as an extrovert. The different roles are played by a single person in a different situation (Hawkins, Best and Coney, 2003). Hence, situational factors play an important role to influence individual behaviour.

Consumer behaviour is influenced by individual, environmental and decision-making factors, and its process includes buyer recognition, information search, evaluation of alternatives, purchase decision and post-purchase decision (Barmola and Srivastava, 2010).

To begin with, consumers take many decisions in their daily lives, and one of these is the buying decision (Al-Suleiman and Al-Hassan, 2016). According to the authors, they decide to buy some products because of several reasons: the need for these products, want to try them, products are strongly recommended by others, or the products will be given as a gift (Al-Suleiman and Al-Hassan, 2016). To this end, consumer behaviour studies are crucial in strategic marketing planning, which guides the company towards the most appropriate tactics to be adopted in their respective market (Business Teacher).

Consumer behaviour studies help in decision-making (Saeed, 2019). This knowledge helps marketers understand how the consumer thinks, feels and selects from the various alternatives such as products, brands and services. This also helps in understanding how the buying behaviour of the consumer is influenced by environmental factors. According to Palmer (2000), it is very important to understand how buyers choose products and alternatives. The study of consumer

buying behaviour also includes an analysis of internal and external factors that influence buying decisions and product use (McDaniel, Lamb and Hair, 2006).

In order to understand this behaviour and satisfy target markets, marketers must consider and carefully design the marketing mix and its relevant components (McDaniel, Lamb and Hair, 2006). These components have a major impact on consumer buying behaviour (Palmer, 2000). Globally, consumer buying behaviour varies tremendously in age, income, education and tastes (Kotler and Armstrong, 2016).

Jobber (2007) provided five key dimensions of consumer buying behaviour that can be understood by answering the following questions:

- 1) Who is important in the buying decision?
- 2) How do they buy?
- 3) What are their choice criteria?
- 4) Where do they buy it?
- 5) When do they buy?

Answering all five questions can be provided by personal contact with consumers and increasingly by the use of marketing research.

According to Kotler and Keller (2011), understanding consumer buying behaviour and the way customers select their goods and services can be very important for the organisation as this provides them with information on consumer habits and deliver a competitive advantage in several aspects over its competitors. For example, the organisation can use the knowledge of consumer

buying behaviour to establish their various strategy offering the right product and services to the right market by reflecting their desires and needs effectively (Peter, Olsen and Grunert, 1999).

There are various factors that influence consumer behaviour. These are external and internal.

External factors include cultural factors and social factors, and internal factors include personal factors and psychological factors (Clifton et al., 2016). Among all these, Upadhyay and Shukla (2017) state that the cultural factors influence consumer buying behaviour most, which includes the culture of buyers, sub-culture as well as social class. Social factors consist of reference groups, family, role and status etc. (Kotler and Armstrong, 2016), personal factors are age, education, profession, income, personality and lifestyle of people, and psychological factors are perception, motivation, beliefs and attitudes as well as learning (Tang et al., 2001).

2.5.1 Factors Affecting Consumer Behaviour

According to Jisna (2014), consumer buying behaviour is strongly influenced by consumer characteristics such as cultural, social, personal, and psychological. Although the marketing manager cannot control most of these characteristics, they must take them into account (Kotler and Armstrong, 2016).

Here is a brief overview of what these characteristics refer to:

2.5.1.1 Cultural Factors

According to Kotler and Armstrong (2006), cultural factors have a broad and deeper influence on consumer buying behaviour. Culture is one of the most important determinants which talk about the behaviour as well as the wants of an individual. "A culture is the complex of learned values

and behaviours that are shared by a society and are designed to increase the probability of the society's survival" (Churchill and Peter, 1998, p.150).

Culture is also the set of basic values, perceptions, wants, and behaviours that are learned by a member of society from family and other important institutions. A subculture is a group of people with shared value systems based on common life experiences. Social class is a relatively permanent and ordered divide in a society whose members share similar values, interests and behaviour (Brajesh, 2012). The culture of that region directly influences the buying behaviour of the consumers (Frank et al., 2015), and marketing is a channel where cultural meanings are transferred to consumer goods (Kotler et al., 2016).

Euro Garages maintain open convenience services stores where people can buy some brands that are well known in their specific industry. Organizational Culture, therefore, influences consumer buying behaviour because consumers are looking for a good environment that values them while using services in stores.

2.5.1.2 Social Factors

Social factors are also equally as important as the other factors, which decide the mindset of the consumers and their buying behaviour (Andersone and Gaile-Sarkane, 2008). The people of the same social classes usually have the same values and norms which they follow (Kilbourne and Carlson, 2008). Social talks about the groups to which an individual belongs, and these influence the consumer's behaviour.

There is an utmost need for marketers to pay attention to these groups because the choice of these individuals is very similar. However, the level of influence may vary as some may have a high level while others have a low level. Marketers, therefore, need to monitor their process according to the different social classes to determine the important factors which govern the buying behaviour of the consumer. A person belonging to a low-level income may purchase the items that should be within his or her budget, while a person from a higher level may look at factors like quality and uniqueness (Nagarkoti, 2009).

Groups and social networks

Group and social networks can have a direct and indirect influence on consumer buying decisions (Iyengar, Han and Gupta, 2009). A group is made up of two or more people who interact to accomplish individual or mutual goals. Social networks are where people socialise or exchange information and opinions. People live in society and groups in which a person spends more time that may influence their behaviour (Kim et al. 2017). Social group and professional group, which have more importance to an individual, influence their behaviour. If someone wants to buy a car, for example, and his or her professional group suggest buying a specific brand, they contribute to influencing their buying decision.

Family

The family is the most important social institution for many consumers, strongly influencing values, attitudes, self-concept and buying behaviour (Langner, Hennigs and Wiedmann, 2013). Family, whose role can be the spouse of kin, can strongly influence a consumer's purchase of different products and services. Family and family members have more importance in buying

decisions because they use products and services. Consumers have to understand their family members' requirement and consider it in buying decisions (Mostert, 2002).

Roles and status

Consumer role in society and their status also have major influences on their buying habits (Goodwin et al., 2008). Roles and status are the images a consumer maintains within groups, social networks, and among families by buying certain products and services. A brand's relationship with consumers is determined by the consumer's individual view and overall point of view set by society. The marketers' role is, therefore, to understand the position and status and offer products which meet the level (ACCA Global, 2018). Social factors have therefore been said to play an important role to support consumer behaviour, and changes in their factors may change consumer perception towards products and services.

2.5.1.3 Personal Factors

There are a number of personal factors that affect the consumer's buying behaviour greatly. Occupation, for example, plays an important role in affecting the buying behaviour of the consumer (Perreau, 2014). Age is another important factor, and marketers must develop strategies aimed at targeting and satisfying different age groups. Economic condition, lifestyle and personality are also factors that govern the buying behaviour of the consumer (Bray, 2008).

Age and life cycle stage

According to Spitteri and Dion (2014), customer age and life cycle have a significant impact on consumer buying behaviour. With the change in age, various changes occur, such as maturity level,

experiences, income and status. Marketers should set their strategies by considering their customers' attitudes, income levels and age groups so that offering can effectively match consumer needs (Lynn, 2011).

Occupation

Today, people are highly concerned about their image and status in society, which directly connects with their material prosperity (Morris et al., 2012). Profession and occupation have direct links with the products those consumers consume (Perreau, 2014).

Economic situation

A person's economic situation will affect the store and product choices. Marketers watch trends in spending, personal income, savings and interest rates (Kotler and Armstrong, 2010). The economic situation, which is set by finances and living condition, change as their surroundings do. The economic condition thus focuses on the financial health of consumers and supports them to buy expensive products (Perreau, 2014).

Lifestyle

The concept of lifestyle as a personal factor that affects consumer behaviour can help marketers understand changing consumer values and their influencing capability. Various companies organise research to examine the lifestyle of the target group of their consumers. Psychographics combines consumer lifestyle traits and their personality styles with an analysis of their attitudes, activities, and values to examine the similarities among a group of consumers (Perreau, 2014).

VALS model is used to classify people on the basis of psychographic factors. The VALS (Values, Attitudes, and Lifestyles) framework is mainly used to assess consumer lifestyle and attitudes and some demographic information such as marital status, education level, and income to provide a better understanding of consumers (Steinhart et al., 2013).

Personality and self-concept

Personality can be described in terms of traits such as self-confidence, dominance, sociability, autonomy, defensiveness, adaptability, and aggressiveness (Kotler and Armstrong, 2016). It is a collection of various inner traits and external gestures and postures that decorate a person. It is also described as a person's disposition mainly concerned with differentiation among people (Spitteri and Dion, 2014).

Although the link between people's personality and their behaviour is unclear, marketers still give it importance when analysing consumer behaviour in order to frame effective marketing strategies (Pintrich, 2003). Self-concept supports consumers to buy the product to improve their feeling about themselves (Roberts and Jones, 2001).

2.5.2 Buyer Behaviour Model In Relation To Euro Garages:

2.5.2.1 The Black Box Model

Buyer behaviour models are useful to marketers because they map out market assumptions. (Pieterse, 2005). This enables marketers to understand, criticise, analyse, evaluate, and monitor a particular market or product. (Pieterse, 2005). The model of consumer buying behaviour, therefore, incorporates various elements that present the characteristics of the consumer and are closely

related to marketing decisions; hence consideration of these elements in order to analyse consumer behaviour becomes essential in the competitive marketing environment.

The Black Box Model

The black box model is also known as the stimulus-response model, which mainly focuses on the psychological position combined with certain customer characteristics of the consumer's decision process and purchase decisions (Kotler et al., 2016). The buyer's black box symbolises a consumer's mind and how it reacts to marketing efforts. Each consumer's Black Box is the result of environmental stimuli such as economic, technological, social and cultural happening mixing together with the market stimuli.

The black box is an invisible process that leads to the consumer's final decision (Kotler and Armstrong, 2016). In this model, the consumer is a thinker or problem-solver who considers different internal and external factors when deciding buying decisions (Hawkins et al., 2007).

According to Srinivasan (2015), consumer perceptions are influenced negatively or positively, and this depends on the quality of the services offered by the marketers. Euro Garages offers convenience stores at all its fuel stations to delight consumers. These stores comprise various food chain brand products and other basic-needs products so that customers can enjoy their travels. Euro Garage also maintains various brands of fuel and engine oils so that brand-sensitive customers can easily make a buying decision.

Content redacted due to copyright restrictions. Original figure can be found in Hawkins, Mothersbaugh and Best, 2007.

Source-(Hawkins, Mothersbaugh and Best, 2007)

The Black box buyer model is especially suited to Euro Garages and the current research as 'the relationship behaviour towards brands and companies is a result of the things going on in the buyer 'black box'" (Claessens, 2015). The 'black box is thus the central element of consumer buying behaviour.

According to Kanagal (2016), the stimulus-response model of consumer behaviour is also useful to understand the buying behaviour of individual consumers in the context of individuals buying consumer products. The model proposes that the behavioural process of consumer decision making

is a result of the interaction of three aspects of individual buyer behaviour: communication sensitivity; enculturated individuality; and rational/economic decision making (Kanagal, 2016).

The Black Box buyer model helps Euro Garages gain a deeper understanding of the thought process and, subsequently, buying process of their customers and potential customers. As external factors play a notable role in how a consumer buys and influences what and how they eventually purchase, Euro Garages can develop workable product, pricing and marketing strategies that yield stronger outcomes.

A buyer model, according to Chisnall (1975) as cited in Pieterse (2005), should map out characteristics that may affect the purchase of goods or services in a simplified manner and enable more effective marketing strategies to be developed based on likely outcomes produced from the model. Since the environment and consumers within the environment are constantly changing, models need to be continuously reviewed and modified in order to be useful (Pieterse, 2005); nonetheless, an effective and well-structured model must be relevant to real market situations, comprehensible and valid in the real world (Chisnall, 1975 as cited in Pieterse, 2005).

To develop an effective strategy so that overall functioning may be enhanced in the business by top-level management in ensuring that consumer satisfaction, loyalty and profitability are met, the Black Box Buyer Model will assist Euro Garages marketing managers in understanding how their customers buy and if existing pricing methods are effective or not.

2.5.3 Consumer Decision Making Process

2.5.3.1 The basic decision-making model

The marketing implication of understanding of consumer decision-making process can be regarded as how consumers buy particular products or services (Jobber, 2016). The process of buying a product starts long before the actual purchase, as consumers go through various steps before making a choice (Kotler and Armstrong, 2016). According to Kurniawan et al. (2002), the consumer decision-making process is the process of selecting a particular product among alternatives. These include the process of perceiving, eliminating, comparing and selecting form alternatives. O'Shaughnessy (1996) defined decision-making as the method used by marketers in order to track and identify how humans make the decision and the buying journey of a customer from start to finish.

Kotler and Armstrong (2016) identified five different stages of the consumer decision-making process with every purchase starting with need recognition, information search, evaluation alternatives, purchase decision and finally, post-purchase. The five-stage model is considered one of the simplest models which can clearly explain and illustrates how a consumer makes a buying decision (Jobber, 2016). Furthermore, it was argued by Blackwell et al. (2006) that this model is clearer and more precise compared to other models as it focuses on consumer motivational factors, which help to understand the reasons behind the purchase.

2.5.3.2 Need recognition

The consumer decision-making process starts with a need recognition, where the consumer recognises a problem or need (Kotler and Armstrong, 2016). The need can be triggered by internal

stimuli when one person requires general needs (Bray, 2008). However, it can also be an external stimulus, for example, an advertisement or buying a suggestion from a friend. The recognition of a problem or need depends on individual circumstances and situations, for example, human personal or professional, and the results of that recognition are considered as a creation of a purchasing idea (Neal and Quester, 2006).

A marketer's main objective at this stage is to research the consumer to find out what kind of problem or needs may arise, what bought them about and how they led to their present status and their proffered state. However, they must note that according to Maslow's theory, when one need is satisfied, another will come, and this trend continues repetitively; therefore, human beings will always be dissatisfied.

2.5.3.3 Information search

Information search is the next stage of the consumer decision-making process. Once the need is recognised, the consumer is likely to search for more product-related information before making a purchase decision. The sources may be either commercial as well as personal or depending on the person and the urgency to choose the products and services (Hawawini, Subramanian and Verdin, 2003). Nonetheless, the consumer becomes very conscious about the needs and the searches with regard to the products and the services (Fiegenbaum and Thomas, 2004).

2.5.3.4 Evaluation of alternatives

Evaluation of alternatives is the third stage in the consumer decision-making process, and it starts after the gathering of information and when the consumer arrives at a set of final brand choices.

This is the process of information choosing among alternative products (Kotler and Armstrong, 2016). In this step, the customer analyses all the information obtained through the search and considers various alternative products and services and compares them according to the needs and wants (Stankevich, 2017). Moreover, various aspects of the product such as size, quality, brand and price are considered at this stage. Therefore, this stage is considered important; however, the process of evaluation alternatives can be difficult, time-consuming and can provide extra pressure on the customer (Ha et al., 2010).

2.5.3.5 Purchase decision

Once the information search and evaluation process is over, the consumer makes the purchasing decision, and this stage is considered to be the most important stage throughout the whole process (Kotler and Armstrong, 2016). In this stage, the consumer makes the decision to make a final purchase as the consumer has already reviewed all the alternatives and come to a final decision point (Stankevich, 2017). This is the fourth stage in the buying behaviour process and comes into effect after the consumer evaluates all the options and processes (Hackl, Scharitzer and Zuba, 2000). In this step, the consumer is ready to buy any product and does not overthink it.

2.5.3.6 Post-purchase behaviour

The final stage in the consumer decision-making process is the post-purchase evaluation stage, where the consumer evaluates their satisfaction or dissatisfaction (Stankevich, 2017). Many companies tend to ignore this stage as this takes place after the transaction has been done. However, this stage is an important one as it directly affects the future decision-making processes

by the consumer for the same product. At the same time, the satisfaction of a customer is the key to building a profitable relationship with the customer (Kotler and Armstrong, 2016).

The Kotler and Armstrong decision model is a logical way to evaluate the consumer buying process by looking at the entire buying process rather than just the purchase in order to understand why a consumer may make a purchase and why they become loyal or disloyal (Pieterse, 2005).

2.6 Effect of Pricing on Consumer Behaviour

A number of studies have been conducted on consumer behaviour at petrol stations and with petrol retail services (Denning and Freatly, 2006; Sartorius et.,al, 2007; Wahid, 2009; Jaureguiberry, 2010; Bailey, 2011; Kakunu, 2012; Kishore and Patel, 2012; H Jung, 2019; Benoit et al., 2020).

In his study on consumer buying Behaviour at select petroleum shops in Cape Town, Bailey (2011) aimed to highlight factors used by consumers when choosing a particular store. He aimed to determine if a relationship existed between store choice and age, gender, home language, group and income level of the consumer. He also intended to find out if there was a significant difference in the choice of the store with respect to location, product range, service offered, store personnel, the price charged, physical characteristics of the store, etc.

His study revealed that a large proportion of the respondents in the study agreed that prices were fair in the convenience store. However, they did not agree that the store could charge lower prices and still be profitable. There was a significant relationship between the age of the respondents and the prices charged. There was an inverse relationship between gender and the price charged.

ANOVA showed a significant difference between the price charged by the store and the store choice of the respondents. Hence, price affected consumers' decisions on where to buy fuel.

Salifu (2014) conducted a study to determine the relative factors that influenced consumer branch choice for fuel brands. This study was mainly concerned with two major drivers that are commercial and personal drivers. It was found that personal drivers considered convenience as the most significant factor that influenced their behaviour, while commercial drivers focused on price. It was therefore clear that personal drivers were high-quality and convenient oriented because they were ready to pay more for goods as they chose their fuel stations. Drivers of commercial vehicles, on the other hand, focus on the price of the product because they have less time to stay to enjoy the convenient goods and services due to time-bound job to supply their goods at a specific location.

Another study conducted by Alvi et al. (2016) was with the aim of getting an idea of people's perceptions towards the petrol pump choice in Karachi. It was found that the location of the fuel station had a significant impact on consumer buying Behaviour. The quality and facilities that were offered were highly effective for managing the consumer perceptions positively.

Srinivasan (2015) found in his study that petroleum brands were using different marketing strategies to attract customers to convenience stores. Fulfilling consumers' needs was essential to increased fuel consumption. Government liberalised policies for the private petroleum corporations to establish their own retail outlets are supportive of increasing the demand for fuel products (Yap and Gaur, 2014). In his study to determine the factors that influenced patronage

Behaviour in selecting a petroleum service outlet in Nairobi, Kakunu (2012) found that of the 100 consumers sampled, prices of the fuel and services offered ranked high with quality as what influenced their choice of a petrol outlet. Family and social influence did not impact their choice of petrol outlet.

In their study to compare managerial beliefs with customers' price perceptions and buying Behaviours, Benoit et al. (2020) found that store managers based their pricing decisions on beliefs that were only partially accurate. By interviewing 33 store managers of petrol service outlets and surveying 154 customers of 2 convenience store chains at petrol stations, the authors found that managers relied strongly on intuition when setting prices. This gave rise to wrong product pricing, which invariably would translate to a loss for the business.

These studies have filled a number of important and valuable gaps in research on this subject. The studies will therefore prove useful as a guide and framework for the current research. However, the current study will adopt the mixed methodological research approach to obtain data and thus make an analysis. It will also focus strategically on examining how the different pricing strategies employed by the store managers to price the products in their convenience stores impact the consumer's buying behaviour at the store.

By narrowing its focus to consumer behaviour inside the convenience store of the fueling station, this study hopes to have filled the gap in the dearth of literature available on this very aspect of the subject. Three (3) demographic and personal factors that affect consumer buying behaviour will be considered in this study. These are Age, Income Level and Household. Brand Awareness, Social

Influence and the consumer's attitude and behavioural response during buying will also be considered. According to Lynn (2011), marketers should set their strategies by considering their customers' attitudes, income levels and age groups so that offerings can effectively match consumer needs.

With regards to pricing strategies, Kotler et al. (2016) state that managing relations with the customer is difficult due to low switching costs and availability of similar products as well as different cultures, situations and individual characteristics in the market. Consequently, too low a product price might be perceived as having low quality (Hawkins et al., 2007). This study will consider three pricing strategies and examine how they impact the consumer's buying behaviour. These pricing strategies are Low Pricing, Bundle Pricing and Promotional Pricing. These are prices usually employed at the Euro Garage stores.

2.7 Chapter Summary

This chapter presented previous literature work on the subject of study to highlight their contributions and identify gaps that would justify the undertaking of the current research. Concepts and theories relevant to the topic were also highlighted. These provided a framework for the current study. The literature review is an important part of a research presentation as existing literature on the subject of interest is critically reviewed to highlight contributions and identify gaps. A research study must fill an existing gap in the literature in order that adds valuably to academics.

CHAPTER THREE

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK OF THE RESEARCH

3.1 Introduction

In this chapter of the research, a few theories are discussed related to the study. The theoretical framework is one of the most important aspects of a research process, providing a blueprint for the entire research that assists as the structure and support to the rationale behind the study, the purpose, problem statement, significance as well as the research questions.

3.2 Theoretical Foundation

The following theories have been found relevant to this research and therefore make up the theoretical foundation of the current study. They are thus highlighted as follows:

3.2.1. Theory of Planned Behaviour (TPB)

In understanding consumer behaviour, the Theory of Planned Behaviour (TPB), also called the Fishbein Model or Theory of Reasoned Action, receives significant attention in this research as it facilitates the understanding of human beliefs and behaviour by measuring overall attitude towards an object (Conner and Armitage, 1998). As a psychological theory, the TPB is most commonly used in explaining human behaviour (Sussman and Gifford, 2018) as well as predicting it (Margaretha Ardhanari, 2013).

It was first developed by Fishbein (1980) in an attempt to explain and understand how the consumer-led to a certain buying behaviour, the Theory of Reasoned Action was later modified by

Icek Ajzen in 1985 when he proposed the Theory of Planned Behaviour in his article "From Intention to Action: A Theory of Planned Behaviour" (Ajzen, 1985, p.29).

According to the TPB, human behaviour is determined by intention and perceived behavioural control (Ajzen, 1991). By linking beliefs to behaviour, it maintains that 3 core constructs of attitude, subjective norms and perceived behavioural control shape an individual's behavioural intentions.

Put succinctly, the TPB's central premise is that behavioural decisions are the result of a reasoned process in which the behaviour is influenced by attitude, norms and perceived behavioural control (Smith et al., 2007, as cited in Sommer, 2011).

These influence behaviour primarily through the impact on behavioural intention (Sommer, 2011); thus, the relationship between intention and behaviour can best then be summed up in this statement: "People do what they intend to do and do not do what they do not intend to do";(Sheeran, 2007 as cited in Sommer, 2011).

It is important to note that predicting behaviour is the ultimate goal of the TPB (Keat, 2009), and it has, over the years, providing support for the ability to predict a wide range of behaviours (Sommer, 2011, Fielding, McDonald, and Louis, 2008), such as in marketing (Han and Kim, 2010), organisational behaviour (Ajzen, 1991) and health-related behaviours (Godin and Kok, 1996).

In predicting consumer buying behaviours, the TPB highlights that attitudes, one of its three core components, do not determine consumer buying behaviour directly. Rather, they influence intentions instead, which in turn influences behaviour (Ajzen, 2005). Along with attitude, subjective norms and perceived behavioural control are the two key determinants of consumer behavioural intentions.

Some studies propose that the model is highly associated with analysing human behaviour in daily life (Ajzen, 2011). Nonetheless, the TPB has been widely used as one of the most powerful theories to test consumer behavioural intentions (Ajzen, 1991, Ajzen, 2005).

The components of the Theory of Planned Behaviour are discussed separately below:

Content redacted due to copyright restrictions. Original figure can be found in Ajzen, 2005.

Figure 3. 1: The Theory of Planned Behaviour. (Ajzen, 2005)

3.2.1.1 Behavioural intention

An individual's intention is the central construct of the theory of planned behaviour. According to Ajzen (1991, p.181), behavioural intentions are assumed to "capture the motivational factors that influence a behaviour; they are indications of how hard people are willing to try, or how much of an effort they are planning to exert, in order to perform the behaviour". The intentions of the human represent the decision to act in a way that motivates a person's tendency towards a goal.

The theory suggests that the stronger the intention to engage in a particular behaviour, the more likely that behaviour will be performed (Ajzen, 2005). When measured appropriately, behavioural intentions account for an important proportion of variance in actual behaviour.

When an individual finds an opportunity to act, the intention results in behaviour; hence, if the individual measures the intention accurately, the intention will provide the best predictor of behaviour (Fishbein and Ajzen, 1975). According to Ajzen (1991, p. 199) "the TPB is, in principle, open to the inclusion of additional predictors if it can be shown that they capture a significant proportion of the variance in intention or behaviour after the theory's current variables have been taken into account".

3.2.1.2 Attitude toward the behaviour

Attitude towards the behaviour is the first component of the TPB that predicts an individual's behavioural intentions (Ajzen, 2005). Attitudes influence behavioural intention but never determine behaviour directly. That is an individual's belief that a certain behaviour or act makes a positive or negative contribution to that person's life. According to the theory, the attitude toward the behaviour represents the individual's overall negative or positive evaluations of performing a

given behaviour. Attitude toward the behaviour determined the total set of accessible behavioural beliefs linking the behaviour to various outcomes and experiences. This refers to the degree to which a person has a favourable or unfavourable evaluation of the behaviour of interest.

According to Ajzen (2005, p.3), "an attitude is a disposition to respond favourably or unfavourably to an object, person, institution, or event". Attitude towards the behaviour represents the individual's overall negative or positive evaluations of performing that given behaviour. It determines the total set of accessible behavioural beliefs linking the behaviour to various outcomes and experiences.

According to Ajzen (2005), researchers must measure the attitudes toward a particular behaviour in order to understand and find a higher correlation between attitudes and behavioural intention to act on a given behaviour. In measuring this attitude and behavioural intention, all measures must be specified in terms of time frame, action, target and context because lack of correspondence may attenuate the relationship between attitude, intentions and behaviour. Correlations between behavioural intentions and attitudes are substantial only when these variables are measured at compatible levels of specificity or generality (Ajzen, 1991).

3.2.1.3 Subjective norms

Subjective norm is the second element of TPB that determines behavioural intention. Subjective norms represent the normative **beliefs that are located within**. According to the theory, subjective norms focus on everything around the individual, in other words, the individual's social networks, cultural norms, groups, beliefs and more. These have a great impact that is relevant to others'

opinions of that individual and encourages or discourages them from performing the specific behaviour.

Fishbein and Ajzen (1975) state that individual behaviour might change when the individual is aware of a given subjective norm. Therefore, subjective norms have an important effect on consumer behavioural intention that, in turn, affects the individual's actual behaviour (Ajzen, 2005).

Previous literature proposes that subjective norms represent the values and beliefs dictated by specific people (e.g. friends, family members, neighbours, relatives or an expert reference). Kotler and Armstrong (2016) also provide a similar description of this concept that social network has direct or indirect points of comparison that forms the individual's attitude or behaviour.

Chang (1998) highlighted the impact of the social environment in shaping the individual's action toward certain behaviour, and McClelland (1987) opines that people have the tendency to exhibit certain behaviour that reflect their reference groups as humans are group-associated and seek relationships. However, the literature has supported the subjective norms that provide predictive ability in terms of human behavioural intentions (Al-Swidi et al., 2014; Ajzen, 2005; Chang, 1998). These reflect the perceived pressures or expectations from relevant people that motivate an individual towards performing a certain behaviour.

3.2.1.4 Perceived behavioural control

In order to increase the accuracy predictively of the model, Ajzen (1985) extended the theory from TRA to TPB by adding the third construct. Perceived behavioural control is the third component of the theory of planned behaviour that refers to the human perception of how easy or difficult performing a certain behaviour. This component of the TPB relates to self-efficacy, which refers to people's internal perceptions that individuals are capable of executing a particular action (Bandura, 1982).

Perceived behavioural control is closely related to an individual's thinking, ability, belief and resource to perform a particular behaviour or not (Ardhanari et al., 2013). This might be the result of previous experiences or indirect information related to that certain behaviour, where they perceive other people's experiences who did that behaviour, reference group's experience or a friend's experience.

According to Shim et al. (2001), perceived behavioural control has an important, influential role on the purchase decision of the individual as it helps to answer to the question of a person's "can I do it?" while performing a particular behaviour. Individuals with high perceived behavioural control are expected to be more motivated to perform the behaviour.

In contrast, they would be less motivated to perform the behaviour if they had a low perceived behavioural control. Therefore, this component helps to understand "people's perception of the degree to which they are capable of, or have control over, performing a given behaviour" (Fishbein and Ajzen, 2010, p. 64).

The TPB assumes that when individuals intend to perform a specific behaviour, they actually do. (Gu and Wu, 2019). In relating this to the current research, it can be theorised that the majority of customers who go into the Euro Garage store do so with an already established intention to make a purchase and so are likely not going to be influenced by the prices of the products in the store. Family and friends may influence how they buy, and if they buy, however, based on this theory, they still end up with a purchase as it was their intent.

For these class of customers, it can be theorised that prices and pricing may not play a significant role in influencing how they buy, if they buy or what they buy, and therefore, store managers predict the behaviour of the customers to the store and feel more confident about the implementation of a given pricing structure they have come up with.

Since its development, the theory of planned behaviour has been successfully applied to predicting human behaviour and thus presents relevancy to the current research in a bid to understand how consumers buy and if price influences this behaviour.

3.2.2 Motivation-Need Theory

Motivational need theory, also called Maslow's Hierarchy of Needs, is a theory of psychology consisting of a five-tier model of human needs, often depicted as hierarchical levels within a pyramid. According to the theory, there are five stages of human needs that start from the bottom of the hierarchy and eventually move upwards.

The needs are physiological needs (food and clothing), safety (job and security), love and belonging needs (friendship), esteem and self-actualisation. The theory, therefore, describes that

the needs at the lower hierarchy of the pyramid must be satisfied before moving higher up (Lester, 2013). Motivation internally forces an individual to achieve some specific objective (Abbah, 2014). According to Maslow's hierarchy of needs, people have to fulfil their basic needs primarily.

At an initial level, people focus on the fulfilment of basic needs like food, water and clothes and then move towards an upper level of needs before they can begin fulfilling higher-level needs (Schraw, Crippen & Hartley, 2006). When a need has been satisfied, it will go away, and activities become habitually directed towards meeting the next set of needs that is yet to be satisfied.

However, some needs are recurring, like food but other needs, such as shelter, clothing, and safety, tend to be enduring needs that are fulfilled for some time (Solomon, 2011). Some needs have a specific time in everyone's life, like education and social values, which arise when people start getting involved in society (Williams, 2002).

Maslow designed the theory in the shape of a pyramid with five layers where the largest and most fundamental needs at the bottom are called physiological needs. The physiological needs describe the foundation of motivation. They are the biological requirements or universal needs for human survival, such as food, drink, air, shelter, clothing, warmth and sleep. The human body can not function optimally if these needs are not satisfied. Therefore, physiological needs are considered the most important of all other needs (Gawel, 1996).

Content redacted due to copyright restrictions. Original figure can be found in McLeod, 2007.

Figure 3. 2: Maslow's Hierarchy of Needs (McLeod, 2007)

Consequently, once humans satisfy their physiological needs, the needs for safety and security become salient. Individuals want to experience order, predictability and control in their lives. These can be satisfied by family and society, such as police, business, school and medical. If an individual does not feel safe in an environment, they will seek safety before attempting to meet the next level of needs (Lester, 2013).

Accordingly, after fulfilling the physiological and safety needs, the third level of human needs is love and belongingness needs which are interpersonal relationships that motivate behaviour. These

can be friendship, intimacy, acceptance, trust, giving and receiving affection and love (Mitchell and Moudgill, 1976).

The fourth level of Maslow's hierarchy is esteem needs, which can be classified into two categories. Firstly, esteem for oneself can be dignity, achievement, independence and mastery. Secondly, desire for reputation, such as status or prestige (Gawel, 1996).

Finally, the highest level of Maslow's hierarchy is self-actualisation needs which refer to the realisation of a person's potential, self-fulfilment, peak experiences and seeking personal growth. According to the theory, there is a need for personal growth and discovery that is present throughout a person's life (Gawel, 1996).

Attracting consumers for a business is not only essential to proving itself as a successful venture, but the fulfilment of the consumers' needs brings new challenges. By acknowledging these challenges, Euro Garage has effectively designed its convenience stores to fulfil all needs of the traveller. It offers in its store food products and fuels, as well running other service facilities such as toilet facilities for males and females. These conveniences are designed to meet the basic needs of each visiting customer. The customer is, thus, by this theory, likely to pay to satisfy these basic needs. Whether price or other external factors influence the need to have those needs satisfied is not included in Maslow's Theory. The theory is foundational and thus would imply that human is, first and foremost, interested in satisfying their basic needs before all else. Euro Garage customers come to the store with the primary need to satisfy some basic needs and thus will tend towards purchase making more times than not.

3.2.3 Engel, Kollet, Blackwell (EKB) Model of Buyer Behaviour

Researchers Engel, Kollet and Blackwell developed a problem-solving model of the consumer decision-making process known as the EKB model or the Engel-Kollet-Blackwell model in 1968, and the model is still beneficial to marketers today. According to Simon et al. (2013), the Engel-Blackwell-Kollet (EKB) Model explains consumers' decision process in regard to how decisions are made when choosing from a list of alternatives available.

The EKB model is one of the most important models and still works in the field of consumer behaviour. It consists of four major areas, which include information processing, central control unit, decision process and environmental influences. Information processing here includes the exposure, attention, comprehension, and retention of various marketing and non-marketing stimuli. For a more fruitful sales campaign, the consumer will be given utmost importance in the delivery of the message (Simon et al., 2013).

The central control unit is geared toward how the stimuli progress and how the information received by the individual is interpreted. This can be achieved in four major psychological factors such as the process of storage of relevant information, criteria of evaluation, state of mind or attitudes and the personality of the consumer. The satisfaction and dissatisfaction of the decision will only be dependent on the type and the value of the purchased product. This is mainly dependent on environmental influences. (Simon et al., 2013).

Content redacted due to copyright restrictions. Original figure can be found in Holland, 2019.

Figure 2. 2: Engel, Kollet, Blackwell (EKB) Model of Buyer Behaviour (Holland, 2019)

The environmental influences are primarily focused on income, culture, social class, family influences, and physical and other considerations that may give favourable or unfavourable purchase behaviour (Simon et al., 2013).

The model relates to the current study in trying to understand how customer makes their buying decision. It can be theorised that customers to the Euro Garage start their buying process from adverts they see, word of mouth, and more. They pay some attention to these stimuli, begin to evaluate a problem and a need for the product advertised to them, and may then see a need to purchase but consider other factors such as income, family, and more before they make the actual purchase.

If this is so, it becomes imperative that the store managers pay attention to the kind of marketing stimuli they put out there and that their customers are exposed to. Not only that, they must acknowledge that in buying, it does not require the customer's decision alone, but other factors play a key role in deciding for them as well.

For these classes of customers, therefore, pricing may and would play a key role in how they buy as income and family influence determine the eventual outcome in the store.

3.2.4. The Hawkins Stern Impulse Buying Theory

According to Agarwal and Chetty (2019), the Hawkins Stern Impulse Buying theory, which got its name from the proposer, Hawkins Stern, in 1962, offers a fresh perspective on consumers' buying behaviour as most of the contemporary consumer behaviour theories like Maslow's Need Hierarchy Theory of Motivation (1943) and Engel, Kollat and Blackwell (1968) which believed that consumers always make rational and well-planned buying decisions (Dutta and Mandal, 2018).

Indeed, it offers an important consideration for this research, building on the Theory of Planned Behaviour by Ajzen, which does not explain spontaneous, impulsive, habitual or mindless behaviour (Bentler and Speckart, 1979, as cited in Keat, 2009).

Stern made a deviation from the perspective that consumers always made rational decisions and postulated instead that consumers indulged in impulsive buying behaviours under the influence of

external forces. His theory argued that marketers could convince consumers to buy more than what they had actually planned (Dutta and Mandal, 2018, as cited in Agarwal and Chetty, 2019).

Figure 3. 3: The Hawkins Stern Impulse Buying Theory (Rook, 1987)

An important contribution of Hawkins Stern's model is the categorisation of impulse buying behaviour (Shapiro, 2015, as cited in Agarwal and Chetty, 2019). The model suggests four kinds of impulse buying:

3.2.4.1 Pure impulse buying

This includes buying purely on the basis of impulse; hence the customers end up buying something which is not a routine item on their shopping list. Also known as 'escape purchase', it breaks the normal pattern of purchasing (Agarwal and Chetty, 2019).

Visuals play an integral role in pure impulse buying (Dutta and Mandal, 2018). Such purchases generally include items that are new to the customer but that attract visually.

While consumers end up overspending, the marketers earn higher revenues (Agarwal and Chetty, 2019).

3.2.4.2 Suggested impulse buying

Suggested impulse buying occurs in the case of products usually being seen by the customer for the first time, and then the consumer develops an impulse to buy them (Stern, 1962; Dutta and Mandal, 2018, as cited in Agarwal and Chetty, 2019).

In a brick-and-mortar shop, this kind of buying generally happens through the activities of a salesperson.

3.2.4.3 Planned impulse buying

This kind of impulse buying occurs when the customer has the need for a product but is not sure about its specifications. Generally, a lower price or other kinds of sales promotion techniques lead to planned impulse buying (Stern, 1962, as cited in Agarwal and Chetty, 2019).

3.2.4.4 Price as a factor that triggers impulse buying behaviour

According to Agarwal and Chetty (2019), marketers make use of several strategies in order to trigger impulse buying behaviour among consumers. The pricing decision, according to Stern, is the most important trigger for an impulse buying decision. This is because it makes the consumer spend more than they originally planned. However, it is may not be applicable for expensive items such as automobiles. It is most common in products that have a low shelf life, marginal need for

the consumer, are of a smaller size and have ease of storage. Marginal need for an item with short shelf life triggers impulse buying.

Since consumers have to purchase them repeatedly, they spend less time planning to buy them and hence purchase them when they encounter them (Stern, 1962). This refers to the degree of need for an item, for example, many convenience goods such as daily staples, milk, bread and sugar for which regular purchases are made. However, some items are non-convenience goods, so there is a marginal need for them. The consumer postpones purchasing these items until there is a greater degree of need for it. Hence these purchases are likely to be less planned and more impulsive (Chhabra, 2010, as cited in Agarwal and Chetty (2019)).

Mass distribution and self-service

As cited in Agarwal and Chetty (2019), the more places a product is available, the more chances the customer will buy it. Since impulse buying is not planned, marketers make the product available at multiple locations to have more chances of a customer buying it (Stern, 1962).

The self-service option gives the customer the opportunity to freely explore their options and buy more quickly. Since there are many products readily available for the consumer, they are more likely to buy products impulsively. Hence marketers prefer to make their products available more at self-service locations (Iyer and Ahlawat, 1987).

Prominent store displays and advertisements trigger impulse buying

As impulse buying decisions are not planned, increased visibility of items increases their sale impulsively. This positioning includes shelf location, distinctive packaging and in-store promotions (Mohan, Sivakumaran and Sharma, 2013).

Ease of storage

Items which can be stored easily without any special requirements are more likely to be purchased impulsively. The size and weight of a product have a profound impact on a consumer's decision to purchase an item impulsively. Heavyweight or big size requires a buyer to make special arrangements such as transportation. This can reduce the chances of buying it impulsively (Stern, 1962).

Yu and Bastin (2010, as cited in Muruganantham and Bhakat, 2013) found that impulse buying varies across a broad range of product categories which include clothes, books and equipment for exercise.

Hawkins Stern's Theory must be seen as a welcome relief to marketers and managers who may now know the integral role they can play in the customers' buying process. Managers, by this theory, know they have the power to get the customer to buy more than they had planned to, thus meeting revenue targets.

Although they must be careful how they execute this or how much they should rely on this so it does not backfire, consumers would tend towards impulsion if the right factor and motivation are present.

One of the edges of the Euro Garages stores will be in their stocking of well known, proprietary brand products and products of need in their stores. Marketing managers may then count on this, among other strategies, to help induce, create or increase impulse buying with their customers who go into the stores. To these classes of customers, pricing would rarely influence how they buy.

The researcher nonetheless believes that it may be counterproductive to rely heavily on impulse buying to ramp up sales. Instead, managers can balance this with the rational, well-planned action of the customer in addition to their needs motivation. In other words, strike a balance between the essential elements of the TPB, Maslow's Needs Theory and Stern's Impulse Buying theory, to come up with an almost complete and wholesome picture that explains how their customers buy and the role pricing has in that process.

3.2.5 Pavlovian Theory

According to Husson University Online (2018), the Pavlovian theory is a learning procedure that involves pairing a stimulus with a conditioned response.

In the famous experiments that Ivan Pavlov conducted with his dogs, Pavlov found that objects or events could trigger a conditioned response. The experiments began with Pavlov demonstrating how the presence of a bowl of dog food (stimulus) would trigger an unconditioned response (salivation). But Pavlov noticed that the dogs started to associate his lab assistant with food, creating a learned and conditioned response. This was an important scientific discovery.

Pavlov then designed an experiment using a bell as a neutral stimulus. As he gave food to the dogs, he rang the bell. Then, after repeating this procedure, he tried ringing the bell without providing

food to the dogs. On its own, an increase in salivation occurred. The result of the experiment was a new conditioned response in the dogs (Husson University, 2018). Pavlov's theory later developed into classical conditioning, which refers to learning that associates an unconditioned stimulus that already results in a response (such as a reflex) with a new, conditioned stimulus. As a result, the new stimulus brings about the same response.

Figure 3. 4: Pavlovian Theory (Lashley and Wade 1946)

The Pavlovian theory can be applied to consumer behaviour in the form of the response that some consumers have when they hear the word “sale.” It can generate an urge to shop even if people have no specific need at the time (Husson University Online, 2018).

The theory can also work with specific brands. A consumer may start associating a brand name or product with a certain perception after repeated marketing efforts and/or experience with the brand or product. As consumers receive verified experiences with brands, a conditioned response is possible (Husson University Online, 2018).

The pricing strategies by the Euro Garage stores will based on this theory, play a role in determining how their customers buy. A number of studies have shown that consumers, more often than not, respond favourably to promo, sales and discount pricing.

One of the pricing strategies employed by the Euro Garage stores is the promotional pricing strategy, which is expected to attract customers into purchasing and improve sales in the long run.

3.3 Research Framework

In their work on intuitive pricing by managers of petrol convenience stores, Benoit et al. (2020) conceptualised a framework that showed the interplay between managerial and consumer factors associated with pricing decisions.

Here, individual beliefs about how consumers perceive and respond to pricing influence pricing decisions, which determines their behaviour in setting prices. On the other hand, product-level price image influence consumer acceptance and behaviour, including purchase decision. (Benoit et al., 2020).

In a nutshell, a manager chooses a price that consumers or the market accept or reject by buying or not buying. Over time, the manager, from consumer purchase behaviours, may adjust their

pricing beliefs and practices accordingly. (Benoit et al., 2020). Though the managers employed the 3C's of pricing (cost, customers, competition), they deviated slightly from their underlying principle (Benoit et al., 2020).

In a further bid to understand consumer buying behaviour in selecting and at fuel service stations, Kakunu (2012) anchored on the Blackwell and Kotler Models of Consumer Decision Making Process. It was found that in making product choices, customers followed the needs recognition models of Blackwell and Kotler, although skipping some steps. They were highly influenced by their social circle in the form of family and/or friends. Alvi. et al. (2016) found that people got excited and motivated by rewards and discounts if it was of significant value to them.

This study will draw on the Theories of Planned Behaviour, Motivation's Need, Impulse Buying and Pavillion theory to understand the buying behaviour of Euro Garage customers. The study finds that it cannot anchor on a single theory as each has its criticism, and a newer theory serves to strengthen an existing one.

For example, Ajzen's Theory of Planned Behaviour is not without its criticism. According to Keats (2009), predicting behaviour is the ultimate goal of the theory, but it does not explain the behaviour (Conner and Sparks, 2005, as cited in Keat, 2009). The TPB also does not explain how well the intentions predict the behaviour (Sommer, 2011); neither does it explain spontaneous, impulsive, habitual or mindless behaviour because these behaviours might not be voluntary or performing such behaviours does not entail any conscious decision-making process (Bentler and Speckart, 1979 as cited in Keat, 2009).

The Engel-Blackwell-Kollet model also has its shortcomings. According to Osei and Abebyin (2016), although the EKB Model has been slightly modified, for instance, consumption and divestment are other variables that were included in the revised model, which, according to some researchers, is one of its major key strengths because the added factors embrace contemporary definitions of consumer behaviour which include such stages of consumption in their scope (Solomon 2006; Schiffman and Kanuk 2008 as cited in Osei and Abebyin, 2016), the model suffers the weakness of a clear definition of variables, vagueness and complexity.

The model attempts to define the variables and specify functional relationships between the various constructs (Osei and Abebyin, 2016). However, it fails to adequately explain how each of these influences consumer decision making. In the view of Loudon and Bitta (2002), as cited in Osei and Abebyin (2016), the environmental and individual variables have drawn criticism due to the vagueness of their definition and role within the decision process.

The EKB model has also been criticised as being too restrictive to adequately accommodate the variety of consumer decision situations (Osei and Abebyin, 2016). According to the authors, the EKB model, like other consumer decision theories, suggests that a consumer's purchase decision process consists of stages through which the consumer goes through in purchasing a product or service; however, it is not necessary for every consumer to go through all stages when making a decision to purchase and in fact, some of the stages can be skipped. It rather depends on the situation in which the consumer find themselves (Osei and Abebyin, 2016).

Content redacted due to copyright restrictions. Original figure can be found in Blackwell et al. 2001.

Figure 3. 5: Consumer Decision Model
Source: Blackwell et al. (2001)

By drawing on the four distinct but subtly connecting theories of Planned Behaviour, Motivation's Need, Impulse Buying and Pavillion theory, it is theorised in this study that the majority of customers to the Euro Garage come to the store primarily with an intent to buy a product.

The store offers the solution they seek by stocking on basic needs items, and although several external factors may influence how and what they will eventually buy, products on sales or promos will attract them to buy on impulse or buy more. In other words, pricing may play a role in influencing how they buy but only in enticing them to buy more or off their shopping list, as the

majority of the customers will still make a purchase regardless of the pricing strategy in place because they already came into the store with an intent to buy.

Besides the above theoretical frameworks, the work of Philip Kotler (1988) on "*Marketing Management: Analysis, planning, implementation and control*" present a unique framework of analysis for pricing strategy and consumer behavioural patterns. Kotler, who has considered the father of marketing, developed his Pricing Strategies, also known as the Nine Quality-Pricing Strategies since it is a matrix covering nine options. Precisely, the objective of this framework is to assist companies to position their products and or services in relation to their competitors in the market, as well as implementing pricing strategies according to the quality that is delivered to the customers. According to Kotler opined that "you can use the Price-Quality Strategy Model to review competitors' product and services and review their strategies. Why do they charge more? Why do they charge less? Sometimes if an aspect of a service is removed, this can contribute to lower prices (Kotler, 1988).

Indeed, the uniqueness of the Kotler model is the ability to relate pricing to the quality of products and services delivered. Kotler Framework/Model take a form of a nine-box matrix. While along the left side are three levels of product quality; low, medium and high. Across the top are levels of price; High, Medium and Low. However, Kotler's most frequently used strategies are based on different objectives, including, among others:

1. Maximum current profit objective: This is a premium strategy. Here, there are few competitors but with a stronger brand demand; hence a high price can be set.

2. Product Quality Leadership objective: It is a high-value strategy where a higher quality product or service is provided and more expensive components are used.
3. Survival objective: This can be said to be a "buying work" or, better still, a strategy that ensures dropping the price to gain market share. It is said to be a good value or economic strategy
4. Maximum sales growth objective: This strategy is similar to the low pricing strategy and involves setting a low price to capture market share initially; then, when the market grows and costs decrease, costs are reduced further (Hanlon, 2022, p.2).

Find below Kotler Pricing Strategy Matrix: This is often used when consumers need change or when competitors move into a market.

Content redacted due to copyright restrictions. Original figure can be found in Hanloh, 2022.

Figure 3. 6: Kotler Pricing Strategy Matrix

Source: Adapted from Hanloh, (2022)

Other frameworks and models of pricing and consumer behaviour include the earlier work of Howard, who developed the first consumer decision model in 1963 and further revised by Howard and Sheth in 1969. Precisely, the model provides " a sophisticated integration of various social, psychological and marketing influences on consumer choice into a coherent sequence of information processing" (Foxall, 1990, p.10). This comprehensive model is utilised to analyse a wide range of purchasing scenarios.

3.4 Theoretical Framework of the Research:

Figure 3. 7: The Theory of pricing and consumer buying behaviour. (Adopted by the researcher)

From the above framework for this study, the model is a simple one depicting the determinants of consumer purchase decisions. As illustrated in the model, these determinants areas are outlined on the left-hand side, pricing strategies, which inform or influence consumer characteristics variables. The variables on both sides constitute a decision problem for the consumer's decision to buy, i.e., purchase or not. This framework highlights the mutually reinforcing effect of pricing strategies (Left side variables) on the Right side variables (Consumer Characteristics), both of which constitute a decisional behaviour before the rational consumer. However, given the consumer desire to buy and the service station/garage intention to sell more, problem-solving schemes sets in with mutually reinforcing pricing strategies and consumer characteristics. While the consumer wants to buy valuable goods and services, they must first prioritise their need recognition, followed by an information search of favourable pricing strategies while evaluating available alternatives before making their final buying decision (Purchase or Not Purchase). Therefore, this theoretical framework developed for this study clearly shows a causal relationship between pricing strategies and consumer characteristics and how this affects the purchase decision of a consumer.

3.5 Chapter Summary

This chapter presented an overview of a number of theories that exist within the consumer behaviour space. These theories provide a framework on which this study is based.

The theory of planned behaviour provides fundamental knowledge to understand human beliefs and behaviour by measuring overall attitude towards objects. Motivation need theory focuses on consumer psychology containing a five-tier model of human needs. EKB Model of buyer Behaviour explains how decisions are made when choosing the list of alternatives. Hawkins Stern's

impulse buying theory explains that marketers can convince consumers to buy more than what they had actually planned. The pavlovian theory provides famous experiments and found that objects could trigger a conditioned response.

These will guide the study in its attempt at providing answers to its research questions.

The next chapter highlights the research methodology that was followed in this study to obtain data.

CHAPTER FOUR

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

4.1 Introduction

The research methodology is a systematic and methodical process that gives an idea of the tools and techniques important in guiding the research in collecting, analysing and interpreting data (Collis and Hussey, 2009). It is a process that provides information and a clear guide on how to undertake research and investigate the unknown to solve a problem (Maylor and Blackmon, 2005). According to Leedy and Ormrod (2015, p.20), research refers to a "systematic process of collecting, analysing, and interpreting information or data to increase the understanding of a phenomenon about which one is interested".

The research methodology is, therefore, the theoretical framework for undertaking research (Ade Bilau, Witt and Lill, (2018). It justifies the technical framework that is applied in producing the data and analyses towards knowledge creation (Gray, 2014). Clear research purpose, a systematic way of data collection and a systematic way of interpreting collected data are the three main characteristics of research (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2014). Therefore, to meet the characteristics of actual scientific research, a research methodology should be adopted by the researcher, which refers to the various scientific techniques and systematic methods to generate scientific knowledge (Kothari, 2004).

This chapter highlights the various tools and techniques that have been used to collect and analyse information for answering the research questions as well as meeting the aims and objectives of the research (Yin, 2012).

The current study explores how pricing impacts consumer buying behaviour, with the Euro Garage in the United Kingdom as a case study. This section presents the research process employed to include justification of the research approach used, research philosophies assumed in carrying out the research, research strategies, choices, time horizon, and the techniques or procedures of data collection and data analysis following Saunders Research methods for business students. This chapter also describes the researcher's main methodological choice that has been taken in every stage of the research process, along with the rationale and justification behind each methodological decision made.

The study is primary in which data will be collected using survey questionnaires from customers and semi-structured interviews with managers at the store. This is to provide an insight on the influence or impact various pricing strategies have on the buying behaviour of the customers to the store.

Pragmatist research philosophy, which describes the real facts and information from the literature to conclude (Williams & May 2000), has also been employed in this research. The inductive and deductive research approaches were considered in the study as they were suited to an explorative research design. Sampling techniques were employed to select respondents for the interview data collection. Respondents for Qualitative data collection were obtained using snowball sampling, while convenience non-probability sampling was employed in selecting respondents for the survey questionnaire. Research validity and ethics are also discussed in this chapter.

4.2 Research Design /Nature

The research design provides a framework for the collection and analysis of data that reflects decisions about the priority being given to a range of dimensions of the research process”(. Byrman, 2016, p.40). It is the overarching plan for the collection, measurement and analysis of data which describes the purpose of the study and the kinds of questions being addressed, the techniques to be used for collecting data, approaches to selecting a sample, and how the data are going to be analysed" (Gray, 2014, p. 128).

Different authors describe research design as an interplay of qualitative and quantitative research methods. Others argue that it is a specific method of data collection and analysis. In this research, the research method is defined as a general plan and process to answer the research questions. It can be classified based on the purpose of the research (Gray, 2014).

According to Robson (2002), exploratory, descriptive and explanatory are the three possible forms of the research study based on the nature of research. Additionally, Maxwell (1996) adds interpretive studies along with them. In general, an exploratory study asks open questions to explore what is happening and gain topics insights. They are predominantly useful when there is not enough knowledge about the situation.

A prime objective of this research is to investigate the unseen impact of pricing strategies on consumer buying behaviour at Euro Garages; hence, an exploration of the factors becomes essential to analyse the existing problem in this study.

An exploratory research design effectively brings new changes in the existing literature by emphasising hidden factors (Hart, 2003). In this kind of study, where such information is not available related to the dependent factors, a researcher must conduct an exploratory study to carry out the expected findings (Kothari, 1985).

To familiarise me with the research concepts, the researcher undertook preliminary work. Consumers and managers of Euro Garages were the sources for this review and work. The store managers were interviewed, and survey questionnaires were distributed to their customers. This was done to investigate the way consumers responded to the marketing decisions on pricing as implemented by the store's managers. This is especially significant as the store under study is not a stand-alone, but a forecourt convenience store to a petrol filling station.

Content redacted due to copyright restrictions. Original figure can be found in Saunders et al. 2014.

Figure 4. 1: Research onion (Saunders et al., 2014)

The figure above shows the "research onion" by Saunders et al. Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill (2014) described the entire research process as a sequence, breaking it down into different layers called 'research onion'. Although the layers are separated eventually, they all are interrelated. The decision of the choice of the inner layer depends on the choice of the outer layer.

Research onion is an important part of the research methodology, which tells the researchers about the various methods adopted in the research (Crowther & Lancaster, 2009). The research onion helps a researcher conduct the research properly and systematically, but it is not assumed as the individual tool for the evaluation and data analysis. It is mostly assumed as the set of the six different tools which are used in the research (Stentz, Plano Clark and Matkin, 2012) and which can be used in a systematic way to carry out the research study, and these all the six elements are considered as the layers of the onion.

In undertaking the current research study, qualitative and quantitative data were sought; hence inductive and deductive research approaches were suitable to conclude.

4.3 Research Philosophy

Research philosophy describes a theory or methods of knowledge development in a particular field and describes various beliefs and assumptions that underlie the research approaches (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2014). It is the way of research embarking and attempts the study to develop knowledge (Guba and Lincoln, 1994). The assumptions are mostly concerned with the nature of reality and how we can know reality (Maylor and Blackmon, 2005). Furthermore, it is the way to present the study and the solution to the resolving problem. Similarly, it refers to how researchers

view the nature of the world and belief in what acceptable knowledge is. Assumptions are indispensable to the perception of viewing the world (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2014).

At every research stage, the researcher makes various types of assumptions. Nature of society and nature of science are two major dimensions for researchers while making various assumptions and developing philosophical positions (Burrell and Morgan, 2017). The assumption about human knowledge and the nature of reality that encounter in the research helps the researcher to understand the research questions and the appropriate methods and to interpret the findings (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2014; Maylor and Blackmon, 2005). However, it also can be explained by the researcher in which way views the world (Saunders et al., 2004). The assumption is the construct of research strategy where methods as part of that strategy.

Similarly, Collis and Hussey (2009) demonstrate that Research philosophy is the nature of the study that helps or develops knowledge of how research is conducted. It develops the knowledge incrementally, extends vocabulary with high confidence and provides a valuable framework for experiencing the ideas about the research (Collis and Hussey, 2009). Similarly, Collins (2010) described Research philosophy as a method or a way in which the whole of the research is conducted. It categorises the whole research into specific nature which suits the research hypothesis or research question (Collins, 2010). In detail, research philosophy is usually described as a belief in which the data about a particular phenomenon should be collected with care.

Philosophical commitments are significantly important for business and management research because they allow for designing an intelligible research project where all elements of research fit

together, which will drive the research into data collection and analysis (Caeswell, 2014). According to Creswell (2014), research philosophy is necessary at every stage during the study process of its effect on understanding the research subject dimensions. Conventionally, Ontology, Epistemology and Axiology are the three fundamentals of the research process; however, Ontology and epistemology are the two major ways of thinking about any research philosophy (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2014). Each highlights the philosophical approaches that determine the approach should be and influence how researchers think about the research process derived from research questions. The basic understanding concept of research philosophy enables the researcher to assist different types of methodologies and to be more exploratory and creative in the method of research while at the same time avoiding unsuitable and unrelated works.

Ontology: - According to Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill (2014, p.130), "ontology is concerned with the nature of reality. This raises questions about the assumptions researchers to have about how the world operates and the commitment to a particular view." In general, ontology deals with the nature of existence or reality (Maylor and Blackmon, 2005). Gray (2014) also described ontology as a study of being and the nature of existence, and what constitutes reality. According to Carson, Gilmore, Perry, and Gronhaug (2001), Ontology is the nature of reality and epistemology describes the linking between the researcher and the reality of how this reality is observed.

The word ontology comes from two Greek words, "Onto" (being real, or what existence) and "Logi" (Science, or Study). The word ontology is used in a philosophical context in business research. In research philosophy, ontology is the study of what exists and what is real. Researchers

use this concept of ontology to discuss questions, theories, and models, consequently, better understanding the ontological status of the world. This philosophical study focus on the nature of existence, being, becoming or reality.

Consequently, Bryman and Bell (2015) explain ontology as some assumptions about the nature of social entities. And it develops the understanding of how researchers see the natural world of business differently. The position of research ontology is critical realism, which posits the research that reality can be understood imperfectly and probabilistically as, in general, the human aspect impedes its complete understanding (Guba & Lincoln, 1994; Howell, 2013).

Objectivism and subjectivism are the two aspects of ontology where both have their devotees among business and management researchers, where both are accepted as producing valid knowledge (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2014). Objectivism is the first aspect of ontology as it describes the position that social objects persist in reality external to social actors. Subjectivism is the second aspect of ontology where it holds the social phenomena which are emerged from the perceptions and consequences of those social actors concerned with their existence (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2014).

Objectivism: Objectivism describes the position of social entities that exist in reality (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2014). This portrays the position that social entities exist in reality external to social actors concerned with their existence. According to Glynn and Woodside (2009), in objectivism, the researcher can independently gather data, and the knowledge can gain objective and real. The objectivist approach to social research developed from the natural sciences – social

science researchers decided to employ the highly successful methods of the natural sciences to investigate social science phenomena.

However, the objectivists view the formal structural position of management where they get particular job descriptions to prescribe the roles (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2014). Bryman (2016) also describes every organisation as a tangible object structured with rules and regulations for getting things done. People are appointed for various divisions of labour, where they have to learn those rules and regulations to apply for their jobs. However, the objectivist belief that reality exists independently and human beings have a direct relation with reality exists through different sense perceptions.

Subjectivism: Subjectivism simply describes that Social phenomena are created from the various perceptions and consequent social actor's actions (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2014). This social phenomenon is continuously revising through endless social interaction. However, in subjectivists, it is believed that consumers are social actors who interpret a situation based on their world perception and through their environmental interaction. Subjectivism is a fundamentally social mode that comes with numerous interactions within society. The social actors describe the situation from their view of the world.

Epistemology: Epistemology is a philosophical position that describes the constitutes acceptable knowledge in the research. Epistemology is simply a theory of knowledge; it is the branch of philosophy that studies whether we can know things with certainty, how we know things and what

counts as knowledge. According to Carson, Gilmore, Perry, and Gronhaug (2001), epistemology describes the linking between the researcher and the reality of how this reality is observed.

According to Gray (2014, p 19), "epistemology provides a philosophical background for deciding what kinds of knowledge are legitimate and adequate". Gilbert (2008) described epistemological orientation as an approach to developing knowledge and theory based on how the world works. The general theory is the form of organising and explaining knowledge in epistemology (Crowther and Lancaster, 2009). Crowther and Lancaster (2009) also have described that epistemology is a perfect and easy way of understanding and explaining what we know about it and how we apply it to achieve a specific objective.

On the other hand, Molina, Azorín and Cameron (2010) said that epistemology is mainly concerned with providing the philosophical ground for deciding on what kind of knowledge is possible and further how the research can ensure that these are both adequate and legitimate. Easterby-Smith, Thorpe and Jackson (2013) point out several reasons for epistemological perspectives inquiring about the nature of the social and physical worlds. Firstly, it can help clarify the issues of research design. It helps the researcher to decide the kind of data required and how to collect as well as interpret the information in order to meet the research questions answer and research objectives. Secondly, it helps the researcher identify which design, thereby or research methodology will fit appropriately for the research and which will not (Gray 2014). Thirdly, epistemology can contribute to improving knowledge of new research designs.

There are many epistemological positions identified by reviewing the literature on research methodology. These include positivism, interpretivism, realism, and pragmatism (Saunders, Lewis, and Thornhill, 2014), positivism and interpretivism (Collis and Hussey, 2009), positivism, interpretivism, critical inquiry, feminism, postmodernism and pragmatism (Gray, 2014), positivism and social constructionism (Easterby-Smith, Thorpe and Jackson, 2013) and postpositivism, constructivism, transformative and pragmatism (Creswell, 2014). Despite these criticisms, the popularity of positivism and interpretivism remains higher in the research paradigm with others. Furthermore, Collis and Hussey (2009) attributed that most business research broadly uses either positivism or interpretivism paradigm research. However, according to Guba and Lincoln (1994), epistemology seeks to answer two questions below.

- A) How do we know the world?
- B) What is the relationship between the inquirer and the known?

4.3.1 Types of Research Philosophies

Several research paradigms are distinct in terms of assumptions and beliefs, including data or information for concluding as realism research philosophy targets the existing realities and the beliefs concerning the issue related to the common feeling, perceptions and experiences (Creswell, 2009). The second paradigm is known as constructivism which tells the researchers to focus on the real facts

.

The positivism research approach is mainly used by scientists due to its relation to objectivism. Scientific studies are related to the real problem. Positivism also describes post-positivism, which emphasises the imperfect way through which the target can be easily achieved. It is confirmed by

Creswell (2009) that reality is not the reality and is usually held the belief which is usually enforced by the general warrants. While concerning with the pragmatism research philosophy, major attention goes on the issue of interpretation of the problems of the world from a different perspective. According to Robson (2002), there is not only a single way to reach a conclusion or the target, but several approaches can be used for concluding using a different approach. Researcher consciousness provides consistency for this study, and properly integrating one part to another is handled appropriately.

4.3.1.1 Positivism Research Philosophy

Under the positivism research philosophy, the researcher adheres to “factual” knowledge, which is gained through observation (the senses), experiment and measurement (Collis and Hussey, 2009).

In the positivism research philosophy, the researcher's role is limited to collecting data and interpreting it as per the research objective with the deductive approach (Gray, 2014). Positivism research philosophy is based on the assumption that it is quantifiable and can easily be handled using statistical research tools as it holds more quantitative than qualitative research (Creswell, 2014). It allows the researcher to apply highly structured scientific methods and follow specific structures that facilitate replication and data collection to develop hypotheses from existing theories (Gill and Johnson, 2010). The hypotheses can be tested for further research or development of the theory (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2014). It helps the researcher focus on quantifiable observations, which can be statistically analysed (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2014).

This approach warns the researcher to focus on interdependency on the study's objective, which is available to senses (seen, smelt, touched) (Gray, 2018). The interdependent focus over the less interaction with the researcher respondent but focuses on the facts and information that comes from the theoretical background (Creswell, 2014). In another way, it can be said that the positivism research paradigm mainly focuses on the facts and consider the world to be external and objective (Hart, 2003). Neuman (2000) described that the positivists that reality is a thing that is quite stable and is observed as well described from a crucial viewpoint.

It does not affect the phenomenon in which the whole study is going because it tests the theories and provides information for the development of laws (Bryman, 2016). It focuses on the thing that the phenomenon should be isolated well as the observations should also be repeatable. It sometimes relates the thing with reality and the variations in the only single dependent variable to identify the regularities so that the relationships can be easily made among the constituent parts (Ritchie & Lewis, 2003). It has been embedded in society to a deep extent and is simply assumed as the scientific and invalid. Neuman (2000) said the empirical studies were positive in approach. Additionally, it helps the researcher to focus on quantifiable observation, which can be statistically analysed (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2014).

4.3.1.2 Interpretivism research philosophy

This research philosophy is considered the key to the research for analysing natural phenomena or environments (Schwandt, 2000). It is also assumed that there may be different forms of reality and that these are regarded as an important and crucial part of scientific knowledge (Black, 2006).

Interpretivism highly believes the social reality is subjective, not objective, like positivism, because it's shaped by human experience (Collis and Hussey, 2009).

The key difference between interpretivism and positivism is that interpretivism focuses on exploring social phenomena; on the other hand, positivism focuses on measuring social phenomena. Therefore, interpretivism usually adopts qualitative methods rather than quantitative that describe the social world by analysing the human mind (Van Maane, 1983).

In this research, interpretivism philosophy was employed so that respondents' views could be interpreted as per the research problem to analyse the existing issues (Creswell, 2014).

Interpretivism tends toward qualitative due to data collection, which is usually unstructured interviews or participant observations (Gray, 2014).

4.3.1.3 Realism research philosophy

Realism research philosophy focuses on ideas independent of the human mind and sensible reality (Saunders, Lewis & Thornhill, 2014). Philosophical position realism reflects that what we can sense is reality. Scientific assumptions are used in this philosophy to develop the knowledge and understanding of the research problem. According to Bryman (2016), realism is similar to positivism, which believes that natural science and social science can be used in the same kind of research approach to collect data, explain and communicate the researcher's view of the external reality is separated from our descriptions. Hence, knowledge is developed through a theory-building process that is already discovered (Gray, 2014).

Realism is the opposite of idealism (Crotty, 1998), where the mind and its contents exist. According to Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill (2014), realism is an epistemological position similar

to positivism, where scientific methods are used to develop knowledge. Therefore, it is a systematic analysis process of natural phenomena (Gray, 2014). Gray (2014) also defines that, in general, realism believes that there is an external reality that can be measurable. However, sometimes those can be very difficult to measure even if a scientist cannot access reality directly (Easterby-Smith, Thorpe and Jackson, 2013). Therefore, the researcher rely on indirect evidence in order to develop knowledge.

This research philosophy has been divided into two major groups: direct realism and critical realism. According to Saunders, Lewis & Thornhill (2012), realism relates to scientific enquiry that describes what we can see in reality. Realism is similar to positivism which underpins a scientific approach to developing knowledge. Direct realism and critical realism are two forms of realism contrasted for business and management research.

4.3.1.4 Pragmatic research philosophy

Pragmatic research philosophy only allows for the concepts that affect the study (Kelemen and Rumens, 2008). Pragmatics portrays the different ways to recognise the external world and interpret it. No single view can give the entire picture of the world; hence the world might have many realities so that the researcher can interpret the world in many different ways (Saunders, Lewis, and Thornhill, 2014).

According to Collis and Hussey (2009), the researcher should have the freedom to choose a mixed method to answer the research question from various paradigms. This approach attempt to "cross the divide between the qualitative and the quantitative and the positivist and the non-positivist"

(Curran and Blackburn, 2001, p.123). The pragmatic research philosophy includes more information to make the study valuable by using much collecting and analysing data (Creswell, 2014).

4.3.2 Justification of Chosen Research Philosophy

The current research aimed to explore how product-pricing decisions impacted consumer buying behaviour at fuel service stations convenience stores by examining the mediating role of consumer emotion and interviewing store managers.

This was achieved through testing various pricing models and embarking on a deeper understanding of the phenomena being researched. In order to meet the research aims and objectives, the researcher followed a laid-down sequence of steps, which was, analysing the relevant existing literature and then identifying the research idea. Next, was develop research hypotheses, collected and analysed data and finally drew the findings.

In addition, one of the study's research questions hinged on how pricing influenced the consumer's purchase behaviour from the organisation's perspective. Thus, interpretative research philosophy became better suited to the study than positivism philosophy as the researcher required a deepened understanding of the social phenomena.

The focus here was on pricing strategy and consumer buying behaviour from the organisation's perspective; the findings were not precisely derived from quantitative data and statistical analysis. Employing the Interpretivist approach here is thus in line with Collis and Hussey (2009, p.57),

who state that "interpretivism.....rests on the assumption that social reality is in our mind, and is subjective and multiple. Therefore, social reality is affected by the act of investigating it. This research involves an inductive process to provide an interpretive understanding of social phenomena within a particular context".

The organisational perspective of how pricing strategy influences consumers' buying behaviour can be understood by seeing what meaning people give to it and interpreting their meanings from their perceptions (Blumberg et al., 2008). Finally, this part of the research "seeks to describe, translate and otherwise come to terms with meaning, not the frequency of certain less naturally occurring phenomena in the social world" (Van Maanen, 1983,p.9).

On the other hand, another research question in this study was how pricing influenced the way the consumer bought in the store from the consumer's perspective. The positivist approach and paradigm were more suited to employing survey questionnaires to answer this question.

The researchers believed that "the social world exists externally, and that its properties should be measured through objective methods, rather than being inferred subjectively through sensation, reflection or intuition" (Easterby-Smith et al., 2012, p.75).

Finally, it can be presumed that this research objective was based on the assumption that it is quantifiable and can easily be handled using statistical research tools (Creswell, 2014).

Pragmatic research philosophy is used when positivism and interpretivism are included in the same study to present and interpret the qualitative and quantitative data (Johnson and Onwuegbuzie,

2004). Pragmatic philosophy is a combinational philosophy that allows for the inclusion of numerical and non-numerical data in a study to interpret the result (Curran and Blackburn, 2001).

Table 4. 1: Research Philosophy

Content redacted due to copyright restrictions. Original table can be found in Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2014.

Source: Adopted from Saunders, Lewis & Thornhill (2014).

This research employed the pragmatist approach to support the qualitative and quantitative research study (Collis and Hussey, 2009). It was particularly relevant to this study as the research questions do not suggest clearly either interpretive or positivist approaches or which of the two to be adopted (Ihuah and Eaton, 2013).

In answering how pricing influenced the consumer's buying behaviour from the organisation's perspective, interpretive research philosophy was more appropriate than positivist as it adopts qualitative methods rather than quantitative that describe the social world by analysing the human mind (Van Maane, 1983).

At the same time, to answer how pricing strategy influenced how the customer purchased from their perspective, the positivist approach was more appropriate than the Interpretivist approach as it was based on quantifiable assumptions.

By requiring two different philosophical positions, the pragmatist approach was therefore considered well suited to the research. It allowed for the possibility of working with both positivism and interpretivism positions within this single study (Saunders, Lewis, & Thornhill, 2014). With the help of the pragmatist research philosophy, the researcher can integrate qualitative and quantitative methods within this single study that aims to utilise the strengths of both (Gray, 2018).

4.4 Research Approach and Rationale for Choice

According to Bryman and Bell (2011), the research approach describes the researcher's views of the relationship between the theory and research. The research approach plays a vital role in research and includes the three different natures to present and analyse the research problem (Schwandt, 2000). However, based on the researcher's logic, the research approach mainly differentiates into two major approaches: deductive and inductive (Saunders, Lewis, & Thornhill, 2014).

In the deductive approach, "the researcher starts with a general theory then applies this theory to a specific case." In the inductive approach, "the researcher observes specific phenomena and, on this basis, arrives at a general conclusion" (Sekaran, and Bougie, 2009, p.28). The deductive approach usually tests the validity of the assumptions, which are usually made from existing literature. On

the other hand, the inductive form of the approach contributes a lot to the emergence of new and real theories (Ritchie & Lewis, 2003).

In general, the inductive approach begins with observations to understand why it is happening rather than what is happening (Hyde, 2000). The research approach is an important element of the research methodology, which helps in guiding the process of the interpretation of the data. The selection of a suitable research approach is, therefore, crucial a task, and it can be challenging to pick the one that is appropriate and that meets the research aims and objectives.

4.4.1 Deductive Research Approach

The deductive approach illustrates the study in a theoretical and conceptual structure to develop and test the existing theory or hypothesis by empirical observation (Collis and Hussey, 2009). Usually, this approach shifts the research from general to specific or particular. According to Barman and Bell (2011), the deductive approach is broken into six several assumptions starting with the theory, developing hypotheses, collecting data, findings, hypotheses confirmation or rejection, and finally revising the theory.

A deductive approach mostly involves developing a theory or hypothesis from existing literature and coming up with the research strategy to test the hypothesis (Saunders, Lewis, and Thornhill, 2014). It also helps the researcher move from general to specific (Collis and Hussey, 2009). Search for causal relationships between variables, quantitative data collection in most cases, the use of high structure methodologies, concepts operationalisation that helps in measurement, and generalisation, are the five main characterises of the deductive approach (Robson, 2002).

Blaikie (2010) described six sequential steps in the deductive approach, as cited by Saunders, Lewis, and Thornhill (2012, p.145).

- Put forward a tentative idea, a premise, a hypothesis (a testable proposition about the relationship between two or more concepts or variables) or a set of hypotheses to form a theory.
- By using existing literature or by specifying the conditions under which the theory is expected to hold, deduce a testable proposition or number of propositions.
- Examine the premises and the logic of the argument that produced them, comparing this argument with existing theories to see if it offers an advance in understanding. If it does, then continue
- Test the premises by collecting appropriate data to measure the concepts or variables and analysing them.
- If the results of the analysis are not consistent with the premises (the test fails!), the theory is false and must either be rejected or modified and the process restarted.
- If the results of the analysis are consistent with the premises, then the theory is corroborated.
- This approach is highly appropriate when the sample is large to generate comparable results (David and Sutton, 2011). It is also effectively suited to quantitative data (Ritchie et al., 2014).

4.4.2 Inductive Research Approach

An inductive approach is a process where the researcher observes a particular phenomenon and generates conclusions (Cavana, Delahaye and Sekaran, 2001). This approach cannot be used to check or test a hypothesis as there is not sufficient data; hence the inductive approach is a theory-generation process (Sekaran and Bougie, 2009).

Building theory is the main aim of this approach, where the researcher uses a particular event to generate data (Saunders, Lewis & Thornhill, 2012). It does not include the formulation of the hypothesis and usually starts with questions about the research aims and its objectives, which are needed to be achieved during the research process (Hair et al., 2007).

The inductive research approach, also known as inductive reasoning, starts with an observation of empirical reality, and the result of the observation will be proposed as a theory at the end of the research process (Collins and Hussey, 2009). Codes are characteristically identified in this approach from the data themselves, rather than using codes from existing literature or from the researcher's own beliefs and knowledge of a particular topic (Wagner, Kawulich and Garner, 2012).

The inductive research approach has been adopted by social scientists where the researcher tries to get a feel of what is happening around for better understanding (Saunders, Lewis & Thornhill, 2012). Small samples of subjects are more appropriate than large samples under this approach, and qualitative methods are used in order to see the different views of phenomena (Easterby-Smith, Thorpe, and Jackson, 2013).

4.4.3 Abductive Research Approach

Talking about the abductive form of the research approach, which is usually devoted to the explanation and discussion of the incomplete observation, facts and puzzles, which are usually specified at the starting point of the discussion (Littlejohn & Foss, 2009). This three-part of research approach makes the study complete in every manner, and the study can be made effective and devoted to the explanation of this particular phenomenon (Etherington, 2004).

Abductive research philosophy is also referred to as the abductive approach, which removes the weakness linked with deductive and inductive approaches (Suddaby, 2006). Specifically, a deductive approach has been criticised by Saunders, Lewis, & Thornhill (2014) for how a selection of the theory is tested for framing the research hypothesis. Inductive reasoning criticised how theory can be built without concern with empirical data, which is highly necessary for producing the theory (Maylor and Blackmon, 2005). The Abductive approach is one of the best alternative approaches to deploy in the study that needs more focus on facts and theoretical perspective of human behaviour (Saunders, Lewis, & Thornhill, 2014). This approach emphasises theories and primary data to draw the conclusion using top to down (observations/findings to theory) and bottom-up (theory to observations/findings) approaches (Bryman, 2016).

However, Easterby-Smith, Thorpe and Jackson (2008) distinguished three significant points of the abductive research approach. Firstly, it enables a researcher to make a more informed decision about the research design in order to provide the best answers to the initial research question. It helps the researcher to involve with a question about what kind of evidence is gathered as well as from where and how. Secondly, it helps the researcher to think about research strategy and research methodology, which will work crucially. Thirdly, Easterby-Smith, Thorpe and Jackson (2008)

argue that the knowledge of various research helps the researcher to adapt research design to cater for constraints.

In an abductive approach unique to the qualitative, the study starts with a puzzle as a surprising fact and the whole research process is devoted to explaining the puzzles (Ritchie et al., 2014). 'Surprising facts' or 'puzzles' may emerge in a study when the researcher focuses on empirical phenomena that cannot be explained by the existing range of theories. In order to explain the surprising facts, a researcher has to use numerical as well as non-numerical data. Hence in the course of explaining 'surprising facts' or 'puzzles', the researcher has to combine both the qualitative and quantitative data for making the interpretation and move the research from exploratory and descriptive to analytical and predictive research (Collis and Hussey, 2009).

4.4.4 Justification of Chosen Research Approach

According to Saunders, Lewis & Thornhill (2012), the selection of an appropriate research approach that will predominate the study depends on the nature of the research topic as well as on the emphasis of the research.

A topic with extensive existing literature and can define a theoretical framework and hypothesis is principally associated with the deductive approach. On the other hand, a topic that is comparatively new with little existing literature and that excites a reasonable amount of debate may be more suited to the inductive approach by generating and analysing data to establish a theory. Sound empirical research begins with a strong grounding in related literature, identifies a research gap, and proposes research questions that address the gap (Eisenhardt and Graebner (2007,p.26).

In order to understand the relationship between pricing strategy and the buying behaviour of the consumer and to understand this from the customer's perspective, existing literature was first examined and analysed, and existing supporting theories were highlighted before one was developed to be tested in the research. Survey questionnaires were employed to obtain data to test the theory, and thus, the deductive research approach was found suitable for the research.

Another prime goal of the research project was to answer the what, why and how questions in investigating the impact of pricing on the consumer's buying behaviour from the organisation's perspective. To understand this particular research objective, the inductive approach was undertaken where the researcher attempted to get a feel of what was happening around for better understanding (Saunders, Lewis & Thornhill, 2012).

Being an explorative study on how pricing impacts consumer buying behaviour at the Euro Garage, inductive and deductive approaches were thus needed to collect data and draw conclusions (Bryman & Bell, 2015). By also employing the abductive research approach, the researcher was able to link the deductive and inductive approaches together (Suddaby, 2006). This approach emphasizes theories and hypotheses, as well as primary and secondary data, to draw conclusions using top to down (observations/findings to theory) and bottom-up (theory to observations/findings) approaches (Bryman, 2016).

4.5 Research Strategies

Research Strategies is the third layer of the research onion defined by Saunders, Lewis, and Thornhill (2012, p.173) as the “plan of how a research will go about answering the research

question”. It creates a link between research philosophy and research choice of methods in order to collect and analyse data (Denzin and Lincoln, 2005).

Research strategies allow researchers to answer the research questions, which are essential to the flow and structure of the study (Saunders, Lewis, and Thornhill, 2012). It also guides a researcher in planning, monitoring and executing the whole research (Johannesson and Perjons, 2014).

Selection of the research strategy is often based on the research aims and objectives, and it supervises the main theme of the study, which principally links with qualitative, quantitative and mixed methods, respectively (Saunders, Lewis, and Thornhill, 2012).

The following are the research strategies adopted in this study:

4.5.1 Survey Research Strategy

Sapsford (2006) described the survey strategy as a quantifiable description of a population. The strategy uses a systematical data collecting method, be it by questionnaires, structured interviews or structured observations (Gray, 2016).

It is highly associated with a positivist study, where primary or secondary data is used from a large sample and analysed statistically (Collis and Hussey, 2009). The survey is often linked with deductive research, and a majority of the studies are associated with management and business research (Saunders, Lewis, and Thornhill, 2012). The survey strategy allows the researcher collect data from a large number of people (Tuli, 2011; Denscombe, 2011).

Data in a survey research study can be analysed using inferential statistical techniques or using descriptive analysis tools (Leavy, 2017). This kind of strategy is frequently used when looking to answer the 'what', 'who', 'where', 'how many' and 'how much' in a study (Saunders, Lewis, and Thornhill, 2012) and is thus highly associated with exploratory and descriptive research (Saunders, Lewis, and Thornhill, 2012).

This thesis aims to investigate the effect of pricing strategy on consumer buying behaviour. In order to achieve this, the researcher adopted the pragmatist research philosophy and focused on both inductive and deductive approaches as the researcher is not only interested in the subjective meaning of the managers at the store in the study but is also trying to establish relationships between the variables of pricing and the purchase reaction of the consumer.

In order to examine this from the perspective of the buyer and consumer themselves, the survey questionnaire was employed. Being a large sample, this strategy was well suited to this part of the research.

4.5.2 Case Study Research Strategy

Collins and Hussy (2009, p.82) define a case study as a methodological process that is "used to explore a single phenomenon in a natural setting using a variety of methods to obtain in-depth knowledge". Easterby-Smith, Thorpe, and Jackson (2013) also define the same characteristic of a case study that, in general, looks in-depth at any event where research has the freedom to make any interpretation.

A case study strategy is highly associated with qualitative research rather than quantitative research because it allows the researcher generate data through multiple perspectives (Ritchie and Lewis, 2003), which then helps them understand in detail a particular context (Gray, 2016). This research approach is highly relevant when research questions are started with 'why', 'What' and 'how' (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2012).

In this strategy, the researcher uses interviews, examples, documentaries, observations and questionnaires to generate the data (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2012). According to Barman (2016), a case study is a theory-generating process for a wider purpose of a context rather than a specific situation.

It is "an empirical inquiry that investigates a contemporary phenomenon within its real-life context; when the boundaries between phenomenon and context are not clearly evident; and in which multiple reassures of evidence are used" (Yin, 2009, p. 18). Furthermore, the case study is important for an in-depth understanding of a real-life phenomenon (Yin and Davis, 2007).

Creswell and J. David Creswell (2018) define a case study as a design of inquiry where the researcher develops an in-depth understanding of a case which is bounded by time as well as various activities, with detailed information usually collected using different data collection methods.

The case may focus on a specific activity, event or other phenomena, where real-life examples are examined and the relationship between real-life settings and all the variables identified (Hair et al.,

2007). Therefore, the aim of the case study is to provide a reconstruction or description of cases (Flick, 2011).

Thus, this strategy is highly associated with explanatory and exploratory research (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2012). Yin (2009) identified the key characteristics of the case study strategy as follows:

- The aim of the researcher is to explore certain phenomena as well as understand them within a particular context.
- The researcher does not begin with structured questions notions about the limits that the study will take place.
- For collecting data researcher may use multiple methods that are both quantitative and qualitative data.

The case study research strategy is well suited for this research on consumer buying behaviour at fuel forecourt stores as existing knowledge seems inadequate (Eisenhardt, 1989), and it is highly associated with the inductive approach that is supported by many researchers (Yin, 2009; Gray, 2016).

The current study examined pricing strategy and its impact on consumer behaviour in fuel convenience stores. The researcher explored the influence pricing had on the buying behaviour of the consumer from both the perspectives of the store managers and the customers.

To do these, it was vital to have data from the customers and managers at the same time. As a result, the data was collected from respondents using interviews and survey questionnaires (Robson, 2002), which suggested both qualitative and quantitative methods for an in-depth

understanding of the real-life context (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2012; Yin, 2009). The researcher thus employed the case study research strategy because of its inherent flexibility.

4.5.2.1 Process and Case Study Selection

Eisenhardt (1989) discovered the process of theory building from case study research, where the researcher follows eight steps starting with getting started, selecting cases, crafting instruments and protocols, entering the field, analysing data, shaping hypotheses, enfolding literature and reaching closure. Getting started is the first stem of the theory-building process from a case study where the researcher formulated the research problem and developed the research question. According to Mintzberg (1979, p. 585), "No matter how small our sample or what our interest, we have always tried to go into organisations with a well-defined focus-to collect specific kinds of data systematically." The rationale is the same for both defining the research question and hypothesis testing in research.

Selecting cases is the second important aspect of building theory, where researchers select either single case or multiple cases for studies (Perry, 1998; Yin,1994)—thirdly, crafting instruments and protocols where the researcher employs various data collection methods to identify specific issues. The method can be either a qualitative method that is used in social science for collecting primary data from the respondents in order to get an in-depth understanding of human behaviour (Bryman, 2016) or a purely quantitative method for collecting secondary data and analysing them using statistical methods (Collis and Hussey, 2009). However, the researcher can use mixed methods where the researcher can combine the best elements of qualitative and quantitative methods (Gray, 2018).

Accordingly, entering the field where the researcher chooses the source of data. Identifying the right people, gaining access to collect data, and gathering information from primary and secondary research. However, most frequently, researchers overlap data analysis with data collecting in this stage. Glaser and Strauss (1967) argue that most frequently, it happens for joint collection, coding and analysis of data. To avoid those overlapping, researchers commonly use field notes as an ongoing stream-of-consciousness that helps to record not only what is happening in the research but also the observation and analysis (Van Maanen, 1988).

Consequently, analysing data, also known as the heart of building theory, is the most difficult and least codified part of the process (Eisenhardt, 1989). According to Gray (2018), there are two ways case study data can be analysed. Firstly, data can be analysed based on the original theoretical proposition where the objectives of the research followed from them. Secondly, the researcher can develop a descriptive framework when the whole case study has been completed.

The next step of the process of case study is shaping hypotheses where the researcher compares theory and data systematically. This is a two-step process where the researcher is firstly involved with refining the definition of the construct and, secondly, building pieces of evidence that can measure the construct in each case. At this stage of the process, qualitative data is a highly suitable source of evidence as it helps to understand the reason behind the relationship between the underlying hypotheses (Günther, 2012). The use of various diagrams and tables can help the shaping hypotheses that summarise the whole data into a specific construct.

After shaping hypotheses, the researcher enfolded the literature where scholars compare case studies with existing literature in order to increase their quality (Günther, 2012). In general, a case study is based on a limited number of cases; therefore, this step is an important part of the extent of the research process. It is distinct between conflicting literature and similar literature that consider an opportunity to refine and deepen the constructs and categories.

Reaching closure is the final step of the process of the case study where the researcher stops adding cases as well as stop iterating between data and theory and acknowledge the evidence has been exhausted. In general, when the theoretical saturation is reached in the research, the researcher stops adding cases for further investigation (Eisenhardt, 1989). The "theoretical saturation is the point in analysis when all categories are well developed in terms of properties, dimensions, and variations. Further data gathering and analysis and add little new to conceptualisation, though variation can always be discovered." (Corbin and Strauss, 2008, p.263).

4.5.2.2 Case Selection

Selecting a case is the primordial task in the case study research (Seawright and Gerring, 2008). Nielson (2016) defines the case selection as the process of selecting or choosing cases for case study research. Accordingly, Gerring (2004, p.342) defines a case as "a spatially bounded phenomenon ... observed at a single point in time or over some delimited period of time, and it's an intensive study of a single unit for the purpose of understanding a larger class of (similar) units". Virtually, researchers make a decision on case selection, which entails selecting single or multiple cases that have similar characteristics (Nielson, 2016). Yin (2009) discovered four types of design for case study research based on the number of cases and nature of the research. These include a

single case, multiple case, holistic and embedded case, but they got common principles that investigate a contemporary problem within a real-life context (Scholz and Tietje, 2002).

4.5.2.3 Single case:

Generally, a single case study is commonly used where the researcher represents a critical, extreme or unique case that provides the opportunity to analyse a particular phenomenon that has few considerations before (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2012). Similarly, Eisenhardt and Graebner (2007, p.26) revealed that "single-case research typically exploits opportunities to explore a significant phenomenon under rare or extreme circumstances". Likewise, it can be considered as a unique, revelatory, salient or prototypical to the understanding of a problem or phenomenon (Scholz and Tietje, 2002). Additionally, Siggelkow (2007) also provide the positive description that a real-life phenomenon can be described magnificently by a single case study.

Depending on the purpose of the study and the entity being studied, the single case study can be quantitative or qualitative or a combination of both (Bryman, 2016). Similarly, Seale (2018) provided a similar explanation of a single case study that this strategy is principally associated with qualitative data and analysis but doesn't have any restrictions on using quantitative data. Therefore, a single case study research can meet all the requirements for testing a well-formulated theory that provides the opportunity to confirm, extend or challenge the model (Yin, 2009). By the same token, a single case study significantly represents a contribution to knowledge and theory building (Swanson and Chermack, 2013).

Compared to multiple case studies, researchers commonly use singly as multiple case studies can be extremely expensive and time-consuming (Baxter and Jack, 2008). In a similar perception, Dyer and Wilkins (1991) argued that a single case study is always better than multiple cases in order to produce a high-quality theory because it provides an extra and better conception. This type of strategy is bounded by time and certain activities that allow the researcher to develop an in-depth analysis (Creswell, 2014). Therefore, this approach is highly associated with the researcher those who are related to the organisation as its suitable for the nature of the research question and objectives (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2012).

4.5.2.4 Multiple cases

When research requires more than one cause for a better understanding of the phenomenon, it is called multiple case study research (Matthews and Ross, 2010). The multiple case studies provide strength for theory testing and building as they investigate several cases (Yin, 1994). Multiple cases are often used when researchers require broader theoretical elaboration and exploration of research questions that will allow the scholar to analyse within each setting as well as across settings (Baxter and Jack, 2008).

This strategy is frequently associated with a number of experiments within the same study (Scholz and Tietje, 2002). The key difference between multiple cases and a single case is that the researcher uses different cases to understand the similarities and differences between the cases (Stake, 1995). Furthermore, in multiple case studies, researchers carefully choose the cases based on the prediction of similar results from each case (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2012).

The results from the multiple cases are frequently considered more compelling; therefore, the whole study is regarded as being more robust (Herriott and Firestone, 1983). Mostly, researchers purposefully select multiple cases in order to show the different perspectives on the issues (Creswell, 2007). However, this particular "approach to case study strategy, therefore, commences deductively, based on theoretical propositions and theory testing before possibly incorporating an inductive or abductive approach" (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill 2012, p.180).

4.5.2.5 Holistic case:

Single and multiple cases also can be holistic, where the researcher can choose either a single case, which is one case with one unit analysis, or multiple cases, which is one case with several units of analysis (Yin, 2009). A holistic approach allows for the evaluation of complex programs. According to Scholz and Tietje (2002), "a holistic case design shaped by the principles of qualitative research may serve for the evaluation of complex programs that have not been treated effectively with quantitative designs".

4.5.2.6 Embedded case:

When research containing more than one subunit of analysis is called an embedded case study (Yin, 2009), usually, this approach is not limited to qualitative analysis alone. According to Scholz and Tietje (2002), an embedded case study approach can provide a means of integrating qualitative and quantitative methods into single research. Subunit provides the opportunity to get a detailed level of inquiry. Generally, this strategy is used for an empirical form of descriptive studies, where the main goal is to describe the phenomenon.

In this research, the researcher will explore how various pricing strategies affect consumer buying behaviour at Euro garage. This research is concerned with nature of the reality, and neither focuses on the ideas that are independent of the human mind and sensible reality (Saunders, Lewis & Thornhill, 2014). The single case study approach has been chosen because it highly supports the qualitative and quantitative research study within a single study (Bryman, 2016). This research is also bounded by time and certain activities that allow the researcher to develop an in-depth analysis (Creswell, 2014). Consequently, a single case study will be effective for this research as it plays a significant role in testing a hypothesis or theory (Gray, 2016). Therefore, the single approach is highly associated with the researcher as the researcher is currently related to the organisation as its suitable for the nature of the research question and objectives (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2012).

Therefore, the process of selecting the single case (Company – Euro Garage) was purposive. While there are other large and convenient shops across the UK that would have been easily selected, the Euro Garage stood out as a single interesting case with multiple measurable variables. Firstly, Euro Garage receives large numbers of a motorist travelling across the UK daily because it does not only serve as a fuel service station but has attached convenience stores whose goods and services appeal to travellers. Secondly, on a personal note, I have worked at Euro Garage as a Line Manager since 2015, and I became enthusiastic about consumers' attitudes and perceptions towards the purchase of products that are largely affected by pricing strategies. Therefore, the combination of these factors drives my academic desire to understand how various pricing strategies are significant in explaining product choice, store choice, purchase amount, and purchase timing. By focusing on

fuel service stations with particular reference to the Euro Garage in the UK, the study will be filling a gap in the literature on this subject.

4.6 Research Design

The research design refers to the blueprint, which comprises all stages that systematically complete the study (Robson, 2002). According to Byrman (2016, p.40), “research design provides a framework for the collection and analysis of data that reflects decisions about the priority being given to a range of dimensions of the research process”.

Different authors have defined research design in a variety of ways. Some believe it is a design that takes into consideration both the qualitative and quantitative research methods (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2012); others argue that it is a specific method of data collection and analysis that builds a strategy or a general plan to guide the research project (Collis and Hussey, 2009).

In this research, the research method is defined as a general plan and process to answer the research questions (Leavy, 2017). It can be classified based on the purpose of the research (Gray, 2014). Thus, the selection of an appropriate research design is essential in a study in order to manage consistencies between different stages of the study that provide a basic formula or direction (Hair et al., 2007).

The quantitative and qualitative methods and research choices are most commonly used in business research as these approaches are principally different in both their philosophical and methodological foundations (Marshall, 1996).

Content redacted due to copyright restrictions. Original figure can be found in Saunders et al, 2012.

Figure 4. 2: Research Choices (Saunders et al., 2012)

In above figure identify how researcher choices are categorised on the basis of the nature of the data. Data has two different natures; one is qualitative, and another is quantitative, which diversified research choices. Here comparative analysis of qualitative and quantitative data incorporating their advantage and disadvantage into account that highly recommended in business and management research (Bryman, 2006).

According to Molina Azorín J. and Cameron R. (2010), qualitative data have the power to produce a more detailed analysis of the problem. The qualitative method originated from social science research. This approach is principally associated with investigating social and cultural phenomena (Barman and Bell, 2011). On the other hand, quantitative research methods originated from natural sciences that are highly associated with examining natural phenomena (Hair et al., 2007). The researcher conducted several debates to increase the emphasis on the credibility of specific research choices (Golicic and Davis, 2012). However, many researchers are adhering to the incompatibility of the mixing of qualitative as well as quantitative research choices.

Some researchers are in favour of engaging two or more methods in a study so that it can increase the involvement of new facts and information that improve researcher confidence in the accuracy to investigate the same subject (Denscombe, 2011). It is not important for the betterment of the study that data is qualitative or quantitative, but managing reliability and validity is highly important for the study (Robson, 2002). Some researcher supports the combination of both kinds of data in the study as being more positive and increasing the reliability and validity of findings (Creswell, 2014). A combination of both methodologies is known as a mixed research approach, and it increases research credibility towards the findings because both kinds of data have their own importance for findings (Creswell and Plano Clark, 2011).

4.6.1 Qualitative Research

Qualitative data is one of the preeminent research choices used in social science for collecting primary data from the respondents in order to get an in-depth understanding of human behaviour (Bryman, 2016). This research approach is concerned with interpretivism research philosophy (Denzin and Lincoln, 2005). The collection of qualitative data covers a wide range of epistemological positions and theoretical frameworks for inductive research approaches (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2012).

According to Stentz, Plano Clark and Matkin (2012), qualitative data collection is one of the suitable research approaches in the case of constructivism and interpretivism paradigms. The nature of the question is different and easy to start in qualitative research to gain more detailed views of respondents, which is not possible in the case of the quantitative data collection method (Collis and Hussey, 2009). Qualitative data focus on the phenomenon of the real-world (Crowther

& Lancaster, 2009). Hence, it can be said that the real world is the strength of qualitative data. It allows the marketers to analyse the actual situation of the market and business world.

In general, qualitative research is widely used in research that neither finding to quantitative nor quantification analysis. This type of research process focuses on the study that is based on the understanding of humanistic or idealistic approaches. Similarly, Bryman (2008) define qualitative research as a strategy that typically emphasises words rather than quantification in the collecting and analysing of data. Likewise, Sandelowski (2004) described this concept as an umbrella term for an array and strategical process for conducting the inquiry, especially aiming at discovering how human beings understand and experience as well as interpret and produce the social world.

Usually, this method "characterised by inductive approaches to knowledge building aimed at generating meaning is used to learn about the social phenomenon; robustly unpack the meanings people ascribe to activities, situations, events, people, or artefacts; or build a depth of understanding about some dimension of social life" (Leavy, 2014, p. 266). The result of depth understanding is mainly appropriate when the main purpose of the research is to describe, explore or explain. Therefore, it focuses on the question of why rather than what that helps the researcher to seek an in-depth understanding of social phenomena within their natural setting.

However, compared with qualitative and quantitative data, most researchers consider quantitative methods to be a more reliable approach as it's based on numeric methods and can be propagated by other researchers and are interchangeably related to the term called fieldwork (Glesne, 2016). As qualitative research is based on the understanding of human belief, behaviour, attitudes, experiences and interaction hence it produces non-numerical data (Hair et al., 2007). As a result,

it can be said that the history of this design comes from the humanities, anthropology, sociology and evaluation, where the different authors described the concept of qualitative method in various types and completed the procedure on a particular qualitative approach (Creswell, 2014). For example, Yin (2012) and Stake (1995) constructed a picture of the qualitative method involved in case study research. Wolcott (2008) and Fetterman (2010) summarised ethnography research highly associated with qualitative design. Similarly, it also can be considered as narrative research by (Clandinin and Connelly, 2000), action research by Kemmis and McTaggart (2000) and Grounded theory identified by Charmaz (2006) and Strauss and Corbin (1998).

Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill (2012), Collin and Hussey (2009) and Silverman (1993) defined the benefits of using qualitative research are as follows:

- In-depth understanding of the social world
- Greater confidentiality
- Easy to organise
- Control of the quality
- Cost-effective
- Fast turnaround
- Time-efficient
- Aims and objectives are directed at providing an in-depth understanding of
- The social world.
- The data are rich, detailed and complex.
- Analysis retains complexity and nuance and respects uniqueness.
- Openness to emergent categories and theories at the analysis and interpretation stage

- Outputs that include a detailed description of the phenomena being researched.
- Using personal experiences in the field.

According to Papadimitriou, A. (2010), qualitative data collection is social research that has close integration in terms of views to mitigate the existing problems. Qualitative research focuses on ongoing phenomena that topic being researched for understanding social science. Even though this approach uses an unstructured data collection method, case study research, grounded theory, action research and ethnography are the most common research strategies are used in this qualitative research approach (Collis and Hussey, 2009; Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2012; Bryman and Bell, 2011).

In this study, one of the research questions is how pricing strategy influences consumer buying behaviour from the organisational perspective. The qualitative research design becomes more favourable than the quantitative research design as the researcher requires a depth understanding of social phenomena. To address this research question researcher focusing the pricing strategy and consumer buying behaviour from the organisational perspective; therefore, the research finding is not precisely derived from quantitative data and statistical analysis. Therefore, a qualitative research design is required for an understanding of social phenomena within this particular context.

4.6.2 Quantitative Research

Primarily, quantitative research is explanatory research in natural science and social science. According to Collis and Hussey (2009), quantitative research is an approach that addresses the

research question involving collecting quantifiable data and analysing them using statistical methods. Given (2008) described quantitative research as a systematic way of investigating a phenomenon via mathematical, statistical or computation techniques. The key objective of this method is to employ and develop mathematical models and hypotheses that can test the theories. The measurement is the fundamental and central process of quantitative research as it is unable to connect empirical observation and the mathematical expression of quantitative relationships.

Seers and Critelton (2001), quantitative research is exclusively associated with the population as it mainly focuses on individuals or groups of people or populations. Although the data was mostly collected from individuals, this method was concerned with the group rather than an individual response. The data is mainly concerned with numbers rather than words that are collected by quantitative research (Punch, 2012). However, the origin of quantitative research came from positivism, which believes that there is an objective in our surrounding world that can be quantified and measured or observed in some way (Seers and Critelton, 2001).

Similarly, Creswell (2009) described the concept of quantitative research as an approach that investigates human or social problems based on a testing theory using variables, mainly measured with numbers and used numerical procedure to analyse data that determine whether the generalisation of the hypothesis holds true or false. As a result, this method is generally associated with objectivism, which leads to the positivism paradigm and adopts a deductive research approach (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2012).

Accordingly, Leavy (2017) provided similar characteristics of quantitative research that predominantly uses a deductive approach, mainly aiming at proving or disproving the existing theory. In this type of research, design involves measuring and testing differences between variables in order to identify correlations, relevant patterns or causal relationships. The Linear data collection method can be used and analyse that data statistically.

Based on Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill (2012), Collin and Hussey (2009), and Barman (2016), the common characteristic of qualitative research are as follows:

- Structured research instrument for gathering data.
- Usually based on a larger sample size.
- Research can be repeated or replicated.
- Focusing on objectivities.
- All aspects are highly structured before collecting data.
- Used numbers or statistical forms of data are frequently arranged in charts, tables, figures or other non-textual forms.
- Research can be used to investigate causal relationships or generalise a particular concept.

In this research, the aim is to explore how pricing strategy impacts consumer buying behaviour in service stations through interviewing store managers and taking survey questionnaires from customers. Therefore, one of the research questions is how pricing strategy from the customer perspective influences consumer buying behaviour. Hence, to answer this question, the positivism paradigm is more useful by conducting a survey questionnaire. To address this research question, a quantitative research design is required as it focuses on examining "relationships between

variables, which are measured numerically and analysed using a range of statistical techniques and will incorporate controls to ensure the validity of data" (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill 2012, p.162).

4.6.3 Mixed Methods Research Design

A mixed-method is a research approach that is used to answer the research question through the collection and analysis of both quantitative and qualitative research and data (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill 2012). Qualitative data is usually collected using open-ended responses without a predetermined structure; on the other hand, quantitative data are collected using closed-ended responses such as questionnaires or psychological instruments (Creswell, 2014). Combining two methods together, the technique will provide insight into understanding and provide a clear picture of the research problem than using either one (Creswell and Plano Clark, 2011). Conversely, Leavy (2017) also described similar aspects of mixed that qualitative and quantitative data are integrated in a way for collecting and analysing data in order to describe, explain or evaluate a phenomenon in a single project.

The idea of mixed-method research was raised by neutralising weaknesses of each form of data as both quantitative and qualitative approaches contain some kind of bias and weaknesses (Creswell, 2014). Qualitative research is generally easier at the beginning of the research project, but researchers frequently find it difficult to analyse data and write the final report (Collis and Hussey, 2009). On the other hand, researchers find difficulties with quantitative research as it requires mathematical, statistical or computation knowledge but is easier to analyse as it is highly structured (Given, 2008). Therefore, these multiple methods have become popular in business and

management research because of overcoming weaknesses in a single method and providing a more convenient research approach for collecting, analysing and interpreting data (Bryman, 2016).

However, the combination of both quantitative and qualitative research can be combined in a variety of ways; for example, it can be from range to simple, from convergent to extremely complex or can be fully integrated forms (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill 2012). The phases of the mixed-method research are synergistic or integrated, where the qualitative phase or step can influence the quantitative phase or vice versa (Hesse-Biber, 2010). Because of the integration of both qualitative and quantitative data, the result of a mixed-method produced can be a more comprehensive understanding of the phenomenon under the investigation. Therefore, mixed-method research is highly associated when the purpose of the research is to describe, explain or evaluate. However, most of the time, it requires additional extra time to complete the study because of its characteristic of collecting and analysing two different types of data (Creswell and Plano Clark, 2011).

At present, the use of mixed-method research is increasingly employed in social science and natural science research (Brannen, 2005) as this method provides the opportunity for enhancement. Accordingly, Gough, Oliver and Thomas (2017) also provide the positive aspect of using the mixed method that it is useful when the research contains multiple layers of review questions or when a single study is insufficient to answer the research questions adequately. These provide the opportunity to have both depth and breadth as well as cover a broad area, which helps to undertake a greater extent of the research problem. In addition, there is no restriction for collecting data but is guided by a foundation underlies by the researcher (Creswell, 1994). Consequently, it is also

appropriate for social research as the social phenomena are so complex that different types of methods are needed to best understand the complexities (Creswell et al., 2003). As this process considered multiple reviews, the method usually is demanding of extra resources and time and cannot be conducted quickly (Gough, Oliver and Thomas, 2017).

However, the linkage of data or integration is an essential step of mixed-method research, which can be done at an appropriate stage of the research process (Ivankova, Creswell and Stick, 2006). Integration of different type of data enables the researcher to see a more panoramic view of the research landscape and provide an opportunity to view the phenomena from different viewpoints through diverse research lenses. Therefore, this method is highly associated with answering research questions that neither qualitative nor quantitative methods could answer alone (Tashakkori and Creswell, 2007). Accordingly, Greene et al. (1989) analysed 57 evaluation studies and identified five main purposes of using the mixed method or combination of methods, namely.

- **Triangulation:** This represents the combining of several same methods or combining qualitative and quantitative methods. The main idea of combining methods allows for one method to compensate for blind spots or weaknesses of the others and work side by side (Flick, 2011). Therefore, triangulation seeks corroboration, convergence, and correspondence of results from different approaches in order to increase the validity by maximising the heterogeneity of irrelevant sources (Gray,2016).
- **Complementarity:** With complementarity mixed-method research, the qualitative and quantitative methods are combined together to measure the overlapping and different elements of the phenomenon. It is an epistemological design that helps to understand

human behaviour by using a separate research approach (Carroll and Rothe, 2010). It is seeking for enhancement, elaboration, clarification and illustration of the results of one particular method with the results from other methods in order to increase the validity and meaningfulness.

- **Development:** Here is the final result of one method informing the development of the second method. For example, quantitative data collection can be built directly on the bases of qualitative results (Creswell, 2014). Therefore, the result of one method helps to develop other methods in order to increase the validity of constructs and inquiry results.
- **Initiation:** Mixed methods have initiation criteria to discover a new perspective and uncover paradoxes and contradictions. This seeks the discovery of paradox and contradiction, new perspectives for depth and breadth of inquiry results.
- **Expansion:** Expansion uses mixed-method to extend the breadth and range of investigation by using different components from different methods (Schoonenboom and Johnson, 2017). This provides the opportunity to use the appropriate component in the appropriate situation as a group of processes taking place with the same study.

Hence, because of the integration of both qualitative and quantitative data, mixed-method research provides the opportunity under investigation and delivers a comprehensive understanding of the phenomenon (Leavy, 2017). The researcher also can use all the resources are available to collect data that are more comprehensive, and results have a broader perspective of the overall research problem. In view of that, Creswell and Plano Clark (2011), Tashakkori and Creswell (2007) and Tashakkori and Teddlie (2010) provide some basic characteristics of mixed-method research are as follows:

- Collecting both qualitative and quantitative data in response to research questions or hypotheses.
- It includes analysing both forms of data.
- The procedures of collecting and analysing both quantitative and qualitative data are conducted rigorously.
- Integration of two forms of data analysed through merging, connecting or embedding the data.
- These techniques can also be informed by a philosophical view or a theory.
- Mix two different forms of data in different ways.
- Provide priority to one or both forms of data.
- It can be in a single study or in multiple phases of the study.

4.6.4 Justification of Chosen Research Design

Therefore, methodological eclecticism is the universal characteristic of mixed-method research, where synergistically selecting the most appropriate techniques from the qualitative and quantitative methods for more thoroughly investigating the phenomena (Tashakkori and Teddlie 2003). This undertaken study is based on the topic of an exploration of how pricing strategy impacts consumer buying behaviour in a service station setting. In order to conduct the study, the researcher selected a systematic approach to make an in-depth understanding of phenomena and complete the study (Robson, 2002). Therefore, researchers attempt to find the answer to questions or resolution of the problem (Walliman, 2005).

Indeed, one of the research questions is how pricing strategy influences consumer buying behaviour from the organisational perspective. In order to address the research question, qualitative research design become more favourable and related to interpretive philosophy followed by an inductive approach than quantitative research design as the researcher requires a depth understanding of social phenomena (Denzin and Lincoln, 2005). This is also because researchers need to make sense of the subjective and socially constructed meaning (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2012). These can be understood by seeing what meaning people give to them and interpreting their meanings from their perceptions (Blumberg et al., 2008). As a researcher focusing on the organisational perspective, qualitative data is one of the preeminent research choices used in social science for collecting primary data from the respondents in order to get an in-depth understanding of human behaviour (Bryman, 2016).

However, to answer the question of how pricing strategy influences consumer buying behaviour from the consumer perspective, the quantitative research design is more appropriate than qualitative as it is based on the assumption that it is quantifiable and can easily handle using statistical research tool and require larger sample (Creswell, 2014). The data is exclusively associated with a large population as it mainly focuses on individuals or groups of people or populations, and that can be investigated via mathematical, statistical or computation techniques Given (2008). Although the data was mostly collected from individuals, this method was concerned with the group rather than individual response (Seers and Critelton, 2001). Hence, to answer this question positivism paradigm is more useful by conducting survey questionnaires and applying high structured scientific methods as well as following specific structures that facilitate replication and collecting data to develop hypotheses from existing theory (Gill and Johnson,

2010). To address this research question, a quantitative research design is required as it focuses on examining "relationships between variables, which are measured numerically and analysed using a range of statistical techniques and will incorporate controls to ensure the validity of data" (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill 2012, p.162).

As a result, for this research combination of both qualitative and quantitative methods is required to answer the research questions in a single study, which can be called a mixed-method research design (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill 2012). As different research questions indicate different research methods, a mixed-method research design can provide insight and understanding and provide a clear picture of the research problem than using either one (Creswell and Plano Clark, 2011). A mixed-method research design provides the opportunity for collecting and analysing both forms of data, qualitative and quantitative and integrating in a way that can describe, explain or evaluate a phenomenon in a single project Leavy (2017). Mixed method research is useful as this study contains multiple layers of research questions; there, a single method is insufficient to answer the research question adequately (Gough, Oliver and Thomas, 2017). It also neutralises weaknesses of each form of data as these multiple research phases of study viewing pricing strategy influence the consumer buying behaviour from both the consumer perspective and the organisational perspective (Creswell, 2014). Therefore, this research is highly associated with a mixed-method research design that answers research questions that neither qualitative nor quantitative method could answer alone (Tashakkori and Creswell, 2007).

4.7 Type of Mixed Method Research

The mixed-method research focuses on the same research question or different research questions where both types of methods, qualitative and quantitative, can be used independently or interdependently (Gray, 2016). Developing mixed-method research can be challenging where researchers must select the appropriate qualitative or quantitative approach to answer the research question (Leavy, 2017). According to Easterby-Smith, Thorpe, and Jackson (2013, p.61), "using a range of different methods within the same study the researcher will increase the validity and generalizability of results and the potential theoretical contribution; the sceptics point to practical limitations such as the competence of researchers in conducting different methods, and to possible contradictions between the paradigms underlying different methods". Mixing of both kinds of methods, qualitative and quantitative, can be occurred at every stage of implementation or only stage or a particular stage; for example, it can be occurred during the data collection stage but not in terms of choosing a data analysis technique (Saunders, Lewis & Thornhill, 2012) Using both methods at every stage of research process indicated fully integrated mixed-method research, on the other hand using both methods at a particular stage of research process indicates partially integrated mixed-method research (Teddlie and Tashakkori, 2011).

Creswell and Plano Clark (2011) classified several mixed-method research based on the field of evaluation, education policy and research, nursing and public health, as well as social and behavioural research. Therefore, mixed-method research can be undertaken in many different ways (Barman and Bell, 2011). In this situation, the researcher must consider two issues firstly, which type of data is required to address the research question and secondly, how different types of data bring together to conduct the research (Gough, Oliver and Thomas, 2017). For this discussion, Creswell (2016) identified three basic types of mixed-method research based on the nature of the

research process and integration of both methods, including when and how mixing occurred. These are convergent parallel mixed-methods design, explanatory sequential mixed method and exploratory sequential mixed methods.

4.7.1 Convergent Parallel Mixed-Method Research

This is the most familiar of the basic and advanced mixed-method approach, especially for those who are new to mixed-method research, as most researchers believe that this method consists of combining both qualitative and quantitative data (Harrison III, 2013). In this design researcher collect both types of data simultaneously, analyse them separately and mixes the databases by merging data (Creswell and Plano Clark, 2011). The different results from different methods, qualitative and quantitative, are integrated during the interpretation process (Creswell et al., 2003). Finally, the researcher compares the result in order to see whether the finding confirm or disconfirm each other (Creswell, 2016).

Accordingly, the convergent parallel mixed method provides equal priority to both qualitative and quantitative data where different components are independently kept and mixed during the result stage (Stentz, Clark and Matkin, 2012). The basic rationale for using this method is to bring different approaches together, which can provide different strengths to offset the weaknesses of the other (Teddlie and Tashakkori, 2011). However, as for the philosophical assumption, this method reviled from umbrella terms of a worldview that can be called pragmatism since it holds mixed methods (Watkins and Gioia, 2015).

In the same context, Watkins and Gioia (2015) identified several strengths that make it one of the popular research methods in social and natural research. Firstly, this design is suitable for those researchers who are relatively new to mixed-method research because of its clear distinction of both methods and does not require to relate the finding until the interpretation phases (Saunders, Lewis & Thornhill, 2012). Secondly, both types of data are collected separately during one phase of the research, saving the researcher time (Gray, 2016). Finally, this design is team-friendly, where each type of data can be collected and analysed separately using the most suitable component of each data type. Accordingly, Creswell and Plano Clark (2011), Tashakkori and Creswell (2007) and Tashakkori and Teddlie (2010) provide some basic characteristics of convergent parallel mixed method research are as follows.

- Collecting and analysing two types of data, qualitative and quantitative, independently at the same time in a single study.
- Equally, prioritise both qualitative and quantitative methods.
- Analysing both data qualitative and quantitative separately.
- Merge the results during the interpretation
- Compare the results to see if the findings confirm or disconfirm each other.

4.7.2 Data Collection

In this method, the qualitative data can be generated by using any of the forms such as observation, interviews, documents and other records and quantitative data through using the close-ended instrument (Creswell, 2016). The main purpose of using this method is to collect two types of data using the same variables or constructs. Both types of methods, qualitative and quantitative, can use the same concept to collect both types of data (Gough, Oliver and Thomas, 2017). In this

situation, the sample size is the biggest challenge for both the qualitative and quantitative data collection process (Creswell and Plano Clark, 2011). Unquestionably, the qualitative data sample size is much smaller than the quantitative (Collis and Hussey, 2009). This is because of the characteristics of qualitative data where the researcher focuses on a small sample but produces extensive information that is rich, detailed and complex for providing an in-depth understanding of the social world (Ritchie et al., 2014). Whereas, in quantitative research, large sample size is required for a systematic way of investigating a phenomenon via mathematical, statistical or computation techniques (Given, 2008). In most cases, researchers collect both types of data from the same number of individuals. This means the qualitative sample will be increased naturally; therefore, the researcher limits the amount of data collected from those individuals (Creswell, 2016).

4.7.3 Data Analysis

Merging or converging the data is convergent parallel mixed method design research (Creswell, 2016). In this method, two types of data are collected and analysed separately after bringing them together (Stentz, Clark and Matkin, 2012). Two types of data can be merged in several ways. It can be merged side-by-side where the researcher report quantitative result statistically and then qualitative findings to discuss that will confirm or disconfirm the quantitative statistical results (Creswell and Plano Clark, 2011). Alternatively, it can be reversed where; research can start with qualitative findings and compare them with quantitative results (Teddlie and Tashakkori, 2011). The data transformation process is another way of merging two types databased, where researchers transform qualitative codes into quantitative variables and combine two types of similar databased (Watkins and Gioia, 2015). However, mergers also can be done by a joint display of data where

researchers combine two forms of data in a graph or a table (Creswell, 2016). These can be displayed by using themes on the horizontal axis and categorical variables on the vertical axis (Creswell and Plano Clark, 2011).

4.7.4 Interpretation

The convergent parallel mixed method also called the concurrent mixed-method, involves the using qualitative and quantitative methods within a single study for collecting and analysing data (Beck and Gable, 2012). The different results from different methods, qualitative and quantitative, are integrated during the interpretation process (Creswell et al., 2003). In this type of mixed-method, the interpretation can occur during the discussion section of the research. It also can be occurred in the results section, where research produces a report from an analysis of both methods qualitative and quantitative databases (Ritchie et al., 2014). These include the result from comparing both databases that determined the convergence or divergence of those two sources of information (Creswell, 2016).

4.7.5 Validity

According to Collis and Hussey (2009), validity is the extent that measures the research finding and provides an accuracy of the study. In the convergent parallel mixed method, validity should be based on both databases qualitative and quantitative (Creswell and Plano Clark, 2011). Creswell (2016) identified some potential threats to using the convergent parallel mixed method to validate the finding. These include unequal sample size, which is more prominent on the quantitative side and smaller on the qualitative side. Likewise, it could be challenging to merge both kinds of data as concepts and variables are different (Creswell et al., 2003).

4.7.6 Explanatory Sequential Mixed Method:

The explanatory sequential mixed method involves more than one phase for collecting and analysing the data. The basic construction of this method is that the use of one method helps to constrict the second method. The process consists of a two-stage project where the researcher first collects quantitative data, analyse the data and produce a result, then use those result to build the second qualitative phase. Indeed, it can be called quantitative data followed by qualitative data (Creswell, 2016). In this process, qualitative data are collected secondly based on quantitative data that helps to elaborate or explain the quantitative result. The quantitative and qualitative phases are connected in the intermediate stage of the study.

4.8 Time Horizon

The time horizon is the time framework allotted for conducting the research (Saunders, Lewis & Thornhill, 2012). This is one of the major issues that a researcher has to consider when planning a research project, whether the project will be completed within a particular time or a given period. There are two types of research horizons that are specific in undertaking research onion, namely the cross-sectional, also known as snapshot and the longitudinal, also called diary (Bryman, 2012). Selection of the time horizon does not have any link with research design or research approach, but it depends on the convenience of the researcher. Selecting an appropriate time horizon mostly depend on the purpose of the research, available time for the study, the research question, resources and the sample size (Saunders, Lewis & Thornhill, 2012; Collis and Hussey, 2009; Gray, 2016).

4.8.1 Cross-sectional

This time horizon is already established for completing the study. This time horizon chose when the study is concerned with a particular phenomenon at a specific time (Saunders, Lewis & Thornhill, 2012). Collis and Hussey (2009) described cross-sectional studies as a methodological process where research investigates a group of subjects or variables in a different context within a particular period of time.

In general, the researcher often uses questionnaires and survey strategies within positivist traditions in order to carry out cross-sectional research (Easterby-Smith, Thorpe, and Jackson, 2013). Time constraints and limited resources are the main reason for conducting the cross-sectional study (Bryman, 2016). The data are collected within a short period of time before they are analysed and reported and provide a snapshot of research phenomena (Collis and Hussey, 2009). However, a case study research strategy can also be used in a cross-sectional study as it is based on interviews (Saunders, Lewis & Thornhill, 2012).

4.8.2 Justification of Chosen Time Horizon:

In this research, the researcher selected cross-sectional time horizon to carry out the empirical work. The study employed a case study strategy where data will be collected using a semi-structured interview with managers, and a survey questionnaire will be done to collect data from the consumer at the store. Even though survey strategy is highly associated with cross-sectional studies (Churchill, 2001), they may also use in case studies that are conducted over a short period of time and based on interviews manner (Saunders, Lewis & Thornhill, 2012). Furthermore, the data will be collected once from limited resources over a short period of time (Collis and Hussey, 2009). The researcher will adopt a snapshot approach where the data will be collected at one point

in time (Gray,2016). Therefore, this research is highly associated with the cross-sectional time horizon because of its sample of the case, a single point in time, quantitative data and the patterns of association (Bryman, 2016).

4.9 Population and Sampling Techniques

Sekaran and Bougie (2009, p.262) described the research population as "the entire group, events, and things that the researcher wishes to investigate". Similarly, according to Collis and Hussey (2009, p. 62), a population is a precisely defined body of people or objects under consideration for statistical purposes. In addition, the population is whom the researcher wants to generalise results (Lee and Lings, 2008). However, Leavy (2017) defined a research population as a group of elements that might be claimed later by the researcher and help to draw a research sample.

This study is intended to explore how product price impacts consumer buying behaviour at the petroleum convenience store. In order to achieve the research aims and objectives, some random Euro- Garage was utilised as the study context for this research. Employees of the organisation are the key players in this research. Employees at the managerial level have much knowledge about consumer perceptions and their behaviour. Therefore, it is the full set of cases from which the sample will be taken (Saunders, Lewis & Thornhill, 2012).

Under investigation, a researcher can collect data from all members of a population. In general, which is not feasible; therefore, it is required to draw a sample of the population in order to collect data (Hair et al., 2007). There are a number of important characteristics of the population, and the factors like the statistical study and the sample sizes affect the research to a very greater and deep

extent (Merriam and Tisdell, 2015). The power of the hypotheses is mainly responsible for the conduction of the research studies. The larger and greater the sample size in the study, the more and more effective will be the research (Ghauri & Gronhaug, 2005). So it can be finally said that the researcher must be very careful in choosing the sample size in the study (Gill & Johnson, 2006).

Customers and the employees who are working at the Euro Garage are the main respondents for primary data. Some of the customers visiting the fuel stations might refuse to give the answers to the questions due to a number of reasons; therefore, an observation will be conducted in order to get the data from customers. These responses, which were provided by the respondents, have been used for the purpose of the data analysis (Scotland, 2012). Hence the population and the size of the sample of the respondents is 16, and these all are managers working at different branches of Euro garage stores in the UK.

4.9.1 Sampling Technique

It might be possible the researcher would like to use the census approach to collect and analyse data from entire members of the population (Hair et al., 2007). However, in most cases, it is not feasible because of access, money and restrictions of time (Saunders, Lewis & Thornhill, 2012). Therefore, a researcher may select "a subset of the population" from the whole population to carry out the research, which is called research sample (Collis and Hussey, 2009, p. 62). Saunders, Lewis & Thornhill (2012) discover the following situations of the usefulness of using sampling as an alternative to a census.

- When it is impossible for the researcher to survey the whole population.
- When the budget and resources prevent the researcher surveying the entire population.
- When the time limits prevent the researcher surveying the whole population.

Along with Saunders, Lewis & Thornhill (2012), discoveries Greenfield (2002) introduced quality issues, that samples can increase the quality of research and more accurate results. However, sometimes it may seem unnecessary when the researcher uses a particular case study or action research project in their mind (Blaxter, Hughes and Tight, 2006).

Sampling is the feasible course of action and systematic technique in any of the studies carried out in the marketing world (Kent, 2007). The sample may be assumed as the set of persons or individuals which helps in the process of gaining the answers (Easterby-Smith, Thorpe and Jackson, 2013). It helps in getting the required and accurate form of the information (Wahyuni, 2012). It becomes quite necessary for the researchers to carry out the sampling work very effectively, which can bring out the best results for the entire study (Merriam and Tisdell, 2015). The researchers should also focus on the issue of handling and asking the perfect set of questions in the interview, which can meet the research objective (Creswell and Creswell, 2018). This research undertakes the qualitative approach for the collection of primary data, and semi-structured interview comprises open-ended questions that favour smaller sample sizes (Leavy, 2017). Some of the respondents may use more description in such questions because they are free to give their views (Gray, 2016). finally, it can be said that there is a need of keeping the precautions and attention while selecting a sample (Hair et al., 2007) from interviewees during the interview session and keeping them interested in undertaking the research topic.

Probability and non-probability are the two main types of sampling techniques discovered by Saunders, Lewis & Thornhill (2012). In probability sampling, the member of the population has an equal opportunity or chance to appear in the sample (Lee and Lings, 2008). On the other hand, non-probability sampling refers to unknown and unequal where the researcher uses personal experience, expert judgement and convenience to select the elements in the sample (Hair et al., 2007).

Content redacted due to copyright restrictions. Original figure can be found in Saunders et al, 2012.

As shown in the above figure, probability sampling techniques involve simple random, systematic random, stratified random, and cluster random. Non- probability sampling techniques include convenience sampling, quota sampling, purposive sampling and volunteer sampling.

4.9.1.1 Probability sampling

Lee and Lings (2008) described probability sampling as a gold standard of quantitative sampling, which allows a researcher to draw statistical generalisations. This sampling technique relies on the theory of probability (Leavy, 2017), which involves selecting random samples from a population that can be represented as a whole (Gray, 2016). In this sampling technique, samples are selected where an individual element in the population has a known and nonzero chance of being selected. Therefore it minimises the selection bias (Hair et al., 2007). Every member of the population has an equal opportunity of being selected for the study (Blaxter, Hughes and Tight, 2006). Consequently, this technique involves randomisation, where a method is used that is independent of human judgement to select the sample from a list of the population (Kent, 2007).

Sampling bias and systematic sampling are the two major advantages of using probability sampling (Greenfield, 2002). As these sampling techniques represent the whole population, therefore, it is highly associated with survey research (Saunders, Lewis, and Thornhill, 2012). Simple Random, Systematic, Stratified, Cluster and Multi-Stage sampling are the most commonly employed probability sampling technique (Hair et al., 2007).

Simple Random Sampling: This is the most straightforward and basic type of probability sample (Lee and Lings, 2008). As the name suggests, this sampling method relies on the completely random process of selecting the sample from the population (Gray, 2016). Every member of the population has an equal opportunity of being part of the sample (Easterby-Smith, Thorpe and Jackson, 2013). In general, this technique works with a large population using the lottery system or using software (Hair et al., 2007). Therefore, simple random sampling can be representative of the whole population without having any bias (Saunders, Lewis, and Thornhill, 2012).

Systematic Sampling: This is a probability sampling strategy that involves a random selection process at the initial starting point and selecting other members after the fixed sampling interval (Gray,2016; Saunders, Lewis, and Thornhill, 2012). The sampling interval represents the number of population elements between each unit selected (Hair et al., 2007). Furthermore, Leavy (2017, p.79) also described systematic sampling as a strategy "in which the first element in the study population is selected randomly and then every kth element, after the first element, is selected". As this sampling process is organised randomly, therefore, it doesn't introduce any bias in the study (Easterby-Smith, Thorpe, and Jackson, 2013).

Stratified Sampling: Stratification represents the specific characteristics of individuals from a list of the population that represent and reflect the true proportion of the population (Creswell and Creswell, 2018). It's a modified form of random and systematic sampling (Dattalo,2010) where the researcher divide the total population into a number of subsets called sampling strata (Saunders, Lewis, and Thornhill, 2012). Therefore, the stratified sample can be selected using either the simple random or systematic random sampling strategy from the strata of the target population (Hair et al., 2007). All strata must be taken into account while taking elements of stratified sampling that increase the accuracy of the sample information without having any bias (Collis and Hussey, 2009).

Cluster Sampling: This is a sampling strategy where the target population are viewed as the heterogeneous group called clusters (Hair et al., 2007). This means the researcher divides the total population into separate groups (Easterby-Smith, Thorpe, and Jackson, 2013). With this strategy, the researcher started with a random selection of clusters; after that, elements of each cluster were

sampled (Leavy, 2017). Sometimes all elements of the selected cluster are taken into the sample (Lee and Lings, 2008). As it divides the total population into discrete groups so that it is similar to stratified random sampling (Saunders, Lewis, and Thornhill, 2012). Therefore, it is useful when the researcher can't get access to a comprehensive sampling frame (Gray, 2016).

Multi-Stage Sampling: Multi-Stage sampling uses a combination of all probability sampling techniques in order to achieve technical and operational efficiency (Easterby-Smith, Thorpe, and Jackson, 2013). It is also called multi-stage cluster sampling, which is a modification of cluster sampling that requires face to face contact, money and time consuming as it works with large geographical areas (Saunders, Lewis, and Thornhill, 2012). Therefore, this is used when selected cluster samples are so big to sample (Collis and Hussey, 2009). Sometimes it involves using random sampling at more than one stage (Gray, 2016). Typically, this strategy is used when researchers address large scale studies and cover larger geographical areas (Kothari, 1985).

4.9.1.2 Non-probability sampling:

Non-probability sampling represents a list of sampling methods that helps the researcher to collect specific units from the total population (Leavy, 2017). The sample is generated in a way that does not give an equal chance of being selected (Lee and Lings, 2008). In this sampling strategy, not all members of the population have a chance to participate in the study (Saunders, Lewis, and Thornhill, 2012). The main characteristic of non-probability sampling is that the researcher selects the sample based on subjective judgement such as convenience, personal experience, expert judgement and so on for the research (Hair et al., 2007).

Non-Probability sampling, also called purposeful sampling, mainly seeks out the best cases to produce high-quality data for the study, especially for qualitative research (Potton, 2015). Qualitative research is usually used for the in-depth understanding of particular phenomena from a small amount of sample. Therefore, it relies on some form of non-probability sampling (Leavy, 2017). There are more than 15 different non-probability sampling strategies based on the purpose of the study (Gray,2018). However, this sampling process cannot provide the same level of confidence as probability sampling can (Easterby-Smith, Thorpe, and Jackson, 2013). Quota, purposive, volunteer and haphazard are the most common types of non-probability sampling techniques that are used to conduct the study (Saunders, Lewis, and Thornhill, 2012).

Quota Sampling: A quota is a fully non-random sampling technique mostly used for structured interviews (Saunders, Lewis, and Thornhill, 2012). First, it "divides the relevant population up into categories (perhaps male/female. Or the country of origin for students) and then selection continues until a sample of a specific size is achieved within each category" (Easterby-Smith, Thorpe, and Jackson. P.228, 2013). Therefore, quota sampling is similar to stratified random sampling, where the researcher selects cases within strata (Barnett, 2002). For random stratified sampling, the sample is selected randomly; however, in the case of quota sampling researcher used non-random sampling techniques for gathering data from the stratum (Gray, 2016). Indeed, it can be said that the selection of each element can be made on the basis of convenience from strata (Hair et al., 2007).

Purposive Sampling: Purposive sampling is a process of judgement in which a researcher makes the judgement in order to select the best cases that meet the research objectives and answer the

research question (Saunders, Lewis, and Thornhill, 2012). According to Neuman (2005), this sampling method is useful when the researcher works with a small number of samples, like in case studies where cases are more informative. In general, with this sampling technique, the researcher selects each sample for a specific purpose (Hair et al., 2007) that provide important information that cannot be gained from other sampling technique (Maxwell, 1997). As the researcher got full control and the idea of selecting the appropriate sample (Easterby-Smith, Thorpe, and Jackson, 2013) therefore, convenience, low cost and speed are the main advantages of these sampling methods. However, there is a high chance to be subconsciously biased with this sampling technique while selecting the sample (Gray, 2016).

Volunteer Sampling: Volunteer sampling is a sampling method where participants use the self-selection technique to become part of the study rather than chosen by the researcher (Saunders, Lewis, and Thornhill, 2012). In general, this sampling method works very well when individuals are very rare and very difficult to identify the member of the desired population (Easterby-Smith, Thorpe, and Jackson, 2013). The initial contact is the difficult part of this strategy as it uses a chain sampling strategy where one case leads to another (Patton, 2015). The initial contact helps to identify further members. Eventually, they help to identify further members, and this will continue until the researcher reaches the required sample size (Hair et al., 2007). Therefore, it is exclusively associated with interpretivism study, where human experience is essential to be studied (Collis and Hussey, 2009). However, the negative side of this sampling process is that there is a high chance to be biased as the member identifies as a similar member to themselves (Lee, 1993).

Haphazard Sampling: According to Saunders, Lewis, and Thornhill (p.290, 2012), "haphazard sampling occurs when sample cases are selected without any obvious principles of an organisation in relation to the research question, the most common form being convenience sampling". In this sampling, strategy samples are selected which are most readily available and can provide the information required (Hair et al., 2007). This sampling method is principally used in research because it's well convenient (Easterby-Smith, Thorpe, and Jackson, 2013). It helps the researcher to complete a number of interviews with the least costly in terms of money, time and effort (Gray, 2016). However, as an individual are different from the target population, therefore, it is very difficult to generalise the finding, and there is a high chance of being biased (Bryman, 2016).

4.10 Sample Size

The sample size is the number of a participant in the study who are potentially strong to give their ideas for conducting the study (Bryman, 2016). Sample size plays an important role to increase the credibility of the data (Lee and Lings, 2008). Choosing the perfect sample design is also much crucial for the study as this governs the proper alignment for the entire study work (Remenyi, et al., 2005). The size mostly depends on the research question and research objectives (Saunders, Lewis, and Thornhill, 2012).

In general, qualitative research requires a small amount of sample size (Leavy, 2017). According to Leavy (2017), there is no hard and fast rules and regulation for selecting the appropriate sample size. Selecting a sample size for interpretivism is not a big issue because its nature is to gain a deep understanding of social phenomena that can be possible to conduct the research with a single sample (Collis and Hussey, 2009). If the sample size is larger, that will be more representative of

the underlying population (Gray, 2016). On the other hand, if the sample is smaller than, the precise will be less than larger samples (Easterby-Smith, Thorpe and Jackson, 2013).

However, according to Patton (2002, p.246), a minimum sample should be determined "based on expected reasonable coverage of the phenomenon given the purpose of the study". In the same way, Strauss and Corbin (1998, P.292) recommended that the data collection process should be performed until reaching theoretical saturation, which means "the researcher finds that no new data are being unearthed" whilst considering "the limits of available time and money". Furthermore, Arksey and Knight (1999, p.58) suggest "keep trying to increase the sample size, or size of sub-samples that represent different perspectives, until you are not hearing any new points".

The decision of sample size is not straightforward; most of the time, it is affected by available resources, money and time (Bryman, 2016). When sampling size increase, at the same time, sampling error decrease (Gray, 2016). However, to meet the research purpose, the researcher needs to provide justification or rationale for the sample size (Roller and Lavrakas, 2015). Similarly, Brinkmann (2013) recommends that qualitative interview research should not have more than 15 participants (Leavy, 2017). Similarly, Isaac and Michale (1995) also recommend 10 to 30 samples for exploratory studies in order to gain an in-depth understanding.

4.11 Data Collection Procedure

Data can be defined as "known facts or things used as a basis for inference or reckoning" (Collis and Hussey, 2009, p.187) that can be either qualitative form with no numerical data or quantitative form with numerical data (Collis and Hussey, 2009). It becomes necessary for the researcher to

give emphasis on the method used for data collection as it is an important task in the research process to maintain the reliability and validity of the study (Hair et al., 2007). Data is a raw material for study, and managing its quality increase the credibility of the finished product (Study result) by providing information about the experiences, ideas, views, beliefs, opinions, views and behaviour of the participants (Wagner, Kawulich and Garner, 2012). It helps to answer the research question or test hypotheses and allows the researcher to see the world through the eyes of the participant (Matthews and Ross, 2010; Wagner, Kawulich and Garner, 2012).

In general, researchers use two types of data which are either primary or secondary data, and that can be obtained from various sources (Easterby-Smith, Thorpe and Jackson, 2013; Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2014; Collis and Hussey, 2009; Sekaran and Bougie 2009). Primary data, also called original data, which the data are collected for the first time by the actual researcher for a specific research project or specific purpose through interviews, self-administrated surveys, direct observation or experiments (Picardi and Masick, 2014). On the other hand, secondary data refers to the data that has previously been generated and that can be accessed by the researcher. Company annual reports, company documentation, and government publication are the most common sources of secondary data (Blaxter, Hughes and Tight, 2006).

4.11.1 Primary Data

According to Malhotra and Birks (2003, p.85), "primary research is originated by a researcher for the specific purpose of addressing the problem at hand". Primary data is fresh in nature due to its production. Similarly, according to Teddlie and Tashakkori (2011), primary data is directly collected from respondents and does not have its footprint earlier in any study.

Hence this data is directly connected to the current problem or original source of the study, such as focus groups, interviews, surveys or won experiences (Collis and Hussey, 2009). Primary data is reliable and maintains more reliability in a study as well as generates confidence in the research outcome (Easterby-Smith, Thorpe, & Lowe, 2002). Major benefits of the primary data usage and its application in the study makes it more and more effective as it does not require a long time, money or access to collect data from government, non-government or other organisation (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2014). However, this data collection process can be time-consuming and quite expensive compared to the secondary data collection process (Hair et al., 2007).

4.11.2 Secondary Data

Some researcher considers re-analysing data that has already been collected by someone else in order to answer the research question or meet research objectives (Hakim, 2000). Likewise, Crouch and Housden (2000) described secondary data as the data that consists of information that already exists somewhere or has been published by someone else, usually being collected for another purpose. Researchers consider secondary data for further analyses that include raw data as well as published summaries (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2014).

As secondary data is not generated directly and purposefully, this may save researchers effort, expense and time, but this may not provide a clear answer to the current research question in mind (Hair et al., 2007). However, the researcher can collect those data from the researcher's own company as well as various external sources such as databases, publications, data collection companies, governmental and non-governmental agencies (Collis and Hussey, 2009).

Consideration of secondary data increases the chances of getting more statistical and theoretical knowledge due to the exploration of the source (Easterby-Smith, Thorpe & Lowe, 2002). The secondary data is collected using the exploration method of authentic data sources.

There is not much effort required in the collection of the secondary data and gets easily available through the literature discussed earlier (Teddlie and Tashakkori, 2011). Another advantage, which comes in this list, is that the second form of the data provides more clarity than the primary form of the data (Stentz, Clark, and Matkin, 2012). Moreover, the data is much more convenient and coefficient than the primary form of the data. However, Bryman (2016) claim in the research methods book that cost and time effective, high quality, the opportunity for longitudinal analysis, subgroup analysis, the opportunity for cross-culture and more time for data analysing is the main advantage of secondary data. On the other hand, the lack of familiarity with research data, the complexity of data, no control over data, and the absence of key variables are the limitation of this data (Bryman, 2016).

4.11.3 Justification of Using Data

In this research project, the researcher conducted primary research to collect primary data where the author will directly collect information from the original source (Gray, 2016). Predominantly this data will be collected by using interviews as well as conducting surveys to support finding (Collis and Hussey, 2009). In order to achieve the aims of this research, this data will lead to new insights as well as general confidence in the outcome of the research (Easterby-Smith, Thorpe & Lowe, 2002). This data will generate information for the specific purpose of the study (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2014) and will explore how product and price affect consumer buying

behaviour. Compared to secondary data, collecting primary data is quite time consuming and expensive (Bryman, 2016); however, it will provide the opportunity to understand the social phenomena of consumer buying behaviour in Euro Garage (Gray, 2016) as this data is original and relevant to the research topic, so the degree of accuracy is very high and highly reliable. Therefore, primary data is highly associated with this research as the researcher directly collects data for a specific purpose (Hair et al., 2007).

4.12 Collecting Primary Data Using a Semi-Structured Interview:

A research interview represents a purposeful meeting or conversation between two or more people (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2014). It "is a verbal exchange in which one person, the interviewer, attempts to acquire information from and gain an understanding of another person, the interviewee" (Gray, 2016, p.382). Similarly, Collis and Hussey (2009) also described that interview is a primary data collection method where the researcher asks questions to interviewees to find out what they think, do or feel about social phenomena.

In general, respondents are invited as a consumer, citizens or employees to talk about their own beliefs, attitudes, experiences and behaviour. Essentially, in the interviewing researcher ask unambiguous purposeful questions and listen to the answers very carefully to explore these further. Depending on the structure and level of formality used, the interview can be categorised as structured, semi-structured and unstructured (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2014). However, based on the nature of research and interaction between researcher and participant, the typology also can be categorised as standardised interviews and non-standardised interviews. On the other hand, Robson (2011), and Watts (1987), refer to two other types of interviews, such as focused

interviews and non-directive interviews. There is some overlap between these types of interviews, although each interview process provides the overall understanding of the nature of research. Based on the nature of the interaction between participants and researchers, Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill (2012) categorised interviews in the following dimension.

Content redacted due to copyright restrictions. Original figure can be found in Saunders et al, 2012.

Figure 4. 4: Interviews Structure

Source: Saunders et al. (2012)

Structured interviews also refer to standardised interviews where the researcher uses questionnaires based on a predetermined theme or set of questions. In this interview process, the researcher reads out each question and uses a standardised schedule to record the response. Usually, the researcher conducts the interviews with the use of pre-coded answers. As there is a social interaction between the researcher and respondents, the researcher must read out the questions exactly as it written and use the same tone of voice in order to avoid any bias.

However, semi-structured is under the non-standardised categorised. These are mostly referred to as qualitative research interviews (King, 2004). In this interview process researcher takes a list of themes and possibly some most important questions to cover, depending on the interview to interview. Depending on the answers and flow of conversation, some questions may vary, and some additional questions may be added with probes for in-depth understanding and exploring the interviewee's answers in more depth (Collis and Hussey, 2009).

Accordingly, unstructured interviews are also under the non-standardised categorised where the researcher explores in-depth knowledge in a particular area that is interested. In this data collection process, the researcher needs to have a clear idea about the aspect that the researcher is going to explore. Therefore, there is no predetermined theme or set of questions to work through. Respondents are given the opportunity to talk freely about their beliefs and behaviour in relation to the topic area.

As this research incorporates more than one type of method, such as qualitative and quantitative, for more thoroughly investigate the phenomena (Tashakkori and Teddlie 2003). In order to conduct the study, the researcher selected a systematic approach to make an in-depth understanding of phenomena and complete the study (Robson, 2002). Indeed, one of the research questions is how pricing strategy influences consumer buying behaviour from the organisational perspective. In order to address the research question, qualitative research design become more favourable and related to interpretive philosophy followed by an inductive approach than quantitative research design as the researcher requires an in-depth understanding of social phenomena (Denzin and Lincoln, 2005).

This is also because researchers need to make sense of the subjective and socially constructed meaning (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2012). These can be understood by seeing what meaning people give to them and interpreting their meanings from their perceptions (Blumberg et al., 2008). As the researcher focuses on the organisational perspective, the semi-structured interviews data collecting process is highly associated in this exploratory study for collecting primary data from the respondents in order to get an in-depth understanding of human behaviour (Bryman, 2016).

4.12.1 Semi-Structured Interview

The research interests forming semi-structured interviews, conducting the face-to-face meeting with Euro Garage managers to understand the relationship between the range of products and pricing with consumer behaviour. The purpose of the interview is to use conversation, discussion as well as questioning of the manager to get insight into the research themes. The semi-structured interview has a specific framework and direction to ask a question that allows a lot of flexibility to include unstructured questioning (Hair et al., 2007). It will also find out in what ways an interviewee voices and from the challenging perspective on how and why consumers choose this convenience store.

A semi-structured interview is a non-standardised data collection method that is mostly used in social research (Gray, 2016). According to Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill (2014), a semi-structured interview typically refers to qualitative research where the researcher takes a list of themes and possibly some most important questions to cover, depending on the interview. However, depending on the answers and flow of conversation, some questions may be varied, and some additional questions may be added with probes for in-depth understanding and exploring the

interviewee's answers in more depth (Collis and Hussey, 2009). Even though in this data collection process researcher or interviewer has a list of questions and issues to cover but sometimes it might not be possible to cover everything in each interview (Gray, 2016).

This interview process is a meeting of people face to face where questions are asked, and answers are given, a form of managing verbal exchange (Ritchie and Lewis, 2003). The effectiveness of this kind of interview mostly depends on the performance and communication skills of the interviewer (Clough and Nutbrown, 2006). This includes the capability to ask a clear and structured question (Cohen, Manion and Morrison, 2007); listen carefully and attentively (Clough and Nutbrown, 2006); prompt, probe, or pause appropriately (Ritchie and Lewis, 2003); and make the sure interviewee feel free to talk and make it easy for interviewees to respond (Clough and Nutbrown, 2006). At the same time, interpersonal skills are also important in a semi-structured interview in order to establish a rapport with humour and humility (Maxwell, 1997).

The semi-structured interview implies the interviewee's personal language to data. Face to face interview is important when the researcher is primarily focusing on gaining insight and depth understanding (Gillham, 2002). It could be argued that a semi-structured interview recognises the potential significance of context. This data collection method is consistent with emancipatory and participatory models.

In general, the researcher changes the interview direction when new issues arise. Indeed, the additional question may ask which was not anticipated at the beginning of the interview process (Gray, 2016). In order to document the responses, the researcher can take notes or record the whole

interview (Easterby-Smith, Thorpe & Lowe, 2002). Probing the respondent's views and opinions allows them to expand their answer more deeply. This data collection method is vital when researchers use a phenomenological approach where typically, objective explore subjective meaning ascribed to respondent's concepts (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2014). Therefore, this probing allows the diversion of interviews and creates a new pathway to meet the research objective.

The advantage of this data collection process is to probe deeply to uncover new clues based on participants' personal experiences, as this kind of interview is related to the personal experience of the interviewee. Therefore, researchers mostly conduct on one to one basis between the interviewer and the interviewee. The researcher can develop questions on the spot through interactions and dialogue and lead the whole research (Glesne, 2016). In the interview, the schedule researcher can dispose of, modify, abandon, replace or add a new question on the question list. The goal of this approach is to gain an understanding of a phenomenon from respondents' perspectives, include not only to see what their viewpoint is but also why they have this particular viewpoint (Easterby-Smith, Thorpe & Lowe, 2002).

Semi-structured interviews were conducted using open-ended questions with respondents so that respondents could explain and justify their responses. Similarly, Glesne (2016) also state that in semi-structured interviews, research questions generally emerge in the course of fieldwork and that may add to or replace pre-established ones. The researcher cannot ask anything that does not relevant to the research problem.

This research will collect interview data from those who are directly and indirectly involved at the management level. The main method of the research will be used semi-structured interviews in order to gain primary data. Sixteen interviews will be conducted, including one pilot interview. The interview will be face to face in a separate room, with one interview at a time. However, there will be an option to conduct the interview over the phone if any interviewee is required. The interview consists of both men and women who got experience working at different levels of management positions in the company. The interview will last an average of 40 minutes. Responses will be recorded on an electronic device, and take field notes, including some body language.

Based on the above statement, an individual, face to face interview is accepted as the most suitable method for collecting qualitative data as it "offers advantages of flexibility, interactivity and informality. These features mean that you steer the interview in the direction suggested by the response can prompt and probe, explore meanings and thus generate rich qualitative information" (Cameron and Price, P.637, 2009). Therefore, this research project employed non-standardised interviews that mostly referred to qualitative research interviews (King, 2004). A semi-structured interview will provide the opportunity to talk freely without having a predetermined list of questions. However, the researcher must have the knowledge and a clear idea about what to explore (Saunders, Lewis & Thornhill, 2012).

4.13 Collecting Primary Data Using Survey Questionnaire

4.13.1 Survey Questionnaire

Questionnaires are frequently used in quantitative marketing research and social research (Roopa and Satya, 2012). According to Ponto (2015), survey research may use a variety of data collection methods, with the most common being questionnaires and interviews.

A questionnaire is a series of questions asked to individuals to obtain statistically useful information about a given topic, and when properly constructed and responsibly administered, questionnaires become a vital instrument by which statements can be made about specific groups of people or the entire population (Roopa and Satya, 2012).

Questionnaires are defined as simply a list of mimeographed or printed questions that are completed by or for a respondent to give his opinion (Roopa and Satya, 2012).

According to (Eaden et al., 1999), questionnaires may be open-ended or closed-ended, where open questionnaires tend to encourage qualitative responses which are harder to analyse and are not given easy measurements, and closed questionnaires require some 'yes' or 'no' type answers and allow a numerical value to be attached to the responses. The closed-ended questionnaire type was thus favourable for this research.

The popularity of questionnaires is founded on the speed with which results can be obtained without significant capital investment (Eaden et al., 1999). However, there is a commonly held view that because of these elements, questionnaires can easily be constructed and used without training (Eaden et al., 1999).

It thus became important for this study that its questionnaires were well-structured and that they were reliable. To that end, a test for reliability was conducted on it using a pilot sample size of respondents before it was finally administered to the primary respondents for the study.

In order to construct the survey questionnaire, the research objective was first matched with the proposed questions to be asked.

Here, the objective was to investigate how the pricing strategies implemented in the Euro Garages store influenced how the customer bought in the store. Data was to be extracted from the customers themselves, and in order to extract information that was to be used in the research, the researcher relied on questions from existing literature, those from researcher observations and that researcher came up with, modifying these accordingly.

These questions were to be structured, closed-ended questions as data had to be quantifiable; hence the Likert style Questionnaire format was employed to develop the study's own Questionnaire tool.

A pilot sample size of 10 respondents was then used to test the reliability of the questionnaire.

The questionnaire was then edited until an acceptable reliability level, the score was reached, and the questions were stronger. The final document was then printed and made available to be distributed to the larger sample population.

Collection of data was carried out at different times of the day, throughout weekdays and weekends, to ensure better representation.

4.14 Research Procedures

The researcher employed the strategies of telephoning and emailing to gain access to the organisation in order to reach the primary participants for this study (Collis and Hussey, 2014; Saunders et al., 2012).

A consent letter was sent to each manager referred to obtain interview permission. Fifteen days were given to participants to decide on a response to the consent letter sent. Participants who did not respond to the consent letter with their signatures were assumed to not be interested in participating in the study, and new participants were selected to complete the research sample target using the same method.

For the survey questionnaire exercise, customers who, for some reason, did not indicate a willingness to participate in the study were not handed a questionnaire. Those who were required to respond to the same set of questions. The questionnaire exercise was carried out at different times of the day, throughout weekdays and weekends, to ensure better representation.

Interviews with the managers were done in a neutral and quiet room environment so that the information was not passed to other participants. During the interview and survey questionnaire exercises, the researcher adopted an anonymous code for individual participants so that their identities were not revealed.

Data was only accessed by the researcher, and no other research member was allowed to access the data. Full confidentiality was managed during and after the completion of the research exercise. The use of own device and Secured Password was considered essential to the researcher as it ensured a hundred per cent confidentiality of personal data gathered during the research exercise.

4.14.1 Ethical Consideration

Only individuals who indicated interest were made to participate in the current study. The data and information were kept in a locked personal computer, and only the researcher had access to it. The researcher ensured the privacy of the participants by respecting their dignity. Participants' personal contact details, home addresses and other similarly sensitive data were not disclosed to third parties without their consent. (Gray, 2014). It was also ensured that data was kept and protected according to the UK Data Protection Act (1998 as cited in Gray, 2014). Data was no longer kept after the successful completion of the exercise, and these were destroyed lawfully after that (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2012).

The researcher ensured that the results of the study were not altered and were reported accurately. The researcher will not publish the results if it causes harm to participants or any of the parties (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2012). Finally, the researcher will maintain his integrity by being honest and truthful throughout the study.

4.15 Data Analysis Method

Likert questionnaires were analysed using the Excel application (Excel 2013) for frequencies, means, percentages, standard deviation and SPSS for Pearson's Correlation analysis to determine an association between the pricing strategies of Euro Garage stores and the buying Behaviour of their customers. The correlation was performed using SPSS.

Before the questionnaire exercise was carried out, a reliability test was conducted on a pilot study of 10 questionnaires to determine the reliability of this quantitative tool to be employed. This was

to ensure that this instrument would give results that could be analysed to produce valid scientific conclusions. According to Gliem and Gliem (2003), when using Likert-type scales, it is imperative to calculate and report Cronbach's Alpha Coefficient for internal consistency and reliability for any scales or subscales one may be using. The Likert questionnaire to be used in this study was thus tested for reliability using the Cronbach's Alpha Coefficient formula before it was finally administered. Results and findings from analysing both data gotten from the interview and questionnaires were then presented for interpretation.

4.16 Chapter Summary

This chapter presented the roadmap to the gathering and collection of the data that will be tested and analysed in this study. Population and sample design for the study was presented. The sampling technique to be used and sample size were also presented.

Method of data collection, research procedure and data analysis method was highlighted in this chapter. The chapter also highlighted ethical considerations observed when carrying out qualitative interviews and surveys in storing and using information.

The next chapter will present the results and findings from the data analysed and offer interpretations of them.

CHAPTER FIVE

RESULTS AND FINDINGS

5.1 Introduction

This chapter presents the research data findings on how pricing impacts on consumer buying Behaviour at the Euro Garage. The mixed research approach was employed to collect primary data from respondents of this study. Respondents were made up of 16 employees at the Euro Garage comprising branch managers, one area manager and one assistant manager. They participated in 40-minute semi-structured interviews face to face.

The second group of respondents in this study were customers of the store. 400 structured questionnaires using the Likert-scale format were administered to them.

Qualitative data from the interview were subjected to thematic analyses using traditional and manual, while quantitative data from the Likert questionnaire were analysed using the Excel application (Excel 2013) for frequencies, means, percentages, and standard deviation.

A Pearson's Correlation analysis was performed on the data to determine an association between the pricing strategies of store managers in the garage and the buying Behaviour of their customers. The correlation was performed using SPSS.

Findings are presented as follows:

5.2 Results from Semi-Structured Interviews

16 employees of Euro Garage were sampled using the snowball sampling technique as justified in the previous chapter to take part in a 17-question, semi-structured interview for the purpose of this study.

Table 5. 1: Participants Profile for Qualitative Research

Variables	Levels	Frequency (F)	Percentage (%)
Gender	Male	15	93.75
	Female	1	6.25
	Total	16	100
Management Levels	Branch manager(s)	14	87.5
	Area Manager	1	6.25
	Assistant Manger	1	6.25
	Others		
	Total	16	100
Years worked	Less than 1 year	2	12.5
	1-3 years	3	18.75
	4-7 years	4	25
	8-11 years	0	00
	11 years and more	7	43.75
	Total	16	100

Source: Field Survey (2022)

From the table above, the study carried out a semi-structured interview with 16 employees of Euro Garage. There were 15 males and 1 number of females. Of these, 12.5 per cent had worked less

than 1 year there, 18.75 percent 1-3 years, 25 percent 4-7 years, 0.0 percent 8-11 years, a 43.75 percent 11 years and more. The 16 sampled employees consisted of 14 branch managers, 1 area manager, 1 assistant manager. Respondents for the interview were sampled using the snowball sample technique.

5.2.1 Effect of Pricing on Consumer Buying Behaviour As Observed by Employees Of The Euro Garage

The purpose of the study was to explore how pricing impacted consumer buying Behaviour with a focus on Euro Garage. It aimed to approach this in two ways; first, from the perspective of the store managers at the garage, and then from the customers themselves.

In order to obtain this data from Euro Garage employees, a semi-structured interview was conducted. This had 17 questions and lasted 40 minutes for each respondent. From the qualitative interview conducted, the following list of codes were drawn.

Table 5.2 reflects the codes derived from the qualitative research interview conducted and coded by the researcher.

From the table, all of the 16 respondents who participated in the interview saw the subjects of pricing and consumer behaviour as important and believed that there was an influencing element between both variables. Consumer buying behaviour and pricing were mentioned 82 and 71 times, respectively, in individual segments of the transcript as shown by the references column.

Location was also talked about by all respondents and mentioned 71 times. It is believed that the proximity of the store attracted customers' patronage.

Table 5. 2: Codes from Qualitative Data

Name	Files	References	Name	Files	References
Consumer buying behaviour	16	82	Bundle pricing	11	11
Pricing	16	71	Local business	5	9
Location	16	70	Religions	5	8
Promotion	14	52	Compare with supermarket	5	8
Convenience	16	48	24 hours access	3	8
Different function	14	39	Type of consumer	4	7
Time saving	10	30	Cultural background	6	7
Price setting	13	27	Club card	3	7
Ages	16	25	Consumer compare price	5	6
Managerial experience	16	24	Promotional price	1	6
Manager skills	14	23	Communicating with local consumer	5	6
Family	14	23	Price reduction	4	6
Customer service	12	23	Health census consumer	3	6
Consumer complain about pricing	10	21	Some consumer coming for Toilet	4	6
Branded products	10	19	Price influence to buy more	3	5
Shopping daily basis	11	19	Seasonal product pricing	5	5
Occupation	15	18	Weekly shopping	3	5
High low pricing	15	18	Price change affect consumer buying behaviour	3	4
Quality of products	9	18	Buy one get one free	3	4
Willing to pay extra for convenience	13	17	Why service station is expensive	3	4
Fast service	9	17	Social background	3	3
Ethnic	9	17	Consumer plan before coming here	3	3
Status of consumer	13	16	Major factors affecting consumer buying behaviour	2	2
Economic situation	10	16	Offering different facilities	1	2
Everyday low pricing	13	16	Regular pricing strategy	1	2
Seasonal products	11	16	Availability	2	2
People class	7	15	Freedom to make decision	1	2
Competitors	6	15	Upselling	1	1
School children	11	15	One-pound product promotion	1	1
Meal deals	11	14	History of EG	1	1
Geographical area	7	13	Space	1	1
Easy access	8	13	Footfall	1	1
Negative feedback from promotion	11	13	Offering free	1	1
Car parking	7	13	Red sign to attract more consumer	1	1
Market research	9	12	Shop Design	1	1
Positive feedback from promotional offers	10	12			

Source: Field Survey (2022)

14 of the 16 respondents mentioned promotions. It can be theorised that the majority of the store managers think promotional pricing attracted consumers significantly.

11 of the 16 respondents thought bundle pricing was important to their customers. Only 5 thought that the customer compared prices in the store before they bought.

3 out of the 16 respondents thought that prices influenced consumers to buy more. This could suggest that although the price was important to the customer, it didn't always mean that consumers bought more because of it. Other factors played a role.

13 of the 16 respondents believed that the customer was willing to pay more for convenience. This is quite an interesting take as it would suggest that Euro Garage customers did not compromise convenience over price.

All 16 interviewed managers and staff talked about location and convenience, which could suggest that these were important elements to their consumers.

14 out of the 16 respondents believed that consumers came to the Euro garage for different functions in addition to buying fuel.

10 of the 16 respondents indicated that branded products were important consideration to the customers.

All of the respondents mentioned age in their responses. This could suggest that the age of the customer played many important roles while at the store.

More than half believed that high-low prices and everyday low pricing had an impact on how the consumer purchased goods.

14 out of 16 believed that family played a role in influencing how their consumers bought.

11 out of the 16 said that consumers shopped daily. Only 5 thought that seasonal product pricing was important to the consumer.

In each of the following items of offering different facilities, regular pricing strategy, upselling, free offers and shop design, only one out of the 16 respondents each thought that these were important to the customer or influenced how they bought. This should mean that from the overall managers' perspective, these items did not appear important to their customers.

The responses from the store employees and managers suggest that pricing impacts the buying behaviour of their customers. This conclusion will be consistent with various research studies available that show that pricing impacts consumer behaviour. For instance, this finding corroborates Bailey (2011), whose study indicated that most consumers' buying behaviour gets influenced by issues germane to pricing. Key among this is the impact of promotional prices on buyers' behaviours, as indicated by the result of the respondents. Therefore, this corroborates earlier arguments by reviewed scholars who posit that price promotions are an essential element of a company's marketing policy because they affect sales, profits, and key intangible assets, such as brand equity (Kuntner and Teichert, 2016).

According to the response from the interviews, it can be plausibly argued that to be successful in a competitive environment, many companies take into consideration different sales techniques like promotion (Urun, 2011). They spend immense amounts of money on promotions, be they as a direct result of coupons, rebates, contests or payments to retailers to display or promote a product at a reduced price (Urun, 2011). Kotler (2003) states that promotions can be described as

stimulations and rewards which lead customers to buy now rather than later. They are short-term tools that trigger buyer actions, and their effect on sales revenue can be measured quickly and easily (Kotler, 2003, as cited in Urun, 2011).

Furthermore, there was a significant relationship between the age of the respondents and the prices charged. There was, however, an inverse relationship between gender and price charged. ANOVA showed a significant difference between the price charged by the store and the store choice of the respondents. Hence, price affected consumers' decisions on where to buy fuel.

However, as shown by the responses of the managers, pricing impacts the consumer in varying ways. This will be consistent with some existing literature that pricing doesn't always make the customer buy more. Quality and other factors sometimes take priority place instead. This can be inferred from the submissions of Kotler et al. (2016) and Hawkins et al. (2007). According to Braun and Clark(2012), thematic analysis can be approached from different perspectives. In this study, themes were derived from a combination of literature and primary data. Table 5.2 illustrates how themes were derived in the data analysis process.

This study will obtain responses from the Euro Garage customers themselves and evaluate its consistency with the responses of the managers. In other words, data obtained from accessing store customers will be tested to determine if pricing impacted their buying behaviour if this was a positive or negative impact, and what other factors influenced how they bought.

What follows is a more precise focus on the core variables of the study and the presentation of data elicited from respondents concerning them.

5.2.2 Theme 1- Consumer Buying Behaviour

The objective here is to present data from Euro Garage managers concerning their perception of consumer buying behaviour. However, it is pertinent to note that the consumer is the most important element for marketers in the marketplace (Kotler and Armstrong, 2016), and understanding consumer behaviour is a significant factor that leads the organisation to success (Dapkevicius and Melnikas, 2009). According to Hawkins, Mothersbaugh and Best (2007:6), "consumer behaviour is the study of individuals, groups, or organisations and the processes they use to select, secure, use, and dispose of products, services, experiences, or ideas to satisfy needs and the impacts that these processes have on the consumer and society". Consumer behaviour describes how individual consumers or groups make a purchase decision and how they use and dispose of goods, services, experiences or ideas to satisfy their needs and demand (Kotler et al., 2016).

According to McDaniel, Lamb and Hair (2006), understanding consumer buying behaviour helps to recognise internal and external factors that influence the consumer buying decision. An equally significant aspect by London (1993:5), "Consumer buying behaviour can be defined as the decision process, and physical activity individuals engage in when evaluating, using, or disposing of goods and services". Therefore the key objective of this theme is to investigate the factors that influence consumer choice in the decision of selecting a service station. With this theme, researchers focus on understanding the factors that influence consumer decision making as this is a complex critical phenomenon.

Consequently, the field research reveals that consumer buying behaviour is profoundly influenced by expedient and priority needs as well as easy access to goods and services, comfort/convenience and environmental ambience. These factors are significant in consumers' buying behaviours, as aptly captured by the interview participants thus:

“poor people to the big millionaires they hate coming to petrol station because of they need petrol, that’s the most important things in there or whether they want to travel or whatever they want the first things is food and petrol”. **(Participant-1)**

"yes, because the thing is, easy access like if you want to go to the supermarket, you park the car and you have to walk a long way, 2 minutes or sometimes you have to park in different places. But in petrol station is an easy access like customers can come grab the stuffs and go. Because most of the customer coming to petrol station, they do not want to spend half an hour like supermarket and one hour time. Because they come to buy a, grab the stuffs go quickly as soon as possible and that is why we have to give good service, because we do not want to keep the customer long time here the till area. That is why I am saying to my cashier guys you cannot keep the customer holding in a big que. You have to get rid of the que because customer do not want to wait more than single minute. We provide easy access and first selling products in the customer waiting area and low selling items in the corner that’s how we setup petrol station”. **(Participant-1)**

“It's first face, so you see lots of customers, don’t see lots of regular customers, yes some occasional regular customers, but not lot. Lots of them passing by customer

want some convenience. I know some site has regular customers; we have some but most of our customer are irregular. because of the situation of my site is, in between two junctions of the m25, and I am close to m1. So, I got junction 21a and m25 down there and junction 20 up there. So, customer come through lots of traffic by catch.”(Participant-2)

“most customers are not concern about pricing; they are more concern about convenience, that’s the way that EG have operated, so they make sure they have got different brands in the garage for example, we have Grage here, we have got a subway here and we have PFS the fuel side of the business. So, everything under one roof and we have the Starbucks coffee machines so most customers will come here because everything under one roof, its more continence for them, they do not stop to buy petrol, so years ago, you buy petrol then you go somewhere else to get your foods and the lunch. Now they want everything under one place. all ordinary people coming to it.” (Participant-2)

The above evidence shows that all types of customers come to shop in the petrol station, mostly because of its easy access, product availability and time-saving, where customer can fuel their car and quickly do their shopping within a short period of time. Most customers are not concerned about pricing. They are more concerned about the convenience. Therefore, the company offer everything under one roof, such as fuel, all fast-moving grocery products, subway, Greggs, Starbucks coffee etc.

"consumer buying behaviour in forecourt business compare with five, six years its now very changed, now people are more buying from forecourt retail compare with five years ago. I think even now people doing regular shopping at the forecourt retail even its expensive. People now day-to-day things they are buying from here. majority of our customers are local customer, either they local or they work in this area, so it is really one of the factors that affect our business. Especially in our site it is affecting the local factors. product availability convenience and I can say fast shopping that are the main factors that affecting this retail business, especially in our site." (Participant-3)

Data also indicate that, at present, people from the local area or those who work around the shop area they are more frequently buying their regular shopping from forecourt retailers compared to the last five years. This is because of products availability, convenience, and a fast shopping environment.

"time saving, and in my experience what I found is the regular customer, you know why we get regular customer because they feel more confident than they go to new shop because once they come to inside our shop, they know which product is where exactly even sometimes they know better than us, they know what the price are, and they know it's expensive. So example they just park and they want to the orange juice, they know exactly where to go. They don't want to go around. So most of customer more confidence to come and for the regular shopping rather than going to new place because it is saving their time and they know what we have, and they

know what we do not have so normally what I found the most of customers they have an pattern what they are buying. Someone who like orange juice the next day they are very unlike to buy something else so that is what I found in this petrol station. So, they have same kind of food varieties they are eating so maybe they change the flavours but if they buy one pack of chocolate per day and plush one crisp, they have a pattern, same pattern so always coming for same things”. (Participant-3)

“Supermarket shopping experience and the forecourt shopping experience is a little bit different so you can’t see any people hanging around 10-15 minutes. It is fast for customs so fast serving is like they do not want to spend time, and they do not like to stay on the long time on the que. So, they expect everything happened very quickly so that is one reason I believe they come, and they choose petrol station”. (Participant-1)

Additionally, some respondent strongly believes that the shop size also affects consumer buying behaviour. Generally, the fuel station is smaller compared to the high-street supermarket, where the consumer can easily find products, especially regular customers, they exactly know which products wherein the shop. It is also clear that most of the customers are regular bases and they come for the same products. Customers know the products are expensive, but it is saving their time that is the key reason for shopping in the petrol station. The data also suggested that customers do not like to spend more time or stay in a long queue; they want everything to happen very quickly and fast.

"So, forecourt retail is mainly customer come to here to buy the petrol at the same time while they are paying for fuel, we give them the opportunity that's how its starts. They are important things to save time. That's why they start the forecourt retail shop." (*Participant-1*)

However, another respondent stated that the customers mainly come here to fuel their vehicles. The company offers fast-moving products and offers them to do their shopping while they come to pay, which saves their time.

"sometimes people come in and they just come and get offers such as one-pound products or the one-pound drinks or two for pound. they tend to make use of all the offers there whether that's just for their lunch or if it is for just general, they come in and they don't spend on anything else but the cheaper products". (Participant-4)

The findings suggest that some customers only come for promotional offers.

"it depends on the petrol station if it is in a village area, so they come for the normally grocery products if it is in a motorway, then it's a different concept. my shop is located in a village not a very urban area, so it is depending on the village type thing it is like off-licence. Half off-licence and half petrol station products." (*Participant-5*)

“This petrol station basically customers are always passing traffic it's near a roundabout. We don't have much local customer because 5 minutes way from local Sainsbury, so local people normally going to Sainsbury for their regular shopping, here we mostly getting passing customer. We got high competition with Sainsbury because they also do the fuel, so the local people mostly go to Sainsbury because they can fuel their car and do their shopping, which is much cheaper and good quality than us. Even the convenience products Sainsbury cheaper than us so local people who knows Sainsbury is 5 minutes away from us they are going there. So, we mostly getting passing customer, or irregular customer who is new to this area, also we are next to motor way and near the roundabout so whoever need fuel in the motorway they come to us.” (Participant-5)

However, some respondents describe consumer buying behaviour differently. The respondent believed that consumer behaviour depends on the location of the shop. If the shop is situated in the village area, then the consumer would come for normal grocery products. If it is located next to the motorway, then it is a different concept. Consumer mostly considers product quality, price, and accessibility.

Another respondent stated that:

“with my store we have lot of competition around us like we got cheaper shops we go Sainsbury's cross the road and I got a Liddle cross the road and we have community shops along the streets. So, there are lot of competition with my store,

and we need to give what customer needs with keeping in mind we have competitors all over the place, so we offer lower price products.” (Participant-6)

“We got two types of business model one is petrol, and another is shop, convenience product. Mostly the competition not with the petrol, mostly with convenient product.” (Participant-7)

"with EG they roll out in a way every story is similar sort of or kind of same shop kind same layout. Selling most of the prioritised products, customer cannot live without it. For that they do not mind paying extra." (Participant-7)

The above quotes are evident that the company offer lower-priced products where they have too many competitors and shop location. The shop layout is similar where they sell all prioritised products.

Related to previous data, some respondents stated that

"in this area is very rich area so when we compare with other branch some of them got petrol price little bit down compare with our price. So, we have competition with the BP and the Tesco in the other side, our shop is in perfect place consumer can't ignore the place. And we got the big forecourt, we got the toilet facilities, we got the Greggs with us and a Starbucks. so, we give lots of choice. when they come in, they never go empty ok, so they are coming they are happy and happy to go". (Participant-8)

"This area like you can't sell spar brands that much, right because when we started like we had about 95 percent of the products from spa brands, when we open this new shop, and they weren't like moving because consumers expecting high quality products. The local customer expecting like high quality of products." (Participant-9)

"This area is quite posh and reach the consumer demanding good quality product and good service. Spar, they're the only supplier but they do have certain products which is like to see high-end sort of like high quality. and like what I normally do is like I try to reduce much as possible or spa brand ok and try to get the branded products brand, almost every customer know what Mcvitties is rather than having a spar branded product, Spar is like where we get like even though we the local community is the same like others on the other side you get some customers like who are looking for products which are like in low price sort of, other side of this area so like we have to deal with both of them like mixture. So, we have mixture of product high price and low price and branded product this is how we approach to the customer." (Participant-9)

However, related to previous data, another respondent stated that location and many competitors always do not affect consumer buying behaviour. When the shop is in a reach area and offers a lot of facilities, then customers always will come happily in reach and posh areas consumer demanding high-quality products and service.

“So, in the morning if customers coming yeah, some customers, they have lunch or they have breakfast, so they buy petrol and going. some customers they are rushing to go to work, so they put petrol and they buy breakfast in the morning who are on the way to work. afternoon people if they are coming here if they are bypassing dinner get fuel, they buy lunch or buy whatever they feel like they have it that time.”

(Participant-7)

“People come to get fuel, they see subway, Starbucks, when they see those things, they say o let's go and get some so under one roof they get all famous brands. When they come to petrol station if they see different famous brand, they will buy it. It saves their time. Instead of going two places they come to one place petrol station they are getting three branded foods or products. So, in one place they got three brands, so they do not need to spend time to go different directions.” **(Participant-7)**

“in the morning, the people who did not get a fuel they come in the evening and then they buy different products, in the afternoon lunch time people come for lunch they buy lunch, and they get fuel. So, they saving their time getting fuel and lunch together. So, they are using the convenient, so the people want petrol they come in the morning they buy the breakfast the people who has come in the lunch time to buy lunch they get fuel in the afternoon, so they do not need to worry about in the evening or the next day. I see some people come back again, even if you put price

down still people going to complain there are some people they will complain still until they get it free, they will keep complain.” (Participant-7)

The above data also indicate that consumers use petrol stations for convenience purposes where they can do multiple things at a time. The company also provide the branded products under the same roof, and it saves their time. Consumers do complain about the higher price, but they do come regularly.

“Normally when the school kids come yes like they will go for the promotional stuff and like they go for the offices, but they do their spend basket is like five pounds six pounds per day. Whenever they come, normally they come regularly, dally and the other customers like the basket spend this around like some like who are doing their shopping some customers are around 60 pounds 70 pounds some go up to 100 pounds also so kids they are spending less than others yes because they come after school. before they get into their coaches like they will buy the offices and they are always looking for offers.” (Participant-9)

“This is because the budget like whatever the allowance they get from their parents. Maxima spend between like three to five pounds in average but the older people they are the one who is spending lots of money. So it somehow affecting our business and sales volume, because when the schools are closed when the sales go down I school because whenever they like they open like we have about during one and one and a half hours when they're there like we like increased sales by about two hundred pounds, if you staying here until afternoon you'll see like what I don't know

that depends on whether the schools are like the kids will be coming but if you see this whole shop will be crowded with kids within an hour sort of like between 3 and 4 o'clock". (Participant-9)

Furthermore, one of the respondents suggests that school kids are highly attracted by promotional offers. They are the regular customers of the company with a small budget compared to older people who spend more.

"Mostly in this area there is no other shop, there is no petrol station around this area also. To do shopping in this areas people have to go to town centre, where lots of supermarket including Morrison, Tesco. The other thing this area is reach area. Mostly when they are going to work, they come for sometimes they come for coffee and fill petrol, buying some like chocolate or something like that on the way to their destination. So specially when consumer on the way to their work they are coming here and get the things they needed. And evening also they come here mostly they buy day to day products that means milk, bread, eggs sometimes fruits something like that this by sometimes." (Participant-10)

"we have passing customers as well, but they care about our fuel price, but they fill fuel and after that come to the shop also they care about the prices mostly the passing customer. Passing customer those people only buy the petrol mostly not buy anything else, but we have promotion products we display on front of the shelf and those items are very cheap so mostly students, some people who thinking about cheap prices they buy those promotional items. (Participant-10)

“In the petrol station if the fuel price low your customers coming inside, we can increase the customers if the fuel price is low, we can target that customers, but we cannot reduce the fuel price because they said fixed price that they are giving the price. So, consumer always check the fuel price before they are coming here. I am talking about other people not the regular people. That is the only way to increase the customers in this area”. (Participant-10)

Additionally, some respondents believed that there are two types of consumers coming to the petrol station. One is local, and another is a passing customer. Local customers will come when there is no alternative choice, and they are ok with the higher price. On the other hand, the passing customer cares about the fuel price. They are the ones who plan or check fuel prices before coming to the petrol station.

“The customers coming here because we try to understand the customers locally, so we decide what is sell best for our local customers. which is in other places I don't know 100% to say this comment on that but I work for different rocks which is a similar situation in different petrol stations in the at the moment as well so I can tell EG we decide most best for customers like I said in this place manager said ok let's increase the popcorn variety which we did and at the same time we go for more snacking because in the middle of the city and customers want quick things whatever they missed or if they hungry they just want to have a little snack quick because I don't expect them to do the weekly shopping here basically because that's

not the place. there are some sites customers do weekly shopping yeah but that's because sites here this purely based on snacking really so our day-to-day shopping or quick shop.” (Participant-11)

"they may come in here for different reasons every single customer is different, some customers just come for food they don't even look at the shop just fill up directly to the till yes I have a couple of sites like that in Luton they just straight to the till they don't want to do any shopping because obviously they thing is petrol stations expensive but some other places yes they coming for fuel they fill up in the meantime they see the Greggs they see the Starbucks signs inside the store and they make the quick decision ok let's have a bite while I'm here. if they have to stop something else, they have to stop the car again find the parking all that hassle is there but in this case they don't have any hassle. because then it's only coming here to fill up while they fill up, they make another decision ok well I mean why not I eat something one bringing another". (Participant-11)

"it's a geographic I think because like you said before is Luton it's very price sensitive and the community is very different to most of my other areas so I have to always offer them more promotions and price cuts something like that then they will look into the shelves so that's something I did when I take over one of the Luton site recently I have to completely change the shop because nobody is looking at the shop which is going to the till so I wanted them to look the shop ok so we introduced complete new range one pound range basically and put red like to attract customers eyes I like red signs and markers and bits and pieces so even though customers

don't want to they'll see it oh that's a pound let me stop have a look they might buy might not let's try all bits so that's how we change it. Now it is picking up because customer thinking, a lot of people say petrol stations expensive look that is a pound. I have complete full to base actually 1-pound stuffs, this is like one pound shop. So, the perception changes slowly when they see the one pound what they think of the petrol station changes so then they say ok this is not expensive".

(Participant-11)

Some respondents mentioned that they are trying to understand the local consumers. Based on that, they decide the product, price, and other facilities such as food and drinks, mostly focusing on day-to-day shopping. Sometimes, they even change the shop layout, adding new cheap product line to make them feel that petrol station is not expensive. Therefore, when they consume to fuel their vehicle, they quickly make a new decision for convenience products, food, or drinks.

"Most of the consumer coming here because we got free ATM machines here, we got a Subway and a free toilet here and carwash is here most people most people come coming here they are looking for car washes". **(Participant-12)**

"When they come to buy petrol, they see the car wash here they see the ATM machine here, they see free to use two toilets here, they can see Subway food here for the breakfast, lunch, and dinner, they can see the coffee machine, this machine can provide the cold coffee as well as hot coffees the shop open 24 hours a day

normally few shop open 24 hours only very few shops. So, you can get everything under one roof which is all attracting the consumer". (Participant-12)

"By the meantime when they come to the shop they see other products. So, when people see the things like he supposed to buy one for one pound when they see three for pound they simply buy this. When it's on the promotional offers sometimes they buy three or four together. Especially for drinks when they find it's cheap, they just buy it".(Participant-12)

Similar to the previous data, another respondent highlighted that it is all about the different functions of the business and accessibility where customers can get everything under one roof, where promotional offers are highly effective.

"In this area it's very difficult to find a parking, so we provide the good opportunity to consumer offering them free parking, so it's easy to park the car here and do their shopping or if they want to eat they can easily take some time and have their breakfast or lunch or dinner. So, the free car park attracting more customer in my shop. So it's very easy to park the car here, because if you do normal shopping in this area, you cannot find any place for free parking so here you can park your car and do your shopping. It's also convenience for the consumer, saving time and money, they can have their food and fuel from the same place as well as their daily necessary things". (Participant-13)

“We are getting mostly passing customers they do not bother about the price. Compare with other supermarket we are bit expensive but as a petrol station we are reasonable, as most of the petrol station are expensive, compare with them we are not very expensive.” (Participant-13)

"People always thinking of the price ok so if you do some promotional offers, they will come they come daily and they will become regular customer. And they do not have to worry about to find the place where they can park their car. The important things in petrol station or whatever the business once we give the good customer services, the people come on repeat. Whatever it is they will come again even you increase price. So good consumer service work positively even you increase the price it will not affect the consumer buying behaviour, consumer still will come". (Participant-14)

“Another problem is parking, in this town area we do not have free parking, so we free parking her. So, in our petrol station you can fuel your car and do your regular shopping everything whatever you want. So, you are not spending more on that you are spending nothing for parking, and you can shop I mean you can have shop in here and it's very easy not like a busy shop, it's very fast-moving shop, so you can quickly fuel your car as well as do your shopping” (Participant-14)

Additionally, some respondents believed that free car parking also affects consumer buying behaviour in the petrol station. Data also indicated that people do think about the pricing and they

knew petrol station is more expensive than a normal supermarket. Passing customers do not bother about the pricing. However, good customer service and convenience work positively even if it is expensive where consumers quickly fuel and do their necessary shopping together.

In synopsis, within the context of consumer buying behaviour, respondents believed that consumers coming to do their regular shopping did so, especially for product availability, easy access, time-saving and convenience. Most consumers are not concerned about the price; they are more concerned about the convenience. Consumers know the products are more expensive than the normal shop, but it saves their time, that's the key reason people do shopping in the petrol station. Local people mostly do their regular shopping in petrol stations because of its shopping environment. The business is taking advantage of its small shop size, where consumers do not need to spend a long time doing their shopping in the petrol station. Some believe that it depends on shop location. If the shop location is in the village area, then the consumer will come for grocery products and fuel. If it is next to the motorway, then they will come for fuel mostly. Product quality is considered one of the most important elements in a petrol station as consumers expect high-quality products from the petrol station. The finding also indicated that consumers expect lower prices when there are many competitors in the poor area. People from the rich area are looking for high-quality products and good customer service. It is also highlighted that free car parking has a positive impact on consumer buying Behaviour which makes the shop more convenient for the consumer.

Consequently, the views of the participants from the above significantly corroborate with extant literature. However, while most opinions largely support the aforementioned factors influencing

consumer buying behaviour, the cultural factors, as espoused by Kotler and Amstrong (2006), were seen as less important factors influencing consumer buying behaviour. At the same time, a person belonging to a low-level income may purchase the items that should be within budget, while a person from a higher level may look at factors like quality and uniqueness (Nagarkoti, 2009). This explains the impact of social factors on consumers' buying behaviours. Within this social spectrum, it has been argued that groups and social networks can have a direct and indirect influence on consumer buying decisions (Iyengar, Han and Gupta, 2009). A group is made up of two or more people who interact to accomplish individual or mutual goals. Social networks are where people socialise or exchange information and opinions. People live in society, and groups in which a person spends more time that may influence their behaviour (Kim et al., 2017). Social group and professional group, which have more importance to an individual, influence their behaviour.

Therefore, this section offered answers through the propositions below, which are key factors.

- P1: Easy access affect consumer buying Behaviour
- P2: Product availability impacts consumer buying Behaviour
- P3: Time saving impact on consumer buying Behaviour
- P4: Consumers mostly do shopping in petrol stations because of the convenience
- P5: Small shop size affects consumer buying Behaviour
- P6: Everything under one roof makes the shop more convenience
- P7: Consumers from the village area coming for fuel and grocery products
- P8: Consumers from motorways mainly come for fuel
- P9: Consumers looking for high-quality products
- P10: Consumers from poor areas looking for low price products
- P11: Consumers from many competitors are looking for low price products
- P12: People from the reach area looking for high-quality products and good services
- P13: Free car parking has a positive impact on consumer buying Behaviour

Figure 5. 1: Key factors from social groups.

5.2.3 Theme 2 - Pricing Affecting Consumer Buying Behaviour

The objective is to find out how various pricing strategies influence consumer buying behaviour.

The data presented below describe the manager's perception of pricing and how it influences consumer buying behaviour.

"We are little bit expensive, bit more than supermarket but people are not moaning, some time people moan but most of the customer they know it expensive. most of the time they to come to the shop because of convenience and easy to access and they can quickly grab the stuff and go. Because people don't want to spend long time, think about Marlboro cigarette and going to super market, sometime think about ok £2, £3 different in petrol station and supermarket but staying in the que 5 minutes to 10 minutes and people don't bother to pay for most of the people buying cigarette not bother to because if the person going to buy a cigarette packet and if he wait another 5 minutes and he has to buy another 2 packets because of the tress".

(Participant-1)

"Mostly very reach people and the professional people so lots of older professional people so they don't care about the price but some people around this area that are not that much reach. When they come here they little bit hesitant to buy goods and thing, they compare the petrol price and the other prices with the other supermarket and they always tell their some prices are very high sometimes they ask the price and leave the goods and go but our local customer they don't care about the price they care about the quality actually not the quality only our some items are not that much high-quality but they don't have any other place to buy things. So they don't

have any choice and its very convenience to buy it from here I think that's one of the main reason people coming here. So people coming here mostly for convenience and the other things is most of them are regular customer". (Participant-10)

"To be honest our price bit high, I think we charge that price because of the convenience like people is still buying, it little bit expensive but people still buying from us because its convenience to them and its very fast. Especially products like tobacco, like normally its one or two pounds higher than normal shop. And the all customer is mention like 90% of the customer come her and ready with money 10 pound and I say o its 12 and they said it's more expensive. Only few people refused to buy few of them saying like oh it's too expensive I leave it. But most of the time they buying it they don't care". (Participant-15)

The above data indicate that most consumers know the petrol station is more expensive than a regular shop. Some respondents strongly agreed that convenience, easy access, and time-saving are the key reasons consumers shop here. Consumers are willing to pay extra as it saves their time. Some respondents believe that it depends on the economic condition of the local area, where most of the professional people live in the reach area. They focus on product quality, not price. The data also indicate that sometimes consumers do not have an alternative choice. Therefore, they pay extra for convenience. Most of the consumers are regular, and they like to do regular shopping here because of its convenience, easy access, very fast service, and saving their time.

“I would say more convenience so price is not really an issue for customers because if you can compare our pricing to motorway pricing, we are lot cheaper on fuel and shop products and where we are on the motorway, there is no service station between the junctions, if they want fuel they have to come off and I believe there’s a shell garage nearby and there is another shell garage but they don’t have as many functions as we do so we got subway and grage. So others competitors are more cheaper so EG focus on margin rather than volume so on fuel they are happy to sell less volume but they want to make more money the volume on they sell. Whereas previous strategy was with rock so esso was fuel volume, they want to sell more on fuel less money. So yes, in terms of EG policy is they rather the margin then the volume”. (Participant-2)

Related to previous data, another respondent stated that consumers like convenience where the price is not an issue. Compared to other fuel retailer EG provide extra facilities and function such as subway and Greggs and make the shop more convenient to the customer where overpricing is not really an issue. However, compared to the motorway petrol stations, Euro Garages products are cheaper.

“Not necessarily be that expensive honestly speaking we done some research and found out we are cheaper than most of the other forecourt we have because of the spar and the pricing. We wanted to change the customer concept or the perception they had basically because customers obviously think petrol stations expensive and

it is expensive in most cases but we introduce spa because customers can at the same time customer can do the shopping here as well spar shopping and there are stores that customers do their weekly shopping so anything basket and trollies so yes convenience is the main things but same time we try not to be too expensive and compared to the other forecourt we are in very strong position on that so we are not that expensive”. (Participant-11)

Similarly, another respondent mentioned that some research has been conducted and shows that EG is cheaper than most fuel retailers. Consumer perception regarding petrol stations is expensive, but research shows that not in all cases. However, in some stores, people do large shopping where the consumer can fuel their car and at the same time do their shopping.

“price is always high level compare with others but people they're happy, we know this area is English area reach area so on hallowing day everywhere you couldn't find the pumpkin last two days. Pumpkin runout everywhere so we are selling pumpkin four three one pumpkin three pound so you know the Tesco they are silly for 50p to 1 pound. Even we put the price up we also run out of the product, Easter eggs we only left one egg bag. So seasonal products working much batter here compare to other products even it expensive because of the area”. (Participant-8)

“we geographically located in a good area, there are three roods join together here. There's not great deal between here and Watford. So, they haven't got much choice in on that way so I the next petrol station is few miles faraway. Another this is the

price used to be quite good on petrol - it did at one point attracts more consumers. The pricing used to be quite good previously. But the EG much higher so petrol price make much difference in this business. I think I used to sell 80 thousand litters more litters more before the EG. Then again EG making higher margin". (Participant-16)

"This area more like Asian people and this is the main area for the whole Luton because this is the area where all people will come and buy the all groceries, food, meat everything. This is the center of Asian people in whole Hertfordshire so obviously, they are price sensitive. Our store located like a hundred meters beside this all this grocery stores so they always compare with the price with the exam but they say sometimes some customers say that yeah you're right but the when the kids comes into the store with the family they were said oh no don't purchase anything because of price. So, they compare the price with Conner shop because they are always cheaper compare with us. For example, sweets, confectionaries, chips everything cheaper than us. Most of the family do care about the pricing and they know where they can get cheaper products". (Participant-14)

"yeah if, you have reach customers they don't check the price they've got the product and the brand names if you are in the Luton Town Centre they don't care about the product they go for the price they are price sensitive. but in my side is don't that much and I can't say it does not affect also sometimes it does affect, because it's a village area not very urban area that's why I told you earlier words will spread if you increase the price coca cola for five pounds they're will tell to your friend or yes five

pounds don't go there that going to affect negative. I said that's why in the village it is negative effect is the most important nor than the positive effect. If I rued to one customer he go said to everybody oh don't go there the manager was rude to me especially Asian culture they're going to spread out don't go there".(Participant-5)

The results suggest that pricing and consumer buying behaviour strongly depend on the location. The data indicate that in the reach area, consumers do not care about product price but are highly cautious about product quality and convenience and good service. They don't even check the product price; they only check the brand name. Some respondents believe that it also depends on alternative choices. Consumers are willing to pay extra when there is no alternative choice. At the same time, the consumer is highly cautious about prices in the poor and Asian areas. They mostly spend their money on fuel, not in the shop because it is more expensive than the normal shop. However, a higher price does not affect consumer buying behaviour heavily, but words will spread quickly.

"If cashiers don't say thank you or recognize the local customer they'll be very upset but if we increase the price by for example let's say three pounds compare to other places that not bothering them what bothers them is the service. So this is because that customers are very rich and they just have it's kind of a village style so the village style customers they want standard, every day the customer come here for paper and the coffee and in let's say the sausage roll so when you go to Gregg's they see ok – hi sausage holds ready for you sir, you know what I mean that's the service we need to give them they know every morning he come for the paper and the sausage roll and

the coffee. when he walks in the store we get the sausage roll and the coffee ready for him. Here you go it's ready for you and that service is what they expect. When they have that price doesn't matter to them service matters for them they won't that happiness they want that privilege". (Participant-11)

Additionally, one respondent mentioned that consumers from the reach area highly expected good customer service. Price doesn't matter to their good customer service is the first priority.

"The people always thinking of the price okay so if you do some promotional offers they will come they come daily and they will become regular customer. And they don't have to worry about to find the place where they can park their car. The important things in petrol station or whatever the business once we give the good customer services, the people come on repeat. Whatever it is they will come again even you increase price. So good consumer service work positively even you increase the price it won't affect the consumer buying behaviour, consumer still will come". (Participant-14)

Similar to the previous statement, another respondent strongly mentions that good customer service is key to any business that works positively, even if the price is higher than normal. However, promotional offers help the consumer daily and become regular.

"The previous company used to offer cheaper fuel to get more customer, so basically make no money on petrol, just to keep the business run and get more consumer, they

just were happy to keep the Esso brand very highly rating. But in EG obviously set their own price off the Esso petrol but because of the competition they put the petrol price cheaper. Obviously when EG came they increase the price so they lost some customers. But again we gain customers because we introduce Subway and Greggs and other things to get more customer”. (Participant-16)

“The people they can't go anywhere because what happen is the next petrol station around here over eight to ten miles away, other thing is we open 24/7 other thing is I mentioned before this petrol station run by Exxon Mobil Esso. So prices compared with the supermarket we not very cheap and not very expensive we are reasonable price. So people coming here for petrol and buy the other things”.(Participant-12)

“So special in the sense they need fuel, that's the most important things and flowingly the fuel price as well as shop products price because some people only comes for the convenience stores yeah because they're like to have some promotional offices as well and quality of products. What I belief they need petrol. Most of the people in this country have their own car so they need petrol. So they will come to us, if we can offer them something special like on petrol price they will come to us and when they come to us they will buy other things not only petrol”. (Participant-14)

“There are people who look at the prices regularly. And obviously some people don't care about the price of petrol is but there are people who does look at the price of petrol if they see 2pence cheaper than us, up the road, they will go there. So when we

get more traffic we get more business as well, when they see Greggs, subway they go to buy some food as well and some shop products". (Participant-16)

"We have passing customers as well, but they care about our fuel price but they fill fuel and after that come to the shop also they care about the prices mostly the passing customer. Passing customer those people only buy the petrol mostly not buy anything else, but we have emotional promotion things we display on front of the shelf and those items are very cheap so mostly students, some people who thinking about cheap prices they buy those promotional items". (Participant-10)

"The problem is passing customers always because they checked our fuel sign check our fuel price. And if they decide to come here then They will buy some cheap product otherwise they are not coming here". (Participant-10)

The above finding suggests that cheaper fuel can increase consumer traffic. However, consumer traffic can be increased using various facilities even with higher fuel prices. Anytime accessibility also works effectively as consumers know this is the only place opened all the time. Some respondents believe that most people in this country have their own car so they must require fuel and petrol station is the only place where they can get fuel. Lower fuel prices can bring more consumers, and when they come, they will buy other products too. Mostly, consumers are more concerned about fuel prices, not convenience products. However, passing consumers are always concerned about the price of everything. They are only influenced by promotional products.

Another respondent illustrated pricing and consumer buying Behaviour with an example:

“In terms of the other shop goods we twice high in tobacco and as managers what we are told is the company discourage tobacco smoking, so we normally a couple of pounds more expensive. But if the customer wants to smoke they will pay that price. I worked in retail in long time I remember when we had customers saying when the price of pack of cigarettes goes over five pound they going to stop smoking. Then customer said when they goes over 10 pound they will stop smoking. Unfortunately, they don’t, they just adjust with new pricing. They pay the high price some of my cigarettes are 14 pound a packet close to 14 pound 13.88 I think I charge for Marlboro, customer still buy those because yes if they go to a supermarket it will be cheaper, but quantity is coming down to convenience. I got quite a lot of land here quite a lot of parking spaces and they come in I have got their tills. Obviously, customer spend a lot less time filling up with fuel here then you would not do that at supermarket. You spend less time buying your shop goods here, then in the supermarket. So, I find a lot people value their time now over price. So, I think we had that dip in probably in 2009 to 2014 customers were focused on price because of the recession they cutback. I think now it’s starting to go back up to people value their time more and they are happy to pay a higher price if they get service faster”.

(Participant-2)

The above evidences show that these days consumer value their time more than price. Consumers are happy to pay higher price if they get faster service.

"pricing affecting customer, as I told for example yeah okay, let's say the customer coming to buy milk, compare with other petrol station or shop our milk is expensive but still customer will buy but it will prevent the customer buying something extra for example we call it Upselling so whatever if the price is expensive then the capability of upselling is decreased. For example, the customer buying and if prices are expensive he will buy less. So, if the price is expensive they buy what they want only the main items but there is a less chance they buy the extra item. Let's say customer come to buy two chocolate but if the price expensive, they will still buy the chocolate but may be one chocolate. So instead of buying two he will buy just one".

(Participant-2)

Similar, another respondent illustrated pricing and consumer buying Behaviour with an example, as stated that higher price works negatively on consumer buying Behaviour. However, with the higher price, the consumer will not stop buying products from the petrol station; instead, they will buy less.

"I think, they nowadays after the financial crisis and everything I just feel like where people shop is not like a big deal anymore and because if it's a cheap place it's a cheap place and if you're expect if you go to an expensive place it's probably because of convenience. I think people were just like if you go to the little corner shop down the road people be like oh why are you buying those from there. the sparse stuff why you're buying their own brand you know why don't you buy actual Cadbury's instead of own brand chocolate. but nowadays people just don't care where you shop what

you buy like it's all to do price or convenience it's one or the other and if you get both of them they're a happy customer". (Participant-4)

"Normally when they doing shopping yeah so, they're basket is 30 pounds or 40 pounds, when they do in 30-40 pounds shopping our budget is already going higher, because we know when they're doing a 40-pound shopping that will pay us 5 pounds. so, we already have up sales going up even that kind of basket if we got few times our target is done. So, there is not point put cheaper product on the shelf, even it waste our place and our time or hours to fill up the store. Mainly we put the cheapest items then we selling cheapest items so they will get more bigger basket, and we will get big que so that means we have to put another person to deal that que, then we have to pay for him to finish the que. So normally other retailer need at list 2 to 3 person on the tills with self-service check-up as well because they selling cheaper products. Here we not doing cheaper product but the product is high value and only one person doing the till, so we paying only one person. We are getting weekly margin with our range and things so it better to sell expensive product which make more profit and saving labor cost. So, one person can run the business. Even for the bigger shop we need big delivery to full fill the shop so we need more human power, more labor cost and time consuming. So that would be crazy we wouldn't have to do other things if it bigger shop and cheaper shop. Also it handy for us as we have to check every stock counting and check, that's why they give us the target to do this. So there is no point to keep the price low". (Participant-8)

The above evidence with example shows that some respondents believe price and convenience are the most important elements in the petrol station. Lower price and convenience are the only elements that can make the consumer happy. However, another respondent argued that lower prices got a negative impact on the business, which can make it more time-consuming as the low price will bring more consumers, to serve those consumers more time and more labour required. The consumer might spend more time than normal if the shop is busy, which can lead to negative attention for the consumer.

Therefore, it is plausible to argue that while pricing is profoundly important in shaping consumers' buying behaviour, the willingness to pay for particular goods and services is hinged particularly on both internal and external factors. Manali Khaniwale (2015) viewed the relationship between consumer buying behaviour and the factors that influence the consumer's purchasing process and purchase decision. He thus opined that the consumer's buyer behaviour is significantly influenced by the consumer's internal and external factors. Thus, Kotler & Keller (2012) opined that price is the one component of the marketing mix that produces revenue; the other elements produce costs. They further argued that purchase decisions are based on how consumers perceive prices and what they contemplate the present actual price to be. Consequently, understanding how consumers arrive at their perceptions of prices is an important marketing priority.

To corroborate the above arguments, Al-Salamin, Al-Baqshi, Al-Rassasi and Al-Salem (2015) aver that the price of well-known brand products affects the purchase process negatively. Although young people are interested in purchasing brand products, their low income prevents them from the buying process while they are considered a major segmentation for brand names. Furthermore,

Aysel Boztepe (2012) observes that environmental awareness, product features, promotion activities and prices affect the purchasing behaviours of the consumers in positive way. Lefa Teng (2007) argued that when a price discount with and without a minimum purchase requirement is applied to a brand in a hold set, the brand moves from the consumers' hold set to the consideration set. However, the effects of the two types of price discounts on consumers' attitudes and purchase intentions are not significantly different. Finally, there is a positive relationship between prices and consumer buying behaviour. This is significantly possible because suitable prices make consumers more willing to purchase items.

5.2.3.1 Promotion

It is reported that almost all respondents talked about promotional pricing and indicated that promotion had played an important role in influencing the purchasing behaviour of consumers. The data presented below describe how promotional prices influence consumer buying Behaviour.

“With promotional products pricing always I have no issue so they will go if the price goes down if the customers buying one you know and the normal price they might buy two it's not affecting that much because once the promotion finish they will still buy product again so people get used to with it after promotion. I never experience any negative experience with promotional offers, whatever you put one the promotion it will go. So it really affect consumer buying behaviour especially in this area”.

(Participant-9)

“I said earlier the people was always thinking of the price okay so if you do some promotional offers they will come they come daily and they will become regular customer. And they don’t have to worry about to find the place where they can park their car. The important things in petrol station or whatever the business once we give the good customer services, the people come on repeat. Whatever it is they will come again even you increase price. So good consumer service work positively even you increase the price it won’t affect the consumer buying behaviour, consumer still will come”. (Participant-14).

“Sometimes they moaning about the price but we do have some offers like meal deal that means the morning they can like sandwich, drinks and snakes in a reduced price. mostly they buy those things because so I think they are very busy people they are normally in my experience they are not having the breakfast in at home they are having on the way when they are going to work”. (Participant-10)

“The other thing is there is a very good school here private school those children's are always coming to buy the cheap products like promotional products like crisps, drinks, chocolate. Sometime we have like tow for one price they always come to buy those type of product. Otherwise, as like shop wise it not easy to sell the products like normal supermarket products that very difficult to sell. day-to-day things you can sell not like massive shopping not like full bucket of shopping sometimes we can sell that like chocolate boxes like that is no other shop to buy around here. Otherwise the weekly shopping is very difficult to sell here”. (Participant-10)

“we have passing customers as well, but they care about our fuel price but they fill fuel and after that come to the shop also they care about the prices mostly the passing customer. Passing customer those people only buy the petrol mostly not buy anything else, but we have emotional promotion things we display on front of the shelf and those items are very cheap so mostly students, some people who thinking about cheap prices they buy those promotional items”. (Participant-7)

“So special in the sense they need fuel, that's the most important things and flowingly the fuel price as well as shop products price because some people only comes for the convenience stores yeah because they're like to have some promotional offices as well and quality of products. What I belief they need petrol. Most of the people in this country have their own car so they need petrol. So they will come to us, if we can offer them something special like on petrol price they will come to us and when they come to us they will buy other things not only petrol”. (Participant-14)

“Normally we reduce the price. Like Doritos, or Pepsi normally we sell it to 2.50 when we put on the promotion we put 1 pound, so it quite big different. Sometimes we get new products we keep that product very low price so people can try them stuff like that. Its work really good bring in lots of customer, and people know there is a promotional section where they can get cheap products”. (Participant-15)

“Obviously, our promotional section is cheap option for consumer. Also, the ready male to go especially we offer sandwich mean so if you compare for example the price

of meal with us you get sandwich, crisps and drinks for 350 for example if you compare with garages we have food here as well with them we are lot cheaper. We have sandwich deal 350 where you can get sandwich, drinks and crisp but in garages only sandwich and drinks so with us you got crisp extra with same price. So it brings more customers especially for the busy people for example you see moms in a hurry and buy just a meal for the kids because they don't even have time they simply come here and have their breakfast". (Participant-15)

"we do mostly the promotion things, and like seasonal products, or out of date product, once the date is over we reduce the price and try to sell it as quick as possible. Think about the seasonal product, before end of season we selling more products but when the season end even you put on the promotion it won't move that fast like before. So those things re reduce price after the season". (Participant-16)

Above quotes are evident that almost every respondent believed promotional pricing create a feeling of urgency as human are always looking for the best quality products at the lowest price. Promotional pricing drives better consumer traffic and influences the consumer to buy more. Promotional pricing creates high levels of consumer loyalty, and consumers will keep buying the products even when is promotional offers closed. The data also indicate that promotional prices motivate the consumer to come daily and make them regular. School children are highly motivated by promotional offers, and mostly they look for cheap products as they have a limited budget.

Two respondents compared promotional pricing with time and believed that these days' time is very important, and consumers do not like to waste it. Therefore, consumers like promotional offers such as meal deals so they can have this promotional offer on the way to their object. Promotional pricing also has a positive impact on seasonal products. It worked very well before the season and eventually dropped after the season. Data also indicated that passing customers are price-sensitive. They are mostly looking for low price products. They are inspired by promotional offers.

“Yeah we do the promotion every three weeks yeah after three weeks we put the new promotion. So we do offer them special prices so any store you go you will see specific promotions not just one item for many items low prices for customers if they wish to buy and now that changes every three weeks it is a continuous process every two different in three weeks different”. (Participant-11)

“when we do the promotion every two weeks its works really good. So EG is partner with the spar supermarket so they do every two week they do the some kind of promotion. So the promotion is they don't do buy one get one free thy do everything for a pound. So every two weeks we change the promotion so they bring the people in the shop you know they oh yeah when you got the shop you can buy this product by a pound. By the meantime when they come to the shop the see other products. So when people see the tings like he suppose to buy one for one pound whey they see three for pound they simply buy this. When its on the promotional offers some times

they buy three or four together. Especially for drinks okay when they find its cheap they just buy it”. (Participant-12)

“We do like two for one it’s like buy one get one free, and two for one pound. We also do upselling like we ask them in the morning like would you like to have some coffee or car wash. In the morning they will defiantly will think about it because when they driving they need coffee to refresh them self. And car wash represent them how clean they are if they go to a meeting. So we provide good customer service to get more customers or come back again. And we always something in the shop on promotion which work really good. Every two weeks we change our promotion with different products. Customer find its very cheaper and convenience and they can park the car and buy something at the same time they can get coffee car wash everything. Because of that convenience consumer don’t mind to pay little extra for convenience purpose. Even local customer come as well for promotional products, they come regularly for fuel because we not much different than our competitors buy some times when they see our promotional offers they go for it”. (Participant-13)

“Every month we change promotion, but we always have two section of promotion normally like drinks, crisps, chocolate, so we always something on promotion. I think that attract lot of consumer as well. Especially customers who go to cinema they always come here for crisps, drinks. So once a month we got new promotion and change promotion and its works really good”. (Participant-15)

"Also we have promotion for every three weeks so the new promotions comes we will ask the customer are you interesting in to take this offer we are doing a good portion it is helpful for you if they have a kid if they come with we will say that we are doing the this is a good for you yeah if they interest they will right away buy it they don't care about the money as well. So we also telling them there is an offer going in the store, we try to encourage or influence them to buy more by providing good customer services. For example when is Easter time yeah we will say would you like to have some Easter eggs, and we are doing a promotional offers on it, so most of the customers simply buy it. Even though, they never planned to buy this products we try to make them to buy one buy nicely and politely". (Participant-14)

The results highlighted that promotional pricing increases positive consumer affect, in turn, increases consumer and perceived value. The promotional price is an essential element for the business because its affects sales and profits. The data suggested that all respondents change their promotional offers every two weeks, three weeks or monthly, which works very well and increase the shop sales. Some believe that local consumers are highly influenced by promotional pricing and regularly come for promotional products.

"Promotional offer is not affecting that much in this area, even though we reduce the prices we can't sell more things, think about the people sometimes they are coming here to buy crisp packet and some other like that they never buy two chirp's packets. Sometimes even though it expensive or not or we reduce the price or not they don't buy two. Those things they buy because sometimes like think about chocolate

sometimes more expensive than buying two chocolates for example at this moment the snickers one chocolate is 1.05 but two for 1.00, those items consumer buying 2 at a time but our profit margin is going down. But we cant expect more customers in this area because most of the customer are regular not much are passing customer. In this area we go lots of regular customer, and when they come they know what to have even though it little cheap on the offer it doesn't affect that much to the".

(Participant-10)

Additionally, only one respondent believed that promotional pricing has no impact on consumer buying Behaviour. It all depends on products and the geographical area.

"it's all depends on the product you offer, for example if you offer 2 waters for 1 pounds in summer time you will sell lots. Sometimes it happen negatively as well for example after season even you try hard you can't sell a lot like after Christmas or Easter or like father day, mother day whatever the festival is after the festival it is very difficult to sell the products even you put on the promotion people will not buy the products. It also happen the umbrella in summer time it's very difficult to sell one and in rainy season even if you put price high it will go. Also, it depends on different ethnicities, because this is quite Asian area so they don't bother about different seasonal products, even I try to sell lots of Christmas products as they are most of them Muslim people they don't care about this seasonal products".(Participant-13)

Furthermore, one respondent suggested with an example that the effectiveness of promotional offers depends on the products, area, season, ethnicity and religion.

“Usual, things like 2 drinks for 2 pound, nectar card, car wash promotion, coffee buy five get one free, obviously, greggs and subway things you know. They all run their own promotion here. You can come in if you don't want to spend so much as usually some sort of deal here but obviously the range of offers which affect you to buy more. I would not say the shop is design for cheap and for promotional items, I would say when people come here to do their shopping, they buy promotional items too. If something in the shop if they come in they will buy it, they never particularly come to buy those products. So mostly they never plan what to buy, as soon as if they see some sort of deal around here they will go for it while doing their main shopping”.

(Participant-16)

“Yeah, mainly chocolates, drinks, these days protein bars are more effective for the promotions compared with the lets say if you put promotion on very large box of chocolate still it will increase the sale about that specific product but you can't say the compared with the normal day to day product, compared with small chocolate bar and the big box of cholate bar. Its different selling patterns even there is a good offer on the big bar of chocolate I mean the box of chocolate its slow selling compared with the small bar of chocolate. So it's all depending on customers and customers eating pattern so as I told, most of customer they comer for the buy day to day needs

the milk, small bar of chocolate, orange juice or protein drink yeah day to day things not like the special occasion things". (Participant-3)

The above evidence proves that promotional pricing has an important impact on consumer buying Behaviour. It helps them to make a quick decision when they see a lower price. They may understand that the promotional price is only available for a limited time. Kotler (2003) states that promotions can be described as stimulations and rewards which lead customers to buy now rather than later. The opinion of the various participants, as presented above, clearly aligns with existing scholarly research on the invaluable nature of promotion to consumer buying behaviour.

Arguably, Promotions are short-term tools which trigger buyer actions and their effect on sales revenue can be measured quickly and easily (Kotler, 2003 as cited in Urun, 2011). Jarvenpaa and Todd (1996), as cited in Jean and Yazdanifard, 2015), indicate that the types of sales promotion have played an important role in influencing the purchasing behaviour of potential customers. Monetary sales or price promotions are mostly favoured by consumers, especially immediate price reductions (Huff and Alden, 1988 as cited in Jean and Yazdanifard, 2015). For the consumer, price and quality of products are the two main characteristics that determine purchasing behaviour (Jean and Yazdanifard, 2015), and due to the competitive marketplace, most retailers have selected price reduction promotion to promote their products and compete with rivalry brands, rather than spend money on advertisement or designing coupons (Jean and Yazdanifard, 2015).

Groceries and/or supermarkets use price promotions because these types of sales promotions have traditionally focused on convenience goods (Zerres and Hunerberg, 2009 as cited in Urun, 2011), however, according to Aydinli et al., (2014), although the most distinguishing feature of price

promotion is its emphasis on getting consumers to take action and managers tend to defend its use as the fastest and most reliable means to increase sales, it is not only an incentive to purchase, but it can also be a disincentive to think.

According to MBA Skool Team (2021), the various types of promotional pricing include basic price discount as a percentage, buy one get one free, bundled products, absolute discount in currency, and cashbacks.

5.2.3.2 Convenience and pricing

“Mostly very rich people and the professional people so lots of older professional people so they don't care about the price but some people some areas including this area people are not that much rich. When they come here they little bit hesitant to buy goods and thing, they compare the petrol price and the other prices with the other supermarket and they always tell their some prices are very high sometimes they ask the price and leave the goods and go but our local customer they don't care about the price they care about the quality actually not the quality only our some items are not that much high-quality but they don't have any other place to buy things. So they don't have any choice and its very convenience to buy it from here I think that's one of the main reason people coming here. So people coming here mostly for convenience and the other things is most of them are regular customer”.

(Participant-10)

Above evidence indicate that professional people and reach people are not census about pricing they only care about quality. Geographical location also important for consumer, consumer are happy to pay extra when there is no other choice.

“The main thing is our company they want to keep highest profit margin at any item. So they give us some target so we have to keep that profit margin so automatically they put the high price. Yeah its affecting consumer buying behaviour the problem is we can't keep the more stock and we can't aspect lot of sell as well, because most of the people they com to fill the petrol, and they always in hurry or rush so they can't wait long time here, I seen people small time because to that we can't expect people buying lot of things so we can we can sell items we can't reduce the price actually but the things is that's not happening because people are not spending that much time here. Because, mostly they coming here when they are on the way to somewhere like their work, home, kids school etc. they are always buy people”. **(Participant-7)**

The above data indicated that mostly busy people are coming to petrol station who do not have much time to spend. Consumers come here when they are on their way to somewhere, which is clearly indicated that people come here for convenience.

“Yeah, because of the convenience, so they can quickly shop and buy the things they need and go. Because of that I think they are happy to pay little extra. that's why we always keep the day-to-day things and promote day to day things. The other things is if you try to sell lot of quantities they are not buying it think about they want to buy

3-4 pizza they will go to supermarket. So they always planning to buy small quantities from here. Because of the small quantities we to charge little higher than nor shop. If they buying big quantities we can reduce the price even though we have to spend some money for the stock. So because of those things we increase the price and we get our profit margin. So for that convenience of small quantities people don't mind to pay little extra. So people buying weekly shopping from big supermarket because it cheap and lot of stock but we have limited choice or limited stock. Normally, people not buying that much that's why we have limited stock because they are not buying big quantities. like think about drinks and ice cube people buy three four packets at a time. So when they come here thy buy small amount because it's expensive. If they want to buy quantity wise high they are going to supermarket because they can spend to time there and lot of varieties there, not even food others items also. Even I also go to supermarket because I can spend there more time and do more shopping with small amount of money. Also the leasur time we can spend there, and do our shopping, here you can't. so normally who coming here most of them got less time. They just quickly come buy the product and go especially day to day things. Its very convenience to them to come here because they don't have to spend lots of time because of that we also charging extra. I would say they don't bother the price because only for few items they can't go to any other shop and sometimes they can't part the car, its very difficult. So they don't mind about the price". (Participant-9)

The results also suggested that compared to pricing and convenience, convenience is the most important phenomenon for fuel retailers. People like to shop in petrol stations because it is quick

and fast where consumers do not mind paying a little extra for this convenience. Therefore, people do day to day shopping in petrol stations because is convenient for them.

“Sometimes we face the problem with the local families because we are located opposite to the Sainsbury so they always compare the price with the opposite of the Sainsbury's so they'll says that you are selling this product for higher price so we will convince them like we are doing the business or like we don't get much profit on the fuel stage and fuel we will get the profit on these. We have to say that we have explained them at last we can't convince them and they will buy the product. So, when they complain about the pricing then we try to convince them to buy the products and make them regular customers. They will listen to us and love they were not like fight for price. It happens sometime like the bad that's, bad experience we have but overall, they won't care about this at the end of the day they will come again as well to see us”. (Participant-14)

"Yeas pricing affecting customer, as I told for example yeah okay, let's say the customer coming to buy milk, compare with other petrol station or shop our milk is expensive but still customer will buy but it will prevent the customer buying something extra for example we call it Upselling so whatever if the price is expensive then the capability of upselling is decreased. For example, the customer buying and if prices are expensive he will buy less. So if the price is expensive they buy what they want only the main item but there is a less chance they buy the extra item. Let's say customer come to buy two chocolate but if the price expensive, they will still buy the

chocolate but may be one chocolate. So instead of buying two he will buy just one".

(Participant-3)

Furthermore, it was observed that local family and competitor has a negative impact on consumer buying Behaviour. Local families are happy to do shopping in the big supermarket even if it is convenient for them. However, with the higher price, the consumer will buy what they need, but when the price is low, they will buy extra.

5.2.3.3 High Lough pricing

"Yeah, we do those things, those things mostly the promotion things, and like seasonal products, or out of date product, once the date is over we reduce the price and try to sell it as quick as possible. Think about the seasonal product, before end of season we selling more products but when the season end even you put on the promotion it won't move that fast like before. So those things re reduce price after the season". (Participant-10)

"Yes, we do it on seasonal products, when we start putting products on the shelf we put reasonable price, quite high price but when the season come near to finish we reduce the price because we know we can't sell it after the season so we have to finish the products before season finish". (Participant-13)

“yeah, we do sometimes like that, for example our retail product Easter eggs. If you sell on Easter time the price will be very high price. After the Easter we do promotional offers like half price eventually we discount the price to get rid of it because we can't keep it for next year. So we can give them any offers like if they like to buy more we reduce more. Once people see the price competitively cheap they will come repeatedly. If we runout anything they will come to us and ask us is the offer still available. So it does affect the business and bring more consumer in the store”.

(Participant-14)

“only when we have products that are going to expire we reduce them as much as we can, obviously we reduce them and sell them to get rid of it rather than going bin. So we do this kind of things only when we see the products life runout. Depending on the products we do at list one week before we reduce the price. Normally we reduce one third of the original price. Approximately, 30% we reduce at least sometimes 50%”

(Participant-15)

“Yeah, they buy it, when you reduce the price they simply buy it. Also, sometimes when we have some damage packages, like the product is fine but the packet is damaged the box whatever. When we reduce it they buy it. Even though they never plan to buy that product. When they see it cheaper they simply buy it. We have few customers they always come for those products, after 12.00 o'clock we reduce the price in our chiller the products that will expire today. So I see some customer usually come that time and they buy the reduced items”. **(Participant-15)**

“yeah, we reduce the price and sell it off, we put it by the till area, we do date check and reduce the price and put it next to the till so people don’t need to walk around to see that, anything you put by the till area it will sales off. rather than throwing it away you're getting something so that also affecting the consumer right so people can get it with very cheap rate”. (Participant-16)

“Not rally, when we take chicks stick yeah so we doing offers yeah you know the price going for the expired like one weeks or two weeks lifelong products, so we give the offers to buy. So we reduce the price of that product and bring to the till area. So we showing customer this things like you can buy this with this price or you can buy and get one free. So we give opportunity to sell our products and reaching our margin and we not losing anything.” (Participant-8)

The above quotes suggested that high low pricing encourages consumer purchases. Organizations generate additional sales and reach more price-sensitive consumers. Seasonal products and nearly out of date products are popular for this pricing strategy. The data indicate that when they reduce the price, the consumer simply buys those products. When consumers see a price reduction, they make an instant decision to have it even though they never planned to buy those products. In order to get more consumer attention, managers put those products near the till area, which helps them to encourage consumer purchases.

From the foregoing, it is plausible to argue that High low and Everyday low pricing are two dominant retailing formats. According to the CFI (n.d), high-low pricing is a pricing strategy in which a firm relies on sales promotions to encourage consumer purchases. It is a pricing strategy where a firm initially charges a high price for a product and then subsequently decreases the price through promotions, markdowns or clearance sales, with product prices alternating between ‘high’ and ‘low’ over a given time period.

This pricing strategy aims to drive store traffic and hopefully encourage consumers to purchase additional items once they are at the store (CFI, n.d). High-low pricing is intended to give the consumer perception of a bargain, thereby generating high sales during a promotional period, and by applying a discount to a product priced "high", consumers will be more likely to purchase the product because of their presumption that it is a bargain (CFI, n.d).

5.2.3.4 Everyday low Pricing

Everyday low pricing is a pricing technique in which retailers offer consumers that their prices will be consistently low. Below, the data highlighted the general perception of everyday low pricing and how it affects consumer buying Behaviour.

"We always keep our fuel price to be low, compare to others. Sometimes its not on our hand its government regulated so we cant do anything but we try to keep it as low as possible. And also in the grocery we try to provide cheaper than others. if you go for confectionaries item we do always low prices, and its bring in more customer".

(Participant-14)

“obviously, our promotional section is cheap option for consumer. Also the ready made to go especially we offer sandwich mean so if you compare for example the price of meal with us you get sandwich, crisps and drinks for 350 for example if you compare with garages we have food here as well with them we are lot cheaper. We have sandwich deal 350 where you can get sandwich, drinks and crisp but in garages only sandwich and drinks so with us you got crisp extra with same price. So it brings more customers especially for the busy people for example you see moms in a hurry and buy just a meal for the kids because they don't even have time they simply come here and have their breakfast”. **(Participant-15)**

“we do have a few cheaper products I think our butter is one pound which is one of the cheapest like grocery items that we have so we do offer cheaper items but the majority of the store is a little higher there's also something that we've partnered with which I've just remembered is that we give away for the price with your groceries you get a free sun paper and so a lot of people do come for that because you know all they come in with the sun and then you say no it's fine you've got it free and then they're like oh okay so it makes me want to come back more because a lot of people read the Sun so they like the fact that they can get it free. So company offering free sun with their groceries if they come in and buy some stuff from the store”. **(Participant-4)**

“We have some of our own product own brand drinks which are always two for one pound and they can be quite popular because rest of our drinks is too expensive for people. but they really want something it's like a flavoured sparkling water and we

get two flavours of that so that's two for one pound and that's quite a popular drink. I am just thinking what else like I said the chicken on a stick is always a pound and those are our main things and our price our butters always one pounds but those are the main. we also have some own brand we have a lot of own brand stuff I think those are our everyday low prices we don't do a lot of branded stuff that is an everyday low price like we have next to our Grey's snack boxes that the nuts normally expensive Spar put up their own brand like their own brand of stuff which is 99 P of little snack boxes. different flavours with coconut tropical just nuts you know all of that and we have muffins four for a pound with all our other more expensive maybe and products so people want something like that which you can kind of get cheap in supermarkets you can also get cheap from us". (Participant-7)

"we do have a section in our store called one pound items, it's throughout the year it's only one pound so it's always one pound it's all sort of things like few sweets few drinks that will attract people to come in they're always there. So we show them we do have some cheaper option compare to other competitors". (Participant-6)

"Yeah we have some products they always lower than our competitors, like pepsi our meal deal always low price, our coffees every day same price and cheap compared to other computers. So these are the product always same price so they know the price. When you compare with tesco we don't have that much cheap product here because our branch is, our area is rich so we not keeping that much low". (Participant-8)

“Compare to other shop we don’t have low price of any product, more or less all price are expensive, other than promotion, so only our promotional section are always low price product compare to others, sometimes it cheaper than supermarket. For example, like Dorito big packet is one pound normally is 1.79 and the other things is chocolate is 2 for 1 pound normally other place is 75p”. (Participant-10)

The above evidence shows how fuel retailers regularly offer products at lower prices without offering any discount or sales offer. They offer fuel prices cheaper compared to other fuel retailers. Some grocery products are also included with this everyday low pricing strategy, which positively impacts consumer buying Behaviour. Some of the products in the promotional section are always lower than others, especially combination products of meal-deal.

One respondent mentioned with an example that majority of the product's prices are higher, but only a few products always keep lower prices, including free products; therefore, consumers do not need to compare prices to find the best seller. However, one respondent hasn't agreed with this notion but suggested that all prices are high except for promotional offers.

As a matter of evidence from the above data interpretation, the majority of participant acknowledges, in tandem with other scholars, that the Everyday Low Price (EDLP) strategy is a product-portfolio level pricing strategy by which a firm attempts to convey to consumers that prices across its product portfolio are consistently low. (Sin et al., 2009). Everyday Low Pricing (EDLP) strategy has proved to be a successful innovation resulting in higher profits for supermarkets adopting it in competition with Promotional Pricing (PROMO). Conventional

wisdom attributes this success either to lower costs or to EDLP better serving time-constrained consumers while discouraging cherry pickers who seek promotions (Lal and Rao, 1997). EDLP is a pricing strategy in which a company charges a consistently low price over a long-time horizon (CFI, n.d).

5.2.3.5 Meal deals pricing and consumer buying behaviour

Meal deals in euro garage usually involving the main product such as a sandwich or pasta salad, with drink and snack for a set price, are considered by many to be an affordable food option. They are packaged food items sold together at a discount in a store and are usually bought by those in a hurry as a time-saving option for a ready to eat a meal.

Below, the data from Euro Garage managers suggested how meal-deal impact consumer buying behaviour.

"Sometimes in the morning they are coming for their breakfast, and at the same time, they feel petrol. Sometimes they come for the petrol though our prices are a little bit high compared to Tesco and BP but they used to come here and they sometimes they fill petrol and they buy something to eat in the way and mostly confectionary items and not household items so confectionary items are the main selling items here and cigarettes and all convenient products. sometimes they moaning about the price but we do have some offers like t we have some offers like meal deal that means the morning they can like sandwich, drinks and snakes in a reduced price. mostly they buy those things because so I think they are very busy people they are normally in my

experience they are not having the breakfast in at home they are having on the way when they are going to work". (Participant-10)

"Male deal is more popular because like I said customers coming in certain times they wish to the target the petrol station sometimes for lunchtime meal is famous and also two for a pound some sort of that sort of things also works as well. value for money any deal if it is a good deal then customers will go for it. Consumer expecting good deal in petrol station". (Participant-11)

"We do like male deal like buy sandwich, drinks and crisps or some kind of chocolate with 350. We sell those thing quite a lot here because what happen is people when they go to the Wembley stadium for any football match them come here and buy those things. 350 is good value for the day. Yeah, people like it and they come for the same thing again". (Participant-12)

"We do the male deal like few products, for example food, drinks and snakes all together to a small price, sometimes it's come down to half price. For example 2.99 sandwich we offer for 3.50 where you can get sandwich, drinks and crisps as well so with 50p extra they getting more products". (Participant-13)

"Yeah we do bundle like promotional offers and we'll do like meal deals, the meal deal is a very good offer. we do meal deal for 3.50 P like you can have one sandwich, crisp and one drinks, so three products at a time at one price. Whoever on his way

and rush to work they come here and simply grab the offers. So they can have food on the way to work”. (Participant-14)

“Obviously, our promotional section is cheap option for consumer. Also the ready made to go especially we offer sandwich mean so if you compare for example the price of meal with us you get sandwich, crisps and drinks for 350 for example if you compare with garages we have food here as well with them we are lot cheaper. We have sandwich deal 350 where you can get sandwich, drinks and crisp but in garages only sandwich and drinks so with us you got crisp extra with same price. So it brings more customers especially for the busy people for example you see moms in a hurry and buy just a meal for the kids because they don’t even have time they simply come here and have their breakfast”. (Participant-15)

“When they see the deal they will buy it, because it lot cheaper than normal price. Because they getting the drinks for free. Usually, most people buy sandwich, they want a snake that he want to have a pack of Chris and he want drinks. So you can get all cheaper and its all in the same area in the shop so it’s easy for them to pick up you know. if we sell a sandwich we normally tell them to get the drinks and crisps for free. It’s really affecting consumer, some of our regular customer only come for those products. So it works quite well, and it does affect consumer buying behaviour. This is quite common for every places, so people knows they can get this kind of things from here”. (Participant-16)

“I think the place because as I said before its near the station so but people coming in the morning commute you know coming in there’s a Starbucks here so a lot of people getting their coffee in the mornings and there’s a few building sites going on around so people do want to come and get their coffee and come get their meals and you know all of that I think because like I have said there’s a meal deals that we have got, I think it’s just a convenient place to quickly come in and we got quite a large forecourt. Lots of lorries are coming in you know filling up with their fuel cards and everything so I feel like that it’s also helps them because they wouldn’t want to go to small little dinky you know petrol station that they can’t fit their lorries whatever”.

(Participant-4)

“Yeah we do meal deal, like sandwich, drink , but yeah because they see the prices like on those so because it's all are individually the drinks also individually priced and chrisp and snakes are also got their individual price so when they see the meal deal is 3.50 and if they buy the three items separately to come to about five or six pounds depending on what they're buying so they do go for either they do go or we offer it. So it quite popular here, its affecting their behaviour to come more in this shop. Or any others offers, if you put any offers it will go. So petrol station little bit expensive but because of the convenience customer will buy it”. **(Participant-9)**

The above evidence with examples suggests that the right meal deal drives traffic, brings repeat business, generates loyalty, increases profit, and enhances customers' experience. Meal-deal link to food and drinks items especially focusing on breakfast and lunch. The notion is highly effective

in the morning when the consumer can fuel their vehicle and at the same time have their breakfast. One respondent highlighted his own experience that now a day's, people are very busy, and they don't have time to have breakfast at home. Therefore, they come to a fuel station to fuel vehicles and have their breakfast within a short period of time.

Another respondent stated that it's highly effective in lunch too as this is one of the best deals and good value of price, especially for petrol station. The data also indicated that the offer always remains the same; therefore, consumers keep coming for the same offer over and over again. The consumer normally buys this offer because it is cheaper than the normal price, and it is convenient as well as time-saving.

Meal deals, usually involving a main (such as a sandwich or pasta salad), drink and snack for a set price, are considered by many to be an affordable lunch option (Independent, 2017). They are packaged food items sold together at a discounted price in a store and are usually bought by those in a hurry as a time-saving option for a ready-cooked meal.

In his study to address the relationship between meal bundling called "Meal Deal" and driving customer traffic in food service and food retail stores, Zwanka (2017) found that; " if we aim to grow customer acquisition and sales, and entrepreneurial innovation process with a current trend (meal solutions) can be used as a traffic builder for the foodservice department".

The right meal deal drives traffic, brings repeat business, generates loyalty, increases the perceived value of your restaurant, increases profit, enhances your customers' experience and brings in traffic on slow days (Restaurant Engine, n.d).

However, according to Reeves (2020), increased consumption of food outside the home means that the nutritional content of meals served in restaurants now makes a significant contribution to the overall diet. Studies have found a logical sequence of effects linking food promotions to individual-level weight outcomes, especially in children (Kelly et al., 2015). Since eating out is a simple pleasure that many people enjoy, the key is not only to create the right meal deal by considering the business' brand and promoting with a purpose (Restaurant Engine, n.d), including healthier snack options in the bundles is a successful consideration for the firm.

5.2.3.6 Branded products and pricing

Consumers view a brand as an important part of a product, and branding can add value to a consumer's purchase. Brand names help customers to identify products that might benefit them. Below, the data from managers described the relation between product brand and pricing.

“If we come back to role and status, I really doubt it because customers basically if they won't fuel they won't fuel I think it's based mostly based on what we offer to the customers not the of course brand matters and that's why we provide varieties of big brands like I said Burger King, KFC's Sainsbury's now and a lot of varieties of all brands linked with Euro Garage. So that's why as a EG brand we not lack of brands you have plenty of good brands around us so when the customer think okay I need to go there the EG is kind of a destination for them. so, they go them they get the branded stuff in one place basically. So we targeting all role and status of people to shop here”. (Participant-11)

“and we selling all branded items and good quality item so any one can come to do their shopping. Most of the customers, they don't care about the price, they just want products and go”. (Participant-13)

“No they will defiantly come again, because it's very difficult to find a place where you can park the car and do shopping and its very fast line you don't have to wait long time and we selling all branded products and we do lots of promotion which is cheaper than others. So, they definitely will come back”. (Participant-13)

“Most customers are not concern about pricing; they are more concern about convenience, that's the way that EG have operated, so they make sure they have got different brands in the garage for example, we have Grage here, we have got a subway here and we have PFS the fuel side of the business. So everything under one roof and we have got the Starbucks coffee machines so most customers will come here because everything under one roof, its more convinence for them, they don't stop to buy petrol, so years ago, you buy petrol then you go somewhere else to get your food's and the lunch. Now they want everything under one place”. (Participant-2)

“I think because its fast and you don't have very large collection compare with supermarket in a forecourt retail business, they always we choose the most popular items in whatever done by the market research. So it's more chance when people come or customer come they can find their favorite items. Bit compare with supermarket maybe they have hundred items but different brands so example we do

coca- coal yeah, but if you go to supermarket maybe they have their own brand to tesco value or maybe asda value. but the coke is famous so its more chance to people buying the coke rather than we putting different brands. So its for them easy picking. So its because if you have hundred items in the same products, people have to think a lot time, to select which one. Because too many selection means too many time so people are so fast life isn't it. So for them is so easy and the how we store the product there is a system. So you buy the example the crisp section and drinks and the shop is also small and for them its so quick shopping time. So they are fast life so it's very easy for them to come here and the second reason especially in our petrol station is parking. Even our price is expensive is for them is very convenience to come here. Even it's price are expensive still even they don't bother". (Participant-3)

The results highlighted that the Euro garage is the combination of all popular brands under one roof where the consumer never asked for fuel brand but was highly concerned about shop products. Under one roof and branded products concept makes the shop more convenient as they don't need to go different places for different products.

Some respondents described with examples that the forecourt retail business is smaller compared to the supermarket, but they sell only fast-moving branded products. Therefore, consumers don't need to spend lots of time doing their shopping.

Furthermore, respondents believed that the company provides all famous branded products with good quality; therefore, most consumers are only concerned about products, not price. Therefore, the car park, very fast service, all branded products and promotional offers made this place highly effective to the customers, so they keep coming back.

"Coca-cola is already best market in the world. We do have lots of branded products but the people only think about the price. Some cares more about the price, say if you go to the Conner shop you will get a 500ml 1.20 but in the petrol station you buying it 2.20 its very expensive compare to them. This is because of the different suppliers, we got different suppliers who provide us quality products that's why little expensive. The travelers they don't care of the money but the regular guys who live in local they are worries about the price. We are with spar retail so we having products from spar. So spar is one of the best retailer in uk and good quality products so people recognize the products and buy the products". (Participant-14)

Additionally, one respondent believed that it all depends on the location where local consumers are concerned about the price compared to travellers.

"Its not less choice, its like what are the lines we have, the branded lines. In super market they have all kind of varieties they have their own branded product as well as all famous branded are there. By the time they go through there they're wasting their time, here if they come straight they can see you know what they want in the small space so instead of like going through the aisle yeah, what they want you can get all

branded products here in short time. so they saving time people are more conscious about timing especially when they come to petrol station and in general shopping. Also when they want to do small shopping, that's not a weekly shopping so for weekly shopping people like to go around, and buy lots of things". (Participant-7)

"I'll talk about this area, because this area like you can't sell spar brands that much, right because when we started like we had about 95 percent of the products from spa brands when we open this new shop and they weren't like moving because consumers expecting the high-end stuff due to the locality like branded plus high-end like high-end means like you know like Tesco got the finest sort of products, those sort of products they expect around here. The local customer expecting like high quality of products or high-end products. Or you can say like yeah for example if I stay like you get Tesco brand so you can get normal Tesco brand and Tesco finest brand at Tesco, that's what the customers around this area expect". (Participant-9)

"Because of this area is quite posh and reach the consumer demanding good quality product and good service. Spar, they're the only supplier but they do have certain products which is like to see high-end sort of like high quality sort of things. and like what I normally do is like I try to reduce much as possible or spa brand okay and try to get the branded products brand, almost every customer know so if you if you say mcbities is they know like what mcbities is viscous are like so rather than having a spar branded product, Spar is like where we get like even though we the local community is the same like others on the other side you get some customers like who

are looking for products which are like in low price sort of , other side of this area so like we have to deal with both of them like mixture. So we have mixture of product high price and low price and branded product this is how we approach to the customer". (Participant-9)

Additionally, respondents believed that consumers are more concerned about the time when they shop in the petrol station. People can have all branded products without wasting their time. The data highly indicated that the people from the reach area are extremely looking for branded products with high quality, not price.

"There was some certain products I think they're usually sponsoring like a football competition or something in there that brand they tried to pull it into but didn't go well. And some energy drinks, everybody like to buy Red Bull it does it doesn't matter what you do it doesn't matter what promotion you put on a different energy drink they're gonna keep buying Red Bull. Because that brand is so strong. So in petrol station, brand also works really good. Even though you push like low branded product it would be very difficult to sell products. Non branded products is really cheap compare to Red Bull. People just very sucked in by advertisement and pranced and that's why people spend and the brandy products always cost the most. People love branded products, and the way company advertise them, people love brand. The only things are changing that is owned by Aldi's and needles their own brands are coming in now and there so people trust their own brands which is usually cheaper.

Spa had their own brand the people would rather buy Heinz baked beans even spar brand selling half price they rather buy Heinz baked beans". (Participant-9)

"yeah the example, lets say the morning time the customer come to do the shopping while they going to work or maybe while they are going to drop their children to school so they don't have much time specially they have the concern about the traffic or avoiding traffic so the retail forecourt is very fast, as I told you before we have everything but not very large number of selection. So they have less time to think what they want I mean for them its so easy to pick what they want and they are pre decided what they want to buy. Example customer smoke the Benson cigarettes, he don't buy something else he know what he want exactly so if the customer read the newspaper he don't change everyday, he buy the same newspaper everyday probably for his whole life". (Participant-3)

The above quote is evident that branding has become so strong that today's market hardly goes anything unbranded. The brand reflects the product quality and consistency buyer who always buys the same brand know that they will get the same quality and benefits each time they buy. Consumers mostly pre-decided about their shopping habits where price does not affect consumer buying Behaviour.

From the above data, participant views integrate previous research tha has investigated experimentally the influence of price, brand name, and store name on buyers' perception of product

quality. The nature of consumer buying behaviour shows that, for consumer products, the relationship between price and perceived quality and between brand name and perceived quality are positive and statistically significant (Rao, 1989:351). This validate Leavitt (1954) thesis that buyers' tendency to use price as an indicator of quality is a preponderant feature of consumer pricing behaviour. Furthermore, when suggesting that people may judge quality by price Scitovsky (1945) cited in Rao (1989) pointed out that such behaviour is not irrational; it simply reflects a belief that the forces of supply and demand would lead to a "natural" ordering of products on a price scale, leading to a strong positive correlation between brand/product quality and price.

5.2.3.7 Price reduction and consumer buying behaviour

Price reduction is a prevalent marketing technique to attract consumers by providing an incentive that encourages consumers to purchase discounted products immediately. Below the finding suggests the how price reduction affect the consumer buying Behaviour

“Yeah I have very less very people when they see the promotion especially when we run the promotion we make sure we put those promotional items right in front of the door, when the people walk in they can see the promotional items straight way which it attracting them to buy so people buy it. I never experience live very negatively with this price change or promotion. When you put promotion whatever you put people will buy. Also when we do the promotion we print the label in very red markers so its eye catching to the people as well. And people will simply buy it”. (Participant-12)

“Sometimes it happen negatively as well for example after season even you try hard you can’t sell a lot like after Christmas or Easter or like father day, mother day whatever the festival is after the festival it is very difficult to sell the products even you put on the promotion people will not buy the products. It also happen the umbrella in summer time it’s very difficult to sell one and in rainy season even if you put price high it will go. Also its depends on different ethnicities, because this is quite Asian area so they don’t bother about different seasonal products, even I try to sell lots of Christmas products as they are most of them Muslim people they don’t care about this seasonal products”. (Participant-13)

"Basically students they're like energy drinks okay so when we put the Lucozade one pound the big bottle it will run very fast. When the offer finish after three weeks new offers coming like fruit juice for one-pound so another drinks on the offer. who's gonna buy for the fruit juice for one pound that deal is finished already they don't like to buy fruit juice because they need energy drink the kids the students, the workers they need some energy to work. So my opinion is keep that product every day if you get the customers here. So we can make the target from another product. It's all depending on the product. For example, like keep one energy drink or something for the everyday value you know then is people coming more because when they changing they don't have a choice they buying and looking for different choice. Even you offer fruit juice on the offer they don't wanna buy fruit juice, they want energy drink . so the company they are doing silly things sometimes". (Participant-8)

The above evidence proves that there is a significant relationship between a price change and consumer buying Behaviour. Respondents believed that any price change effect positively on consumer buying Behaviour. The price effect in different goods and services depends on the elasticity of demand, such as season, area, and religion. It is very difficult to sell products after season. Even they put a lot of price reduction. The price reduction highly influences the student as they have a limited budget. Consumer purchases are influenced strongly by price reduction as data indicated that people would buy whatever they reduced in the fuel station.

5.2.3.8 Bundle product pricing

Product bundle pricing is a pricing strategy in which several products, services, or any combinations of them are presented to the customer as a single package with a single price. Bundling pricing strategy as one of the advanced marketing strategies is best known for its effectiveness. Below is the data presenting how to bundle of products pricing influences consumer buying Behaviour.

“Yeah, because it meal deal and that kind of 1 pound to 1.30 pound discount like 4/6 pound is going to be 5 or 5.25 something like that coming to 3.50. people like it because it is massive money reducing and also get drink, crisps and sandwich three items and without buying one item, 3 products you buying and just only 50p extra you have to pay for it , something like that”. (Participant-8)

“Yeah we do that on the promotion like 2 for 1 and we got some items like localize 4pk for 2 pound something like that. Than what’s happening like someone buy one

bottle and they buy four bottles here, so the same customers buying the more products". (Participant-10)

"Two for a Pound that's a bottle drinks that's a bundle and also sometimes we do deals with especially groceries like if you buy let's say when you do like special what you call Pancake Day for example special pancake day so we have the wine pancake mixture and honey all three in a off so the customers go there and see them and eat so we promote specifically to a different location near the till fall in the fast lane instead of they go they don't need to go to other supermarkets to buy that so they will grab it and it's on offer. So yeah same thing we do for fathers day mother day, velantian day we offer them chocolate, flowers, toys all three together". (Participant-11)

"We do like male deal like buy sandwich, drinks and crisps or some kind of chocolate with 350. We sell those thing quite a lot here because what happen is people when they go to the Wembley stadium for any football match them come here and buy those things. 350 is good value for the day. Yeah, people like it and they come for the same thing again". (Participant-12)

"We have promotion every month, at least we have one or two lines to those products for example 2 products for pound, 4pk for 2 pound something like that. Consumer taking it positively because most of the time the products got bundle promotion its cheaper than other promotion. So if they buy one is expensive but when they buy 2 its

cheaper than one single price. For example we have some chocolate now if you buy one is 1.59 if you buy 2 that will be 1 pound so that offers affecting a lot to customer. When they come to pay I tell them grab another one it will be cheaper for you. So we give them good service as well and make them to feel come back again". (Participant-15)

"we do the bundle for the meal deals and we also like so we have offers which are 4 piece sweets from one pound something and they change every three weeks we have like some every we have like continuously we have little snacks in our cold section for lunches we have like a chicken on a stick which it's usually 139 but it's one pound we an offer that we give". (Participant-4)

"Yea, it is affecting consumer buying behaviour. And attracting more customer. What I normally do I put the actual price label saying actual price 350 and then put a promotional by the same 250 so the customer can see straightaway at a glance so the actual price is 3.50 and its on the promotion is 2.50 so they will buy it". (Participant-9)

The above finding suggests a consumer-like bundle of products because it's cheaper than buying individually. This increases the consumer perception to buy more such as people will buy more when it is cheap. Consumers are taking the concept positively because most of the time, bundle products are cheaper than normal promotions. Bundle products pricing has a positive impact on consumer buying Behaviour as it helps the consumer for making an instant decision.

5.2.3.9 Consumer compare pricing

The finding below suggests how consumers compare pricing when they go shopping in a petrol station.

“When they come here they little bit hesitant to buy goods and thing, they compare the petrol price and the other prices with the other supermarket and they always tell their prices are very high sometimes they ask the price and leave the goods and go but our local customer they don't care about the price they care about the quality actually not the quality only our some items are not that much high-quality but they don't have any other place to buy things. So, they don't have any choice and its very convenience to buy it from here I think that's one of the main reason people coming here. So people coming here mostly for convenience and the other things is most of them are regular customer”. (Participant-10)

“sometimes we face the problem with the local families because we are located opposite to the Sainsbury so they always compare the price with the opposite of the Sainsbury's so they'll says that you are selling this product for higher price so we will convince them like we are doing the business or like we don't get much profit on the fuel stage and fuel we will get the profit on these. We have to say that we have explained them at last we can't convince them and they will buy the product. So when they complain about the pricing then we try to convince them to buy the products and make them regular customers. They will listen to us and love they were not like fight for price. Its happen sometime like the bad that's, bad experience we have but overall they won't care about this at the end of the day they will come again as well to see us”. (Participant-14)

"yeas pricing affecting customer, as I told for example yeah okay, let's say the customer coming to buy milk, compare with other petrol station or shop our milk is expensive but still customer will buy but it will prevent the customer buying something extra for example we call it Upselling so whatever if the price is expensive then the capability of upselling is decreased. For example the customer buying and if prices are expensive he will buy less. So if the price is expensive they buy what they want only the main item but there is a less chance they buy the extra item. Let's say customer come to buy two chocolate but if the price expensive, they will still buy the chocolate but may be one chocolate. So instade of buying two he will buy just one".

(Participant-3)

"they do compare the price, is the convenient where we are. we are in a residential close to the communal area. The town center is close by and as I said the community shops are along with us like two minutes' walk. There is a community stores so there's food fall, so that is what they are bringing the people in" (Participant-6)

The result suggests that consumers do compare prices before coming to a petrol station, especially for the fuel price. Sometimes it depends on the geographical area of the store. In some areas, local consumers demand high-quality products, so they never check the price before coming here. On the other hand, consumers always compare prices when competitors are close to the shop in some areas. However, data also indicated that consumers would buy only whatever they needed at a higher price. When the price is low, they will buy more.

5.2.3.10 Seasonal product pricing influences CBB

Throughout the whole year, the consumer will have a period of time where they will be more motivated to spend more. Below, the evidence suggests how seasonal product pricing influences consumer buying behaviour.

“yes, that also in promotion, Christmas time, Easter time we have a promotion, that also carry for promotion. we do the same like other supermarket do. We also open on that main season like Christmas day, Boxing Day, and Easter. On that day mostly shops are closed, but we are the only one who open, so we taking the opportunity as people don't have any other alternative choice. And it's bringing lots of consumer as well. We put the reasonable price maybe little expensive compare the others but its works good bringing more consumer”. (Participant-1)

“yeah we do seasonal products like every season for example when its Easter we do Easter eggs, when is Eid we have some products related to Eid for Muslim, same for other realism , on Christmas we do Christmas products. The people come on repeat and check the promotional offers. So we always have something, every month going something. If it summer we do summer products, if it winter we will do winter products, we do promotion on sunglass as well in summer time. We do some offer for pets. So it really affect consumer buying behaviour and bring more consumer and make the consumer busy with new thing. We also inform the consume advanced like we going to do this promotion in this coming days”. Participant-14)

"price is always high level compare with others but people they're happy. we know this area is English area reach area so on hallowing day everywhere you couldn't find the pumpkin last two days. Pumpkin runout everywhere so we are selling one pumpkin three pound so you know the Tesco they are silly for 50p to 1 pound. Even we put the price up we also run out of the product, Easter eggs we only left one egg bag. So seasonal products working much batter here compare to other products even it expensive because of the area. Every company they know how much they can sell, because I know when I was working in the Coap we know our target. here we bring we only bring of two cases of easter gees our money branches they are bring six cage of easter eggs and they putting everywhere eggs that's how we making shop look nice because I mean branches so you can't walk like this better than three size from here".

(Participant-8)

The data indicate that the company always offers seasonal promotions to attract more consumers throughout the year. One respondent mentioned that the shop opens every day, even on public holidays such as Christmas day and Boxing day. So, this is the only place where people can shop, especially on those days it comes down to being more convenient to customers.

Even on the seasonal products, the consumer is looking for promotion and works positively to convince a consumer to buy more, bring more consumers and make the consumer busy with a new thing. The data also highlighted that it depends on the area where some shops take competitive advantage of local competitors. It shows the constantly adapting to customer's needs.

From the foregoing, most consumers know petrol station is more expensive than a normal supermarket. Almost all respondents strongly agreed that convenience, easy access and time-saving are the key reasons for consumers doing shopping here. Consumers are willing to pay extra for convenience. Professional people and consumers from the reach area are always looking for high-quality products, and they are happy with a higher price. Extra function and facilities make the shop more convenient to a consumer where over price is not an issue. The data also highlighted that consumers are willing to pay extra when there is no alternative choice.

Anytime accessibility works positively as consumers know this is the only place opened all the time. Low fuel prices can bring more consumers as passing consumer check price before come to shop in a petrol station. However, the lower price can bring a negative impact on the business; consumer might need to spend more time than normal when the shop is busy.

All respondents are evident that promotional offers drive better consumer traffic and influence consumer buying Behaviour. Most busy people are coming to petrol station who don't have much time to spend. Consumers come here when they are on their way somewhere, which is clearly indicated that people come here for convenience.

Similarly, high low pricing encourages consumer purchases more. High low pricing generates additional sales and reaches more price-sensitive consumers. The respondents also highlighted that they offer products at lower prices on a regular basis without offering any discount or sales offer, which positively impacts consumer buying Behaviour.

Furthermore, evidence suggests that the meal deal drives traffic, brings repeat business, generates loyalty, increases profit, and enhances customers' experience. Respondents also believed that the company provides all famous branded products with good quality; therefore, most consumers are only concerned about products, not price.

Additionally, Respondents believed that any price change effect positively on consumer buying Behaviour. It encourages consumers to purchase discounted products immediately. A consumer also likes a bundle of products because it's cheaper than buying an individual. This increases the consumer perception to buy more such as people will buy more when it's cheap.

Consumers compare prices before coming to a petrol station, especially for the fuel price. With the higher price, the consumer will buy only whatever they need. When the price is low, they will buy more. The company also offers seasonal products for constantly adapting to customers' needs. Even on the seasonal products, the consumer is looking for promotion and works positively to convince a consumer to buy more, bring more consumers and make the consumer busy with a new thing. Therefore, this section proffered answers as captured in the propositions below, which are key factors.

- P14: Consumers willing to pay extra for the convenience
- P15: Professional consumer demanding higher quality products and good customer service and okay with a higher price
- P16: Consumers from the reach area are always looking for high-quality products and good customer service and are willing to pay a higher price.
- P17: Extra function and facilities make the shop more convenient to the consumer where overprice is not an issue.
- P18: Consumers are willing to pay extra when there is no alternative choice.
- P19: Consumer value their time more than money
- P20: Anytime accessibility works positively on consumer buying behaviour.
- P21: Promotional offers drive better consumer traffic and influence consumer buying Behaviour
- P22: Mostly busy people coming to petrol station who don't have much time to spend
- P23: High low pricing encourages consumers to purchase more
- P24: Everyday low pricing creates a positive impact on consumer buying Behaviour
- P25: Meal deal drives traffic, brings repeat business, generates loyalty, increases profit, and enhance customers' experience.
- P26: Company provides all famous branded products with good quality; therefore, most consumers are only concerned about products, not price.
- P27: price reduction encourages consumers to purchase the discounted products immediately
- P28: Consumers like a bundle of products because it's cheaper than buying an individual. This increases the consumer perception to buy more such as people will buy more when it's cheap.
- P29: Seasonal products for constantly adapting to customers' needs.

Figure 5. 2: Key factors from social groups (II)

The findings of the study align, to a reasonable extent, with Engel, Kollet, and Blackwell's (EKB) Model of Buyer Behaviour. This is in the aspect of attempting to comprehend how the customer makes their buying decision. Thus, it can be assumed that Euro Garage customers, after being

wooded to come to buy by adverts or any other means, may then see a need to buy but consider other factors such as income, family, etc., before actually making the purchase. With this in mind, it becomes necessary that Euro Garage managers keenly consider the sort of marketing stimuli they put out there. Further, they must have the conviction that besides price, other factors play a key role in deciding for them too.

5.2.4 Proposed Hypotheses

This section of the research proposes a possible relationship between pricing and consumer buying Behaviour. The hypotheses were arrived at by sifting out and measuring the main variables related to the pricing and consumer behaviour as elicited from respondents' submissions. They were tested using Pearson's Product Moment Correlation analysis computed using SPSS. P1, P2, P3, P4, P5, P13, P14 and P20 are Easy to access, product availability, time-saving, small shop size, convenience, free car parking, and anytime accessibility, providing evidence of the relationship between pricing and consumer buying behaviour. Therefore, hypothesis one can be proposed below.

H1: Convenience has a significant relationship between pricing and consumer buying behaviour.

P6 and P17 describe the concept of everything under one roof; extra functions and facilities make the shop more convenient for the consumer, leading to hypothesis two.

H2: Extra function and facilities provide a positive relationship between price and consumer buying behaviour

P7, P8, P10, P11, P12, P16 and P18 provide evidence of a relationship between price and consumer buying behaviour based on store location and area. Therefore, it can be proposed that.

H3: Area and store location have a significant relationship between price and consumer buying behaviour

P9, P15, P19 and P22 prove that professional people and busy people value their time. These consumers mostly expect higher quality products and good customer service, and they are happy to pay extra for this. Hence, hypothesis four can be proposed below.

H4: There is a positive relationship between price and professional people.

P21, P24, P26 and P27 provide the information that promotional price positively impacts consumer buying behaviour. Hypothesis five can be constricted below.

H5: Promotional price has a positive impact on consumer buying behaviour.

P23 indicates a positive impact on consumer buying behaviour, which is the proposed hypothesis below.

H6: High low pricing has a positive impact on consumer buying behaviour

P25 described the significance of meal deal pricing and consumer buying behaviour. Therefore below hypothesis can be proposed.

H7: Meal deal has a significant relationship between price and consumer buying behaviour

P29 described the importance of seasonal products and pricing and how these impact consumer buying behaviour. This leads hypothesis below.

H8: Seasonal product pricing has a positive impact on consumer buying behaviour

P28 described consumers like a bundle of products because it's cheaper than buying an individual. This increases the consumer perception to buy more such as people will buy more when it's cheap. Therefore, the below hypothesis can be proposed

H9: Bundle of product pricing impacts consumer buying behaviour

5.3 Results From Survey Questionnaire

400 customers of Euro Garage were administered a Likert-style questionnaire of 31 questions. These were sampled using the convenience sampling technique. The convenience sampling technique is useful, especially when randomisation is impossible, like when the population is very large (Etikan et al. 2015). The study thus employed convenience sampling to obtain respondents for its survey questionnaire.

5.3.1 Testing for Reliability.

Cronbach's Alpha Test of Reliability

Before carrying out the research questionnaire exercise, a reliability test was conducted to determine the reliability of this quantitative tool to be employed in the study, in this case, the questionnaire.

This was to ensure that this instrument would give results that could be analysed to produce valid scientific conclusions.

According to Gliem and Gliem (2003), when using Likert-type scales, it is imperative to calculate and report Cronbach's Alpha Coefficient for internal consistency and reliability for any scales or subscales one may be using.

A pilot study of 10 questionnaires was carried out to conduct this test.

Cronbach's Alpha Reliability Test was carried out on the 10 questionnaires using Excel 2013. The findings were as follows:

$$\alpha = \frac{K}{K - 1} \left(1 - \frac{\sum_{i=1}^K \sigma_{Y_i}^2}{\sigma_X^2} \right) \text{ (being formula for Cronbach's Alpha).}$$

$K = 31$ (being number of items on questionnaire)

$\sigma_X^2 = 88.56$ (the variance (square of standard deviation) of the observed total scores)

$\sigma_{Y_i}^2 = 24.12$ (Sum of individual variances)

Reliability Coefficient using Cronbach's Alpha formula gave;

$\alpha = 0.75$

The reliability score was therefore 0.75.

This implied that the questionnaire had an acceptable level of internal consistency and could be relied upon as an analytic tool for this study. Therefore, the study utilises construct validity using the test's internal consistency to assess construct validity. This is made possible by accurately measuring theoretical and non-observable constructs or traits where the result from qualitative data is highly correlational with those from quantitative scores.

Table 5. 3: Response Rate

Variable	Frequency	Percentage
Filled and returned	400	100
Non-response	0	0
Total	400	100

Table 4.4 above presents the response data of the 400 respondents in this study. Using convenience sampling, 400 questionnaires were distributed to 400 willing customers of the store on the spot. Only customers who indicated an interest in filling out the questionnaire were handed one. The questionnaire took about 10 minutes to fill. It was returned on the spot. Response and return rate were therefore 100%.

The survey exercise lasted up to 4 weeks. Extreme caution was taken to ensure that customers who had already filled and submitted their responses did not repeat the exercise a second time. The researcher employed 15 petrol stations during the questionnaire administering exercise.

5.3.2 Descriptive Analysis of Questionnaire Responses

Questionnaire respondents were administered questionnaires that had a set of questions where they were to indicate to what extent they agreed or disagreed with a given statement.

Using the 5-point Likert scale, part B of the questionnaire was structured as thus:

1 – Strongly Disagree (SD)

2 – Disagree (D)

3 – Neutral (N)

4 – Agree (A)

5 – Strongly Agree (SA)

The Excel 2013 application was used to run the descriptive analysis. The findings are presented and interpreted below:

Table 5. 4: Low Pricing Strategy

	SD (1)	D (2)	N (3)	A (4)	SA (5)	Total	Mean 1	Mean 2	Std. Dev.
I choose my fuel convenience store based on their low pricing	25	104	90	110	71	400	3.25	11.97	2.95
I will buy a product I don't recognize simply because it is cheap	128	158	53	42	19	400	2.17	5.96	1.95
All the brands in my shopping bucket are always low priced	70	144	106	53	27	400	2.56	7.81	2.29
I am likely to switch to my supermarket because I like low prices	10	75	123	130	62	400	3.40	12.62	3.04
I always have a large shopping bucket when prices are low	26	77	109	125	63	400	3.31	12.23	2.99
I only buy goods which are cheap from any particular supermarket	41	129	116	72	42	400	2.86	9.51	2.58
My buying behaviour of a product increases when prices reduce	13	50	80	172	85	400	3.67	14.53	3.30
Low prices of products increase my willingness to buy	15	30	55	210	90	400	3.83	15.6	3.43
I prefer brands which have a steady low price	30	96	103	144	27	400	3.11	10.8	2.77

Source: Author's construct (2022)

Interpretation:

From the table above, the study found that most of the customers at Euro Garage chose their fuel convenience store based on its low pricing ($m = 3.25$, $SD = 2.95$). However, many of them did not buy products they did not recognise because it was cheap ($m = 2.17$, $SD = 1.195$). The majority of customers also did not agree that all the brands in their shopping buckets were always low priced ($m = 2.56$, $SD = 2.29$).

At ($m = 3.40$, $SD = 3.04$), the study found that a slight majority of Euro Garage customers indicated that they were likely to switch their supermarkets because they liked low prices.

Some customers were undecided when it always came to having a large shopping bucket whenever prices in the store were low; however, a considerable majority agreed that they always had large shopping buckets when prices in the store were low ($m = 3.31$, $SD = 2.99$).

Most of the customers did not only buy goods that were cheap from any particular supermarket ($m = 2.86$, $SD = 2.58$), but they agreed that their buying Behaviour toward a product increased when prices were reduced ($m = 3.67$, $SD = 3.30$).

Low prices also increased the willingness of most of the customers at Euro Garage to buy the product ($m = 3.83$, $SD = 3.43$), and although many of the customers were undecided as regards preferring brands that had steady low prices, the majority of them agreed that they preferred brands that had steady low prices ($m = 3.11$, $SD = 2.77$).

Table 5. 5: Promotional Pricing Strategy

	SD	D	N	A	SA	Tota	Mean	Mean	Std.
	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	1	1	2	Dev.
My product choice is influenced by promotional offers	32	104	97	99	74	400	3.24	11.89	2.94
Promotional price attract me to buy a product	6	29	60	205	100	400	3.91	16.11	3.49
I am likely to suspend my shopping until there are promotional campaigns in the supermarket	72	192	99	25	12	400	2.28	6.08	1.95

Source: Author's construct (2022)

Interpretation

From the table above, the study found that concerning the promotional pricing strategy implemented in the store, most customers did not base their product choice to buy based on promotional offers. In other words, promotional offers did not influence their product choice ($m = 3.24$, $SD = 2.94$). Promotional prices, however, attracted a majority of customers to buy ($m = 3.91$, $SD = 3.49$). On whether they were likely to suspend their shopping until there were promotional campaigns in the supermarket, most customers did not agree ($m=2.28$, $SD = 1.95$).

Table 5. 6: Bundle Pricing Strategy

	SD	D	N	A	SA	Total	Mean	Mean	Std.
	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)		1	2	Dev.
I prefer to buy my needs during sales season	14	120	125	98	43	400	3.09	10.66	2.75
Products have bundle offers (Buy one and other free) attract me to buy more	13	46	61	172	108	400	3.79	15.50	3.42

Source: Author's construct (2022)

Interpretation

The majority of customers in this study were undecided about buying their needs during sales season ($m = 3.09$, $SD = 2.75$). Products with bundle offers such as "buy one and other free" attracted most Euro Garage customers to buy more ($m = 3.79$, $SD = 3.42$).

Table 5. 7: Customer Attitude and Behavioural Response to Buying

	SD (1)	D (2)	N (3)	A (4)	SA (5)	Total	Mean 1	Mean 2	Std. Dev.
I compare the price of different products before I decide to buy	15	48	73	158	106	400	3.73	15.11	3.37
I am price conscious when buying fuel and convenience product	11	62	83	150	94	400	3.63	14.39	3.28
I choose my supermarket based on stability of their prices	15	68	110	155	52	400	3.40	12.64	3.04
I consider my financial condition and social class during shopping	41	94	93	131	44	400	3.13	11.13	2.83
I don't hesitate to pay little more for convenience purpose	28	44	76	183	69	400	3.55	13.85	3.21
I am always willing to spend more time whenever I visit a supermarket with frequent offers	35	137	123	75	30	400	2.82	9.1	2.51
I will shop at any time of the month because the prices are stable	29	88	114	119	50	400	3.18	11.40	2.87

Source: Author's construct (2022)

Interpretation

The majority of customers in this study compared the prices of products in the store before they bought ($m = 3.73$, $SD = 3.37$). Most were also price-conscious when buying fuel and convenience products ($m = 3.63$, $SD = 3.37$). They also chose their supermarket based on the stability of its prices ($m = 3.40$, $SD = 3.04$).

Most of the customers in this study revealed that they considered their financial condition and social class during shopping ($m = 3.13$, $SD = 2.83$). They, however, did not hesitate to pay a little more for convenience purposes ($m = 3.55$, $SD = 3.49$).

The majority of customers were not always willing to spend more time whenever they visited a supermarket with frequent offers ($m = 2.82$, $SD = 2.51$).

A slight majority of customers indicated that they would shop at any time of the month because the prices were stable ($m = 3.18$, $SD = 2.87$). Most were undecided.

Table 5. 8: Social Influence on the Customer's Buying Behaviour

	SD (1)	D (2)	N (3)	A (4)	SA (5)	Total	Mean 1	Mean 2	Std. Dev.
Social groups influence my buying Behaviour	83	125	67	96	29	400	2.63	8.62	2.44
My family are the most influential people that affect my buying behaviour	54	115	96	90	45	400	2.89	9.86	2.64

Source: Author's construct (2022)

Interpretation:

The study revealed that when it came to social influence on the customer's buying Behaviour, most customers in this study were not influenced by social groups ($m = 2.63$, $SD = 2.44$). Their families were not the most influential people that affected their buying Behaviour ($m = 2.89$, $SD = 2.64$).

Table 5. 9: Brand Awareness and Influence on Customer Buying

	SD (1)	D (2)	N (3)	A (4)	SA (5)	Total	Mean 1	Mean 2	Std. Dev.
Major branded product in this shop influence my buying behaviour	68	107	93	91	41	400	2.83	9.54	2.59
Major branded products do not influence my buying behaviour	56	197	88	49	10	400	2.4	6.68	2.08

Interpretation

The study revealed that most customers were not influenced by major branded products in this shop when it came to how they purchased ($m=2.89$, $SD = 2.59$).

5.3.3 Demographic Information

Below are important demographic information as it concerns the respondents for this questionnaire study and customers of the Euro Garage.

Table 5. 10: Gender of Respondents

Gender	Frequency	Percentage
Male	228	57%
Female	172	43%
Total	400	100%

Source: Author's construct (2022)

Table 5.10 shows that of the 400 Euro Garage customers and respondents sampled for this questionnaire study, 57% were male, and 43% were female. Data is presented graphically and in tabular form, as shown above.

Table 5. 11: Age Distribution of Respondents

Age Bracket	Frequency	Percentage
Below 20	12	3%
21 - 30 years	129	32%
31 - 40 years	119	30%
Over 40 years	140	35%
Total	400	100%

Source: Author's construct (2022)

Table 5.11 show the age composition of the 400 sampled respondents for this questionnaire study. 3% of respondents sampled were below 20 years of age from the data presented. 32% were between 21 and 30, 30% were aged between 31 years and 40, and 35% were over 40 years.

Table 5. 12: Employment Status

Employment Status	Frequency	Percentage
Yes	373	93%
No	27	7%
Total	400	100%

Source: Author's construct (2022)

Table 5.12 presents the employment status information of the 400 sampled respondents for this questionnaire study.

Of the 400 Euro Garage consumers sampled for this study, 93% were employed, and 7% were unemployed. Data is presented graphically and in tabular form.

Table 15: Income Level

Income Level Per Year	Frequency	Percentage
Less than £10, 0000	20	5%
£11, 000 - £20, 000	68	17%
£21, 000 - £30, 000	199	50%
£31, 000 - £40, 000	30	8%
Above £40, 000	83	21%
Total	400	100%

Source: Author's construct (2022)

The income level per year of the 400 questionnaire participants is presented above.

5% of all participants had a yearly income of £10, 000 or less. 17% earned between £11,000 and £20,000 yearly. 50% earned between £21, 000 and £30, 000. 8% of the respondents earned £31,000 and £40, 000. Participants who earned above £40, 000 a year stood at 21%.

Table 5. 13: Household of Respondents

Household of respondents	Frequency	Percentage
Single member	60	15%
Two members	137	34%
Three members	87	22%
Four members	59	15%
Above four	57	14%
Total	400	100%

Source: Author's construct (2022)

The number of members of the household of each questionnaire participant is presented in frequency and percentage above.

Single-member households made up 15%. Two member families made up 34%, three-member families made up 22%, four-member households stood at 15%, and households with four members and above were 14%. The information is simplified in the table and graph above.

5.4 Inferential Analysis of Questionnaire Responses

Employing Pearson's Product Moment Correlation to determine a relationship between the various pricing strategies and behavioural responses across select demographic variables, findings are presented below.

Age group, level of income and family (household) of consumers were the demographic variables selected to be tested alongside the independent pricing variable.

Low Pricing Strategy

Table 5. 14: Effect of Low Pricing on Age Groups, Income Groups and Household Types using Pearson Correlation

		Age (years)	Low prices of products increase my willingness to buy them
Age (years)	Pearson Correlation	1	-0.155**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		0.002
	N	400	400
Low prices of products increase my willingness to buy them	Pearson Correlation	-0.155**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.002	
	N	400	400

Notes: **. Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed). Source: Author's construct (2022)

Table 5. 15: Effect of Low Pricing on Household Types

		Household of Respondents	Low prices of Products increase my willingness to buy them
Household of Respondents	Pearson Correlation Sig. (2-tailed) N	1 400	0.103* 0.039 400
Low prices of products increase my willingness to buy them	Pearson Correlation Sig. (2-tailed) N	0.103* 0.039 400	1 400

Notes: *. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed). Source: Author's construct (2022)

Table 5. 16: Effect of Low Pricing on Income Level

		Income Level per Year	Low prices of products increase my willingness to buy them
Income Level per Year	Pearson Correlation Sig. (2-tailed) N	1 400	-0.068 0.175 400
Low prices of products increase my willingness to buy them	Pearson Correlation Sig. (2-tailed) N	-0.068 0.175 400	1 400

Source: Author's construct (2022).

To determine a relationship between the low pricing strategy of Euro Garage store and the demographic variables of age, income level and household types of its consumers, Pearson Correlation established the following:

Pearson Correlation established a significant negative relationship between the low pricing strategy employed by Euro Garages and the age of the consumer ($r = -.155$) ($p = 0.01$). In other

words, as the age of consumers increased, low prices of products did not increase their willingness to buy them. The correlation was negative.

There was also a significant positive relationship between low pricing and respondents' household. The more household members a consumer had, the more low prices of products increased their willingness to buy ($r = 0.103$) ($p = 0.05$). Therefore, the correlation between low pricing and the number of household consumers was positive.

The relationship between low pricing and the consumer's income level was found to be negative at ($r = -.068$). As income increased, consumers were less likely to increase their willingness to buy products because they were low priced. However, this relationship was not significant.

In summary, when it came to the effect of low pricing on the consumer's age, income level, and household, the correlation test revealed that only age and household were significantly correlated. Age had a negative relationship with low pricing, while low pricing had a positive relationship with household.

5.5 Promotional Pricing Strategy

Table 5. 17: Effect of Promotional Pricing on Age Groups using Pearson Correlation

		Age (years)	Promotional prices attract me to buy the Product
Age (years)	Pearson Correlation	1	-0.086
	Sig. (2-tailed)		0.084
	N	400	400
Promotional price attract me to buy the product	Pearson Correlation	-0.086	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.084	
	N	400	400

Source: Author's construct (2022).

Table 5. 18: Effect of Promotional Pricing on household types

		Household of respondent	Promotional price attract me to buy the product
Household of Respondents	Pearson Correlation	1	.049
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.329
	N	400	400
Promotional price attract me to buy product	Pearson Correlation	.049	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.329	
	N	400	400

Source: Author's construct (2022).

Table 5. 19: Effect of Promotional Pricing on income level

		Income Level per Year	Promotional prices attract me to buy the product
Income Level per Year	Pearson Correlation	1	-0.017
	Sig. (2-tailed)		0.742
	N	400	400
Promotional price attract me to buy the product	Pearson Correlation	-0.017	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.742	
	N	400	400

Source: Author's construct (2022).

As the age of consumers increased, promotional pricing did not significantly attract the buyer to buy the product. Hence there was a negative relationship between age and promotional pricing ($r = -0.086$).

There was also a negative relationship between promotional pricing and the consumer's income level. In other words, the higher the consumer's income, the less likely promotional prices attract them to buy a product ($r = -0.017$).

However, a positive relationship was found between the promotional pricing of the store and the household of the consumer. At $r = 0.049$, the study found that the more members of a household the consumer had, the more promotional pricing attracted them to buy the product.

No significant relationships were found in all demography tested here, as p-values were higher than 0.01 (0.05)

Therefore, when it came to the effect promotional pricing had on age, income level and household of respondents, none of these variables showed a significant relationship. Therefore, promotional pricing may not be an effective pricing strategy for Euro Garage consumers based on their age, income level, and the number of households.

5.6. Bundle Pricing Strategy

Table 5. 20: Effect of Bundle Pricing on Age Groups using Pearson Correlations

		Age (years)	Products have bundle offers (Buy one and other free) attract me to buy more
Age (years)	Pearson Correlation	1	-0.191**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		0.000
	N	400	400
Products have bundle offers (Buy one and other free) attract me to buy more	Pearson Correlation	-0.191**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.000	
	N	400	400

Notes: **. Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed). Source: Author's construct (2022).

Table 5. 21: Effect of Bundle Pricing on household types

		Household of Respondents	Products have bundle offers (Buy one and other free) attract me to buy more
Household of Respondents	Pearson Correlation	1	0.080
	Sig. (2-tailed)		0.109
	N	400	400
Products have bundle offers (Buy one and other free) attract me to buy more	Pearson Correlation	0.080	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.109	
	N	400	400

Source: Author's construct (2022).

Table 5. 22: Effect of Bundle Pricing on income level

		Income Level per Year	Products have bundle offers (Buy one and other free) attract me to buy more
Income Level per Year	Pearson Correlation	1	-0.032
	Sig. (2-tailed)		0.522
	N	400	400
Products have bundle offers (Buy one and other free) attract me to buy more	Pearson Correlation	-0.032	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.522	
	N	400	400

Source: Author’s construct (2022).

Pearson correlation established a significant negative relationship and correlation between the bundle pricing strategy of Euro Garages and the age of its consumers ($r = -0.191$) ($p = 0.01$). This suggests that as age increased, products with bundle offers did not significantly attract consumers to buy more.

The more members there were in the consumer's household, the likelihood that bundle pricing attracted the consumer to buy more ($r = 0.080$). Hence, a positive correlation was established. However, it was not significant.

Bundle pricing and a consumer's income level shared a negative, non-significant relationship at ($r = -0.032$). As income levels increased, consumers were not likely to be attracted by bundle offers to buy more. There was a negative correlation between income level and bundle pricing.

Regarding the effect of bundle pricing and the demography of consumers, here, age, income level and household of respondents, age was the only variable with a significant relationship with bundle pricing. This was a negative relationship, however.

Table 5. 23: Social influence on consumer buying Behaviour (emphasis on consumer age)

		Age (years)	My family are the most influential people that affect my buying behaviour
Age (years)	Pearson Correlation Sig. (2-tailed) N	1 400	0.109* 0.030 400
My family are the most influential people that affect my buying Behaviour	Pearson Correlation Sig. (2-tailed) N	0.109* 0.030 400	1 400

Notes: *. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed). Source: Author's construct (2022)

Table 5. 24: Social influence on consumer buying Behaviour (emphasis on consumer household)

		Household of Respondents	My family are the most influential people that affect my buying behaviour
Household of Respondents	Pearson Correlation Sig. (2-tailed) N	1 400	0.113* 0.024 400
My family are the most influential people that affect my buying Behaviour	Pearson Correlation Sig. (2-tailed) N	0.113* 0.024 400	1 400

Notes: *. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed). Source: Author's construct.

Table 5. 25: Social influence on consumer buying Behaviour (focus on consumer income level)

		Income Level per Year	My family are the most influential people that affect my buying behaviour
Income Level per Year	Pearson Correlation Sig. (2-tailed) N	1 400	.027 .589 400
My family are the most influential people that affect my buying Behaviour	Pearson Correlation Sig. (2-tailed) N	.027 .589 400	1 400

Source: Author's construct (2022)

Pearson correlation established a significant positive relationship between social/family influence on the buying behaviour and the consumer's age at ($r = 0.109$) ($p = 0.05$).

As age increased, consumers indicated that family was the most influential people that affected their buying Behaviour.

The correlation was also significantly positive between household and family influence on buying. At ($r = 0.113$) and ($p = 0.05$), the study found that as the number of household members increased, consumers' buying Behaviour was largely influenced by family. The family also influenced consumers' buying behaviour as their income level increased; however, the correlation was not significantly positive.

Regarding social/family influence on the consumer's buying behaviour across the demography of age, income level and household of respondents, age and household had the only significant relationships. These were all positive relationships.

Table 5. 26: Effect of Brand Awareness and buying behaviour of the consumer (focus on consumer age)

		Age (years)	Major branded products in this shop influence my buying behaviour
Age (years)	Pearson Correlation	1	-0.100*
	Sig. (2-tailed)		0.045
	N	400	400
Major branded products in this shop influence my buying behaviour	Pearson Correlation	-0.100*	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.045	
	N	400	400

Notes: *. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed). Source: Author's construct (2022).

Table 5. 27: Effect of Brand Awareness and buying behaviour of the consumer (focus on the household)

		Household of Respondents	Major branded product in this shop influence my buying
Household of Respondents	Pearson Correlation Sig. (2-tailed) N	1 400	0.043 0.390 400
Major branded products in this shop influence my buying behaviour	Pearson Correlation Sig. (2-tailed) N	0.043 0.390 400	1 400

Source: Author's construct (2022).

Table 5. 28: Effect of Brand Awareness and buying behaviour of the consumer (focus on income level)

		Income Level per Year	Major branded products in this shop influence my buying behaviour
Income Level per Year	Pearson Correlation Sig. (2-tailed) N	1 400	0.027 0.591 400
Major branded products in this shop influence my buying behaviour	Pearson Correlation Sig. (2-tailed) N	0.027 0.591 400	1 400

Source: Author's construct (2022).

Pearson correlation revealed a significant negative relationship between brand awareness and the consumer's buying behaviour across the age group ($r = -.100$) ($p = 0.05$). As age increased, the consumer was unlikely to be influenced by major branded products in the shop during the buying process. Hence, branded products did not strongly impact how consumers bought at the store as they grew old.

There was a positive correlation between brand awareness and the household of respondents; in other words, as members of the consumer's household increased, the likelihood of their buying

behaviour is influenced by major branded products in the shop increased. However, at ($r = 0.43$) and ($p = 0.390$), the relationship was not significant.

As income level increased, so did the influence of major branded products on the consumer's buying behaviour. However, this positive relationship was not significant.

In conclusion, when it came to brand awareness and how it influenced the consumer's behaviour across demography of age, income level and household of respondents, age was the only variable tested that had a significant relationship. However, this was a negative relationship.

Table 5. 29: Customer Attitude and Behavioural Response to buying (with focus on consumer age)

		Age (years)	I compare the price of different products before I decide to buy
Age (years)	Pearson Correlation	1	0.021
	Sig. (2-tailed)		0.670
	N	400	400
I compare the price of different products before I decide to buy	Pearson Correlation	0.021	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.670	
	N	400	400

Source: Author's construct (2022).

Table 5. 30: Customer Attitude and Behavioural Response to buying (focus on consumer household)

		Household of Respondents	I compare the price of different products before I decide to buy
Household of Respondents	Pearson Correlation	1	0.109*
	Sig. (2-tailed)		0.029
	N	400	400
I compare the price of different products before I decide to buy	Pearson Correlation	0.109*	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.029	
	N	400	400

Notes: *. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed). Source: Author's construct (2022).

Table 5. 31: Customer Attitude and Behavioural Response to buying (focus on consumer income level)

		Income Level per Year	I compare the price of different products before I decide to buy
Income Level per Year	Pearson Correlation	1	0.012
	Sig. (2-tailed)		0.815
	N	400	400
I compare the price of different products before I decide to buy	Pearson Correlation	0.012	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.815	
	N	400	400

Source: Author's construct (2022).

Pearson correlation revealed that as the age of consumers increased, the more they were likely to compare prices of different products before they decided to buy. This positive relationship was, however, not significant.

When it came to attitude and behavioural response of consumers in the buying process, the relationship was significantly positive for the household of respondents at ($r = .109$) ($p = 0.05$).

As the members of households of the consumer increased, the higher the chance of the consumer comparing prices of different products before they decided to buy.

There was also a positive relationship between income level and behavioural response. However, this relationship was not significant.

Household of respondents was, therefore, the only demographic variable among the three tested that showed a significant relationship with consumer behavioural response. This relationship was positive.

5.7 Triangulation of Analysis and Discussion of Research Findings

The quantitative instrument and data that measured the customer's buying behaviour as influenced by the pricing strategy from the customer perspective revealed that most of the customers at Euro Garage chose their fuel convenience store based on its low pricing. However, many of them did not buy products they did not recognise because it was cheap. Furthermore, results revealed that the majority of customers also did not agree that all the brands in their shopping buckets were always low priced, a slight majority of Euro Garage customers indicated that they were likely to switch their supermarket because they liked low prices, most of the customers did not only buy goods which were cheap from any particular supermarket, but they agreed that their buying Behaviour of a product increased when prices reduced. Low prices also increased the willingness of most of the customers at Euro Garage to buy the product. Although many of the customers were undecided regarding preferring brands that had steady low prices, the majority of them agreed that they preferred brands that had steady low prices.

In this chapter, Pearson's Analysis was used to test for a correlation between low pricing and the demographic variables of age, income level and household types of the Euro Garages consumers; the study established a significant negative relationship between low pricing strategy and the age of the consumer. This meant that as the age of consumers increased, low prices of products did not increase their willingness to buy them. The study also established a significantly positive relationship between low pricing and respondents' household. In other words, the more members of a household a consumer had, the more low prices of products increased their willingness to buy. Pearson's correlation revealed that of the three demographic variables of age, income, and consumer household, only age and household had any significant correlations. Age, however,

negatively responded to the low pricing strategy. The factor of household bore a positive response to it.

More so, analysis from the qualitative data in measuring the Euro Garage employee and managers' perspectives on the influence of pricing strategies and customer buying behaviour revealed that more than half of the 16 store managers interviewed believed that high-low prices and everyday low pricing had an impact on how the consumer purchased goods.

The study also established that with regards promotional pricing strategy implemented in the store, most customers did not base their choice of product to buy on promotional offers. In other words, promotional offers did not influence their product choice. Promotional prices, however, attracted a majority of customers to buy. On whether they were likely to suspend their shopping until there were promotional campaigns in the supermarket, most customers did not agree.

Pearson revealed no significant relationship (positive or negative) between the promotional pricing strategy of the store and the age, income level or household of the consumer. This, in some way, is consistent with the responses of the store managers interviewed, in which only one of the 16 respondents mentioned promotional pricing. The store managers did not think promotional pricing attracted consumers significantly.

Concerning bundle pricing, the study found that products with bundle offer such as "buy one and other free" attracted the majority of Euro Garage customers to buy more. 11 out of the 16 store managers interviewed also indicated that bundle pricing was important to their customers.

However, the Pearson correlation established that the relationship and correlation between bundle pricing and the consumer's age were significantly negative. This implied that as the age of consumers increased, products with bundle offers did not significantly attract them to buy more. The study also found that the majority of customers in this study were undecided when it came to prefer to buy their needs during sales season. Only 5 of the 16 managers also thought that seasonal product pricing was important to the consumer.

The majority of customers in this study compared the prices of products in the store before they bought when it came to consumer attitude and behavioural response to buying. However, only 5 of the 16 managers interviewed thought so. A majority were also price-conscious when buying fuel and convenience products. They also chose their supermarket based on the stability of its prices. Most of the customers in this study revealed that they considered their financial condition and social class during shopping. They, however, did not hesitate to pay a little more for convenience purposes. 13 out of the 16 store managers also indicated that they did not hesitate. The majority of customers were not always willing to spend more time whenever they visited a supermarket with frequent offers. A slight majority of customers indicated that they would shop at any time of the month because the prices were stable.

On consumer attitude and behavioural response to buying, the Pearson correlation revealed that as the members of the consumer's household increased, the higher the chance of the consumer comparing prices of different products before they decided to buy.

The study revealed that when it came to social influence on the customer's buying Behaviour, the majority of customers in this study were not influenced by social groups. Their families were not the most influential people who affected their buying behaviour. Pearson correlation established a significant positive relationship between social/family influence on buying behaviour and age of the consumer; in other words, as age increased, consumers indicated that family was the most influential people that affected their buying Behaviour. The correlation was also significantly positive between household and family influence on buying. The study found that as the household members increased, consumers' buying Behaviour was largely influenced by family. 14 out of the 16 store managers interviewed also believed that family played a role in influencing how their consumers bought.

On brand awareness and buying behaviour, the study revealed that although 10 of the 16 managers indicated that branded products were an important consideration to the customers, the majority of customers were not influenced by major branded products in this shop when it came to how they purchased. Pearson correlation also revealed that a significant negative relationship existed between brand awareness and the consumer's buying behaviour across the age group. As age increased, the consumer was unlikely to be influenced by major branded products in the shop during the buying process. Hence, branded products did not strongly impact how the consumer bought at the store as they got old.

16 managers of Euro Garages were interviewed for this study. Their perspective and views on buying behaviour was solicited in the interview.

From data obtained, the managers revealed that most of their customers were aware that the petrol station was more expensive than the average supermarket.

Almost all of the 16 managers strongly agreed that convenience, easy access and time-saving were the key reasons for consumer shopping. Consumers were also willing to pay extra for convenience. The managers revealed that professionals and consumers from richer areas of residence were always looking for high-quality products, and they were happy with higher prices.

According to the respondents, e

xtra functions and facilities also made the shop more convenient for consumers where over price is not an issue.

The managers also revealed that consumers were willing to pay extra when there were no alternative choices. Lower fuel prices also helped bring in more consumers most of the time as passing consumers checked prices before coming to shop in the petrol station.

However, the managers also agreed that lower prices could negatively impact the business as consumers may need to spend more time than normal when the shop is busy, which may lead to disgruntled customers.

All 16 respondents were of the opinion that promotional offers drove better consumer traffic and influenced consumer buying Behaviour, especially busy people coming to the petrol station who don't have much time to spend. Consumers come here when they are on their way somewhere, which is clearly indicated that people come here for convenience.

Similarly, high low pricing encouraged consumer purchases more. High low pricing generated additional sales and attracted more price-sensitive consumers. The respondents also highlighted that they offer products at lower prices regularly without offering any discount or sales offer, which positively impacts consumer buying Behaviour.

Furthermore, evidence suggested that meal deals drove traffic, bringing repeat business, generating loyalty, increasing profit, and enhancing customer experience. Respondents also believed that the company provides all famous branded products with good quality; therefore, most consumers are only concerned about products, not price.

Additionally, Respondents believed that any price change positively affected consumer buying Behaviour. These price changes encouraged consumers to purchase discounted products immediately from the managers. A consumer also likes a bundle of products because was cheaper than buying an individual. This increased the consumer perception to buy more such as people will buy more when it's cheap.

Consumers do compare prices before coming to a petrol station, especially for the fuel price. With the higher price, the consumer will buy only whatever they need. When the price is low, they will buy more. The company also offers seasonal products for constantly adapting to customers' needs. Even on the seasonal products, the consumer is looking for promotion and works positively to convince the consumer to buy more, bring more consumers and make the consumer busy with a new thing.

The summary of the interview with the 16 store managers on consumer buying behaviour in the store revealed that:

- Consumers willing to pay extra for the convenience

- Consumers with higher income demand higher quality products and good customer service, and we're okay with the higher price.
- More affluent consumers were always looking for high-quality products and good customer service and were willing to pay a higher price.
- Extra function and facilities make the shop more convenient for consumers where overprice is not an issue.
- Consumers were willing to pay extra when there was no alternative choice.
- Consumers value their time more than money.
- Anytime accessibility worked positively on consumer buying behaviour.
- Promotional offers drove better consumer traffic and influenced consumer buying Behaviour.
- Mostly busy people come to petrol station who don't have much time to spend
- High low pricing encourages consumers to purchase more.
- Everyday low pricing created a positive impact on consumer buying Behaviour.
- Meal deals drove traffic and brought in repeat business.
- The company provided all famous branded products with good quality; therefore, most of the consumers were only concerned about products, not price.
- Price reductions encouraged consumers to purchase discounted products immediately.
- Consumers liked a bundle of products because it was cheaper than buying an individual. This increased the consumer perception to buy more such as people will buy more when it's cheap.

- Seasonal products were constantly adapted to customers' needs, and even at that, customers sought promotions and price discounts.

Proposed Hypotheses

Based on the findings above, the study developed the following hypotheses.

H1: Convenience has a significant relationship between pricing and consumer buying behaviour.

H2: Extra function and facilities provide a positive relationship between price and consumer buying behaviour

H3: Area and store location have a significant relationship between price and consumer buying behaviour

H4: There is a positive relationship between price and professional people.

H5: Promotional price has a positive impact on consumer buying behaviour.

H6: High low pricing has a positive impact on consumer buying behaviour

H7: Meal deal has a significant relationship between price and consumer buying behaviour

H8: Seasonal product pricing has a positive impact on consumer buying behaviour

H9: Bundle of product pricing impacts consumer buying behaviour

Three of the hypotheses on pricing were tested using the questionnaire responses of the Euro Garages Customers. This is shown in chapter six.

From the above analytical schemes, the application of theories explained in chapter three provides a framework on which this study is based and on which the analysis of the study's results, as stated above, is built. Thus, the theory of planned behaviour provides fundamental knowledge to understand human beliefs and behaviour by measuring overall attitudes towards pricing strategies

and consumer behaviour. This is apt as this explains the choice of older consumers who are rarely swigged by promotional pricing strategies to buy goods and services. The motivation-need theory focuses on consumer psychology containing a five-tier model of human needs and thus explains consumers' decision to buy based on need priorities, as seen in some cases of the above study results. EKB Model of buyer Behaviour explains how decisions are made when choosing the list of alternatives explaining the utility of convenience buying of consumer's behaviour. Hawkins Stern's impulse buying theory explains that marketers can convince consumers to buy more than they had actually planned through various pricing strategies. The pavlovian theory provides the famous experiments and found that objects could trigger a conditioned response in this regard; the utility of this theory as presented by the above analysis of results shows that the majority of consumers are often influenced by pricing strategies and offer like low pricing, promotional pricing and bundle pricing.

Furthermore, the study distinctly developed and operationalised a theoretical framework that considers two fundamental variables that inform the price – customer's buying behaviour dynamics. The framework highlights the mutually reinforcing effect of "pricing strategies" on "Consumer Characteristics", constituting a decisional quagmire before the rational consumer. However, given the consumer desire to buy and the service station/garage's intention to sell more, problem-solving schemes align with mutually reinforcing pricing strategies and consumer characteristics. When the consumer wants to buy valuable goods and services, he must first prioritise his need recognition, followed by information on favourable pricing strategies while evaluating available alternatives before making his final buying decision (Purchase or Not Purchase). Therefore, the theoretical framework developed for this study clearly shows a causal

relationship between pricing strategies and consumer characteristics and how this affects a consumer's purchase decision.

5.8 Chapter Summary

This chapter presents the analysed data of the current research study. Quantitative data were presented descriptively, showing means, frequencies, standard deviations and percentages. These were computed on Excel 2013 application. Quantitative data was also presented inferentially using the Pearson's Product Moment Correlation analysis computed using SPSS. Qualitative data were coded and themed using the traditional and manual analysis approach. This was also presented. Interpretations were made for all data analysed.

The next chapter, Chapter 6, will discuss these findings, draw conclusions, and present recommendations from the conclusions drawn.

CHAPTER SIX

DISCUSSION, CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

6.1 Introduction

This chapter presents an analysis of the findings obtained in the previous chapter, Chapter 5, and discusses these findings in line with the literature review presented in Chapter 2.

The literature review was structured around the research questions of this study which tried to establish the impact of pricing on consumer behaviour, how pricing decisions affected the buying behaviour of fuel service station consumers as observed by the store managers, and how pricing influenced the way customers bought at the service station as reported by the consumers, themselves. Conclusion and recommendation are presented after.

6.2 Summary of the Study

The purpose of this study was to explore how pricing impacts consumer buying behaviour with a focus on the Euro Garage fuelling station back forecourt convenience stores in the Hertfordshire area in the UK. The study examined how various pricing strategies are significant in explaining product choice, store choice, purchase amount, and purchase timing. In order to achieve this aim, this study specifically addressed how consumer buying behaviour and pricing strategy within service setting stations are determined. Also, it went further to investigate the pricing strategy that influences consumer buying behaviour from the organisation's perspective. Finally, the study evaluated the pricing strategy that influences customer buying behaviour from the customer perspective.

To achieve these aims, therefore, the study was divided into six chapters. Chapter one provided the context of the argument and gave the operational direction for the research. Undoubtedly, customers are one single most important actors in business and marketing dynamics. With competition ruffling to keep and retain customers, many companies and marketers understand the importance of studying consumer behaviour when it comes to purchasing and are now designing pricing strategies that will best address the needs of their customers. Therefore, price, the value placed on a good or service, is the only element of the 4 P's in the marketing mix that directly determines the revenues and profits made by a business, hence its importance to marketers. Consumers have also been found to have their buying decisions influenced by price, according to several studies. Consequently, this chapter raised the research questions which sought to establish the effect of pricing on consumer behaviour, how pricing decisions affected the buying behaviour of the fuel service station consumers as observed by the store managers, and how pricing influenced the way customers bought as reported by consumers themselves.

Chapter two presented previous literature work on the subject of study to highlight their contributions and identify gaps that would justify the undertaking of the current research. Concepts and theories relevant to the understanding of pricing dynamics and customer buying behaviour were also highlighted. These provided a framework for the current study. The literature review is an important part of a research presentation as existing literature on the subject of interest is critically reviewed to highlight contributions and identify gaps. A research study must fill an existing gap in the literature in order that adds valuably to academics. Therefore, this study revealed that little research had been conducted on fuelling stations, especially the Euro Garage,

which aimed at measuring the relational dynamics between various pricing types and customer buying behavioural patterns.

Chapter three presented a clinical overview of a number of theories that exist within the consumer behaviour space. These theories provide a framework on which this study is based and on which the analysis of the study is built. Thus, the theory of planned behaviour provides fundamental knowledge to understand human beliefs and behaviour by measuring overall attitudes towards the object. Motivation need theory focuses on consumer psychology containing a five-tier model of human needs. EKB Model of buyer Behaviour explains how decisions are made when choosing the list of alternatives. Hawkins Stern's impulse buying theory explains that marketers can convince consumers to buy more than what they had actually planned. The pavlovian theory provides famous experiments and found that objects could trigger a conditioned response. These will guide the study in its attempt at providing answers to its research questions.

In chapter three also, the study distinctly developed and operationalised a theoretical framework for research. This model took into cognisance two fundamental variables that inform the price – customer's buying behaviour dynamics. The framework highlights the mutually reinforcing effect of "pricing strategies" on "Consumer Characteristics", both of which constitute a decisional quagmire before the rational consumer. However, given the consumer desire to buy and the service station/garage intention to sell more, problem-solving schemes sets in with mutually reinforcing pricing strategies and consumer characteristics. When the consumer wants to buy valuable goods and services, he must first prioritise his need recognition, followed by information on favourable pricing strategies while evaluating available alternatives before making his final buying decision

(Purchase or Not Purchase). Therefore, this theoretical framework developed for this study clearly shows a causal relationship between pricing strategies and consumer characteristics and how this affects the purchase decision of a consumer.

Chapter four presented the research methodology employed in this study to obtain data for analysis. In order to achieve the objectives of the study, the hybrid or mixed research method was adopted for this study. The method entailed the triangulation of methods, where there was a combination of both quantitative and qualitative methods. These methods are utilised to measure how consumer buying behaviour and pricing strategy within service setting station are determined, investigate the pricing strategy that influences the consumer's buying behaviour from the organisation's perspective, and evaluate the pricing strategy that influences customer buying behaviour from the customer perspective. The study adopted both qualitative data collection instruments (semi-structured interviews were conducted on 16 managers of the Euro Garages stores, who were selected based on the snowballing sampling technique) and questionnaires (Quantitative data, on the other hand, was obtained through a 5-point Likert scale questionnaire administered to 400 customers of the Euro Garages stores who were selected using convenience sampling).

While the qualitative data were analysed using the traditional and manual analysis method applied using a thematic approach, data from the questionnaire were analysed descriptively using Excel 2013 to obtain the means, frequencies, standard deviations and percentages, and analysed inferential employing the Pearson Correlation Analysis to establish relationships between

dependent and independent variables in the study. The SPSS software was used to test for correlation.

Chapter five of the study presented data gathered from both quantitative and qualitative methods and conducted an in-depth analysis using triangulation. The quantitative instrument and data which measured the customer's buying behaviour as influenced by the pricing strategy from the customer perspective revealed that the majority of the customers at Euro Garage chose their fuel convenience store based on its low pricing. Many of them, however, did not buy products they did not recognise simply because it was cheap. Furthermore, results revealed that the majority of customers also did not agree that all the brands in their shopping buckets were always low priced, a slight majority of Euro Garage customers indicated that they were likely to switch their supermarket because they liked low prices, most of the customers did not only buy goods which were cheap from any particular supermarket, but they agreed that their buying Behaviour of a product increased when prices reduced. Low prices also increased the willingness of most of the customers at Euro Garage to buy the product, and although many of the customers were undecided as regards preferring brands that had steady low prices, the majority of them agreed that they preferred brands that had steady low prices.

In this chapter, Pearson's Analysis was used to test for correlation between low pricing and the demographic variables of age, income level and household types of the Euro Garage consumers, and the study established a significant negative relationship between low pricing strategy and the age of the consumer. This meant that as the age of consumers increased, low prices of products did not increase their willingness to buy them. The study also established a significantly positive

relationship between low pricing and the household of respondents. In other words, the more members of a household a consumer had, the more low prices of products increased their willingness to buy. Pearson's correlation revealed that of the three demographic variables of age, income and household consumer, only age and household had any significant correlations. Age, however, negatively responded to the low pricing strategy. The factor of household bore a positive response to it.

More so, analysis from the qualitative data in measuring the EU Garage employee and managers' perspectives on the influence of pricing strategies and customer buying behaviour revealed that more than half of the 16 store managers interviewed believed that high-low prices and everyday low pricing had an impact on how the consumer purchased goods.

Summarily, results as presented in chapter five measuring managers' perspectives revealed amongst other things that: Consumer willing to pay extra for convenience, Consumers with higher income demanded higher quality products and good customer service and were okay with higher price, More affluent consumers were always looking for high quality products and good customer service and were willing to pay higher price, Extra function and facilities make the shop more convenient to consumer where over price is not an issue, Consumers were willing to pay extra when there was no alternative choice, Consumers valued their time than money, Anytime-accessibility worked positively on consumer buying behaviour, Promotional offers drove better consumer traffic and influenced consumer buying Behaviour, Mostly busy people came to petrol station who don't have much time to spend, High low pricing encouraged consumer purchase more, Everyday low pricing created a positive impact on consumer buying Behaviour, Meal deals

drove traffic and brought in repeat business, company provided all famous branded products with good quality therefore most of consumers were only concerned about products not price, Price reductions encouraged consumers to purchase the discounted products immediately, Consumers liked bundle of products because was cheaper than buying individual. This increased the consumer perception to buy more such as people will buy more when it's cheap, and Seasonal products were constantly adapted to customers' needs, and even at that, customers sought promotions and price discounts.

6.3 Results Against the Research Objectives

The study interrogated the research questions; the effects of pricing on consumers' buying behaviour as observed by both EU Garage employees and the consumers themselves. In order to answer this question in tandem with the aims and objectives of the study, the study utilised measurable indicators; low pricing, promotional pricing and bundle pricing, which during testing and analysis of results showed significant impacts on the pattern of buying behaviour of consumers.

6.3.1 Does Pricing have an Effect on Consumer Behaviour?

Considering the indicator, low pricing, respondents preponderantly agreed that the type of pricing strategy has a huge impact on the pattern of consumers' behaviour which informs their decision to buy or not to buy a product or service. Consequently, when it came to low pricing strategy and the buying behaviour of the consumer, many of the Euro Garage consumers sampled chose their fuel convenience store based on its low pricing. However, they did not buy products they did not recognise simply because it was cheap. Results also showed that consumers did not agree that all

the brands in their shopping buckets were always low priced, and most of the customers did not only buy goods that were cheap from any particular supermarket. Pearson correlation established a negative relationship between low pricing strategy and the age of the consumer, which meant that as the age of consumers increased, low prices of products did not increase their willingness to buy them. According to Spitteri and Dion (2014), customer age and life cycle have a significant impact on their buying behaviour. With the change in age, various changes occur, such as maturity level, experiences, income and status (Lynn, 2011). This explained why low pricing impacted negatively on the age of the consumer. Bailey (2011) found a significant relationship between the age of the respondents and the prices charged at petroleum stations in Cape Town.

While there was a negative relationship between the age of consumers and low pricing strategy, further interrogation using Pearson's correlation, however, established a significant relationship between low pricing and the household of respondents. This relationship was positive this time. In other words, the more members of a household a consumer had, the more low prices of products increased their willingness to buy. Low prices increased the willingness of most of the customers at Euro Garage to buy the product. It is believed that this group of customers were majorly those with an increased number of household members. According to Langner et al. (2013), the family is the most important social institution for many consumers, strongly influencing their values, attitudes, self-concept and buying behaviour. Yakup and Sevil (2011) state that many people purchase as one person, but there is actually more than one person behind the decision-making process. During this stage, the buying process can be considered as more than one person in any stage of the evaluation phase (Yakup and Sevil (2011)).

The second variable adapted to interrogate the effects of pricing on consumers' buying behaviour was promotional pricing. Respondent's observation and responses to this indicator showed that whenever a promotional pricing strategy is implemented in the store, the majority of customers indicated that they did not base their choice of product to buy based on promotional offers. In other words, promotional offers did not influence their product choice. On whether they were likely to suspend their shopping until there were promotional campaigns in the supermarket, the majority of customers did not agree.

Although promotional pricing still attracts a majority of customers in the store to buy, Mcconnochie et al. (2017) state that price promotions, especially in retail (FMCG), can result in short-lived sales increases. However, though the promotional goal is to encourage product trials, increase purchase frequency and encourage brand switching, it could be said that the abundance of deals available is 'just white noise to most shoppers.'(Moule, 2013 as cited in Mcconnochie et al., 2017). This is so as most of these purchases are considered low involvement (Mcconnochie et al., 2017).

Thirdly, bundle pricing as a pricing strategy is said to have significant effects on consumers' behaviour. Thus, from the triangulation of data and responses, the majority of Euro Garage customers were attracted to the bundle offer of "buy one and other free", buying more in the process. 11 out of the 16 store managers interviewed also indicated that bundle pricing was important to their customers. In their study to examine the importance of delivering an all-inclusive price bundle to consumers, Naylor and Frank (2001) confirmed that consumers considered more than just benefits (quality) and price when assessing value. Specifically, they found that providing

an all-inclusive price package, even if the actual monetary outlay was higher, significantly increased perceptions of value for first-time consumers.

However, the Pearson correlation established a significant negative relationship between this pricing strategy and the age of the consumer. This implied that as the age of consumers increased, products with bundle offers did not significantly attract them to buy more.

In his study to determine the factors that influenced patronage Behaviour in selecting a petroleum service outlet, Kakunu (2012) found that prices of the fuel and services offered ranked high with quality as what influenced the choice of a petrol outlet. Whereas, Salifu (2014) opined that to determine the relative factors that influenced consumer branch choice for fuel brands, private car owners chose quality and convenience over price, while commercial drivers picked price over other factors in their choice of a petrol station brand. There is no doubt that price and or pricing strategy impact consumer buying behaviour. However, results from the analysis of data in this study show that this impact varies with factors such as personal factors, social factors, demographic factors like age and more.

6.3.2 What is the Effect of Pricing on Consumer Behaviour from the Perspectives of Store Managers and Customers?

The perspectives of store managers and customers on the effects of pricing on consumers' behaviour were collaborative in many instances. Responses gathered from 16 store managers of the Euro Garages branch who were interviewed for this study and 400 customers that were administered questionnaires in the study's survey reinforced each others' position on key variables

for measurement. The purpose of employing the mixed-method research of qualitative and quantitative research was for a robust analysis of the research topic. Mixing data sets can give a better understanding of the problem and yield complete evidence. Amalgamating statistics with thematic approaches can help avoid over-reliance on the former and can also capture "softcore views and experiences" (Jogulu and Pansiri, 2011). Therefore, all 16 respondents who participated in the interview and 400 customers who responded to the questionnaires saw the subjects of pricing and consumer behaviour as important and believed that there was an influencing element between both variables.

Low Pricing strategy, as one of the first variables used to answer the question of manager's and consumers' perspectives on pricing and consumer buying behaviour, elicited significant responses on a causal relationship between low pricing and consumer buying behaviour. Thus, more than half of the 16 store managers interviewed for this study believed that high-low prices and everyday low pricing had a positive impact on how the consumer purchased goods in the store. Although a majority of the customers at Euro Garage indicated that they chose their fuel convenience store based on its low pricing, that low prices increased the willingness of most of them to buy the product, and that they preferred brands that had steady low prices, they, however, did not buy products they did not recognise simply because it was cheap, neither were all the brands in their shopping buckets always low priced.

Consequently, Levy and Weitz (1995, as cited in Njeru, 2017) corroborate the perspectives of both the store managers and customers, as stated above, that everyday low pricing is a strategy that appeals to consumers as a more honest strategy. However, although the majority of consumers are

rather price-sensitive, they also consider other factors such as brand image, store location, service, value, and quality (Tjiptono, 2008 as cited in Albari and Safitri, 2018).

Furthermore, consumers tend to associate price with product level such that a perceived high price reflects the high quality and vice versa (Albari and Safitri, 2018). Tajdar et al. (2015), as cited in (Albari and Safitri, 2018), thus recommend that a brand must come with a reasonable price. Price has a relative effect: some consumers are sensitive to price, whereas others do not consider the price when making a purchase decision (Sangadji and Sopiah, 2013, cited in Albari and Safitri, 2018).

Secondly, results from respondents and participants (consumers and store managers, respectively) suggested that promotional pricing had a positive impact on the buying behaviour of the customers. Although promotional pricing in the store attracted a majority of the customers to buy, they did not base their choice of product on promotional offers. In other words, promotional offers did not influence their product choice. On whether they were likely to suspend their shopping until there were promotional campaigns in the supermarket, the majority of customers did not agree. Lee and Cheng-Yu (2018) state that, according to the economic effects of price discounts, a price discount provides a monetary gain, an incentive to encourage consumers to purchase the product. Consumers perceived a higher level of savings for a product when a higher price discount was provided, and this relationship was confirmed by previous other studies (Lee and Cheng-Yu, 2018). However, although price promotions excite consumers and enable them to save money, consumers usually associate low prices with inferior quality and so may doubt the quality of the products if too many price reductions are offered (Felistas, 2014).

Furthermore, the third variable been investigated to have shaped consumers' buying behaviour was bundle pricing. Results showed that 11 out of the 16 store managers interviewed indicated that bundle pricing was important to their customers. Store managers believed that bundle pricing had a positive impact on the consumers' behaviour at the store. Products with bundle offer such as "buy one and other free" also attracted the majority of Euro Garage customers to buy more, as reported by the consumers.

The above corroborates extant arguments that bundling pricing strategy as one of the advanced marketing strategies is best known for its effectiveness, as shown in the studies of Stremersch and Tellis, 2002; Prasad et al., 2015; Shaddy and Fishbach, 2017, as cited in Musa (2017). Pearson correlation, however, revealed that older consumers were not always attracted to bundle offers.

6.4 Testing the Research Hypotheses

Three of the pricing hypotheses formulated from the findings of the interviews with the store managers were tested in this study.

These were:

1. Low pricing (H6: High low pricing has a positive impact on consumer buying behaviour)
2. Promotional pricing strategy (H5: Promotional price has a positive impact on consumer buying behaviour)
3. Bundle pricing strategy (H9: Bundle of product pricing impacts consumer buying behaviour).

Pearson correlation revealed that with low pricing strategies of the store, older consumers didn't see their willingness to buy a product based on its lower price increase. However, the more

household members a customer of the store had, the more they were willing to buy a product based on its low price.

For promotional pricing, Pearson correlation revealed no significant relationship between the strategy and age, income and household of the Euro Garage consumer.

For Bundle pricing, Pearson established that as the age of the consumer increased, bundle pricing/product did not attract them to buy more.

6.5 Similarities and Differences between Organisations and Customers

While the organisation were of the opinion that low pricing (high-low) had a positive impact on the buying behaviour of the consumer, older customers did not respond positively to it, as established by Pearson analysis. In other words, as the age of the customer increased, their willingness to buy a product based on its low price decreased.

However, this impact was positive for customers who had more members of households living with them. However, store managers believed that promotional pricing made their customers buy more when employing Pearson and based on these responses against the variables of the age of the customer, income of the customer and number of the household of the customer, no significant relationship was found.

On bundling, older customers were not always attracted to buy more products based on bundling pricing, as established by the Pearson correlation.

6.6 Conclusion

This study examined how various pricing strategies are significant in explaining product choice, store choice, purchase amount, and purchase timing expressed in what is termed consumer buying behaviour. In order to achieve this, the study explored how product pricing decisions of retailers impact consumer buying behaviour in EU Garage service stations across the UK.

Retail store owners adopt a varying range of pricing models to appeal to the needs of their customers, increase patronage and sales, and thrive in a competitive space. The pricing strategies employed by fuel service convenience store owners follow a similar path. Therefore, Monroe (2003), as cited in Toni et al. (2015), opined that price decisions are one of the most important decisions of management because it affects profitability and the companies' returns along with their market competitiveness.

While it is pertinent that pricing strategies are invaluable to shaping the pattern of consumer buying behaviour towards a particular product or service, the task of developing and defining prices is thus complex and challenging because the managers involved in the process must understand how their customers perceive prices, how to develop the perceived value, what are the intrinsic and relevant costs to comply with this necessity as well as consider the pricing objectives of the company and their competitive position in the market (De Toni et al., 2015).

A pricing strategy has notable advantages, such as attracting customers. Nafuna et al. (2019) state that pricing is a powerful force in attracting attention and increasing sales and that it can also have a major influence on customer loyalty which determines the ability of the firm to consistently generate revenues to boost profitability and liquidity in the long run. A pricing strategy thus has a

goal to establish an optimum price with current profit maximisation of the number of units sold, etc. (Dolgui and Proth, 2010).

Raymond et al. (2001), using strategy is never sufficient. The use of adequate pricing strategies is critical for making managerial decisions and achieving success in the competitive market. Studies show that the effect of pricing has a far-reaching effect more than the cost of the product (Hameed et al., 2012). Pricing decisions are also made based on internal and external considerations. Internal factors include the objectives of the enterprise, cost factors, characteristics of the product and price elasticity of demand. External factors which influence the pricing strategy of an organisation are the demand of consumers, competition in the market, suppliers, the economic condition of consumers and governmental policies (Jang et al., 2017).

Pricing strategy, therefore, tries to take advantage of the time by playing with the seasonality of demand, for example, customers' preferences and purchasing behaviour, and the spectrum of available products (Dolgui and Proth, 2010). A business organisation needs to focus on pricing strategy if it wants to grab the highest market share and obtain a higher level of profit in addition to long-term growth. However, they have to keep the price in such a way that consumers are willing to pay without any hesitation (Liu et al., 2018).

The study, therefore, revealed that a majority of Euro Garage customers chose their fuel convenience store based on its low pricing. This means Euro Garage meets these criteria for them. Most also indicated that low pricing increased their willingness to buy a product and that they preferred brands that had a steady low price. However, they did not buy products they did not

recognise simply because it was cheap, nor were all the brands in their shopping buckets always low priced. Statistically, a significant negative relationship was established between this pricing strategy and the age of the consumer. As the age of consumers increased, low prices of products did not increase their willingness to buy them. On the other hand, the more members there was the household of the consumer, the more low prices of products increase their willingness to buy.

Secondly, promotional pricing/Promos attracted a majority of Euro Garage customers to buy products. However, they did not base their choice of product on promotional offers. In other words, promotional offers did not influence their product choice. Customers are not also likely to suspend their shopping until there are promotional campaigns in the supermarket. Meanwhile, the study revealed that bundle pricing' products with offers such as "buy one and other free" attracted the majority of consumers who shopped at the Euro Garage stores.

In the cause of the research, it was found that alongside pricing strategies, other variables like consumer attitude, family and brand awareness also formed a significant basis for consumer buying behaviour. Therefore, while pricing strategies remained consequential in shaping consumer buying behaviour, other external and internal factors were also significant to consumer behaviour. Specifically, most Euro Garage customers in this study compared the prices of products in the store before they bought. A majority were also price-conscious when buying fuel and convenience products. They also chose their supermarket based on the stability of its prices. Most of the customers in this study revealed that they considered their financial condition and social class during shopping. They, however, did not hesitate to pay a little more for convenience purposes. The majority of customers were not always willing to spend more time whenever they visited a

supermarket with frequent offers, though, and a slight majority of customers indicated that they would shop at any time of the month because the prices were stable. Members of households of consumers played an important influencing role, whereas a consumer had more members living with them, the more they compared prices of different products before they decided to buy.

With regards to social influence on consumer's buying behaviour, although the majority of customers were not influenced by social groups, neither were their families the most influential people that affected their buying behaviour, customers that had more members of the family living with them and customers who were a little older, indicated that family was the most influential people that affected their buying behaviour. Meanwhile, it is pertinent to note that though brands have, over time, informed consumer buying behaviour, this study revealed that the majority of customers were not influenced by major branded products in this shop when it came to how they purchased. Indeed, as age increased, the less branded products influenced how the consumer bought.

Finally, while it can be plausibly argued that extant literature has understudied the causal relationships between pricing strategies and consumer's behavioural patterns resulting in a litany of various pricing models, their effectiveness as a form of business management strategy as well as consumers' enticement mechanism differs in terms of yielding results. While low pricing and bundle pricing, for instance, yield significant consumer buying behaviour in terms of purchase patterns, promotional pricing though relevant, has shown little significance in swinging customers' desire to buy particular products and or services they intended to buy at the time. Indeed, other fundamental things to observe include the equilibrium between pricing strategies and consumers

characteristics as presented in this study's theoretical frameworks. It is therefore apparent that beyond the influence of pricing strategy, other internal and external factors that include age, convenience, and family, among others.

6.7 The Main Lessons Emerging from the Research (Contribution of the Study to the Area of Research)

There are several other studies that have been conducted to establish the impact as well as correlational dynamics between pricing strategy and consumers' purchase behaviours. While most of these studies have concentrated on a number of large shops and shopping complexes, little research has been done on fuel servicing stations. Therefore, this study, a case study of Euro Garage, is a significant contribution to the body of knowledge in this research area of pricing and consumer behaviour. Furthermore, while this study corroborates existing scholars' position that consumers are price-conscious, however, the study discovered and argued that this did not mean they were always going to buy only low-priced products.

The study's result revealed that while pricing models are important, consumers were also willing to pay a little extra for convenience; this, for instance, is provided within the business premises of Euro Garage. Hence, the study further contributes to the body of knowledge in this regard. While other extant research has preponderantly hinged consumer buying behaviour on pricing strategies, this study has revealed that convenience is as important to a significant number of customers as did pricing.

Another important aspect that was discovered and which forms a contribution of this study to knowledge is the effect of the family on the purchase of goods as well as the price of goods. The

pricing strategy influenced how most customers in this category bought products in the store, and importantly also is the fact that this study revalidates existing literature that the bundle pricing worked well for younger, adult shoppers as compared to older shoppers.

6.8 Limitation of the Research and Recommendation for Further Research

The current study recognises that it is limited in a number of areas.

The study was limited in scope as it focused on just one branch of the over 300 Euro Garage branches all across the UK. Although this was a branch that was strategic in location, thus attracting a lot of traffic, it is suggested that further research cover more outlets and perhaps add a few other outlets not owned by the Euro Garage.

The study's sole focus was on pricing and how it impacted consumer behaviour. Future research should include the variables of location, convenience, store design and/or shop services and how these influence how the consumers buy at fuel station convenience stores for a more robust presentation.

Despite the advantages of using convenience sampling, especially when the population is large and randomisation is almost impossible (Etiken et al., 2015), the sampling method is often considered limiting, having selection bias, being non-representative (Malhotra and Birks, 2006) and lacking some clear generalizability (Jager et al., 2017). However, this sampling method was adopted in this study as it was efficient, less time consuming and affordable for the researcher. Future studies should consider opting for more random sampling techniques that could yield results that can be easily generalised.

Also, the demographic variables of gender, education levels and employment were not included to be tested in this study. Further research can therefore take into consideration the variation of consumer behaviour in terms of these demographics to pricing strategy.

6.9 Managerial Implication (Contribution to Management and the Manager)

Marketing managers at Euro Garage can use the findings in this study to re-evaluate their pricing strategies and position them to be favourable to as much customer demography as they can cover for effective sales and profit.

Store managers can routinely engage in surveys and interviews with their customers and juxtapose those findings with the observations they have made so that they are better informed when making decisions for the success and profitability of their firms.

The results of the study largely favour low pricing and bundle pricing. Therefore, the management and managers of Euro Garage and other convenience-type fuel stations should explore the benefit of this strategy to improve their business loyalty as well as profitability.

In order to improve patronage, the study result shows that Euro Garage management and managers should create a feedback mechanism that will give consumers the opportunity to contribute to improving the kind of pricing strategy that will work better for both the consumers and Euro Garage.

From this study's results, consumer behaviour in response to pricing shows considerable variation in demographic dynamics. Therefore, Euro Garage management and marketing managers can factor in these variables when deciding the kind of pricing to adopt within a specific location and time. Because the significance of taking into consideration the demographic variables of age, income level and household of their customers when designing a strategy aimed at bringing in better sales, creating loyalty and encouraging repeat business. And profitability can not be overemphasised.

6.10 Recommendations

6.10.1 Recommendations for Possible Improvement

Based on the findings in this study, the following recommendations may be considered valuable to the Euro Garage as a store and business, as it aims at profitability and success in the petrol retailing industry.

1. To maximally attain the goal(s) for which the store implements its pricing strategies, Euro Garage managers should employ the everyday low pricing strategy with some caution. While implementing low prices, they should target their younger buyers more.
2. Promos excite customers; however, this strategy should be implemented infrequently and when thought most necessary within the store.
3. Bundle Pricing seemed to work a lot better for the Euro Garage customers. It is expected that the store managers will capitalise on this and research new and innovative ways to present this

bundle offers to the customers that will attract them more. Nonetheless, they should target their younger buyers more as this group of customers showed the most interest.

4. Euro Garage store managers should realise that most of their customers compare the prices of products in the store before they buy, especially those with increasing households. A majority of their consumers are also price-conscious when buying fuel and convenience products. They also chose their supermarket based on the stability of its prices. Most considered their financial condition and social class during shopping. However, they did not hesitate to pay a little more just for convenience purposes. At this point, store managers must strike a balance between low prices and higher prices in their stores. Mid-range pricing for products will see to profitability in the store. In other words, products should not be too low priced, and neither should they be too high priced. And where necessary, for products that offer premium benefits or that are scarce to find, managers should not shy away from pricing them a little higher. The majority of customers were not always willing to spend more time whenever they visited a supermarket with frequent offers, though, and only a slight majority indicated that they would shop at any time of the month because the prices were stable. Therefore, Euro Garage managers must, at this point, realise they have time-sensitive customers. They should therefore stock on products that meet immediate basic needs. Also, they should ensure that prices in their stores are stable for the time as this enhances patronage.

5. Consumers who were a little older (perhaps 40 and above), and those with more family members in their household, had their buying behaviour influenced by family. Dedicating an entire section of the store to primarily household items may bring in more revenue for the business. Euro Garage managers may therefore want to consider such an option.

6. As the age of customers who came to Euro Garage increased, the influence of branded products on their buying behaviour decreased. Euro Garage should therefore target their younger and more income-stable consumers with the major branded products in the store. Younger and adult working customers, perhaps between ages 25 to about 45, will associate with branded products either as a status symbol or as a name they have grown to trust and become loyal to. Older customers would simply seek goods that are worth the price and deliver on meeting their needs optimally.

7. In all, managers should never base their pricing decisions on intuition or assumptions by assuming they know what the customers seek or want. Rather they should carry out strategic marketing surveys and customer research exercises in order to use those findings as a guide during pricing decision processes.

REFERENCES AND BIBLIOGRAPHY

- Abu Auf .M. A., Meddour. H., Saoula .O., Majid, A. H. A (2018) Consumer Buying Behaviour: The Role of Price, Motivation, Culture Importance and Religious Orientation. *Journal of Business and Retail Management Research (JBRMR)*. Vol.12, Issue 4.
- Adams, K. and Lawrence, E. (2015). *Research methods, statistics, and applications*. London: Sage.
- Added Benefits of Convenience stores in fuel stations (2017). Televisory. Retrieved from <https://www.televisory.com/blogs/-/blogs/added-benefits-of-convenience-stores-in-fuel-stations>
- Ade Bilau, A., Witt, E. and Lill, I. (2018). *Research methodology for the development of a framework for managing post-disaster housing reconstruction*. *Procedia Engineering*, 212, pp.598-605.
- Adegboye .A. (2017) The Consumption-Oriented Capital Asset Pricing Model in the Nigerian Stock Exchange. *CBN Journal of Applied Statistics*. Vol. 8, No. 2 December, 2017.
- Agarwal .A., Chetty .P. (2019) Use of Hawkins Stern's Impulse Buying Theory (1962) in Online Shopping. Retrieved from:
- Ajzen, I., 1985. From intentions to actions: A theory of planned Behaviour. In *Action control* (pp. 11-39). Springer, Berlin, Heidelberg.
- Ajzen, I., 1991. The theory of planned Behaviour. *Organizational Behaviour and human decision processes*, 50(2), pp.179-211.
- Ajzen, I., 2005. *Attitudes, personality, and Behaviour*. McGraw-Hill Education (UK).
- Ajzen, I., 2011. The theory of planned behaviour: reactions and reflections.
- Albari; Safitri, I. (2018) The Influence of Product Price on Consumers' Purchasing Decisions. *Review of Integrative Business and Economics Research*. Vol.7, Supplementary Issue 2.

- Al-Salamin, H., Al-Hassan, E. (2016) The Impact of Pricing on Consumer Buying Behaviour in Saudi Arabia: Al-Hassa Case Study. *European Journal of Business and Management*. Vol.8, No.12.
- Al-Swidi, A., Mohammed Rafiul Huque, S., Haroon Hafeez, M. and Noor Mohd Shariff, M. (2014). The role of subjective norms in theory of planned Behaviour in the context of organic food consumption. *British Food Journal*, 116(10), pp.1561-1580.
- Alvi, M.H., Ikram, M., Mieza, M.H. and Khan, M.M.Q. (2016) The Perception of People regarding Selection of Petrol Pump in Karachi. *Imperial Journal of Interdisciplinary Research*, Vol. 2(7), pp.3080-382.
- Andersone, I. and Gaile-Sarkane, E. (2008) Influence of factors on consumer behaviour, in *The 5th International Scientific Conference "Business and Management 2008"*. Vilnius, Lithuania, May 16 17. Selected papers. Vilnius: Technika, 246–252.
- Andersone, I. and Gaile-Sarkane, E. (2008) Influence of factors on consumer behaviour, in *The 5th International Scientific Conference "Business and Management 2008"*. Vilnius, Lithuania, May 16 17. Selected papers. Vilnius: Technika, 246–252.
- Antonides, G. and Raaij, W. (1998). *Consumer behaviour*. Chichester: Wiley.
- Ardhanari, M., Hadiwidjojo, D., Rahayu, M. and Rohman, F. (2013). Consumer Behaviour In Selecting Retail Format: The Perspective Of Theory Of Planned Behaviour. *IOSR Journal of Business and Management*, 7(5), pp.17-23.
- Arksey, H. and Knight, P. (1999). *Interviewing for social scientists*. London: Sage Publications.
- Aydinli .A., Bertini . M., Lambrecht .A. (2014) Price Promotion for Emotional Impact. *Journal of Marketing*. Vol. 78 (July, 2014): 80-96.

Babbie, E. (2008). *The basics of social research*. 13th ed. Belmont, CA: Wadsworth, Cengage Learning.

Bailey, J.F. (2011) *Customer buying Behaviour at selected petroleum shops in Cape Town*. CAPE PENINSULA UNIVERSITY OF TECHNOLOGY.

Bandura, A., 1986. Social foundations of thought and action. *Englewood Cliffs, NJ, 1986*.

Banton, C. (2020, November 28) Theory of Price. Investopedia. Retrieved from:

Barbour, R.S. (2008). *Introducing Qualitative Research*, London: Sage.

Barmola, K., Srivastava, S.K (2010) The Role of Consumer Behaviour in Present Marketing Management Scenario. *Productivity*. 2010: 51(3), pp 268 – 275.

Barnett, V. (2002) *Sample Survey Principles and Methods* (3rd edn). Chichester: Wiley.

Basingstoke, E. (2008, December 18) The way the brain buys. Retailers are making breakthroughs in understanding their customer's minds. Here is what they know about you. *The Economist*. (Online). Available at: <http://www.economist.com/node/12792420> (Accessed on 4 February 2018).

Baxter, P. and Jack, S., 2008. Qualitative case study methodology: Study design and implementation for novice researchers. *The qualitative report*, 13(4), pp.544-559.

Beck, C.T. and Gable, R.K., 2012. A mixed methods study of secondary traumatic stress in labor and delivery nurses. *Journal of Obstetric, Gynecologic & Neonatal Nursing*, 41(6), pp.747-760.

Beck, C.T. and Gable, R.K., 2012. A mixed methods study of secondary traumatic stress in labor and delivery nurses. *Journal of Obstetric, Gynecologic & Neonatal Nursing*, 41(6), pp.747-760.

Benn, Y., Webb, T.L., Chang, B.P.I., and Reidy, J. (2015). What information do consumers consider, and how do they look for it, when shopping for groceries online? ELSEVIER, Science direct. *Appetite*, Vol. 89, pp.265-273. (Online). Available at: <https://ac.els->

cdn.com/S0195666315000422/1-s2.0-S0195666315000422-main.pdf?_tid=6676e6e6-0440-44dd-a3c8-d12a7772d282&acdnat=1521318983_53a1c1cf469af4c027ad392a712c8d68

(Accessed on 5 March 2018).

Benoit, S., Kienzler, M., Kowalkowski, .C. (2020) Intuitive Pricing by independent Store Managers: Challenging Beliefs and Practices. *Journal of Business Research. Vol 115, Pages 70-84*

Bhatti .A. (2018) Promotion and Price Discount Effect on Consumer Purchase Intention with the Moderating Role of Social Media in Pakistan. *Science Arena Publication. International Journal of Business Management. ISSN: 2520-5943. Vol. 3(4): 50-58.*

Bianchi, C. and Andrews, L. (2012) Risk, trust, and consumer online purchasing behaviour: a Chilean perspective. *International Marketing Review*, Vol. 29(3), pp. 253-275.

Blackwell, D. R., Miniard, P. W. and Engel, J. F. (2001) *Consumer Behaviour*, Forth Worth, Philadelphia: Harcourt College Publishers.

Blackwell, D. R., Miniard, P. W. and Engel, J. F. (2001) *Consumer Behaviour*, Forth Worth, Philadelphia: Harcourt College Publishers.

Blackwell, R., D'Souza, C., Taghian, M., Miniard, P. & Engel, J. (2006) *Consumer Behaviour*, 1st edn. Thompson Learning Publishers, South Melbourne.

Blackwell, R., Miniard, P. and Engel, J. (2006) “*Consumer Behaviour*”, Mason: Thompson

Blaikie, N. (2010) *Designing Social Research*. (2nd edn). Cambridge: Polity.

Blaxter, L., Hughes, C. and Tight, M. (2006). *How to research*. 3rd ed. Milton Keynes: Open University Press.

Blumberg,B., Cooper, D.R. and Schindler, P.S.(2008) *Business Research Methods*. Maidenhead: MxGraw-Hill Education.

- Boyle, J.S., 1994. Styles of ethnography. *Critical issues in qualitative research methods*, 2, pp.159-85.
- Brajesh (2012, November 11). Consumer Buying Behaviour. *Iitmaverick*. (Online). Available at: <https://iitmaverick.wordpress.com/2012/11/11/consumer-buying-Behaviour-2/> (Accessed on 4 March 2018).
- Brannen, J., 2005. Mixed methods research: A discussion paper.
- Brannen, J., 2005. Mixed methods research: A discussion paper.
- Braun-La Tour, K., La Tour, M., Pickrell, J., Loftus, E. (2004). How and when advertising can influence memory for consumer experience. *Journal of Advertising; Winter, Vol.33* (4), p. 7.
- Bray, J. (2008) *Consumer Behaviour theory: Approaches and Models*. (Online). Available at: [http://eprints.bournemouth.ac.uk/10107/1/Consumer Behaviour Theory - Approaches %26 Models.pdf](http://eprints.bournemouth.ac.uk/10107/1/Consumer_Behaviour_Theory_-_Approaches_%26_Models.pdf) (Accessed on 10 February 2018).
- Brinkmann, S. (2013). *Qualitative interviewing*. New York: Oxford University Press.
- Bryman, A. (1989) *Research Methods and Organisation studies*. London: Unwin Hyman.
- Bryman, A. (2016). *Social research methods*. Oxford: Oxford University Press.
- Bryman, A., & Bell, E. (2011). *Business Research Methods* (3rd ed.). Oxford: Oxford University Press Inc.
- Bryman, A., 2006. Integrating quantitative and qualitative research: how is it done?. *Qualitative research*, 6(1), pp.97-113.
- Buckley, P., Cross, A. and De Mattos, C. (2015). The principle of congruity in the analysis of international business cooperation. *International Business Review*, 24(6), pp.1048-1060.
- Burnard, P., Gill. P., Stewart .K., Treasure, E., Chadwick, B. (2008) Analysing and Presenting Qualitative Data. *British Dental Journal*, 204, 42-432 (2008).

Burns, D., 2007. *Systemic action research: A strategy for whole system change*. Policy Press.

Burrell, G. and Morgan, G., 2017. *Sociological paradigms and organisational analysis: Elements of the sociology of corporate life*. Routledge.

C.L., Chen, Z.X., Chan, A.K.K. and Chen, Z. (2000) "The influence of hedonic value on consumer behaviours: an empirical investigation in China", *Journal of Global Marketing*, Vol. 14(1/2), pp. 169-86.

Caramia .N. (2018) *Self Concept in Consumer Behaviour: A Psychoanalytic Investigation* Working Paper Series.

Carroll, L. and Rothe, J. (2010). Levels of Reconstruction as Complementarity in Mixed Methods Research: A Social Theory-Based Conceptual Framework for Integrating Qualitative and Quantitative Research. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 7(9), pp.3478-3488.

Carroll, L. and Rothe, J. (2010). Levels of Reconstruction as Complementarity in Mixed Methods Research: A Social Theory-Based Conceptual Framework for Integrating Qualitative and Quantitative Research. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 7(9), pp.3478-3488.

Carson, D., Gilmore, A., Perry, C., and Gronhaug, K. (2001). *Qualitative Marketing Research*. London: Sage.

Cassell, C. and Symon, G. eds., 2004. *Essential guide to qualitative methods in organizational research*. London: Sage.

Cavana, R.Y., Delahaye, B.L. and Sekaran, U., 2001. *Applied business research: Qualitative and quantitative methods*. John Wiley & Sons Australia.

- Chang, C. and Tu, C. (2005) "Exploring Store Image, Customer Satisfaction and Customer Loyalty Relationship: Evidence from Taiwanese Hypermarket Industry", *The Journal of American Academy of Business*, Cambridge, Vol. 7(2), pp. 197-202.
- Chang, M.K., 1998. Predicting unethical Behaviour: a comparison of the theory of reasoned action and the theory of planned Behaviour. *Journal of business ethics*, 17(16), pp.1825-1834.
- Charmaz, K. (2014). *Constructing grounded theory*. 2nd ed. London: Sage.
- Chen, C.L., Chen, Z.X., Chan, A.K.K. and Chen, Z. (2000) "The influence of hedonic value on consumer behaviour: an empirical investigation in China", *Journal of Global Marketing*, Vol. 14(1/2), pp. 169-86.
- Chen, J., Sousa, C.M.P. & He, X. (2016) The determinants of export performance: a review of the literature 2006-2014. *International Marketing Review*, 33 (5), pp.626–670.
- Cherry, K. (2018, February 10). Instrumental conditioning: Another Term for Operant Conditioning. *Verywell Mind*. (Online). Available at: <https://www.verywellmind.com/what-is-instrumental-conditioning-2795408> (Accessed on 9 March 2018).
- Churchill, G. (2001). *Marketing Research:Methodological Foundations* (7th ed.). Fort Worth: Dryden press.
- Churchill, G. and Peter, J. (1998). *Marketing*. Boston: Irwin/McGraw-Hill.
- Claessens .M. (2015) "The Buyer Black Box – Buyer’s Characteristics – Factors Influencing The Consumer Buying Behaviour". *Marketing-Insider*.
- Clarke, V. & Braun, V. (2012) Teaching thematic analysis: Overcoming challenges and developing strategies for effective learning. *The Psychologist*, 26(2), 120-123.
- Coffey, A. and Atkinson, P. (1996) *Making sense of qualitative data: Complementary research strategies*. Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage.

Cohen, L., Manion, L. and Morrison, K. (2007). *Research methods in education 6th ed.* London: Routledge.

Cohen, S. A., Prayag, G. And Moital, M. (2014) Consumer behaviour in tourism: Concepts, influences and opportunities, *Current Issues in Tourism*, Vol. 17(10), pp. 872-909. (Online). Available at: <http://www.tandfonline.com/doi/pdf/10.1080/13683500.2013.850064> (Accessed on 3 February 2018).

Collins, H. (2010) “Creative Research: The Theory and Practice of Research for the Creative Industries” AVA Publications

Collins, H. (2010) “Creative Research: The Theory and Practice of Research for the Creative Industries” AVA Publications

Collis, J. and Hussey, R. (2009). *Business research*. Basingstoke, Hampshire [UK]: Palgrave Macmillan.

Conner, M. and Armitage, C.J., 1998. Extending the theory of planned Behaviour: A review and avenues for further research. *Journal of applied social psychology*, 28(15), pp.1429-1464.

Constantinides, E., 2006. The marketing mix revisited: towards the 21st century marketing. *Journal of marketing management*, 22(3-4), pp.407-438.

Constantinides, E., 2006. The marketing mix revisited: towards the 21st century marketing. *Journal of marketing management*, 22(3-4), pp.407-438.

Consumer Behaviour Theories: Pavlovian Theory (2018). Husson University Online. Retrieved from

Consumer Behaviour. (2018, November). *BusinessTeacher.org*. Retrieved from

Cooper, C., Shepherd, R. and Westlake, J. (1996) *Educating the Educators: A Manual of Tourism and Hospitality Education*, Madrid, WTO.

Cooper, D. and Schindler, P. (1998) *Business research methods*. 6th ed. Boston: Irwin/McGraw Hill.

Corbin, J and Strauss, A (2008) *Basics of Qualitative Research* 3rd edn. London: Sage.

Corbin, J. and Strauss, A., 2008. *Basics of qualitative research: Techniques and procedures for developing grounded theory*.

Corbin, J. and Strauss, A., 2008. *Basics of qualitative research: Techniques and procedures for developing grounded theory* (3rd edition). CA: Sage Publications.

Creswell . J. W. (2003) *Research Design: Qualitative, Quantitative and Mixed Methods Approaches*. *Thousands Oaks CA: Sage Publication*.

Creswell, J. (2014). *Research design*. 4th ed. Thousand Oaks [etc.]: Sage.

Creswell, J. and J. David Creswell. (2018). *Research design*. London: SAGE.

Creswell, J. and Plano Clark, V. (2011). *Designing and conducting mixed methods research*. 2nd ed. London: Sage.

Creswell, J. and Plano Clark, V. (2018). *Designing and conducting mixed methods research*. 3rd ed. London: Sage.

Creswell, J.W., Plano Clark, V.L., Gutmann, M.L. and Hanson, W.E., 2003. Advanced mixed methods research designs. *Handbook of mixed methods in social and Behavioural research*, 209, p.240.

Creswell, J.W., Plano Clark, V.L., Gutmann, M.L. and Hanson, W.E., 2003. Advanced mixed methods research designs. *Handbook of mixed methods in social and Behavioural research*, 209, p.240.

Cronholm, S. and Hjalmarsson, A. (2011) "Experiences from Sequential Use of Mixed Methods", *The Electronic Journal of Business Research Methods*", Vol 9, No. 2, pp 87-95.

- Crotty, M. (1998) *The Foundation of Social Research*. London: Sage.
- Crouch, S. and Housden, M. (2000). *Marketing research for managers*. 2nd ed. Oxford: Butterworth-Heinemann.
- Crowther, D. and Lancaster, G. (2009). *Research methods*. 2nd ed. Oxford, Angl.: Butterworth-Heinemann.
- Cunliffe, A. (2010). Retelling Tales of the Field. *Organizational Research Methods*, 13(2), pp.224-239.
- Curran, J. and Blackburn, R. A. (2001) *Researching the Small Enterprise*. London: Sage.
- Dahlén, M., Granlund, A., Grenros, M. (2009).The consumer-perceived value of non-traditional media: effects of brand reputation, appropriateness and expense. *Journal of Consumer Marketing*, Vol. 26(3), pp. 155-163.
- Danziger .S., Hadar .L., Morwitz .V. G. (2014) Retailer Pricing Strategy and Consumer Choice under Price Uncertainty. *Journal of Consumer Research*. Vol. 41, Issue 3, pp: 761-774.
- Dapkevicius, A. and Melnikas, B. (2009) Influence of price and quality to customer satisfaction: Neuromarketing approach. *Mokslas: LietuvosAteitis*, Vol.1 (3), pp.17-20. (Online). Available at: <https://pdfs.semanticscholar.org/ea1a/941a7203c92f15737a8dcf4d785badccdc48.pdf> (Accessed on 5 February 2018).
- Dattalo, C. (2010) *strategies to Approximate Random Sampling and Assignment*. New York: Oxford University Press.
- David, M. and Sutton, C. (2011). *Social research : an introduction*. 2nd ed. London: Sage.
- De Toni .D., Milan G. B., Saciloto B. E., Larentis .F. (2025) Pricing Strategies and Levels and their Impact on Corporate Profitability. *Revista de Administracao*. Vol. 52, Issue 2, April-June 2017, pp 120-133).

- Denscombe, M. (2011). *The good research guide*. 4th ed. Maidenhead, England: McGraw-Hill/Open University Press.
- Denzin, N.K. and Lincoln, Y.S. (2005) *The Sage Handbook of Qualitative Research* (3rd edn). London: Sage.
- Denzin, N.K. and Lincoln, Y.S. (2005) *The Sage Handbook of Qualitative Research*. London: Sage.
- DePoy, E. and Gitlin, L.N., 2015. *Introduction to Research-E-Book: Understanding and Applying Multiple Strategies*. Elsevier Health Sciences.
- Dibb, S., Simkin, L., M.Pride, W. and Ferrell, O. (2012). *Marketing concepts and strategies*. 6th ed. Andover: Cengage Learning.
- Dibb, S., Simkin, L., M.Pride, W. and Ferrell, O. (2012). *Marketing concepts and strategies*. 6th ed. Andover: Cengage Learning.
- Dogra, B. and Ghuman, K. (2010). *Rural marketing*. New Delhi: Tata McGraw Hill.
- Dolgui, A., Proth, J. M (2010) Pricing Strategies and Models. *Annual Reviews in Control*. 34 (1): 101-110.
- Du Frene, D. D., Engelland, B. T., Lehman, C. M. and Pearson, R. A. (2005) "Changes in Consumer Attitudes Resulting from Participation in a Permission E-Mail Campaign", *Journal of Current Issues and Research in Advertising*, Vol. 27(1), pp. 65-77.
- Durmaz, Y. (2014) The Influence of Cultural factors on consumer buying behaviour and an application in Turkey. *Global Journal of Management and Business research: E-Marketing*, Vol 14(1), pp.36-44. (Online). Available at: https://globaljournals.org/GJMBR_Volume14/4-The-Influence-of-Cultural-Factors-on.pdf (Accessed on 3 February 2018).

- Dworkin, S. L (2012) Sample Size Policy for Qualitative Studies using In-depth Interviews. *Archives of Sexual Behaviour*, 41, 1399-9320. 2012.
- Eaden. J., Mayberry .M. K, Mayberry, J. F. (1999) Research Methods: Questionnaires: The use and abuse of social survey methods in medical research. *Review. Postgraduate Medical Journal*. Vol.75, Issue 885.
- Easterby-Smith, M., Thorpe, R. and Jackson, P. (2013). *Management research*. 4th ed. London: SAGE.
- Easterby-Smith, M., Thorpe, R. and Lowe, A. (2002) *Management Research: An Introduction*, 2nd ed. London: Sage Publications
- Eastterby-Smith,M., Thorpe, R. and Lowe, A (2002) *Management Research: An Introduction*, 2nd edn. London: Sage.
- Edwards, W., 1954. The theory of decision making. *Psychological bulletin*, 51(4), p.380.
- Egan, J., 2007. *Marketing communications*. Cengage Learning EMEA.
- Eisenhardt, K.M., 1989. Building theories from case study research. *Academy of management review*, 14(4), pp.532-550.
- Elimimian .J. U. (2007) Psychoanalysis of Ethnic Consumers and Similarities of Consumption. *Innovative Marketing*. Vol. 3. Issue 3. (2007).
- Ellickson .P., Misra . S. (2006) Supermarket Pricing Strategies. *Marketing Science*. 27(5): 811-828.
- Engel, J.F., Blackwell, R.D. and Miniard, P.W. (1995), *Consumer Behaviour*, Dryden Press, New York, NY.
- Enis, B. (1974). *Marketing principles*. Taipei: Mei Ya Publications.

Erasmus, A., Boshoff, E. and Rousseau, G. (2001). Consumer decision-making models within the discipline of consumer science: a critical approach. *Journal of Family Ecology and Consumer Sciences /Tydskrif vir Gesinsekologie en Verbruikerswetenskappe*, 29(1).

Etherington, K. (2004). *Becoming a reflexive researcher*. London: Jessica Kingsley.

Etikan, I., Musa S. A. Alkassin, R. S . (2015) Comparison of Convenience Sampling and Purposive Sampling. *American Journal of Theoretical and Applied Statistics*. 5(1): 1 – 4.

Everyday Low Pricing (n.d) Corporate Finance Institute. Retrieved from

Everyday Low Pricing May Not Be The Best Strategy for Supermarkets (2011, December 17). Stanford Graduate School of Business. Retrieved from

Fan. X., Qian, Y., Huang .P. (2012) Factors Influencing Consumer Behaviour towards Store Brand: A Meta-analysis. *International Journal of Market Research*.

Fang .Y., Sun .L., Gao .Y. (2017) Bundle-Pricing Decision Model for Multiple Products. *Procedia Computer Science*. Vol. 112, 2017, pp: 2147-2154.

Farrokhi, F., Mahmoudi-Hamidabad, .A. (2012) Rethinking Convenience Sampling: Defining Quality Criteria. *Theory and Practice in Language Studies*. Vol. 2, No. 4, pp 784-792. *Academy Publisher* 2012.

Fassnacht .M., Husseini .S. E. (2013) EDLP versus Hi-Lo Pricing Strategies in Retailing- A state of the art article. *Journal of Business Economics*. 83(3).

Felista, M. F (2014) The Effect of Promotional Pricing on Durban University of Technology Students staying in institution residences. (Dissertations) Durban University of Technology.

Fiengenbaum, A. and Thomas, H. (2004) Strategic risk and competitive advantage: An integrative perspective. *European Management Review*, Vol.1 (1), pp. 84-95.

Fielding, K.S., McDonald, R. and Louis, W.R., 2008. Theory of planned behaviour, identity and intentions to engage in environmental activism. *Journal of environmental psychology*, 28(4), pp.318-326.

Filho .F. F., Conceicao, O. A. C. 92005) The Concept of Uncertainty in Post-Keynesian Theory and in Institutional Economics. *Journal of Economic Issues. Vol 39, Issue 3, pp: 579-594.*

Fishbein, M. (1980), "A theory of reasoned action: some application and implications", Nebraska Symposium on Motivation, University of Nebraska Press, Lincoln, NE, Vol. 27, pp. 65-116

Fishbein, M. A., & Ajzen, I. (1975). *Belief, attitude, intention and Behaviour: An introduction to theory and research*. Reading, MA: Addison-Wesley.

Flick, U. (2011). *Introducing research methodology*. London: SAGE Publications Ltd.

Frank, B., Enkawa, T. And Schvaneveldt, S.J. (2015) The role of individualism vs. Collectivism in the formation of repurchase intent: A cross-industry comparison of the effects of cultural and personal values. ELSEVIER. Science-direct. *Journal of Economic Psychology*, Vol 51, pp.261-278. (Online). Available at: https://ac.els-cdn.com/S0167487015001063/1-s2.0-S0167487015001063-main.pdf?_tid=7df95064-10f7-11e8-82ae-00000aab0f01&acdnt=1518551759_7d0077d71fd11850145fef89ec9e2801 (Accessed on 4 February 2018).

Friedman, M., 2007. *Price theory*. Transaction Publishers.

Furajji, F., Łatuszyńska, M. and Wawrzyniak, A., 2012. An empirical study of the factors influencing consumer behaviour in the electric appliances market.

Gajjar, D.N.B. (2013) Factors Affecting Consumer Behaviour. *International Journal of Research in Humanities and Social Sciences*. Vol. 1(2). Pp.-10-15. (Online). Available at:

http://www.raijmr.com/wp-content/uploads/2017/11/IJRHS_2013_vol01_issue_02_02.pdf

(Accessed on 3 February 2018).

Gardner, D., Vogt, W. and Haeffele, L. (2012). *When to Use What Research Design*. New York: Guilford Publications.

Gawel, J.E., 1996. Herzberg's theory of motivation and Maslow's hierarchy of needs. *Practical Assessment, Research, and Evaluation*, 5(1), p.11.

Gerring, John . 2007. *Case Study Research: Principles and Practices*. Cambridge, UK: Cambridge University Press.

Ghauri, R. & Gronhaug, K. (2005) *Research methods in business studies: a practical guide*. FT/Prentice Hall

Gilbert, G. (2008). *Researching social life*. 3rd ed. London: SAGE.

Gill, J. and Johnson, P. (2002). *Research methods for managers*. 3rd ed. London: Sage.

Gilles .C., Leroy, S. (1991) On The Arbitrage Pricing Theory. *Economic Theory*. 1(3): 213-29

Gillham, B. (2002). *The research interview*. London: Continuum.

Given, L.M. ed., 2008. *The Sage encyclopedia of qualitative research methods*. Sage publications.

Glaser, B., & Strauss, A. (1967) *The discovery of grounded theory: Strategies of qualitative research*. London: Wiedenfeld and Nicholson.

Gliem, J. A., Gliem, R.R. (2003) Calculating, Interpreting, and Reporting Cronbach's Alpha Reliability Coefficient for Likert-Tyoe Scales. *Gliem & Gliem.pdf*.

Glynn, M. and Woodside, A. (2009). *Business-to-business brand management*. Bingley: Emerald JAI.

Godin, G. and Kok, G., 1996. The theory of planned Behaviour: a review of its applications to health-related Behaviours. *American journal of health promotion*, 11(2), pp.87-98.

- Golicic, S.L. and Davis, D.F. (2012) "Implementing Mixed Methods Research in Supply Chain Management", *International Journal of Physical Distribution & Logistics Management*, Vol 42, No. 8/9, pp 726-741.
- Gomes, A. M, (2018) Influencing Factors of Consumer Behaviour in Retail Shops. Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=3151879>.
- Goodwin, N., Nelso, J.A., Ackerman, F. and Weisskopf, T. (2008). *Consumption and the consumer society*. Global Development and Environment Institute, Tufts University. (Online). Available at: http://www.ase.tufts.edu/gdae/education_materials/modules/Consumption_and_the_Consumer_Society.pdf (Accessed on 4 March 2018).
- Gordon, W. & Langmaid, R. (1990) *Qualitative Market Research. A Practitioner's and Buyer's Guide*. Aldershot: Gower.
- Gough, D., Oliver, S. and Thomas, J. (2017). *An introduction to systematic reviews*. 2nd ed. London [etc.]: SAGE.
- Gough, D., Oliver, S. and Thomas, J. (2017). *An introduction to systematic reviews*. 2nd ed. London [etc.]: SAGE.
- Govindarajan, M. (2009). *Marketing management*. New Delhi, II.: Prentice-Hall.
- Graetz, K.A. (2018). The Psychology of Learning environments. Chapter 6. Winona State University. *Educause*. (Online). Available at: <https://www.educause.edu/research-and-publications/books/learning-spaces/chapter-6-psychology-learning-environments> (Accessed on 4 March 2018).
- Gray, D. (2018). *Doing research in the real world*. 4th ed. London: SAGE Publications Ltd.
- Greenfield, T. (2002). *Research methods for postgraduates*. 2nd ed. London: Arnold.

- Gu .S., Wu .Y. (2019) Using the Theory of Planned Behaviour to Explain Customers' Online Purchase Intention. *World Scientific Research Journal*. Vol. 5., Issue 9. 2019.
- Guba, E.G. & Lincoln, Y.S. (2005). Paradigmatic controversies, contradictions, and emerging confluences.
- Guba, E.G. and Lincoln, Y.S. (1994). 'Competing paradigms in qualitative research' in *Handbook of Qualitative Research*, eds. N.K. Denzin and Y.S. Lincoln, Sage, Thousand Oaks, pp.105-117.
- Guerguis, A. (2018) The Impact of Static and Dynamic Identities on Consumer Behaviour. 19.13140/RG.2.2.12307.84001.
- Günther, A. (2012). *Entrepreneurial strategies of professional service firms*. Köln: Kölner Wiss.-Verl.
- Günther, A. (2012). *Entrepreneurial strategies of professional service firms*. Köln: Kölner Wiss.-Verl.
- Gupta, S., Cooper, L. G., (1992) The Discounting of Discounts and Promotion Thresholds. *Journal of Consumer Research*. Vol.19.
- Ha, H., Janda. S. and Muthaly, S., (2010). "Development of brand equity: evaluation of four alternative models", *Service Industries Journal*, 30(6), pp. 911-928
- Hackl, P., Scharitzer, D. and Zuba, R. (2000) "Customer Satisfaction in the Austrian Food Retail Market", *Total Qual. Manage*, Vol. 11(7), pp. 999-1006.
- Hair, J., Money, A., Page, M. and Samouel, P. (2007). *Research methods for business*. Chichester: Wiley and Sons.
- Hakim, C. (2000). *Research design*. 2nd ed. London: Routledge.

- Hameed, I., Soomro, Y.A. & Hameed, I. (2012) Role of Volatile Pricing Strategies on Consumer Buying Behaviour. *European journal of economics, finance, and administrative sciences*, (53), pp.1450–2275.
- Han, H. and Kim, Y., 2010. An investigation of green hotel customers' decision formation: Developing an extended model of the theory of planned Behaviour. *International Journal of Hospitality Management*, 29(4), pp.659-668.
- Harrison III, R.L. (2013) "Using Mixed Methods Designs in the Journal of Business Research, 1990-2010. *Journal of Business Research*, 66, pp. 2153-2162.
- Harrison III, R.L., 2013. Using mixed methods designs in the Journal of Business Research, 1990–2010. *Journal of Business Research*, 66(11), pp.2153-2162.
- Hart, C. (2003) *Doing a literature review: releasing the social science research imagination*. London: Sage Publications
- Hawawini, G., Subramanian, V., and Verdin, P. (2003) Is performance driven by industry - or firm-specific factors? A new look at the evidence. *Strategic Management Journal*, Vol.24, pp. 1-16.
- Hawkins, D. L., Mothersbaugh, D. L. and Best, R. J. (2007) *Consumer Behaviour, Building Marketing Strategy*, McGraw-Hill, New York.
- Hawkins, D.I., Best, R.J. and Coney, K.A. (2003) *Consumer Behaviour: Building Marketing Strategy*. 9th ed. McGraw-Hill Higher Education.
- Herriott, R.E. and Firestone, W.A., 1983. Multisite qualitative policy research: Optimizing description and generalizability. *Educational researcher*, 12(2), pp.14-19.
- Hinterhuber .A. (2008) Customer Value-based pricing Strategies: Why companies resist.” *Journal of Business Strategy*. Pages 41-50. Vol. 29. No.4.

Hirschman, E.C., 1989. Consumer Behaviour theories as heroic quest. *ACR North American Advances*.

Holland, J. (2019). *Navigating Uncertainty: Tourists' Perceptions of Risk in Ocean Cruising* (Doctoral dissertation, University of Brighton).

Hosken .D., Matsa .D., Reiffen .D. (2000) How Do Retailers Adjust Prices? Evidence from Store-Level Data. <https://www.ftc.gov>reports> (pdf).

<http://standford.io/Zolt9P>

<https://businessteacher.org/lectures/marketing/consumer-behaviour/detailed.php>

<https://corporatefinanceinstitute.com/resources/knowledge/economics/edlp/>

<https://courses.lumenlearning.com/boundless-marketing/chapter/introduction-to-price/>

<https://online.husson.edu/consumer-Behaviour-pavlovian-theory/>

<https://restaurantengine.com/important-right-meal-deal/>

<https://wholesalesuiteplugin.com/different-types-pricing-strategies-can-use-wholesale-marketing/>

<https://www.google.com/amp/s/www.wsj.com/amp/articles/price-theory-remains-enduringly-important-11612384709>

<https://www.independent.co.uk/life-style/health-and-families/supermarket-meal-deals-lunch-sugar-content-high-study-wh-smith-boots-tesco-sainsburys-a8029381.html>

<https://www.investopedia.com/terms/t/theory-of-price.asp>

<https://www.pdisoftware.com/blog/inventory-pricing-and-promotion-strategies-for-the-new-convenience-store/>

<https://www.pdisoftware.com/blog/the-price-is-right-strategies-to-price-fuel/>

<https://www.postkeynesian.net/post-keynesian-economics/>

<https://www.projectguru.in/hawkins-sterns-impulse-buying-theory-online-shopping/>

<https://www.rapidretail.co.uk/the-transformation-of-petrol-forecourts/>

<https://www.retail-week.com/retail-voice/the-rise-of-the-forecourt-as-a-convenient-retail-destination/7030723.article?authent=1>

<https://www.talkingretail.com/news/industry-news/forecourt-c-stores-grow-sales-3-8-report-finds-04-03-2020/>

Hu, H. and Jasper, C. R. (2006) "Social Cues in the Store Environment and Their Impact on Store Image", *International Journal of Retail and Distribution Management*, Vol. 34(1), pp. 25-48.

Huang, A., Dawes, J., Lockshin, L. & Greenacre, L. (2017) Consumer response to price changes in higher-priced brands. *Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services*, 39, pp.1–10.

Hummon, N.P. and Doreian, P., 2003. Some dynamics of social balance processes: bringing Heider back into balance theory. *Social Networks*, 25(1), pp.17-49.

Hyde, K.F. (2000) Recognising deductive processes in qualitative research. *Qualitative Market Research: An International Journal*. Vol. 3(2). Pp.82-90

Ihuah, P.W. and Eaton, D., 2013. The pragmatic research approach: a framework for sustainable management of public housing estates in Nigeria. *Journal of US-China Public Administration*, 10(10), pp.933-944.

Introduction to price (n.d) *Lumen Learning*. Retrieved from

Isaac, S. and Michael, W.B. (1995) *Handbook of Research and Evaluation*. San Diego: EdITS.

Ivankova, N.V., Creswell, J.W. and Stick, S.L., 2006. Using mixed-methods sequential explanatory design: From theory to practice. *Field methods*, 18(1), pp.3-20.

Ivankova, N.V., Creswell, J.W. and Stick, S.L., 2006. Using mixed-methods sequential explanatory design: From theory to practice. *Field methods*, 18(1), pp.3-20.

- Iyengar, R., Han, S. and Gupta, S. (2009). Do Friends Influence purchases in a social network? *Harvard business School, Working Paper 09-123*. (Online). Available at: <http://citeseerx.ist.psu.edu/viewdoc/download?doi=10.1.1.259.350&rep=rep1&type=pdf> (Accessed on 5 March 2018).
- J. Leacock, C., Warrican, S. and St. C.Rose, B. (2015). *Research methods for inexperienced researchers*. Kingston: Ian Randle Publishers.
- Jager, J., Putnik, D. L., Bornstein. M. H (2017) More Than Just Convenient: The Scientific Merits of Homogeneous Convenience Samples. *Monogr Doc. Res. Child. Dev. 2017. Jun 82 (2): 13 -30*.
- Jagre, E., Watson, J.J. and Watson, J.G., 2001. Sponsorship and congruity theory: A theoretical framework for explaining consumer attitude and recall of event sponsorship. *ACR North American Advances*.
- Jang, S., Prasad, A. & Ratchford, B.T. (2017) Consumer Search of Multiple Information Sources and its Impact on Consumer Price Satisfaction. *Journal of Interactive Marketing*, 40, pp.24–40.
- Jang, S., Prasad, A. and Ratchford, B.T. (2012) How consumers use product reviews in the purchase decision process. *Marketing Letters*, Vol. 23(3), pp. 825-838.
- Jean .W. A., Yazdanifard .R. (2015) The Review of how Sales Promotion change the Consumer's Perception and their Purchasing Behaviour of a Product. *Global Journal of Management and Business Research and Marketing. Vol. 15, Issue 5, Version 1.0, 2015*.
- Jecheche .P. (n.d) An Empirical Investigation of Arbitrage Pricing Theory: A Case of Zimbabwe. *Journal of Comprehensive Research. Retrieved from www.aabri.com>manuscript (pdf)*
- Jisna, T.K. (2014). Consumer Behaviour Models: An Overview. *Sai Om Journal of Commerce & Management*, vol. 1(5), pp.34-43. (Online). Available at:

<http://citeseerx.ist.psu.edu/viewdoc/download?doi=10.1.1.916.4415&rep=rep1&type=pdf>

(Accessed on 2 March 2018).

Jisna, T.K. (2014). Consumer Behaviour Models: An Overview. *Sai Om Journal of Commerce & Management*, vol. 1(5), pp.34-43. (Online). Available at:

<http://citeseerx.ist.psu.edu/viewdoc/download?doi=10.1.1.916.4415&rep=rep1&type=pdf>

(Accessed on 2 March 2018).

Jobber, D. (2007) *Principles and practice of marketing*. London: McGraw-Hill Education.

Jobber, D. (2016). *Principles and practice of marketing*. London: McGraw-Hill Education.

Jogulu, U. D., Pansiri. J. (2011) Mixed Methods:A Research Design for Management Doctoral Dissertations. *Management Research Review*. Vol. 34, No. 6, pp 687-701.

Johannesson, P. and Perjons, E. (2014). Research Strategies and Methods. *An Introduction to Design Science*, pp.39-73.

Johnson .C.(2020) Inventory, Pricing, and Promotion Strategies for the new Convenience Store. *PDI*. Retrieved from

Johnson, R.B. and Onwuegbuzie, A.J., 2004. Mixed methods research: A research paradigm whose time has come. *Educational researcher*, 33(7), pp.14-26.

Kabir, S. M. S (2016) Sample and Sampling Design. *In Book: Basic Guidelines for Research. An Introductory Approach for All Disciplines (pp.168 – 180)*. Publisher: Book Zone. Bangladesh.

Kakunu, J.K. (2012) *Determinants of consumer preference in choice of petroleum service outlets in Nairobi*. School of Business University of Nairobi.

Kanagal .B. K. (2016). “An Extended Model of Behavioural Process in Consumer Decision Making”. *International Journal of Marketing Studies*: 8(4):87.

Kaplan, A. M., Haenle, M. (2010) Users of the World, Unite! The Challenges and Opportunities of Social Media. *Business Horizons*. Vol. 53, Issue 1, pp 59-68.

Kardes, F. Cline, T. and Cronley, M. (2011). *Consumer behaviour: Science and Practice*. South-Western Cengage Learning.

Keat .O. S. (2009) Factors Influencing Consumer Purchase Intention of Dietary Supplement Products in Penang Island. Thesis.

Keith, R.J. (1960) "The marketing revolution", *Journal of Marketing*, Vol.24, pp. 35-38.

Kelemen, M. and Rumens, N. (2008) *An Introduction to Critical Management Research*. London: Sage.

Keller, K. (2011). *Marketing management*. Harlow: Pearson Education.kuma

Kelly .B., King, H., Chapman .K., Boyland .E., Bauman .A. E., Baur .L. A. (2015) A Hierarchy of Unhealthy Food Promotion Effects: Identifying Methodological Approaches and Knowledge Gaps. *American Journal of Public Health*. 105, no. 4, pp:86-95.

Kent, R. (2007). *Marketing research*. London: Thomson Learning.

Kenton .W. (2019, June 22) Consumption Capital Asset Pricing Model- CCA Definition. Investopedia. Retrieved from: <https://www.investopedia.com/terms/c/ccapm.asp>

Khadwal .P. (2019) Consumer Behaviour: Effect of Branding and Packaging. *International Journal of Scientific Development and Research*. (IJS DR). April 2019, Vol.4, Issue 4,; ISSN: 2455-2631.

Kilbourne, W.E. and Carlson, L. (2008) "The dominant social paradigm, consumption, and environmental attitudes: can macro marketing education help?" *Journal of Macro marketing*, Vol. 28, pp. 106-121.

Kilbourne, W.E., Beckmann, S.C. and Thelen, E. (2002) "The role of the dominant social paradigm in environmental attitudes: a multinational examination", *Journal of Business Research*, Vol. 55, pp. 193-204.

Kim, J., Rasouli, s. and Timmermans, H. J. P. (2017) Social networks, social influence and activity-travel behaviour: a review of models and empirical evidence, *Transport Reviews*, DOI: 10.1080/01441647.2017.1351500. (Online). Available at: <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/pdf/10.1080/01441647.2017.1351500?needAccess=true>

(Accessed on 9 March 2018).

Kirsch, I., Lynn, S, J., Vigorito, M. and Miller, R. R., (2004), "The role of condition in classical and operant conditioning," *Journal of clinical Psychology*, Vol. 64(4), pp. 369-392.

Kothari, C.R., 2004. *Research methodology: Methods and techniques*. New Age International.

Kotler, P. & Armstrong, G. (2009). *Principles Of Marketing*. Pearson Education. 13th ed. New Jersey.

Kotler, P. and Armstrong, G. (2010). *Principles of Marketing*. 13th edn. Pearson Global edition.

Kotler, P. and Armstrong, G. (2016) *Principles of marketing*. London: Pearson.

Kotler, P. and Keller, K. (2011). *Marketing management*. Harlow: Pearson Education.

Kotler, P., Keller, K., Brady, M., Goodman, M. and Hansen, T. (2016). *Marketing management*. Harlow, England: Pearson.

Krishna, G.R. and Shylajan, C.S., 2007. Determinants of Habitual Buying Behaviour: A Study of Branded Apparels. *The ICFAI Journal of Marketing Management*, 6(3), pp.6-21.

Kumar, P. (2010). *Marketing of hospitality and tourism services*. New Delhi, India: Tata McGraw Hill Education.

- Kuntner .T., Teichert .T. (2016) The Scope of Price Promotion Research. An informetric study. *Journal of Business Research*. Vol. 69, Issue 8, pp: 2687-2696.
- Kurniawan, H., Au, Y., Zeng, J., So, R. and Tseng, M. (2002). The Consumer Decision-Making Process in Two Different Web Stores. *Proceedings of the Human Factors and Ergonomics Society Annual Meeting*, 46(14), pp.1261-1265.
- Kurtz, D.L. (2014). *Contemporary Marketing*. Cengage Learning.
- Lal .R., Rao .R. (1997) Supermarket Competition: The Case of Everyday Low Pricing. <https://doi.org/10.1287/mksc.16.1.60>
- Lamb, C., Hair, J. and McDaniel, C. (2005) *Essentials of Marketing*. 5th ed. Mason, Ohio: South-Western.
- Langner, S., Hennigs, N. and Wiedmann, K.P. (2013). "Social persuasion: targeting social identities through social influencers", *Journal of Consumer Marketing*, Vol. 30 (1), pp.31-49, <https://doi.org/10.1108/07363761311290821>.
- Laroche, M., Bergeron, J. and Barbaro-Forleo, G. (2001) "Targeting consumers who are willing to pay more for environmentally friendly products", *Journal of Consumer Marketing*, Vol. 18, pp. 503-520.
- Lashley, K.S. and Wade, M., 1946. The Pavlovian theory of generalization. *Psychological Review*, 53(2), p.72.
- Leavy, P. (2017). *Research design*. New York: The Guilford Press.
- Lee, F.S., 1999. *Post Keynesian price theory*. Cambridge University Press.
- Lee, J. E., Chen-Yu, .J. H.(2018) Effects of Price Discount on Consumers' Perceptions of Savings, Quality, and Value for Apparel Products: Mediating Effect of Price Discount Affect. *FashText* 5, 14;(2013).

- Lee, N. and Lings, I. (2008). *Doing business research*. London: Sage.
- Lee, R.M. (1993) *Doing Research on Sensitive Topic*. London: Sage.
- Leedy, P. and Ormrod, J. (2015). *Practical research*. 11th ed. Boston: Pearson.
- Leedy, P.D. and Ormrod, J.E., 2005. *Practical research*. Pearson Custom.
- Lester, D., 2013. Measuring Maslow's hierarchy of needs. *Psychological reports*, 113(1), pp.15-17.
- Lothian .J. R., (2009) Milton Friedman's Monetary Economics and the Quantity-Theory Tradition. *Fordham University*.
- Loudon, D. (1993). *Consumer behaviour*. New York: McGraw-Hill.
- Loudon, D. and Bitta, A. (2000). *Consumer Behaviour*. New York [N.Y., etc.]: McGraw-Hill.
- Loudon, D.L. and Bitta, A.J.D. (1993) *Consumer Behaviour –Concepts and Applications*, McGraw-Hill, INC., USA, p. 386.
- Lynn, M. (2011). *Segmenting and Targeting your Market: Strategies and Limitations*. Cornell University School of Hotel Administration: The Scholarly Commons. (Online). Available at: <https://pdfs.semanticscholar.org/c736/f493cf24b9414dcc47c6862f9875ce8537f5.pdf> (Accessed on 4 March 2018).
- Madden, T.J., Ellen, P.S. and Ajzen, I., 1992. A comparison of the theory of planned Behaviour and the theory of reasoned action. *Personality and social psychology Bulletin*, 18(1), pp.3-9.
- Malakooti, B., 2012. Decision making process: typology, intelligence, and optimization. *Journal of intelligent manufacturing*, 23(3), pp.733-746.
- Malhotra, N. K., Birks, D. F. (2006) *Marketing Research: An Applied Approach*. Harlow, FT/Prentice Hall.

Margaretha Ardhanari, M. (2013). Consumer Behaviour In Selecting Retail Format: The Perspective Of Theory Of Planned Behaviour. *IOSR Journal of Business and Management*, 7(5), pp.17-23.

Marketing and Forecourts (2019) UKPIA. Retrieved from www.ukpia.com

Marshall, M.N., 1996. Sampling for qualitative research. *Family practice*, 13(6), pp.522-526.

Matthews, B. and Ross, L. (2010). *Research methods*. Harlow: Pearson Education.

Maxwell, J.A. (1997) *Qualitative Research Design: An interactive Approach*. Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage.

Maylor, H. and Blackmon, K. (2005). *Researching business and management*. Hampshire: Palgrave Macmillan.

McBurney, D. and White, T. (2010). *Research methods*. 8th ed. Belmont, Calif.: Wadsworth/Cengage Learning.

McClelland, D.C. (1987), *Human Motivation*, Cambridge University Press, New York, NY.

McConnochie, M., Walton, R., Campton, J., Inglis, G., (2017) Exploring the Influence of Price Promotions on Student's FMCG purchase Decision Making. *Conference paper, 5th International Conference on Contemporary Marketing Issues (ICCMi), 2017, Greece*

McDaniel, C., Lamb, C. and Hair, J. (2006). *Introduction to marketing*. Mason, Ohio: Thomson Higher Education.

McEwen, W., Fang, X., Zhang, C. and Burkholder, R. (2006) "Inside the mind of Chinese consumer", *Harvard Business Review*, Vol. 84(3), pp. 68-76.

McGee, J. E. and Peterson, M. (2000) Toward the development of measures of distinctive competencies among small independent retailers. *Journal of Small Business Management*, Vol.38 (2), pp. 19-33.

- McLeod, S., 2007. Maslow's hierarchy of needs. *Simply psychology*, 1, pp.1-8.
- Merriam, S.B. and Tisdell, E.J., (2015). *Qualitative research: A guide to design and implementation*, London: John Wiley & Sons.
- Mintzberg, H. (1979) An emerging strategy of "direct" research. *Administrative Science Quarterly*, 24, 580-589.
- Mitchell, V.F. and Moudgill, P., 1976. Measurement of Maslow's need hierarchy. *Organizational Behaviour and Human Performance*, 16(2), pp.334-349.
- Moczar .J. (2020) The Arrow-Debreu Model of General Equilibrium and Kornai's Critique in the Height of Neoclassical Economics 1. *Journal of Banking and Finance and Sustainable Development 1* (2020).
- Molefe .M. M. (2006) Consumer Motivation in Forecourt Convenience Retailing in South Africa” Thesis submitted to the University of Pretoria, Gordon Institute of Business Science.
- Molina Azorín, J. and Cameron, R. (2010) "The Application of Mixed Methods in Organisational Research: A Literature Review", *The Electronic Journal of Journal of Business Research Methods*", Vol 8, No. 2, pp 95-105.
- Moore, N., Salter, A., Stanley, L. and Tamboukou, M. (2017). *The archive project*. New York: Routledge.
- Morris, J., Marzano, M., Dandy, N. and O'Brien, L. (2012) Theories and models of behaviour and behaviour change. *Forest Research*. (Online). Available at: [https://www.forestry.gov.uk/pdf/behaviour_review_theory.pdf/\\$FILE/behaviour_review_theory.pdf](https://www.forestry.gov.uk/pdf/behaviour_review_theory.pdf/$FILE/behaviour_review_theory.pdf) (Accessed on 3 February 2018).
- Morris, M.W., Hong, Y.Y., Chiu, C.Y. and Liu, Z. (2015). Normology: Integrating insights about social norms to understand cultural dynamics. ELSEVIER Science Direct. *Organisational*

- Behaviour and Human Decision Processes*, Vol. 129, pp.1-13. (Online). Available at: https://ac.els-cdn.com/S0749597815000084/1-s2.0-S0749597815000084-main.pdf?_tid=e6620429-7546-4027-991d-f707b5d09d9e&acdnat=1521314737_7de00483c4bed75fe5d0dcf4302c006c (Accessed on 6 March 2018).
- Mostafa, M.M. (2007) "Gender differences in Egyptian consumers' green purchase behaviour: the effects of environmental knowledge, concern and attitude", *International Journal of Consumer Studies*, Vol. 31, pp. 220-229.
- Mostert, P.G. (2002). *The consumer Decision-Making Process*. Chapter 3. (Online). Available at: <https://repository.up.ac.za/bitstream/handle/2263/29162/03chapter3-1.pdf?sequence=4> (Accessed on 5 March 2018).
- Mowen, J.C. and Minor, M. (1997) *Consumer Behaviour*. 5th ed. Prentice Hall.
- Mughal, A., Mehmood. A., Mohi-ud-deen, A., Ahmad. B. (2014)The Impact of Promotional Tools on Consumer Buying Behaviour: A Study from Pakistan. *Journal of Public Administration and Governance*. Vol.4., No.3, ISSN 2161-7104.
- Munthiu, M.C., 2009. The Buying Decision Process and Types of Buying Decision Behaviour. *Sibiu Alma Mater University Journals. Series A. Economic Sciences*, 2(4), pp.27-33.
- Muruganantham .G., Bhakat .R. S. (2013) A Review of Impulse-Buying Behaviour. *International Journal of Marketing Studies*. Vol. 5, No. 3, ISSN 1918-7203.
- Musa .M. I. (2017) Bundling Pricing Strategy on Purchasing Decision: A Case of Indihome Product. *Scientific and Academic Publishing Management*. 7(3):126-130.
- Musa, I. M., (2017) Bundling Pricing Strategy on Purchasing Decision: A Case of Indihome Product. *Management*. 2017, 7(3):126-130.

- Myers, M.D. (2008) “Qualitative Research in Business & Management” SAGE Publications
- Nafuna. E., Masaba., A. K, Tumwine. S., Watundu. S., Bonareri, T. C., Nakola. N. (2019) Pricing Strategies and Financial Performance: The Mediating Effect of Competition Advantage. Empirical Evidence from Uganda, a study of Private Primary Schools. *Global Journal of Management and Business Research and Finance. Vol. 19, Issue 1. Version 1.0.*
- Nagarkoti, B. (2009) Factors influencing consumer behaviour of Smartphone users. *ARCADA*. (Online). Available at: https://www.theseus.fi/bitstream/handle/10024/70466/Nagarkoti_Bishal.pdf?%20sequence=1 (Accessed on 2 February 2018).
- Naylor, .G. Frank, K., (2001) The Effect of Price Bundling on Consumer Perceptions of Value. *Journal of Services Marketing. Vol.15, Issue 4.*
- Neely, C.J., Roy, A. and Whiteman, C.H., 2001. Risk aversion versus intertemporal substitution: a case study of identification failure in the intertemporal consumption capital asset pricing model. *Journal of Business & Economic Statistics, 19(4)*, pp.395-403.
- Nelson, P., 1970. Information and consumer Behaviour. *Journal of political economy, 78(2)*, pp.311-329.
- Neuman, L. W. (2000). *Social Research Methods: Qualitative and Quantitative Approaches (4th Ed.)*, USA: Allyn and Bacon.
- Neuman, W.L. (2005) *Social Research Methods (6th edn)*. Thousand Oaks, Sage.
- Nielsen, R. A. (2016). Case Selection via Matching. *Sociological Methods & Research, 45(3)*, 569–597.

- Njeru, I. M. (2017) Influence of Pricing Strategies on Consumer Purchase decision. A Case of Supermarkets in Nairobi County. *Thesis. Strathmore University. Retrieved from <http://du-plus.strathmore.edu/handle/11071/5585>.*
- Nutbrown, C. and Clough, P. (2006). *Inclusion in the early years*. London: Sage.
- Nyoni . T. (2015) Milton Friedman’s Contribution to Present Day MacroEconomic Policy. Postulations and Applicability in Zimbabwe. *Munich, GRIN Verlag, <https://www.grin.com/document/299841>*
- Ofir, C. and Simonson, I. (2005) “*The Effect of Stating Expectations on Customer Satisfaction and Shopping Experience*”, Stanford Graduate School of Business 44p
- Osei . B. A., Abenyin .A. N. (2016) Applying the Engell-Kollat-Blackwell Model in Understanding International Tourists’ Use of Social Media for Travel Decision to Ghana. *Information Technology and Tourism. 16 (3)*.
- Osgood, C.E. and Tannenbaum, P.H., 1955. The principle of congruity in the prediction of attitude change. *Psychological review, 62(1)*, p.42.
- Osgood, C.E., Suci, G.J. and Tannenbaum, P.H., 1957. *The measurement of meaning* (No. 47). University of Illinois press.
- O’Shaughnessy, J. (1996). *Why people buy*. New York, N.Y.: Oxford University Press.
- O’Shaughnessy, J. (1996). *Why people buy*. New York, N.Y.: Oxford University Press.
- Otiende, J. M. (2018) An Assessment of Pricing Strategies and Consumer Behaviour in the Telecommunication Sector: A Case of Safaricom Kenya, Limited.
- Palmer, A. (2000) *Principles of marketing*. Oxford: Oxford University Press.

- Park, C. and Jun, J.K., 2003. A cross-cultural comparison of Internet buying Behaviour: Effects of Internet usage, perceived risks, and innovativeness. *International Marketing Review*, 20(5), pp.534-553.
- Parker. D. (2015) Contemporary Global Property Management Issues. *Being a technical paper presented to the PGD Students, Faculty of Technology, Management and Business. Universiti Tun Hussein Onn. Malaysia.*
- Patton, M. (2002). *Qualitative research & evaluation methods*. 3rd ed. London: Sage.
- Patton, M.Q. (2015). *Qualitative research and evaluation methods* (4th ed.) Thousand oaks, Ca: Sage.
- Perreau, F. (2014) ‘*The Consumer Factor. The Consumer Buying Decision Process*’. (Online). Available at: <http://theconsumerfactor.com/en/5-stages-consumer-buying-decision-process/> (Accessed on 19 February 2018).
- Perry, C. (1998). Processes of a case study methodology for postgraduate research in marketing. *European Journal of Marketing*, 32(9/10), pp.785-802.
- Peter, P., & Olson, J.C. (2007). *Consumer behaviour and marketing strategies* (7th ed.). Singapore: Mc Graw Hill.
- Peter, P., Olsen, J. and Grunert, K. (1999). *Consumer behaviour and marketing strategy*. Chicago, Ill: Irwin.
- Petkus, E. (2010). Incorporating Transformative Consumer Research Into the Consumer Behaviour Course Experience. *Journal of Marketing Education*, 32(3), pp.292-299.
- Petra .S., Petljak .K., Nalentina .D. (2017) “The growing importance of petrol stations as channels for expanding the retail services”. *Conference Paper: University of Zagreb, Faculty of Economics and Business. Zagreb.*

Petrol Stations in the UK- Market Research Report. (2020). *IBIS WORLD*. Retrieved from www.ibisworld.com

Phillips, D.C., and Burbules, N.C. (2000). *Postpositivism and educational research*. Lanham, MD: Rowman and Littlefield

Picardi, C. and Masick, K. (2014). *Research methods*. Los Angeles [etc.]: SAGE.

Pieterse .C. (3005) A Study on Convenience Marketing in the Petroleum Industry in South Africa, specifically relating to Engen Petroleum Limited.” Thesis submitted to the Graduate School of Business, Faculty if Management, University of Kwazulu-Natal.

Pieterse, C. (2005) *A Study on convenience Marketing in the Petroleum Industry in South Africa, specifically relating to Engen Petroleum Limited*. University of KWAZULU-NATAL.

Ponto, J. (2015) Understanding and Evaluating Survey Research. *Journal of the Advanced Practitioner in Oncology*. Harborside Press.

Post-Keynesian Economics (n.d) Post-Keynesian Economics Society. Retrieved from

Price Theory Remains Enduringly Important (2021, February 03. 03:38 pm) The Wall Street Journal. Retrieved from:

Prystay, C. (2002) "As China's women change, marketers notice - Procter & Gamble, like others, tries to appeal to evolving sensibilities". *Wall Street Journal*, May 30, p. A. 11.

Punch, K. (2012). *Introduction to social research*. London: SAGE.

Quester, P., Neal, C., Pettigrew, S., Grimmer, M.R., Davis, T. and Hawkins, D., 2007. *Consumer behaviour: Implications for marketing strategy*. McGraw-Hill.

Raymond, M.A., Tanner, J.F., Jr. & Kim, J. (2001) Cost Complexity of Pricing Decisions for Exporters in Developing and Emerging Markets. *Journal of International Marketing*, 9, pp.19–40.

Reeves .S. (2020) Meal deals, Combos and Bundling: The Impact on the nutrition composition off children's meals in restaurants. *Public Health Nutrition*. 23 (12), pp: 2253-2255(2020).

Reference:

Remenyi, D., Williams, B., Money, A. & Swartz, E. (2005) *Doing research in business and management: an introduction to process and methods*. London: Sage Publications

Remenyi, D., Williams, B., Money, A. & Swartz, E. (2005) *Doing research in business and management: an introduction to process and methods*. London: Sage Publications

Remler, D. and Van Ryzin, G. (2015). *Research methods in practice*. 2nd ed. Los Angeles [etc.]: Sage.

Richarme, M., 2005. Consumer decision-making models, strategies, and theories, oh my. *Strategic Research Analytics*. Retrieved March, 24, p.2015.

Riley, J. (2012). *Buyer behaviour -The decision-making process*. (Online). Available at: http://tutor2u.net/business/marketing/buying_decision_process.asp(Accessed on 17 February 2018).

Ritchie, J., & Lewis, J. (2003). *Qualitative research practice: a guide for social science students and researchers*. London: Sage Publications.

Ritchie, J., Lewis, J., Mcnaughton Nicholls, C. and Ormston, R. (2014). *Qualitative research practice*. 2nd ed. London: Sage.

Roberts, J.A. and Jones, E. (2001) "Money attitudes, credit card use, and compulsive buying among American college students", *Journal of Consumer Affairs*, Vol. 35, pp. 213-40.

Robson,C. (2002) *Real World Research*, 2nd edn. Oxford: Blackwell.

Roll, R. and Ross, S.A., 1980. An empirical investigation of the arbitrage pricing theory. *The journal of finance*, 35(5), pp.1073-1103.

Roller, M. R., and Lavrakas, P.J. (2015). *Applied qualitative research design: a total quality framework approach*. New York: Guilford Press.

Rook, D.W., 1987. The buying impulse. *Journal of consumer research*, 14(2), pp.189-199.

Roopa, S., Satya, R. M. (2012) Questionnaire designing for a Survey. *The Journal of Indian Orthodontic Society*. 46(4): 37-19.

Saeed (2019) A Study of Theories on Consumer Behaviour. *Journal of Computing and Management Studies (JCMS)*. Vol.3, Issue 1.

Salifu, R. (2014) *Investigating factors that influence consumer choice of vehicle fuel retail brands*. Ashesi University College.

Sammut-Bonnici, T., Channing, D. F (2015) Pricing Strategy. *Wiley Encyclopedia of Management, edited by Prof. Sir Cary. I. Cooper. John Wiley & Sons. Ltd.*

Sangvikar, B. V., Katole, H. J (2012) A Study of Consumer Purchase Behaviour in Organized Retail Outlets

Sapsford, R. (2006) *Survey Research*, 2nd ed. London: Sage.

Sarantakos, S. (2005). *Social research*. 3rd ed. New York: Palgrave Macmillan.

Saricayir .B. (2018) Price Perception: How Consumers Perceive Price and What to do. *Driscync*.

Saunders, M., Lewis, P. & Thornhill, A. (2012) "Research Methods for Business Students" 6th edition, Pearson Education Limited

Saunders, M., Lewis, P. and Thornhill, A. (2003) *Research Methods for Business Students*. 3rd ed. Harlow: FT/Prentice Hall.

Saunders, M., Lewis, P. and Thornhill, A. (2003) *Research Methods for Business Students*. 3rd ed. Harlow: FT/Prentice Hall.

- Saunders, M., Lewis, P. and Thornhill, A. (2014). *Research methods for business students*. Harlow, Essex, England: Pearson Education Limited.
- Saunders, M., Lewis, P., Thornhill, A. and Fisher, C. (2004). *Research methods for business students*. Harlow: Prentice Hall Financial Times.
- Schiffman, L. and Kanuk, L. (2007). *Consumer Behaviour*. Boston, Mass.: Pearson Prentice Hall.
- Schiffman, L. and Kanuk, L. (2007). *Consumer Behaviour*. Boston, Mass.: Pearson Prentice Hall.
- Schiffman, L. G. and Kanuk, L. L. (2004) *Consumer Behaviour*, Upper Saddle River, New Jersey: Pearson Prentice Hall.
- Scholz, R. and Tietje, O. (2002). *Embedded case study methods*. Thousand Oaks, Calif.: Sage Publ.
- Schoonenboom, J. and Johnson, R. (2017). How to Construct a Mixed Methods Research Design. *KZfSS Kölner Zeitschrift für Soziologie und Sozialpsychologie*, 69(S2), pp.107-131.
- Schoonenboom, J. and Johnson, R. (2017). How to Construct a Mixed Methods Research Design. *KZfSS Kölner Zeitschrift für Soziologie und Sozialpsychologie*, 69(S2), pp.107-131.
- Schwandt, T. A. (2000). Three Epistemological Stances for Qualitative Inquiry. In N. K. Denzin & Y. S. Lincoln (Eds.), *Handbook of Qualitative Research*. Thousand Oaks: Sage Publications.
- Seale, C. (2018). *Researching society and culture*. 4th ed. London: Sage.
- Seers, K. and Critelton, N., 2001. Quantitative research: Designs relevant to nursing and healthcare. *NT Research*, 6(1), pp.487-500.
- Sekaran, U. and Bougie, R. (2009). *Research methods for business*. Chichester: John Wiley & Sons Ltd.
- Sekaran, U. and Bougie, R. (2013). *Research methods for business*. Chichester: John Wiley & Sons Ltd.

- Shani, A.B. and Pasmore, W.A., 1985. Organization inquiry: Towards a new model of the action research process. *Contemporary Organization development: Current Thinking and Applications*, Scott, Foresman, Glenview, IL, pp.438-448.
- Shapiro .N., Sawyer . M. (2003) Post-Keynesian Price Theory. *Journal of Post Keynesian Economics*, 25 (3): 355-365.
- Shapiro .N., Sawyer .M. (2003) Post Keynesian Price Theory. *Journal of Post Keynesian Economics*. 25(3): 355-365.
- Sharma, R. and Gautam, A. (2016) Impact of retail formats on consumer buyer Behaviour-A study of fast moving consumer goods market in South Africa. *British Journal of economics, Management & Trade*, Vol. 11(3), pp.1-8.
- Sheeran, P., 2002. Intention—Behaviour relations: a conceptual and empirical review. *European review of social psychology*, 12(1), pp.1-36.
- Shoham, A. and Brencic, M.M. (2003) "Compulsive buying behaviour", *Journal of Consumer Marketing*, Vol. 20(2/3), pp. 127-38.
- Siggelkow, N., 2007. Persuasion with case studies. *Academy of management journal*, 50(1), pp.20-24.
- Silverman, D. (1993) *Interpreting Qualitative Data: methods for Analysing Talk, Text and Interaction*, London: Sage.
- Simon .S., Manohar .M., Eduria .O. W. (2013) Marketing Implications of Environmental Influences on Consumer Buying Behaviour. *ELK Asia Pacific Journal of Marketing and Retail Management*. Vol. 4, Issue 2. April 2013.

Sin R. G., Chellappa .R. K., Siddarth .S. (2009) Strategic Implementation of “Everyday Low Pricing” in Electronic Markets: A Study of Airline Pricing on the Internet. *SSRN Electronic Journal*. 10.2139/ssrn.989849

Smith .G. E., Woodside .A. G. (2009) Pricing Theory and Practice in Managing Business to Business Brands –Chapter 9. *Advances in Business Marketing and Purchasing*. 15:429-486.

Smith .G.E., Woodside .A.G.(2009) Pricing Theory and Practice in Managing Business to Business Brands. *Advances in Business Marketing and Purchasing*. 15: 429-486.

Smith, J.R., Terry, D.J., Manstead, A.S., Louis, W.R., Kotterman, D. and Wolfs, J., 2007. Interaction effects in the theory of planned Behaviour: The interplay of self-identity and past Behaviour. *Journal of Applied Social Psychology*, 37(11), pp.2726-2750.

Solomon, M. (2016). *Consumer behaviour*. Harlow, England: Prentice Hall/Financial Times.

Solomon, M. R., and (2011) *Consumer Behaviour: Buying, Having, and Being*. 9th ed. Upper Saddle River, Pearson Education, Inc, New Jersey.

SOLOMON, M., et al., 2006. *Consumer Behaviour: A European Perspective*. 3rd ed. Harlow: Prentice Hall.

Solomon, M., et al., 2006. *Consumer Behaviour: A European Perspective*. 3rd ed. Harlow: Prentice Hall.

Solomon, M., Russell-Bennett, R. and Previte, J. (2012). *Consumer Behaviour eBook*. Melbourne: P.Ed Australia.

Sommer .L. (2011) The Theory of Planned Behaviour and the Impact of Past Behaviour. *International Business and Economics Research Journal*. Vol. 10, No. 1.

Spitteri, J.M. and Dion, P.A. (2014) "Customer value, overall satisfaction, end-user loyalty, and market performance in detail intensive industries", *Industrial Marketing Management*, Vol. 33, pp.675-87.

Srinivasan, T. (2015). A Study on Consumer Preferences of Petroleum Retail Outlets. *IOSR Journal of Business and Management*, Vol. 17(2), pp. 35-40.

Stake, R.E. (1995) *The art of case Study Research*. California: Sage.

Stallworth, P. (2008) "Consumer behaviour and marketing strategic", online, pp.9.

Stamate, V. (2014) PRICE STRATEGIES AS A DETERMINANT OF PERFORMANCE ON ROMANIAN COMPANIES IN EXPORT MARKETS.

Stankevich, A. (2017). Explaining the Consumer Decision-Making Process: Critical Literature Review. *JOURNAL OF INTERNATIONAL BUSINESS RESEARCH AND MARKETING*, 2(6), pp.7-14.

Steinhart, Y., Ayalon, O. and Puterman, H. (2013) The effect of an environmental claim on consumers' perceptions about luxury and utilitarian products. *Journal of Cleaner Production*. Vol. 53, pp. 277-286.

Stentz, J.E., Clark, V.L.P. and Matkin, G.S., 2012. Applying mixed methods to leadership research: A review of current practices. *The leadership quarterly*, 23(6), pp.1173-1183.

Stentz, J.E., Plano Clark, V.L. and Matkin, G.S. (2012) "Applying Mixed Methods to Leadership Research: A Review of Current Practices", *The Leadership Quarterly*, 23, pp 1173-1183.

St-Maurice, I. and Wu, C. (2006) "Understanding China's teen consumers", *The McKinsey Quarterly*, June, pp. 60-8.

Stokes, D. (2002). *Small business Management, a case study approach*. 4th ed. London: Continuum.

- Strauss, A. and Corbin, J. (1998). *Basics of qualitative research*. 2nd ed. Thousand Oaks: Sage Publ.
- Strauss, A., & Corbin, J. (1998). *Basics of qualitative research* (2nd ed.). Newbury Park, CA: Sage.
- Stringer, E. (2007). *Action research*. 3rd ed. London: SAGE.
- Suddaby, R., 2006. From the editors: What grounded theory is not. *Academy of management journal*, 49(4), pp.633-642.
- Supermarket Meal Deals (2017, October Tuesday, 31. 13:58) Independent. Retrieved from
- Sussman, R. and Gifford, R. (2018). Causality in the Theory of Planned Behaviour. *Personality and Social Psychology Bulletin*, 45(6), pp.920-933.
- Swanson, R. and Chermack, T. (2013). *Theory building in applied disciplines*. San Francisco: Berrett-Koehler.
- Swartz, E., Money, A., Remenyi, D., & Williams, B. (1998). *Doing Research in Business and Management: an Introduction to Process and Method*. London: Sage Publications.
- Taherdoost, H. (2020) Sampling Methods in Research Methodology: How to choose a Sampling Technique for Research. *International Journal of Academic Research in Management ((IJARM)* 2016.5.hal-02546796.
- Tashakkori, A. and Creswell, J.W., 2007. Exploring the nature of research questions in mixed methods research.
- Tay .K. (2019, March 15) The Different Types of Pricing Strategies You Can Use In Wholesale Marketing. *Whole Sale Suite*. Retrieved from
- Taylor. G. R. (ED) (2005) Integrating Quantitative and Qualitative methods in Research. *Maryland: University Press of American Inc*.

- Teddlie, C. and Tashakkori, A., (2011). Mixed methods research, *The Sage handbook of qualitative research*, 2(1), pp.285-300.
- Teddlie, C. and Tashakkori, A., (2011). Mixed methods research, *The Sage handbook of qualitative research*, 2(1), pp.285-300.
- Tellis .G. J., Stremersch .S., (2006) Strategic Bundling of Products and Prices: A New Synthesis for Marketing. *Journal of Marketing*. 66(1).
- Tendai, M. and Crispen, C., 2009. In-store shopping environment and impulsive buying. *African journal of marketing management*, 1(4), pp.102-108.
- Thomas, G. (2011). *How to do your case study*. London: Sage.
- Tuli, F., (2011), The basis of distinction between qualitative and quantitative research in social science: reflection on ontological, epistemological and methodological perspectives, *Ethiopian Journal of Education and Sciences*, 6(1), pp. 97-108.
- Turfus, C., 2019. Closed-form Arrow-Debreu pricing for the Hull-White short rate model. *Quantitative Finance*, 19(12), pp.2087-2094.
- Turner, A. G (2003) Sampling frames and master Samples. United Nations Secretariat, Statistics Division. ESA/STA/AC.9313. NOV. 2003.
- UKEssays. (November 2018). The Applications Of Arrow Debreu Model Economics Essay. Retrieved from <https://www.ukessays.com/essays/economics/the-applications-of-arrow-debreu-model-economics-essay.php?vref=1>
- Upadhyay, P., Upadhyay, S. and Shukla, K. (2017). A Mathematical Model of Consumers' Buying Behaviour Based On Multiresolution Analysis. *Procedia Computer Science*, 122, pp.564-571.
- Urun .S. (2011) Price Promotion, Quality and Brand Loyalty. (Thesis) submitted to Karlstand Business School.

- Van Maanen, J. (1988) *Tales of the field: On writing ethnography*. Chicago: University of Chicago Press.
- Van Maanen, J. (1983) *Qualitative Methodology*, London: Sage.
- Wagner, C., Kawulich, B. and Garner, M. (2012). *Doing social research*. New York: McGraw-Hill Higher Education.
- Waguespack, B. , Ayman, .M.R. (1993) Consumer Behaviour: Still normative after all these years in *Advances in Marketing. (SWMA Conference Proceedings) (McKee et.al, Ed's)*. Baton Rouge, LA: Louisiana State University, 29-35.
- Wahyuni, D (2012), The research design maze: understanding paradigms, cases, methods and methodologies, *Journal of applied management accounting research*, 10(1), pp. 69-80
- Walliman, N. (2005). *Your research project*. 2nd ed. Los Angeles: Sage.
- Walliman, N. (2001) *your research project*, Sage: London.
- Wang, C.L. and Lin, X. (2008) "Migration of Chinese consumption values: traditions, westernization, and cultural renaissance", *Journal of Business Ethics*, Vol. 81(1).
- Watkins, D. and Gioia, D. (2015). *Mixed Methods Research*.
- Watkins, D. and Gioia, D. (2015). *Mixed Methods Research*.
- Waweru, N. (2018) *Forecourt Retailing and Competitive Advantage of Total Kenya PLC Service Stations in Nairobi City County*. Thesis.
- Weber, M., 1987. Decision making with incomplete information. *European Journal of Operational Research*, 28(1), pp.44-57.
- Wells .V. K. (2014) Behavioural Psychology, Marketing and Consumer Behaviour: A Literature Review and future research Agenda. *Journal of Marketing Management* 30(11-12) pp: 1119-1158.

Welsh, E. (2002) Dealing With Data: Using NVivo in the Qualitative Data Analysis Process. *Forum Qualitative Social Research. Vol.3, No.2, Article 26.*

Why It Is Important to Have the Right Meal Deal. Restaurant Engine. Retrieved from

Williams, C. C. (2001) Acquiring goods and services in lower income populations: an evaluation of consumer behaviour and preferences, *International Journal of Retail & Distribution Management*, Vol. 29(1), pp. 16-24.

Williams, C. C. (2001) Acquiring goods and services in lower income populations: an evaluation of consumer behaviour and preferences, *International Journal of Retail & Distribution Management*, Vol. 29(1), pp. 16-24.

Williams, T. G. (2002) Social class influences on purchase evaluation criteria, *Journal of Consumer Marketing*, Vol. 19(3), pp.249-276.

Wind, Y. and Bell, D.R. (2007) *The Marketing book: Market Segmentation*. Chapter 11. Pp.222-244. (Online). Available at: https://faculty.wharton.upenn.edu/wp-content/uploads/2012/04/0702_Market_Segmentation.pdf (Accessed on 2 February 2018).

Wisker, G., 2007. *The postgraduate research handbook: Succeed with your MA, MPhil, EdD and PhD*. Macmillan International Higher Education.

Yakup , D., Sevil, Z. (2011) An Empirical Study on the Effect of Family Factor on Consumer Buying Behaviours. *Asian Social Science Published by Canadian Center of Science and Education. Vol.7, No.10.*

Yan, B. & Ke, C. (2018) Two strategies for dynamic perishable product pricing to consider in strategic consumer behaviour. *International Journal of Production Research*, 56 (5), pp.1757–1772.

Yap, S.Y. and Gaur, S.S. (2014). Consumer Dissonance in the Context of Online Consumer Behaviour: a Review and Research Agenda. *Journal of Internet Commerce*, Vol. 13(2), pp.116-137.

Yin, R. (2009). *Case study research*. 4th ed. Los Angeles: SAGE Publications.

Yin, R.K. and Davis, D., 2007. Adding new dimensions to case study evaluations: The case of evaluating comprehensive reforms. *New directions for evaluation*, 2007(113), pp.75-93.

Yin, R.K. (2012). *Applications of case study research* (3rd ed.). Thousand Oaks, Sage.

Zwanka .R. J. (2017) Examining Intrapreneurship: Meal Deals as traffic builders in food retail. *Applied Marketing Analytics*. Vol. 2, November 4, 2017. Pp: 353-366(14).

APPENDIXES

Appendix I: Semi Structured Interview Questionnaire

General information

1. How long have you been working for this company?
2. What is your personal experience working in this petroleum retail industry?

An exploration of how pricing impact on consumer buying behaviour. A case study of Euro Garage

- 1) What is your general perception of consumer buying Behaviour?
- 2) In your opinions, Specify the major factors that influence consumer buying Behaviour in case of convenient stores?
- 3) How consumer buying Behaviours influenced by family?
- 4) What is your understanding about roles and status of consumer?
- 5) Do you think its affect consumer buying Behaviour?
- 6) How do you think age and life cycle stages of consumer affecting their buying Behaviour?
- 7) Do you think occupation and economic situation influence consumer within the service station setting?
- 8) How would you define product pricing?
- 9) In your opinion, how do you think product pricing influence consumer buying behaviour?
- 10) Do you think customer prepared to pay a little more for convenience?
- 11) Have you experienced any price change affecting consumer buying Behaviour?
- 12) What is your general perception of Everyday Low Pricing strategy?
- 13) In your opinions, do you think everyday low pricing strategy influence consumer purchasing decision
- 14) What is your response to High-Low pricing strategy?

15) In your opinions how High-Low pricing influence consumer buying behaviour

16) Do you think bundle offers influence customer buying Behaviour?

17) How does seasons price affect buying Behaviour of consumer?

Appendix II Survey Questionnaire

1) Gender of the respondent

Male Female

2) What is your age bracket?

Below 20 21-30 31-40 Over 41

3) Employed: Yes No

4) Level of income per year?

Less than £10,000

£11,000 – £20,000

£21,000 to £30,000

£31,000 to £40,000

Above £40,000

5) Which of the following size of families do you belong to?

Single member Two members Three members

Four members Above four

Please rate the following statements influential

	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly agree
I compare the price of different products before I decide to buy					
I am price conscious when buying fuel and convenience product					
I choose my fuel convenience store based on their low prices					
My product choice is influenced by promotional offers					
I will buy a product I don't recognize simply because it is cheap					
All the brands in my shopping bucket are always have low prices					
I prefer brands which have a steady low prices					
I choose my supermarket based on stability of their prices					
I am likely to switch my supermarket because I like its low prices					
I always have a large shopping bucket when the prices are low					

I always have a small shopping basket whenever the prices are high					
I only buy goods which are cheap from any particular supermarket					
I will shop at any time of the month because the prices are stable					
I consider my financial condition and social class during shopping					
Social groups influence my buying Behaviour					
My family are the most influential people that affect my buying Behaviour					
Major branded product in this shop influence my buying behaviour					
I don't hesitate to pay little more for convenience purpose					
My buying Behaviour of a product increase when price reduced					
Promotional price attract me to buy the product					
Products have bundle offers (Buy one and other free) attract me to buy more					
Low prices of products increase my willingness to buy them					

I prefer to buy my needs during sales seasons					
Major branded products do not influence my buying behaviour					
I am always willing to spend more time whenever I visit a supermarket with frequent offers					
I am likely to suspend my shopping until there are promotional campaigns in the supermarket					